

EUTHANASIA: THE SCHISM BETWEEN THE CORPOREAL AND HOLISTIC DICHOTOMY OF RIGHT TO LIFE

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 01ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The paper is a research essay with an introduction that will outline the congenital values appended to life and gauge their severability owing to the lack of judicial stance of European Court of Human Rights, American and Canadian Constitutional Courts on the *morality* of the issue. It is followed by the vexed problem of medical ethics along with the issue of a healer's objective. Thereafter, the blurred lines of morality vis-à-vis Human Rights are scrutinized to extrapolate whether qualification of life's *value* is permissible on relative morality. These arguments are subsequently juxtaposed with the *risk of abuse* like the slippery slope of involuntary euthanasia. The conclusion highlights the judicial deference to the legislature with its future effects in the field of interpretation and application of Human Rights.

Keywords: *Dignity, Euthanasia, Life, Medical Ethics, Morality*

The words 'thou shall not kill' ensue moral obligations that drench our socio-legal system with deference to 'sanctity of life.' This tradition has been met by a turbulent debate of competing interests between *preservation of life* vis-à-vis *self-autonomy*. The religious commandment itself was qualified by exceptions befitting the dynamics of passage of time in social context justified by criminal jurisprudence and sovereign affairs. Against the backdrop of this time-induced metamorphosis, the western liberal world witnessed contemporary legal interpretation of *life* embracing the *right to die*, as an extension of the former. Whilst this view is not ubiquitous, it is further obscured in practicing jurisdictions based on the dichotomy of *suicide* and *assisted suicide*. When the common law tradition celebrates

the right to *self-autonomy* of an individual wherein, imposition of treatment against the patient's will tantamount to 'battery'; what then, is the moral authority that limits the expansion of self-sovereignty to include 'assistance' in *right to die*? Is the distinction of right-possession between able-bodied and non-competent persons justified? Is there really a substantial contrast between medical *inaction* against the *positive act* of respecting the patient's will, both leading to the same outcome? Does this bruise the arena of medical ethics or is it instead sustained by 'physician-assisted-suicide?' What is the stance of Constitutional Courts and do they support their position with moral clarity? The present essay endeavors to unveil the present legal and moral positions on the issue of 'assisted suicide' in the liberal western rights-based democracies.

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The introduction will outline the congenital values appended to life and gauge their severability owing to the lack of judicial stance of European Court of Human

Rights, American and Canadian Constitutional Courts on the *morality* of the issue. It is followed by the vexed problem of medical ethics along with the issue of a healer's objective. Thereafter, the blurred lines of morality vis-à-vis Human Rights are scrutinized to extrapolate whether qualification of life's *value* is permissible on relative morality. These arguments are subsequently juxtaposed with the *risk of abuse* like the slippery slope of involuntary euthanasia. The conclusion highlights the judicial deference to the legislature with its future effects in the field of interpretation and application of Human Rights.

1. CAN LIFE BE SEVERED FROM ITS CONGENITAL VALUES?

Life cannot be defined in clinical terms that gauges it solely based on the process of bodily functions divorced from the cognitive process. It connotes the cumulative value of *autonomy, dignity, liberty, identity, personhood, choice, prevention of suffering* and *our experiences and memories*.¹ The question raised in view of proscription on assisted suicide is based on the quantification of these rights and whether they can be severed from right to life. It is contested that life is *sacrosanct*² and must be preserved in order to satiate *state interest* and uphold *medical ethics* enshrined under the Hippocratic Oath.³ However, can the state interest trump self-sovereignty of an individual or does it in fact cast justifiable limitation upon state interest? The courts

¹ Prof Kai Moller, Seminar on Euthanasia, LSE, 12 February 2015

² Cruzan v. Harmon [1988] 760 SW2d [408] [419]

³ Leslie L Mangini, 'To Help or not to Help: Assisted Suicide and its Moral, Ethical and Legal Ramifications' 18 Seton Hall Legis J 728 1993-1994, 747

have hesitated to venture into the *moral* grounds in support of their arguments, yet we can infer the *implicit* moral fiber woven in their legal interpretation of the *Right to Life* wherein, America and the European Court of Human Rights consider such right weak when pitted against State interest in promoting the ‘value of life.’ Canada held a similar stance until 2015, when it partly shared the liberal view of Netherland in affirming the negative right to assisted dying, as an intrinsic part of *dignified living*.

The Predicament of Medical Ethics:
The dominant fraction of the medical community condemns the idea of assisted suicide on the grounds of incompatibility with the profession⁴however; the other group simultaneously supports this practice on the assertion that *beneficence*⁵is the ultimate objective recognized by the practice of assisted suicide. This is a valid argument with the answer being contingent upon the definition of *morality* and *how* it is associated with *value of life*. If morality saves the living body, then assisted suicide is inconsistent with the objective of a *healer* however, if morality guards the *autonomy* and *dignity* associated with life, then such exercise furthers the *ends* of medical practice.

3. THE MORAL INTERROGATIVES:

This issue is ridden with pluralistic interrogatives and few answers, as there are myriad grey areas that further perplex the legal and moral code of the society. When a competent person possesses the right to die, then what is the moral basis for discriminating against personal

characteristics of those who are less abled? When a person has the inherent right to deny treatment, thereby the inaction on part of the physician effectively ending her patient’s life, then why does similar recognition of a patient’s will to seek assistance in terminating his life render immoral? The answer to these rests upon the fundamental query, ‘Is the moral question focused on *life* in strict sense i.e. preservation of the living being or does it propose to protect the *dignity* associated with the living being?’⁶

The Canadian Court has decided that refuting the insertion of *assisted suicide* fundamentally abuses the *right to life* as the patient may be compelled to end his or her life in advance as opposed to the foreseeable future in order to eschew a *degraded* living sans any aid to execute their *free will* to terminate their life on dignified terms on their own volition.⁷ They also have the right to be remembered as solemn respectable members of the society without having tainted their memories of the pernicious vicissitudes of their last moments.⁸ Therefore, assistance in aiding the commission of suicide via action or inaction is not the moral conundrum but tracing the true consent/choice of the person is the germane question. Hence, safeguard mechanisms need to be put in place in order to ascertain that such self-autonomous choices are not corrupted by external influence, damaging the interests of the *vulnerable* class.

⁴*Ibid* n 3, 749

⁵*Ibid* n 3, 728

⁶ Adam J Macleod, ‘The Mystery of Life in the Laboratory of Democracy: Personal Autonomy in State Law’ 59 Clev St L Rev 589 2011, 612-614

⁷*Carter v Canada (Attorney General)* [2012] BCSC 886 [17]

⁸*Cruzan v Director, MDH* [1990] 497 U.S. 261 (Dissenting Justice Blackmun, Marshall and Brennan)

3. THE INHIBITING FACTORS THAT TAINT THIS RIGHT

The traditionalists considered suicide as *malum in se*,⁹ inherently *wrong* and *criminal* as in the United Kingdom until its repeal in 1961.¹⁰ It is *morally wrong* to kill, and this view was widely accepted until the decriminalization of *attempt to suicide* in the western democracies.¹¹ Therefore, the *historical* and *traditional* line of argument has continued to prohibit the inclusion of this negative right as a fundamental interest, pronounced by the Hon'ble Apex Court of the United States of America in *Washington v. Glucksberg*.¹² Majority western countries have not approved of this right.¹³ The right to life does not encompass the right to terminate it, which is considered sacrilegious and found to violate the 'State Interest' in *preservation of life*.¹⁴ Right to Life is inclusive of *security* that translates to the 'well-being' of the person and right to deprivation of this life stands in direct contravention with security.¹⁵ (Although it is debatable since well-being redirects us to *quality* and not prolongation of life) The justification is posited in the *rationale* behind the erstwhile criminalization of 'attempt to suicide' and the abolition of 'death penalty'.¹⁶

The primary inhibition in embracing the inclusion of this negative right is the *risk of abuse*,¹⁷ as the nature of the act is *irrevocable*¹⁸ and the potential risk of *malice* and *mistakes* cannot be ruled out.¹⁹ However, this may not be a valid justification on the part of the state, especially when it is denying a Constitutional Right to its subjects. There has been an elongated debate over autonomous right to abortion²⁰, wherein the State conceded to the primacy of self-sovereignty over *life preservation* but this was rendered possible due to the clinically calculated design of trimesters whereas such appraisal of the human mind has yet not been conceived.²¹

This right further contravenes the collective societal interest, as the deceased would deprive the society from enriching in human experiences in their interaction with the said person whilst also depriving himself or herself from the learning experiences that courses from the enduring of suffering.²² This line of argument may be *speculative* at best, as we cannot ascertain the scope of such personal and inter-personal enrichment. Justice Stevens has urged the court to weigh each case on its merit thereby precluding an imbalance between individual and State interest. These countervailing arguments are also based on the anticipated perils of legalized assisted suicide, which may crane itself to include *involuntary euthanasia*.²³ The courts consider the policing of such an inflated right, an implausible feat especially owing to the involvement of family

⁹*Ibid* n 5

¹⁰*Ibid* n 3, 733

¹¹Rodriguez v. British Columbia (Attorney General), [1993] 3 S.C.R. 519

¹² [1997] 521 US 702

¹³ There is an exception of Netherlands; Washington, Oregon, Montana and Vermont in the United States of America

¹⁴*Ibid* n 8 and 9; *Pretty v U.K.* [2002] 35 E.H.R.R. [9]

¹⁵*Ibid* n 8

¹⁶*Ibid* n 9

¹⁷*Ibid* n 8

¹⁸*Ibid* n 12 (Justice Stevens)

¹⁹*Ibid* n 8, 9, 12

²⁰Roe v. Wade [1973] 410 US 113

²¹*Ibid* n 12 (Justice Scouter)

²²*Ibid* n 3, 737; *Ibid* n 12

²³*Ibid* n 8 (Justice Rehnquist CJ)

members.²⁴ Whilst the *risk of abuse* is a crucial factor, it is not beyond redress and apposite safety valves can ensure that vulnerable sections are not negatively impacted by such practice.

4. EPILOGUE:

Whilst the courts have produced their arguments on a legal parapet in the discussed cases, they have avoided a clear evaluation of the right on 'moral grounds' thereby leaving a vacuum in the moral explication of the issue. The Constitutional Courts of Canada as well as the United States of America have reiterated against venturing into 'explaining every feasible area on the issue' and steering clear of theological and philosophical responses to the moral issues at hand.²⁵ This apprehension can be traced in the following court expressions, "*This Court need not, and has no authority to, inject itself into every field of human activity where irrationality and oppression may theoretically occur, and if it tries to do so, it will destroy itself.*"; "...in answering the important question presented by this tragic case, it is wise "not to attempt by any general statement, to cover every possible phase of the subject."; "Americans are engaged in an earnest and profound debate about the morality, legality, and practicality of physician assisted suicide. Our holding permits this debate to continue, as it should in a democratic society."; and lastly "...In my opinion, the Court should answer this question without reference to the philosophical and theological considerations fuelling the debate on the morality of suicide or euthanasia."

They have instead deferred the matter to the legislature who is alleged to be better equipped to weave the moral quotient consistent with social aspirations. However, the question about whether such Constitutional Courts can avoid their obligation to ascertain Constitutional Rights based on speculative faculties of the legislature (which has so far not been able to resolve the moral debate itself) becomes questionable and leaves us with further marred moral clarity on the issue of assisted suicide. The distinction carved by the new Canadian judgment upholding the constitutional right to terminate life with assistance juxtaposed with Justice Stevens' distinguishing view, which addresses the court's all encompassing verdict bereft of appreciating circumstances, maintaining that not all individual freedoms are trumped by collective interests of the society or state interest, is a welcome contrast against the conventional limitation imposed upon *Right to Life*.²⁶

Netherlands perhaps a precursor of a wider elucidation of the moral question on life, which affirms the morality of *life with dignity* under individual autonomy²⁷ hence, awaiting a likely lifting of the ban on assisted suicide in other jurisdictions treading towards a more self-autonomous approach to interpretation of Life. However, in the absence of the Constitutional Court's unequivocal *moral explication* of the interpretation of right to assisted suicide, the debate over this utterly complex issue is projected to remain convoluted in the moral territories.

²⁴Ibid n 12 (Justice Scouter)

²⁵Ibid n 8, 11, 12

²⁶Ibid n 12

²⁷Ibid n 3, 731, 775-777

TRANSGENDER AND HUMAN RIGHTS – CURRENT SITUATION AND POTENTIAL OPTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 19ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

In a millennium challenge in the arena of human rights, recognition, promotion and protection of rights of Transgender became a biggest challenge. This research summary studies the transgender in human rights perspective in a macro level dealing with current situation with key to their development in India.

Keywords: *Human, Rights, Transgender, Challenges, India*

Transgender are the people who are born with male or female anatomies but they are feel different from their body structure. They are born with cryptic gentiles and are sexually neutral. They transgress social norms. These individuals signifies uncompromising binary gender constitution. They possess a hackneyed rampant gender role culturally. They experience a mismatch between their gender identity, gender expression and their assigned sex. These people either full time or part time live in a gender role opposite to which they are born with.

Due to these characteristics, transgender most commonly live in groups under the umbrella of a “guru”. They are mostly commonly abandoned from their family. They don’t have a permanent home and most of them live in communes thus live in commune slums on the outskirts of the society. They become subject to public humiliation. They are also embarrassed by police more often than any other sector of the society.

Still, these communes possess a very strong social structure. They have a system of

Gurus and chela. Among them they share a loving and nurturing relationship which continues through generations. These communes are also place of social security and safety to the new or young Hijara who are shunned by their families.

Hinjaras¹, enuchs², chakkas, transsexuals, Aravanis, Kothis³, jogappas⁴ are the different names we call them across India.

¹ Hijras are biological males who reject their 'masculine' identity in due course of time to identify either as women, or “not-men”, or “in-between man and woman”, or “neither man nor woman”.

² Hijras in Tamil Nadu identify as “Aravani”. Tamil Nadu Aravanigal Welfare Board, a state government's initiative under the Department of Social Welfare defines Aravanis as biological males who self-identify themselves as a woman trapped in a male's body.

³ Kothis are a heterogeneous group. 'Kothis' can be described as biological males who show varying degrees of 'femininity' - which may be situational. Some proportion of Kothis have bisexual behavior and get married to a woman.

⁴ Jogtas or Jopgappas are those persons who are dedicated to and serve as a servant of Goddess Renukha Devi (Yellamma) whose temples are present in Maharashtra and Karnataka.

Transgender are human being. Still in India till, very recently, they were not recognized as human beings. This itself is a huge violation of Human Rights. This lack of recognition had segregated them from the society and more worst, in the matter of civil rights .they have been destitute from many rights and privileges that we as Indians enjoy. They are not the part of social and cultural participation in public, they are neglected by family and society. The schools did not gave them admission so there was no chance of joining colleges and universities at higher level. Those who joined at lower level school where shunned off once thereality came in picture. Only very few around 1% - 2%, of transgender can make it to higher level of education.

Before 2014, transgender had tethered access to education, health and health services, public spaces, livelihood opportunities, obtaining passport, driving license, ration card etc. while applying for bank account they had to tick male or female as there was no option for third gender. As per the census 2011, there are about half a million Transgender people residing in India.

1. Historical Sketch

The presence of these transgender was recognized way back in “**Kamsutra**” in India, where they were identified as “**TritiyaPrakarti**” way back in **400 BC**.

During **Ramayan** there is an evidence that while going to exile for 14 years, when lord Ram asked all men and women of Ajodhya, to return back to their homes , these transgender kept on standing till 14 years. On his return when Lord Ram saw them standing, he asked transgender as to why they had not returned back to their homes. The transgender replied that they neither came in men nor in women. And since there

'Jogta' refers to male servant of that Goddess and 'Jogti' refers to female servant

was no mention about them in his speech they did not move from their place. Hearing

this lord Ram was so much impressed that he granted them boon to bless people during the auspicious occasions. This is from where the tradition of having hijaras on child birth, wedding or any auspicious ceremony started. All this happened some **8000 – 7000 yearsBC**

During **Mahabharat**, some **5000 years BC** , it is a well-known fact that first daughter of Kind Drupad was Shikhandi , who was a girl but had all qualities of a boy . She played a major role in the 14 day war, to bring down bheesm on the bed of arrows. Then we also have the evidence of Arjun turning into “vrihanalla” during their exile and perform all duties a eunuch or a transgender would have performed during those times.

These examples portray the importance of eunuch/hijara/transgender during the ancient times. Let us now have a look in the more recent years of History -

With the starting of **700 years AD**, **Rajputs** started rising has Hindu kings in west and north part of India. During their tenure, transgender were used as slave who used to do domestic work for the Royal people such as bathing them, massaging them, carrying litters and other house hold work. Since these men were considered to be women, they were consider as safe for women. So they were used to protect royal ladies when they went out of fort. It was believed that since they did not had families, would remain with the royal family till their fag end. Many a time they became ears to kings and queens, and conveyed secret messages as well. Their for even being a slave they had a important role to be played in the society.

Mid-way hrough **15th century**, **Mughal** started evading India and started establishing their kingdom. Among other people of the society eunuch or the transgender played an important role in the society. They were

guard of Harems of Mughalempers, and thus were required in thousands of numbers. They would play with young prince and princess, guard them and teach them moral values and ethics. Some of them were so loyal to the Royalty that they were considered to be the only means to reach the emperor. They were carrier of secret messages among the royalty. During the Mughal era they were paid suitably. The importance was so much that they used to dress in bright clothes, wear heavy makeup and wear bright perfumes. But as the Mughal royalty started descending, the importance and the status of transgender in the society also started diminishing.

But, the **British** rulers in India tried to eradicate the Transgender community from India. They categorized hijaras as a “criminal tribe” under the ‘Criminal Tribes Act’ of 1871.

2. Modern India

Still, people in India consider them as a boon to grant blessing on any auspicious occasion. They are considered to be bearer of luck, prosperity and fertility. But all this is not able to save them from possible discriminations from the society. They belong to the extreme lower class of the society and are most often discarded by the people.

They got right to vote only in **1994** and in **2014** in the historical order by the honorable Supreme Court of India, transgender were recognized as the third gender of the society. They will belong to backward class and get all reservation rights as per government laws. They got their right to education and voted for the very first time in 2014 general elections. Still, for a longest period of time, “transgender” have been excluded from participation in social and cultural life, politics and decision making process. Rather they have been subject to gender discrimination, gender harassment, violence, denial of services and unfair

treatment at public and private places .for all long transgender have been treated a unnatural and as an object of both mockery and fear

3. Current Problem

Exclusion– ever since British rule transgender have faced prejudice against in India. This prejudice is often translated into brutal violence at public places, police stations, prisons and at times in their homes as well.

If we, have a close look at Fig – 1, we can find that in present circumstances, there are three basic kinds of exclusions of Transgender in India –

1. Exclusion from Social and Cultural Participation –
 - a. Exclusion from family and society
 - b. No protection from violence
 - c. Limited entry in education sector , health services and public spaces
2. Exclusion from Economy
 - a. Exclusion from economy
 - b. Exclusion from livelihood and employment opportunities
3. Exclusion from Citizen Participation
 - a. Limited entry to collectiviasion
 - b. Limited rights to citizenship
 - c. Limited right to participation in community decision making process

Though, the situation has changed after the honorable Supreme Court judgment in 2014, the perception of Indian society mindset and their behavior towards Transgender has not changed much.

Low level of poverty– they scrape out their living by begging , (this may include singing in train and bus and collecting money /begging at traffic signals/ forcefully blessing people at public places a common scenario in Delhi and collecting money etc.), doing

humdrum jobs and in some cases sex work too. Their low level background make them susceptible towards harassment by the police.

Less education- Till most recently they were denied right towards education. Thus because of no education they could not get government or private jobs.

Discrimination and ignorance – the class and gender discrimination has made the Transgender group most disempowered group in India. They are threaten of lively hood and thus do mean jobs for their living.

Lack of Medical Facility– due to lack of shelter, education and medical facilities these transgender, are more often prone to various kinds of health risk and setbacks. Since they are deprived of medical facilities in private and public health care system, most of them go to quacks for instant remedy. There due to lack of knowledge and hygiene transgender they become suspect to many contagious diseases.

Carrier of various contagious diseases such as HIV - living in poor hygienic conditions and trading themselves with sex work make them most vulnerable to drugged and contagious diseases such as HIV AIDS.

Alcohol and drug use – it is a fact that a large number Transgender take Alcohol or various other kind of drugs such as, ganja, hashish, brown sugar, cocaine, etc. This is mainly because they want to forget various kinds of hazards they face in their daily life. Consumption of such drugs lead them to risky sexual behavior and sexually transmitted diseases. At times due to lack of money they also use, used syringes to insert drugs into their veins.

Harassment and extortion–since they do not have secure homes and mostly wander in open areas they become much susceptible towards extortion of money and being targeted as sexual objects. A study conducted

by UNDP, in 2007 reported the percentage of various types of harassment which is reflected in Fig 2 –

Fig - 2, Various Types of Harassment of Transgender, 2007

The above figure indicates various categories of harassment of Transgender stands as – Threat of Life – 24%, Blackmail for money – 31%, Verbal Abuse – 56%, Physical Abuse – 44% and Forced Sex at 46%.

Unemployment–unemployment is one of the major problems of the Transgender. The employers are not much interested in giving jobs to the transgender. There are some example of transgender running their small Dhabas, or pan shops. But they can be taken as exceptions. Since, they do not have much employment opportunities they resort to sex jobs or begging as their livelihood. In an unprecedented move recently, LIC has started recruiting Transgender as their agents.

Lack of social Welfare Schemes for Transgender

3. The Vicious Cycle of being a Transgender

- At the time of their birth or 7 – 8 years later when the parents realize the actual of their child. Due to societal pressure

and fear of the truth of their child coming in open, in most of the cases they disown their child. This is the first step of the vicious cycle.

- Now, since the parents disown the child he has nowhere to go. Schools also are not very open to having a transgender child in their institution. They fear that parents of other children may resort to objections of having such a child in their premises. Also education needs money in India and since such child is not supported by their parents they do not have enough money to pay for their education. This is the second step of the vicious cycle.
- Less education, in turn leads to less employment opportunity. In any case before 2014, there were negligible opportunities of employment for transgender. The reason was there was only two sex column Male and Female. After 2014 judgment now the government and private bodies have to have a third column for Transgender. But this does not improve their situation. As in present condition transgender are already uneducated. To educate them and bring them to a level where they can be employed will take another 20 years. This is the third step of the vicious cycle.
- Since the education is less they come under the lowest strata of the society where poverty is at its peak. They live in slums under the most unhygienic conditions. They thus become susceptible to various disease and crime. This is the fourth step of the vicious cycle.
- Combined with less education and poverty, transgender adopt to the lowest means of earning such as sex trade, selling of drugs, begging and some low level of crime. This is the fifth step of vicious cycle.
- Since they resort to above actions, they are again disowned by their families and the vicious cycle continues.

4. Action required for potential development of Transgender Community –

Need to implement 2014, Supreme Court ruling in letter and spirit - though the supreme court ruling is out for last one year now, the social stigma still continues . The implementation of this historic ruling is still not in picture. The harassment and marginalization of the community still continues. The social prejudice still exists against Transgender. Although transgender have been taken as backward community and they will be entitled for all benefits in education and jobs still the government and private agencies need to start focusing on implementing the order so that the benefits start reaching to the transgender community.

Need for Education –education is the basic right of every human being. For a very long time transgender have been deprived from attaining education. Now with Supreme Court ruling it's a new dawn for the transgender. But we need to enlighten the transgender about education and the benefits they can derive. The agencies need to advocate transgender to involve themselves in education. Schools and colleges need to open their doors to the community. Teaching community need to take special interest in education of Transgender and help them to attain success. More than anything it's the willingness of the transgender community to study hard and come out successful.

Need for better Health Care facilities – Since the transgender live in the most unhygienic conditions they are prone to various diseases. For a very long time since they have been denied from public and private health services, they often resort to quacks and thus the prolonged illness starts. Now doctors, health care specialists, policy makers and community service operators, will have to come in front and take the charge. We also need to educate transgender community about personal hygiene and various other health issues.

Need for separate HIV Surveillance – since most of the Transgender are involved in various sex acts under the most unhygienic conditions they are more susceptible to HIV /AIDS. There is a greater need to set up a separate HIV Surveillance for Transgender community to educate them on fair sex practices. Transgender who have HIV / AIDS should have fair access to the treatment and care.

Need to provide Holistic Care – since the transgender have been harassed by the publicly, socially and privately many of them live under continuous depression and thus resort to drugs and other practices. There is a strong need for counselling, both mentally and socially. There is a need of a comprehensive approach that includes health and social services for transgender people.

Need to involve transgender in community – decision – making process – transgender

have been socially deprived for a very long time in India. After they were allowed to vote in 1994 we have seen few political leaders from the Transgender community such as Shabnammausi – MP , Madhya Pradesh, 1998, Kamla Jan – Transgender Mayor of Katini . MP, 1999, Asha Devi – Transgender Mayor of Gorakhpur, 2000, Madhukinnar transgender mayor of India – Raigarh, Chhatisghar. But, due to lack of education they were not able to give back to the society the much needed support.

There is a greater need to involve Transgender in community decision making process such as to involve them in HIV surveillance for their own community, involve them in the education process of Transgender and also to implement the Supreme Court order.

5. Conclusion

It is now time for Indian authorities to implement the Supreme Court directives and bring the transgender to the main stream community. The authorities should also work towards ending the discrimination against the transgender and take care of their protection and social needs.

There is also a need to spread larger awareness campaign in public for the acceptability of the Transgender community. They should be welcomed with open arms in educational institutions, health care systems, work place both public and private, should be treated equally under the law and by the police. They should be provided proper medical facilities which includes health insurance and subsidized treatment.

For the general public it is important to understand the feelings and mental status of the Transgender community. People need to understand that humans are diverse but after all every one is a Human being. Transgender community has a right to behave and live they are and express their feelings without any fear.

The society needs to take off their social stigma towards transgender community and give them a chance to stand equally and participate in together in the community development process.

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MENACE OF CHILD LABOUR: A QUESTION OF COMMITMENT OF HUMAN RIGHTS

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Delegation to the 1st **International Congress on Human Rights & Duties**
(Regd: **02ICHRD2015**)

Abstracts:

Transgender Human rights of child have a legal recognition at International & national level but deprived socio-economic conditions are responsible for exploitation of their rights. This article examines issues for incessant violations as well as provides duty-bound suggestions to uplift human rights of children from menace of child labour.

Keywords: *transgender, human, rights, legal, child labour*

Children form an important asset and soul of any state because they are sole future of such state. It is the duty of state, that, the attention shall be given to ensure that all children shall get proper care, atmosphere, adequate training, education, guidance. So that they will have knowledge to exercise, ask for their interests, rights. But unfortunately, millions of children, across the world, are forced to work as child labourers due to various serious causes. In spite of prohibition by Child labour, various laws, it still continues to prevail, & leads to exploitation, abuse and deprivation of child rights. It has become as universal issue. The issue of the child labour is one of the major human rights issues & mark over its commitments. and is highly sensitive one too. The problem of child labour hampers not only developed nations but developing nations as well. The survival and continuation of child labour is a challenge to the matured human society. It is

really a nuisance and shame upon the society; dishonor for the world of the mankind, a difficulty which may annihilate the economic backbone of the country.

1. CHILD LABOUR: CONCEPTUAL OUTLOOK

The concept of child labour is very complex and difficult one to express and explain. The perfect definition of child labour is neither available in national context nor in international level. But there are several different legislations, institutions have differently defined the concept of child labour as per political, social, economic situations. Basically, the word 'child labour' is an amalgamation of two aspects, i.e. 'child' in terms of his in order to age, and

'labour' in terms of its work culture, amount of work and income generating capacity.¹

The word 'labour' is a notorious conception to define, especially in the background of

child labour and child work. Generally, child labour used as synonyms to the child work. However all work is not hazardous or bad for children because some basic, simple work, properly controlled and regulated, is not child labour. Therefore, it implies that work which derives from activities such as leisure, play and education are not child labour. It can be said that, 'Child labour', is the work which includes some extent exploitation, violations namely, physical, mental, economic and social rights which impairs the growth and health development of children.

According to V. V. Giri, Former President of India and Labour Minister portrayed in tow angles i.e. child labour is nothing but the "economic practice" and "social evil". It shows the negative aspect of child labour. According to him, the economic practice denotes the employment of Children in productive occupations as accumulation to the total income of the family. Secondly, 'social evil' implies that, nature of the jobs in which children are occupied, the menace to which they are exposed and it leads to denial of the opportunities of development.²

At International Level, International Labour Organization(ILO) has given comprehensive definition of child labour. According to ILO, "Child Labour includes children prematurely leading adult lives, working long hours for low wages under conditions damaging to

their health and to their physical and mental development, sometimes separated from their families, frequently deprived of meaningful education and training opportunities that could open up for them a better future".³

In India, as per the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act 1986, employment of children up to the age of 14 years and in case of hazardous employment p to 18 years is defined as 'child labour'. Again this aspect, completely changes the definition of child only.

Therefore, the concept of child labour has many facets. It has become a complex problem at national and international fronts. The deep rooted socio-economic political causes are present in each of the socio-economic fabric of the society. Hence, there are various approaches to define and understand the concept of child labour. So it may not be wise to rely on one single approach to deal with it. There are many factors responsible to this complex problem, so a comprehensive integrated approach is required to tackle and combat child labour. This can be done only by bringing attitudinal change, and social awareness and rigorous campaign against the problem of child labour. Thus, it requires honest effort and strong commitment and support from all concerned.

2. CHILD LABOUR : THE PROBLEM

The child labour has become a social evil when people started exploiting the children of tender age. At rural areas and even in many of urban areas, the children of school going age are found in factories, hotels,

¹ P.P. Jayanti, "Child Labour A Socio-Legal Study", Vol.I (1998) *Kerala University Journal of Legal Studies, Department of Law, University of Kerala, Tiruvantapuram*, p.143.

² Child labour in India : A socio-economic and legal study, Dr. H.M. Mittal, *Journal of the legal studies*, p.no, 74

³ Children in globalizing world : Challenging Our Conscience, Enakshi Ganguly Thukral, *HAQ Centre for Child Rights*, 2002 – p.no. 278

industries, street workers, trafficked, beedi workers, agricultural field which deprives opportunities for normal, physical, mental and social growth and development. The causes of child to join the hands to such fields at initial age of childhood are many. The problem of child labour is present existed in different parts of the world. There are various attempts made by international authorities from time-to-time to remove child labour.

Apart from the poverty, there are several issues and causes keeps alive the menace of child labour. They may be broadly grouped as follows:

- a. *Inadequate income of head of the family*
- b. *Inappropriate distribution of wealth, assets and land*
- c. *Poor implementation of legislations of compulsory education*
- d. *Preference of employers to children as cheap availability*
- e. *Illiteracy / uneducated backwardness of family members*
- f. *Socio-economic, cultural factors*
- g. *Lack of Political will to eradicate and prohibit child labour*
- h. *Poor implementation of rehabilitation schemes*
- i. *Rampant increase of urbanization and industrialization*
- j. *Lack of implementation of scheme of family allowances*
- k. *Ancient zamindari and bonded labour system*
- l. *Early marriages*
- m. *Dowry system*
- n. *Polygamy*
- o. *Illiteracy*

There have been consistent efforts in past two decades to reduce the menace of child labour. In this regard, a very substantial role

has played by employers and workers and their organizations. Earlier Child bonded labour in India is regularly seen in the agricultural sector but has in recent years, it has been reflecting into other parts as well such as commercial sexual child trafficking, beedi workers, brick kilns, carpet weaving, construction, fireworks and matches factories, hotels, hybrid cottonseed production, leather, mines, quarries, silk, synthetic gems, etc. On other side, as per 2011 census, globally child labour is on the decrease side. Though it cannot to be stopped completely, but it can be minimize, reduced or curtail. From a total of 246 million girls and boys in child labour in 2000, the figure reduced to 11% to 218 million in 2004, with a further decline to 215 million by 2010. The number of children in hazardous child labour has fallen more swiftly, with a 26% decline in the period from 171 million to 126 million and a further decline to 115 million by 2010. However, as an ILO report on hazardous child labour notes, "Progress has been uneven, neither fast enough nor comprehensive enough to reach the 2016 goal."⁴

In 2013, another report was published by ILO, wherein the thematic focus was on Child labour and social protection. In 2015, ILO through its research and World Report, aimed to assess the relationship between child labour and youth employment. In this report, ILO has focused on age group of 15-17 years category workers in securing decent jobs.

⁴ Employers' and workers' Handbook on Hazardous work, ILO Office, 2011, http://www.ilo.org/public/english/dialogue/actemp/downloads/projects/cl_handbook.pdf

3. ROLE OF JUDICIARY : PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS OF CHILDREN

The Supreme Court of India has been playing an vital role, to protect the basic rights of poor children by interpreting the Constitutional and Statutory provisions in liberal manner, which are relating to employment of children in its judicial decisions. If one needs to do survey of

judicial precedents in India, The Supreme Court of India has been a very keen and effective in interpreting and widening the scope of human rights of children. The Supreme Court, to help the poor children, changed its attitude towards “traditional rule of *locus standi*” and adopted the liberalized rule of standing.⁵ The Supreme Court accepted letters and telegrams, which came by way of public interest litigations, and converted them as writ petitions to safeguard the rights of the poor children and to protect them from hazardous employment. In the *Asiad Workers’* case⁶ the Supreme Court observed that, “the construction work is undoubtedly hazardous for children, though, it is not mentioned in the Employment of Children Act, 1938.” The Supreme Court in this case further stated that, “even the Article 24 of the Constitution of India prohibits the employment of children below 14 years of age in a factory, mine, or in any other hazardous employment.” Therefore, the implementation of provisions of the Constitution of India has to be strictly done by every State Government and it must ensure that the constitutional mandate of article 24 shall not be violated in any part of the country.

In *Salal Hydro Project’s* case⁷ the Supreme Court uphold that the child labour issue was an economic problem and it is not possible be solved merely by legislation, till there is ‘poverty and destitution’ in this country. The Supreme Court highlighted the root cause child labour in Indian Context. The activist

Supreme Court in this case gave commendable suggestions to the State of Jammu & Kashmir to start schools close to the construction sites so as to facilitate the children of workers of the project to attend the school. In another instance, The Supreme Court in *Sheela Barse vs. Secretary, Children Aid Society*⁸ has protected the basic human rights of children who are staying in the Observation Homes. The Supreme Court in this case directed Maharashtra state Government to take quick action to implement the law, act upon the requirements as per the Constitutional Provisions and directions made by the High Court of Bombay and also by the Supreme Court of India. In the noted case, *M. C. Mehta Vs. State of Tamil Nadu*⁹ emphasized on emphasized on the implementation of the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986. It strengthened to provide the free and compulsory education for all children until they attain the age of 14 years as per Article 45 of the Constitution of India. Along with that, The Supreme court also directed that, the offenders of the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986, have to pay a compensation of Rs. 20,000 for every child employed. It has to be deposited in district-wise fund known as “Child Labour Rehabilitation-cum-Welfare Fund”, it will be used only for child purpose. In addition

⁵ Pritam Kumar Ghosh, *Judicial Activism And Public Interest Litigation In India*, 2013 GJLS Vol.1, No.1,p.79

⁶ *People's Union For Democratic Rights And Others Vs. Union Of India & Others*, AIR 1982 SC 1473

⁷ *Labourers Working On Salal Hydro Electric Project vs. State Of Jammu And Kashmir*, (1984) 3 SCC 538

⁸ AIR 1987 SC 656

⁹ (1996) 6 SCC 756

to that, the court also directed that the parents, guardians, family members of the child should be given a job in lieu of the child.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Children have been considered as most valuable human resources of nation. The potential any social welfare state depends upon growth and development of children. The great poet Milton said "Child Shows the man as morning shows the day". It is not only the question of rights of children but also the duties that needs to be discharged by parents, society, private & public sectors for augmentation of child rights. they are the true custodians and messengers of culture, traditions, ideology, philosophies. Children are the future custodians and torch bearers of the Society: they are the messengers of our knowledge, cultural heritage, ideologies and philosophies. Children are really future components in the form of great teachers, scientists, judges, rulers, doctors, planners, engineers, politicians on whom the entire society founded (rests). Unfortunately millions of children are deprived of their childhood due to issues like child labour, due to which they are deprived from exercising their right to education and thereby they are subjected to exploitation and abuse.

In this regard, the author wants to put forth some suggestions for promotion and protection of child rights from menace of child labour to fulfill its commitment of human rights. In school, the child should make aware of their rights and duties by a appointing a councilor, so it becomes easy for them to identify injustices and to approach to particular authority. The help line numbers in simple form shall be make available for children for 24x7 at local,

rural areas. The police machinery shall be more concerned and voluntarily responsive towards sticking problems of child labour. Child awareness campaigns needs to be

organized to encouraging individuals towards issues related with children. Coordination among commissions and Non-governmental Organizations is required for more efficient outcome towards reducing child labour. Documentations of different laws, policies, and schemes shall be making available in local, regional languages, so that it will reach upto grass-root levels. In addition to that, more empirical research is required to understand impact of child advocacy initiatives.

JUVENILE RIGHTS OF INDIVIDUALS IN MENTAL HEALTH SETUP

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 21ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Juvenile Delinquency which is widely prevalent in various parts of India with different gear is now a major problem in the study of criminology and sociology. This paper is a summary of thorough investigation into the different causes and law of juvenile delinquency in India with reference to human right and socio- psychological perspective.

Keywords: *Juvenile, Delinquency, Psychology, Rights, Children*

Juvenile delinquency¹ is an integral part of criminology. The two cannot be separated since one of the reasons for crime and its continuance into adult life is the ineffective control and treatment of juveniles. Juvenile delinquency is a big breeding centre of criminals.

Section 2 (1) of the Juvenile Justice Act, 2000 has defined- "*juvenile in conflict with law*" as a juvenile who is alleged to have committed an offence and has not completed eighteenth year of age as on the date of commission of such offence"

¹ The word juvenile has been derived from the Latin term juvenis, which means young. In the year 1484, **William Coxtton** used the word delinquent to describe a person who was found guilty. Juvenile delinquency refers to the involvement by the teenagers in an unlawful behavior who is usually under the age of 18 and commits an act which would be considered as a crime. A child is known as a delinquent when he/she commits a mistake which is against the law and which is not accepted by the society. Thus a "juvenile" or "child" means a person who has not completed eighteenth years of age and violates the law and commits an offence under the legal age of maturity (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)).

Physical, mental, moral and spiritual development of the children makes them capable of realizing his/her fullest potential. On the contrary, harmful surroundings, negligence of basic needs, wrong company and other abuses may turn a child to a delinquent. Children constitute about 40% of India's population and India has a National Policy for Children declaring children to be a national asset. Even so majority of India's children continue to be in difficult circumstances. India has signed the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and obligated itself to work towards ensuring all the rights enshrined therein to all its children. India has witnessed an increase both in crimes committed by children and those committed against them. There has been 97.9% increase in crimes committed by children between 2003 and 2004, with more children being appeared for arson, theft and cheating.

Over 33,000 juveniles, mostly between the age group of 16 to 18, have been arrested for crimes like rape and murder across Indian states in 2011, the highest in last decade. A juvenile and five others were arrested by Delhi Police for brutally raping

and assaulting a 23-year-old girl in the national capital on December 16, 2012. Lowering the age limit for juvenile delinquents from 18 years to 16 years is not the answer to the city's crime spiral, women and child rights activists said on Wednesday after getting together to demand a dialogue with the Centre on the draft Juvenile Justice (Care & Protection of Children) Bill, 2014.

The campaign follows Union minister for women and child development Maneka Gandhi's recent statement that juveniles involved in serious crimes like rape should be tried as adults. Her statement has revived the debate on the juvenile age issue that was first raked up after the **Nirbhaya gang rape in December 2012. (TOI)**

According to the latest National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) report 2012, crimes involving children have increased from 0.8 % (2001) to 11.8 % (2011). This report also shows the data on juvenile delinquency that children apprehended under both Indian Penal Code (IPC) and Special and Local Law (SLL) has increased from 30,303 (2010) to 33,887 (2011). In addition to other crime heads, kidnapping and abduction committed by juveniles have also registered a noticeable increase from 2008 to 2011. While kidnapping and abduction committed by a juvenile was recorded at 354 in 2008 and it inflated to 823 during 2011. NCRB data also shows that there are a growing number of girl children in criminal activities and it estimated that from 5.1 % (2010) which increased to 5.8 % (2011). NCRB data points out that a majority of juveniles are mostly involved in the crimes such as theft, hurting, burglary, and riots. As a child rights worker Nicole Manezes pointed out that only 1.1 % of all I.P.C crimes were committed by the juveniles in the year 2011. It has been claimed by the news channels that children who are under 18 years of age are committing heinous crimes and day by day it is rising. According to the NCRB (2011), only 1.1 % of all I.P.C were committed by the juveniles, and 4.5 % of all crimes committed by the juveniles were rape and only 3.5 % of all rapes were

committed by the juveniles. In a National Study on child abuse (2007), the Ministry of Women and Child Development found that two out of every three children had been physically abused, and 53.22 % of children reported that they faced sexual abuse.

Due to the immaturity of the child, he/she easily gets motivated by what he/she sees around him/her. It is the environment and social context that provokes his actions. In a developing country like India, juvenile crimes are steadily rising due to the persistent poverty, unemployment, inequalities and changing values, etc. in spite of these factors there are some more factors such as crimes shows that are shown on the television, media, increasing population, adverse effects of peer pressure, lavish lifestyle, too much freedom from the parents, social maladjustment, and family disintegration.

1. Human rights and mentally ill patient:

Every human body and mind has an integrity which is inviolable. Every human being has certain irreducible barest minimum needs such as right to air, potable water, food, clothing, health, medical care and treatment, clean and hygienic conditions for living accommodation, environmental sanitation, personal hygiene and so on. Deprivation of any one of these amounts to violence to the person. Every human being is entitled to be treated with dignity, decency, equality and freedom regardless of the fact that we are born differently, grow differently, and are different in our mental makeup, thought processes and life-style. Negation of this would mean negation of human rights.

A person with mental illness is entitled to treatment with the same dignity and decency as any other human being. A mentally ill person does not become a non person merely on account of certain disabilities. His human rights flow from the fundamental right to life as in Article 21 of the Constitution which includes:

- Right to living accommodation, food, potable water, education, health, medical treatment, decent livelihood, income, a clean and congenial existence
- Right to privacy, speedy trial (if involved in any criminal offence), information and means of communication.

Correctional mental health refers to the provision of mental health assessment and clinical treatment in a correctional setting.

The term corrections include both the management and treatment of offenders and imply efforts to “**correct**” the persons and his and her misbehavior, presumably through some sort of rehabilitation.

Treatment team members: it includes psychiatrist, social workers, psychologist and nurses working together are called as multidisciplinary model.

Psychiatrist: the psychiatrist plays an active role in the monitoring, evaluation and treatment of the inmates. They educate the nursing and correction staff about the medications, compliance issues and patient care risks.

Social workers: social workers in correctional psychiatric settings have a variety of roles that range from direct patient care to liaison with outside agencies on behalf of their clients. Social workers direct care delivery is most commonly done through counseling and other therapeutic modalities, such as individual and group therapy. In addition, social worker can mobilize appropriate resources to aid inmates with community reinsertion in appropriate discharge planning.

Psychologists: jail and prison employ psychologist more frequently than any other mental health professionals. They are working in jails and prisons conduct crisis, individual and group psychotherapy as

well as perform psychological evaluations for the courts or for classification purposes.

Nursing staff: as in other environment nurses are in correctional setting are the frontline staff when it comes to inmate contact (Weinstein et al 2005). Nurses have a variety of essential duties, including dispensing medication, patient education and identification of signs and symptoms of mental illness.

2. Correctional roles in mental health setting:

- Identifying the social as well as psychological strains effective in the causation of offending behavior. Modifying the offender’s environment, so that strains toward conformity are substituted by those, which press toward criminal deviance?
- Acceptance of delinquent and criminal deviants without condoning anti-social behavior.
- Scientific interest in the contributions of social structure to causation and treatment as well as in psychological determinants.
- Readiness to work experimentally and without undue discouragement in a field where present knowledge is limited, prognosis is uncertain, and failures frequent.
- These roles help the professional social worker to deal more effectively with the offender, i.e., for the reformation and rehabilitation of the offender.
- Social worker helps to strengthen motivation of delinquents and criminals. Through talking with them sympathetically and understandingly, the social worker aids them.
- The correctional social worker allows the offenders to ventilate their feelings. Most offenders need to share with someone, in confidence, their inner feelings, their fear and frustrations, as well as their hopes and aspirations.
- In correctional settings, the social worker provides a safe emotional climate in

which offenders can express and verbalize them.

- The social worker provides needed information to offenders in correctional settings. By giving information, the probation and parole officer can help offenders to make decisions. The probation officer does not make decisions for the probationers, but he helps them to consider rationally, their problems and the alternatives which they have. By defining situations and problems, the social worker helps the offender.
- He assists the offender not only in thinking about a problem, but also in feeling about the situation.
- The social worker also assists the offender in modifying his environment. With his knowledge of community resources, the social worker is able to help the offender and his family to tap different kinds of financial and social resources to meet their needs.

3. Prevalence of psychiatric disorder in correctional setting:

Psychotic disorders-Both the lifetime and current prevalence rates of psychotic disorders in correctional setting appear to be significantly higher than those found in large epidemiological studies conducted in the community. Individuals with the diagnosis of schizophrenia, for example are more likely to be arrested for trespassing, theft, property destruction, assault, drug possession, or drug sales (Prince et al. 2007)

Substance use disorders-The term substance use disorders refers to either substance abuse or dependence. Substance use increases the risk of criminal involvement, re offence and poor institutional adjustment. Inmates with a history of substance abuse tend to have increased numbers of disciplinary sanctions and suicide attempts (peters et al. 1998).

Mood disorders-Major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder and other affective disorder are more prevalent in sample of incarcerated individuals than in general population samples. This information is relevant given the relationship between some affective disorders, such as bipolar disorder and incarceration. For example men with bipolar disorder tend to have a higher prevalence of criminal behavior than do men with unipolar depression or psychiatrically healthy matched control (Modestin et al. 1997)

Anxiety disorders-The prevalence of anxiety disorder including post traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), is higher among incarcerated individuals than among their community counterparts. this fact is relevant for mental health professionals working correctional setting given the association between specific anxiety disorder such as PTSD in men, and suicidal ideation(Cogle et al. 2009)

Personality disorders-Maladaptive and pervasive patterns of behavior that interfere with one's function are highly prevalent in correctional setting. Impulsivity proneness to anger irritability and disregard for societal norms not only can have a negative impact on an individual's life but also can result in arrest and incarceration (Trestman 2000). In addition, antisocial and borderline personality disorders show a high degree of co morbidity with substance abuse, which further increase the likelihood of criminal behavior (Zlotnick et al. 2008). Given this findings, the fact that the prevalence rate of some personality disorders are significantly higher in jails and prisons than in community setting.

4. Elaboration of Main Causes

Psychological causes

It is commonly observed that intelligent persons in teenagers perform delinquent acts in rather refined manner. Early studies by Goring (1913), Goddard (1921), found low intelligence as the single factor influencing juvenile delinquency. In India, Kundu (1969) found delinquents to be of inferior intelligence. In contrast, some researchers have found delinquents to be more intelligent. Muthayya and Bhaskaran (1964) found delinquents to be slightly more intelligent than normals.

Social causes

Mobility-This factor is responsible for crime causation in the society. The rapid growth of industrialization and urbanization has led to expansion of means to communication, travel facilities and propagations of views through press and platform. Migration of persons to new places where they are strangers offers them opportunity for crime as chances of detection are minimized considerably.

Cultural conflict -In a dynamic society, social change is an inevitable phenomenon. The impact of modernization urbanization and industrialization in a rapidly changing society may sometimes result in social disorganization and this may led to culture conflicts between different valves of different sections of society. India has faced this problem during Indo-Pak partition days in 1947 and Bangladesh in 1971. There was in flood of 'Refugees' from Sindh and North West frontiers region in 1947, which broke down their traditional social structure of Indian Society and resulted into enormous increase in crime.

Family background-Sutherland said that the family background has greatest influence on the criminal behavior of offender or Juvenile. The Children are apt to imbibe criminal tendencies, if they find their

parents or members of the family behaving in the similar manner. A child who is brought up in a broken family is likely to face an easy prey to criminality. The lack of parental control over children due to death, divorce, or desertion of parent or their ignorance or illness may furnish soothing ground for children to resort to criminal acts.

Family structure-Family is considered to be the most effective variable in socializing the child and also in serving as a source for learning various types of behavior. The nature and structure of the family are largely responsible for carving out the personality make-up of the children. A functionally adequate family encourages growth, confidence, frankness and ability to face reality. Delinquents mostly come from functionally inadequate homes (Carr and Srivastava).

Broken homes-means a home where either of the parents is dead or living separately or is divorced or that parents are drug addicts or the parents or any other member of the family often fights with each other. In such circumstances, the child feels disowned and insecure. He is exposed to the anti-social activities, which he adopts to satisfy himself and in the process, he is led towards delinquency.

Family size and type- family size has also been cited as a factor in causation of delinquent behavior in juveniles. Delinquents are found more likely to come from larger families as compared to the smaller families. Glueck (1950) found delinquent boys were more often from larger families. Andrew (1976) and Fisher (1984) also found similar results in their studies on juvenile delinquents. The type of family joint or nuclear may also cause juvenile delinquent behavior but studies in this area are still wanting. Similarly, several studies are seen here and there, emphasizing upon the large size of population to be a contributing factor to the growth of juvenile delinquency, but systematic studies are required to be done in India to investigate into this phenomenon.

Parent child relationship-The most important single factor in the developmental picture of children is relationship with their parents including parental behavior. The pattern of interpersonal relationship with a family is important in shaping the interpersonal behavior and cognition of the child (Glueck and Glueck, 1950 and Nye, 1958). According to Desai (1979), "the child needs to feel that there is at least one solid dependable fact in the changing confusion of his social relationships, that he need never doubt his parent's affection for him". But in many cases, misunderstandings, hard feelings and open conflicts occur between parent and the child.

Step parents-The behavior of step-parents is also the main cause of delinquency. When step motherly treatment is given to the child by the step parents the child tries to run away and loiter in street and other places and this also leads the child to commit offence.

Alcoholic parents-It is fact that the behavior of such parents also influences the children's behavior. When behavior of parents is not good and meaningful, behavior of child would also be biased because the mind of child is impressionable. The children of the alcoholic parents are mostly found indulging in the delinquent activities. The children also become addict to alcohol which results in their going out of control of their parents.

Excessive punishment-Excessive punishment given to the children by their parents many a time spoils the child instead of disciplining him because he may feel dejected and frustrated leading to his involvement in anti social activities for the purpose of bringing shame to the parents.

Peer group-The behavior of an individual largely depends on his peers. Some of the individuals (mostly in teen ages) form gangs in which a number of individuals associate together in group activity which often emerges into criminal tendency (Rogers, 1960).

Society-The nature of society whether democratic or authoritarian, also determines the incidence of delinquent behavior of the children in that society. Moreover, the habitat of people in society is also one of the aspects of society which tends to affect juvenile delinquency. For instance, the rural and urban settings in India are much different in terms of occupation, education and interpersonal relationship. These differences seem to have differentially affected the incidence of delinquency in these two populations and this aspect needs to be further studied.

Alcohol -It is also another major cause of crime. After consumption of alcohol one loses self-control. In families, it results in quarrel between husband, wife and children and assault on them. It creates disgusting atmosphere at home.

5. Mental health intervention models:

1. Wellness and recovery model-Mental health interventions in prisons have primarily targeted symptom reduction. Medication compliance, insight development, and behavior change are the most common objectives of treatment. Some federal court cases regarding the adequacy of treatment for inmates with severe mental illness in state hospitals have required a shift from a traditional medical symptom management model to a broader focus on wellness and recovery. Wellness is defined as "an active process through which people become aware of, and make choice towards, a more successful existence." (National wellness institute 2009). Wellness is the process through which a person in recovery is empowered to make purposeful choices that lead to a more satisfying and healthy lifestyle. It includes physical emotional intellectual social environmental occupational leisure and spiritual dimensions and incorporates disease prevention and health promotion approaches. A wellness lifestyle leads to positive outcomes that can be measured in terms of improved health status, greater productivity, enhanced social relationship, and participation in purposeful

activity- all of which provide meaningful opportunities for healing, personal growth and an improved quality of life (Swarbrick 1997, 2006)

2. Rehabilitation model

This model focus on academic classes, vocational training, substance abuse prevention and a set of core curricula relates to reduction of criminal behaviors. Individuals with severe mental illness may have difficulty participating in traditional rehabilitation programs because of psychotic and mood symptoms that lead to problem with attention, concentration or logical thinking. for individual's with severe mental illness who are returning to their communities after incarceration, effective rehabilitation programming, at minimum, needs to incorporate continuity of mental health care and address any connection between the individual's mental illness and his or her criminal behavior. They may require disability benefits, supportive housing and assistance with food and other basic needs.

Group therapy

Group therapy in the correctional setting is to provide information and build life skills. Another proposes is to opportunities for recreation and development of appropriate social interaction. In the community group therapy is usually for the purpose of peer support and for development of insight through shared experience.

Individual psychotherapy-

Individual meeting with the mental health clinicians are an established part of the standard of care for treatment of severe mental illness. Many patients in correctional setting have experienced few relationships with people who are consistent, honest, direct and caring. Patient in jail or prison often perceive mental health staff as part of bureaucracy of the correctional setting. Here the task of the therapist is to differentiate himself or herself from custody staff,

correctional counselors, legal consultants and other mental health personnel. The role of mental health clinicians is to recognize and strengthen the challenges of the individual person.

Person centered approach

The person centered approach recognizes that under adverse conditions, individuals do no fulfill their own potential for growth. The model maintains the following three conditions are necessary to provide a climate conducive to growth and therapeutic change:

- ✓ Unconditional positive regard
- ✓ Empathic understanding
- ✓ Congruence (authentic, genuine presentation of the clinicians).

Therapeutic community treatment

Therapeutic community treatment is used successfully with incarcerated individuals who tend to value peer influence over advice from those in position of power, including treatment providers. TC is originally used as treatment specifically for substance abuse disorders; the perspective of TC treatment has expanded to include difficult behaviors in all aspect of life. Here participates learn through interaction with peers in the community setting, designed to promote wellness, how to change dysfunctional behaviors and acquire positive life skills.

Cognitive behavior therapy

The focus of CBT is on the interaction of the three domain of human behavior: Thought, Emotion & Behavior. Simply put, because thinking affects behavior by modifying thoughts, long term behavior changes can be affected. CBT can be delivered by trained practitioners in either group or individual settings, is a mainstay of treatment in various correctional setting because it is useful in targeting problem

behaviors and maladaptive patterns of thinking.

Dialectical behavioral therapy

DBT is cognitive behavioral approach to treatment that includes perspectives akin to eastern philosophy. (Linehan 2003) It is used in treating the serious problem of the behavior for examples self injurious behavior, violence toward others etc. this form of therapy has particularly targeted inmates with borderline disorder, who constitute a significant minority of jail and prison population. (Chaiken et al. 2005)

Behavioral incentive programs

Behavioral incentive programs and token economies have a long been used to help mental health patients change maladaptive behaviors. Here inmates are given opportunities to earn privileges by exhibiting appropriate behavior and participating in beneficial activities designed by their treatment teams.

Vocational training

It is an important part of a comprehensive program of treatment. It teaches those skills and information necessary to perform a job after release and allows them to work in a sheltered environment before entry into the community (Santamour and West 1982). Vocational training also provides opportunity to engage in meaningful, productive work that decreases behavioral issues and increases feelings of self worth (Shivey 2004). (Haley 1996) advocated for multistage vocational training that deals with vocational training before and after release from prison.

6. Conclusion

An incarcerated individual have a right to quality mental health treatment. Quality mental health requires collaboration between mental health care providers, family members and agencies. Treatment

intervention should meet the need of these individuals especially reentry into their communities. Treatment planning extends beyond the reduction of symptoms to include spiritual, social, educational, and vocational and reentry needs of the population.

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SOCIO-CULTURAL IMPEDIMENTS TO UNDERSTANDING ADOLESCENT FEMALE SEXUALITY IN NIGERIA: AN INTERVENTIONIST PERSPECTIVE

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 06ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Nigerian society has recently been saddled with rising cases of teenage pregnancy, abortions, drop-out, single parenthood and high-profile death cases among female adolescents hinged on various cultural constraints which are multi-faceted. This research was designed to address prevalent cultural barriers of female sexuality in southern Nigeria. Paper was anchored on socio-psychological theories of behaviour and adopted the use of thematic content analysis to interpret the Qualitative data derived from interviews involving forty participants in line with study objectives. Findings revealed that Nigerian cultural orientation hinders rather than help the understanding of female sexuality. Thus, it made a case for government intervention through nationwide sensitization/re-orientation and introduction of comprehensive sex education into the Nigerian school curricula to effectively eliminate adverse cultural impediments to female sexuality.

Keywords: *Adolescence, sexuality, Nigeria, Teenage, Pregnancy*

There is no man or woman who does not face in his or her lifetime the concerns of sexual tensions (Society for Obstetricians & Gynecologists-Canada). From 1960's onward, the global support for sexuality discourse on a comprehensive scale gained widespread support. Experts on issues of sexuality have stressed the need for broader sexual health concerns due to low quality of sexuality education most societies formerly imbibed (SIECUS, 2009). They frowned that the narrow reserve of sexual expression only in marriage has predisposed most adolescents¹ to unhealthy and risky

sexual behaviors which ultimately affects Sexual Reproductive Health-SRH (Planned Parenthood Federation of America, 2012).

This worldwide crusade for understanding on sexuality² issues among adolescents

“adolescents” is often a general term used to refer to persons between this ranges.

² **Sexuality** on the other hand is simply defined as, an integral part of who we are, what we believe in, what we feel and how we respond to others. It also goes beyond to include concerns of gender identity, gender roles, sexual orientations, body image, sexual experiences, thoughts, ideas, fantasies, feelings etc (Quint 2015). The Merriam – Webster online dictionary similarly defined sexuality as sexual habits and desires of a person which is translated into the quality or state of being sexual. Thus, the need to point out that sexuality is usually influenced by the interaction of biological, psychological, social, economic, legal, political, ethical, historical, religious and spiritual factors (WHO, 2006a).

¹ The word adolescence is a coinage from a Latin Verb “adolescere” meaning “to grow into maturity”. This therefore follows that adolescence is a process which in turn is part of the five stages of human development spanning from; infancy, childhood, adolescence, adulthood to old age (Olakunle, 2007). This usually include persons between the ages of 10 and 19 which falls within WHO's definition of young persons' between ages of 10 and 24. This accounts for why

attracted the call to the first international conference on population held in Bucharest in 1974 which led many countries of the world into the joint resolve to start engaging adolescents³ positively on sexuality issues (UNFPA, 1994; Odumegwu, 2005). The gesture was thus believed to have spearheaded a national guidance task force convened in America in 1990, comprising of renowned professionals, employed to design effective curricula for comprehensive sexuality education⁴ which birthed a coalition body known as the Sexuality Information and Education of the United States (SIECUS) currently having 140-member organizations jointly boosting comprehensive, effective and curricular based programs throughout America (SIECUS, 2009; Planned Parenthood Federation of America, 2012).

Many countries also took positive step to safeguard the lives of their adolescents and young persons. Eko et al (2013) gave an expose of some countries across Europe that imbibed new approach to sexuality education; Western Europe in the early 60s, Sweden since 1966 when sexuality education become a mandatory school curricular, Germany since 1970 and by 1992, it became a government duty by law. Furthermore, in Japan, sex education became mandatory

³ Encyclopedia Britannica submitted that that the concept of “adolescence” is narrowly equated with “puberty” and also loosely used interchangeably with the word “teen”, and adolescents are thus often referred to as “teenagers” who often experience heightened urge for adventure and experimentation as a result of various physical changes which culminates in sexual and reproductive maturity.

⁴ The interconnectedness of sexuality to almost every facet of human life affirms the importance of **Sexuality education** which is also referred to as **family life education** and simply defined as “the means of impacting the complete knowledge on sexuality”, usually taking two forms- abstinence-only and comprehensive sexuality education (Mckee, 2008). Conversely, Collins (2008) attempted the definition of comprehensive sexuality education as encompassing “education about all aspects of sexuality including family planning, reproduction, body image, sexual orientation, sexual pleasure, values, decision-making, communication, dating, relationships, STDs and how to avoid them, as well as birth control methods”.

from age 10 or 11years, while in China and Sri Lanka, it comprised compulsory readings in biology textbooks.

All these efforts were mainly targeted at adolescents at young persons of these nations because this stage was generally observed to be the formative years when behavior and character traits have not been fully formed as well as the period when they reach sexual maturity before they actually develop the mental, emotional and social skills needed to appreciate the consequences of engaging in sexual attitudes (UNFPA, 1994; Benzaken, Palep & Gill, 2011).

Conversely however and despite the sweeping global crusade for comprehensive sex education, most sub-Saharan African countries **Nigeria** inclusive still see sex education as a taboo subject; female adolescents especially are yet not allowed to have requisite access to sexual health information (Eko et al, 2013; **Isuigo-Abanihe, 2015**). This is because of perceived societal beliefs that such exposure corrupts the growing female to become a likely victim of early sexual debut/intercourse (Obiajulu, 2004). By extension, traditional predominant values of the past within Nigerian Milieu which centers mainly on over- indulgence in abstinence-only teachings backed up by widely excepted culture of keeping “sealed lips” on every sensitive issue concerning sexuality (Isuigo-Abanihe, 2015).

Comprehensive sexuality education constitutes the following programs: human growth and development, relationships, life skills, sexual attitude and behaviour, sexual

health, society and culture, alcohol and drug use/abuse, vulnerability to sexual advances, premarital sex problems, personal hygiene, puberty, sports, reproductive system education, aging, menopause, abstinence education, HIV/AIDS and other STDs (SIECUS, 2009; UNFPA, 1994, WHO, 2010).

By implication, comprehensive sexuality education does not only focus on refuting traditional widespread beliefs that sexual expressions are wrong but go beyond to clarify that sexual expressions are normal and what matters is how it is controlled or managed in the course of our everyday life as humans who are sexual beings from birth (WHO, 2006a).

Thus, it was against the background that this research was set to examine socio-cultural impediments to understanding sexuality among Nigerian female adolescents.

1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM AND OBJECTIVE

Studies conducted across Sub-Saharan African region between 1980 and 2011 on parent-child sexuality communication investigating; frequency, content, style, tone of discussion, preferences, as well as associations with and barriers to sexuality issues revealed that in virtually all parts of Africa, sexual discussions tend to be authoritarian, uni-directional and characterized by vague warnings rather than direct open discussions i.e comprehensive education (Bastien, Kajula & Muhwezi, 2011).

This can be seen in the Nigerian case where Ajuwon (2005) revealed that parents, schools, religious bodies, governmental, NGOs etc find still it difficult to open up on sexuality issues. Moreover, (Eko et al, 2013) quoting the 2003 Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), asserted that the first comprehensive proposal for sexuality education drafted by Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in conjunction with Federal Ministry of Education for primary and post primary school curricula was received with mixed feeling and generated raging controversy from all quarters mostly among religious leaders to the point that within a short time, the discussion on its acceptability or rejection was hijacked and put to an end by these religious leaders and

other gate-keepers in authority with different connotations and colorations ranging from promotion of early sexual debut to possibility of increasing sexual promiscuity among females (Eko et al, 2013; Ajuwon, 2005).

On the contrary, the barriers to sexuality education within most countries of sub-Saharan Africa have rather proven negative to the point that a significant percentage of young persons have reportedly experienced their first sexual intercourse by age 15 (Gutmacher Institute, 2011a), another instance cited from Benin, Nigeria in Ezimokhai by (Eko et al, 2013), further revealed 55% of secondary school girls within having had sexual intercourse by age 16 and 40% admitting to at least one previous pregnancy. Similarly, Ajuwon (2005) quoting Slap et al revealed a survey in Plateau State where over a quarter of a sample of secondary school girls reportedly having sexual intercourse by age 13 and several abortion cases among female adolescents between ages 12-20 across few hospitals in Nigeria.

These citations lends credence to the fact that abstinence-only sexuality education in Nigeria has not in any way delayed early sexual debut and neither does its continuity embrace the hope of reducing dangers of risky sexual behaviors as widely believed. Rather, comprehensive sexuality education proves to equip adolescents more in navigating sexual relationships more, fostering positive attitudes and healthy outcomes in adult years (SIECUS, 2009; Kirby, 2008; Rosen, Murray & Moreland, 2004).

Consequently, there is an urgent need to examine the various socio-cultural impediments to understanding sexuality among female adolescents in Nigeria with a practical reference to Calabar in southern Nigeria in a bid to advocating practical measures to this ugly trend.

This research was set to examine the following themes;

- *Socio-cultural impediments to understanding sexuality issues among female adolescents of Calabar, Nigeria.*
- *Effects/Consequences of these socio-cultural impediments*
- *Practical measures to eliminating these socio-cultural impediments.*
- *Review the success of proposed intervention program for adolescents across selected schools at the end of the study.*

2. THEORETICAL ORIENTATION

The Self Perception Theory and the Social Learning Theory are two social psychological premises which constitute the theoretical anchorage of this research. Both theories were chosen due to their root in observational learning.

The self perception theory espoused by Daryl Bem (1965) posits that people make attributions about their own attitudes, feelings and behaviors by relying on their observation of external behaviours and the circumstances under which such behaviours occur. By implication, a person acting interprets their own overt behaviours rationally in the same way they attempt to explain others' behaviours in order to infer what is the perceived "right" or "wrong".

In the same vein, social learning theory of Albert Bandura (1970) suggests that a person's motivation to behave in a certain way is the product of learning which has taken place at an earlier time and such choices to behave in that way are not free. This implies that social learning theorists downplay the role of freewill in behavior formation. Thus, the theory maintains that people learn by observing others who serve as a strong influence on their behavior. To do this however, the person must first pay

attention to what the other person called a model (usually parents or elders) are doing.

Realistically, despite criticisms these theories bring to fore the situational realities surrounding sexuality issues in Nigeria, this is because the role of internal thoughts and emotions surrounding attitude formation on matters of sexuality are downplayed while emphasizing the role of observation and patterned ways of treating sexuality concerns. Thus, relating both theories to the understanding of sexuality among Nigerian female adolescents, show that adolescents have through their observation of the culture of sealed lips on matters of their sexuality by their parents and elders imbibed similar attitudes and beliefs that sexuality is something secret and not to be discussed openly (Isiugo-Abanihe et al, 2015).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative one specifically chosen due to its ability to ensure an enabling emotional disposition of participants for probes, monitoring moods and expressions (both verbal/non-verbal) because of the sensitive nature of this topic within Calabar and by extension the Nigeria socio-cultural context.

The research was conducted in two purposively selected locations within Calabar South Local Government (LG) and Calabar Municipality both in Cross River State of Nigeria. It is mainly an **Efik speaking** area although with minor **dialects such as () and** it shares certain cultural affinities with neighbouring Akwa Ibom, Rivers, Bayelsa, Enugu, Imo, Abia, and Ebonyi states all of which formerly constituted eastern Nigeria.

The study population consists of mainly females: (parents, teachers/students, NGO workers, female opinion leaders) within study locations; female teachers and students from four (4) selected schools (two from each LG) were drawn for In-Depth Interviews (IDI). Using the snowballing

technique, eight (8) parents mainly women, two (2) female NGO staff and two (2) women opinion leaders from the both LGs who were assumed to be knowledgeable about Efik culture regarding the topic constituted Respondents for Key informant interview (KII). Also, a total of twenty-eight (28) In-Depth interviews were conducted, five (5) students from each of the schools and eight (8) female teachers (two from each school). Altogether, a total of forty (40) participants were interviewed.

4. RESULTS

The finding of this study are presented and analyzed according to the study themes. Data collated in English and Efik **dialect**, those in **Efik** were first transcribed by research Assistants from the area and thereafter translated to English & thematically analyzed using manual content analysis techniques.

Factors impeding the understanding of sexuality issues among adolescent females in Calabar Respondents generally believed that in as much as parents and elders are usually blamed for leaving their roles on sexuality education, most of the factors impeding sexuality is found mostly within the various constraints of the Nigerian socio-cultural setting.

Respondent-1: (Female NGO Cordinator, 52 years old).

“Hmm! In as much as we do our best to guide our children through many NGOs programs, or even our homes/schools, there is need to also take into cognizance the label placed on the issue of sex discussion in the open throughout Nigeria. It is built into our system and thus limits everyone; parents, religious/community leaders, and in fact the entire public frown at such gestures with the belief that you are corrupting the little minds which you address”

Respondent's Parents: “That is how we were brought up in our time, you cannot discuss sexuality as a young girl if you are unmarried. We live in a male dominated society which restricts women's choice of words somehow. We

avoid that kind of topic in the homes and hope they teach our boys/girls in church to help them grow into responsible adults, although children of nowadays learn/do things you can't even imagine” (female parent, 58 years old civil servant).

Respondent's Community Leader: “We in community leadership are trying our best to teach the young and grown –up ones to live pure; we do our part at home and community level. Sometimes we even allow Counselors who come occasionally to teach them how make good decisions on matters concerning their health. We open up and tell them effects of engaging in sex, smoking drinking etc. Yes! We are doing our part” (female women leader, 64 years)

Respondent -2: (female parent and housewife, 51 years old).

“The truth is that when you look at it very well, there are many things that affect the sex life of our children today which we still find hard to discuss with them, I think it is because Nigeria is too conservative with strict cultural norms also affecting our Efik community. We try to keep issues about sexuality secret from these young unmarried ones believing they will understand when they marry, this often cause many young boys and girls the mistake they regret throughout their life”

Respondent-3: (female SS2 student, 17 years old).

“I grew up finding it difficult to talk to my parents or elders around me about sex or anything concerning my body, in fact, the word “**Kung**” (sex) is the heaviest word in Efik dialect because if you say it openly everyone around will look at you as a spoilt child; I remember when I had something scratching me on my bum-bum (itching of the private part) while living in the dormitory during my junior secondary, I was so afraid of telling anyone and even when I want to a hospital near the school, I was asked to bring my parents. It was my school mother who later took me to a chemist where they gave me drugs”.

Respondent-4: (female JSS3 student, 15+ years).

“Argh! Fear will not let me discuss sex topic with my mum o, she will kill me that day,

she will tell my father and even our pastor about it. Sometimes, if I have something to ask, I talk to my friends because I am free with them. My mother used to tell me and my sisters that a girl is not supposed to talk about sex, it is for married women. So even when discussing it with her friends, she sends us to our room”

Respondent-5: (female SS 3 student, 19).

“My parents are disciplinarians and you don’t try nonsense with them, when I was in primary school there was a day I asked my sister something and she jokingly said, “*itidifo*” (your buttocks in Efik dialect), so I angrily retorted, “*itid fo*” (your vagina). My mother heard us from the bedroom, came with cane and gave us the flogging of our lives. Since then we learnt never to mention such around our house

Consequences and solutions to socio-cultural factors impeding understanding of adolescent sexuality From KII responses:

Respondent-6: (female teacher, 35 years old).

“In fact, our eyes have seen it all. While trying to keep our mouths closed and not teach these children all about their bodies and sexual issues they keep making the wrong moves a lot of things are spoiling before our own very eyes. Many under aged girls are pregnant, young mother and even drop out of school because of this, it is really sad”

Respondent-5: (female parent 49 years).

“Many of our young girls have wasted their lives today because of ignorance; cases of STDs and AIDs are rampant now even among young persons, abortion is now like an easy task that girls you think are innocent engage in many times, some damage their womb in the process and when they marry, it becomes a big problem”

Respondent-6: (Female Parent 41 years)

“We do not need to be asked the consequences as it is clear for all to see, a beautiful young girl died in my neighborhood few months back from excessive bleeding caused by abortion complication, I think we NGO workers have a big role to play that is if the government and society

allow an enabling environment, they can help by creating facilities strictly for counseling and provision of services that will solve the sexuality needs of young girls. This will help a long way in changing our orientation.

Respondent-7: (female teacher, 46 years old).

“I think our churches/mosques should also get involved in giving sexuality education to these girls by maybe changing the approach of giving only bible/Koran recitations to them. Also I think government and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) can engage various Non-Governmental-Organizations (NGOs) and CBOs at the grassroots to empower girls early in life with complete sexuality education”

Respondent-8: (59 years old, community women leader).

Finally, an opinion leader submitted that: “Proverb 22 vs. 6 tells us to train up a child the way he/she should go so that when old, they will not depart from it. I think every parent should learn to teach their children all they need to know on time. We should stop using our culture as an excuse for not teaching them about their body or saying they are being taught in school, doing this will help parents gain their children’s trust and closeness, so that they will always tell you when they have any sexual problem in the future”

5. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

Results from the study revealed that the scope and nature of most sexuality education programs still being conducted across Calabar/Municipal LGs are still very limited and still fall under the scope of abstinence-only programs contrary to the findings of Isiugo-Abanihe et al (2015) that, there is comprehensive sex education which has given rise to increased knowledge of adolescents in Nigeria and Ghana on reproductive health issues and has thus stimulated the interests of these adolescents in seeking sexuality education.

This study recorded lapses in such beliefs but corroborates the findings of McKeon (2008), which submitted that many

governments in sub-Saharan Africa are yet to provide detailed sexuality education for adolescents and that more still needs to be accomplished in this regard. This is more so because it is almost impossible to teach adventurous youth to desist from sex (abstinence-only) without clearly telling them why they should or how they should manage the feelings they have as sexual humans.

Furthermore, the various socio-cultural impediments revealed by this study such as; traditional norms and values, government complacent position on sexual matters, lack of access to healthcare services such as counseling or treatment, parental ignorance, religious barriers, male domination (patriarchy) even in sexual concerns, among others which pose grave dangers ranging from early sexual debut/non use of contraceptives, unwanted pregnancies/unsafe abortions, damage to reproductive system, STDs, HIV/AIDS, , drop-outs etc are in sharp contrast to the principles guiding comprehensive sexuality education.

This agrees with Obiajulu (2004) who citing Isiugo-Abanihe (2003) noted that, "*men are undisputed gate keepers on matters of sexuality and women as mothers, wives and girls are culturally constrained in Nigeria against making decisions on matters concerning them especially on aspects that relate to SRH*" thereby leaving negative backlash. This gave rise to Respondents in this study generally agreeing that a reform of the aspect of our culture regarding sexuality discourse will drastically reduce if not totally eliminate likely consequences of lack/inadequate sexuality education.

6. CONCLUSION

In sum, findings revealed various socio-cultural impediments to understanding sexuality as well as its consequences among female adolescents of Calabar in Cross River State and by extension the Nigerian female adolescents. Also, this research revealed that contrary to general belief that sexuality education may be counter-productive for

young persons, intervention methods result in several positive outcomes.

Unfortunately, despite these strong arguments by scholars supporting that sexuality education in Nigeria should go beyond what it is currently (abstinence – only) to include abstinence – plus (comprehensive sex education) program, it has still till date secured very minimal support from appropriate authorities who should enforce it, such as; governmental organizations, NGOs, ministries/departments of health, schools and CBOs etc. There is an urgent need for this and to salvage such situation, the blame must be shared by every citizen who failed to play their various roles.

Consequently, the researcher with the aid of some volunteer Assistants concluded this work with an intervention program which lasted for a period of six (6) months across selected schools in the study locations with Student-Volunteers who met for trainings on SRH issues once every week. In assessing the success, it remains an undeniable fact that this intervention program is limited in scope. Secondly, it still sent mixed signals to some parents/guardians who withdrew their children/wards from participating in the training, although some who volunteered were allowed to finish the training at the end.

In line with the findings of this work, the following recommendations were made:

1. A *nationwide orientation* to educate parents/guardians who fail to enlighten females on sexuality issues due to cultural constraints.
2. *Effective involvement of* Education administrators, religious leaders, stakeholder, policymakers with the government in re- strategizing on ways to combat extreme cultural impediments to sexuality. Also Other relevant professionals such as Social workers, Psychologists, Medical Doctors, health workers etc to collaborate on boosting sexuality education in Nigeria.

3. *Sensitization programs* by key partners such as NGOs and, CSOs, CBOs etc. Also intervention program at the end of this research or a large-scale type recommended for other areas in Nigeria with the involvement of government and non-government, corporate and social communities.
4. *Sex education* by Government effectively drawing up comprehensive curricula for primary and post primary educational institutions throughout Nigeria.

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RIGHTS OF INDIVIDUALS SEEKING TREATMENT FOR MENTAL ILLNESS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 22ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Individual with mental illness who either voluntarily or involuntarily involved in mental health treatment system has certain legal rights i.e. entitled to be treated with dignity, decency, equality and freedom regardless of the fact that we are born differently, grow differently, different in our mental make-up, thought processes and life-style.

Keywords: *Mental. Health, Juvenile, Justice, Rights*

“What mental health needs is more sunlight, more condor, more unashamed conversation about illnesses that affect not only individuals, but their families as well.”- Glenn Close

The United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and, more specifically, by the UN Principles for the Protection of Persons with Mental Illness and for the Improvement of Mental Health Care, set forth in 1991. These international documents specify three important points which should be taken into consideration: 1) the right of the person to be treated without discrimination; 2) the presumption of legal capacity, unless incapacity can be clearly proven; and 3) the need to involve users and families in the development of policies which directly affect their lives (*UN Principles for the Protection of Persons with Mental Illness and for the Improvement of Mental Health Care*). This evolution is characterised as a shift from a so-called ‘medical model’ of disability to a ‘social model’ in which “people are viewed as being disabled by society rather than by their bodies”(WHO 2011). The latter adopts a

rights-based approach to disability, where the person is at the centre of all decisions affecting him or herself (Quinn and Degener, 2002). In 2007, India was among the many countries that ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which includes People with Mental Impairment (*The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, United Nations 2006*).

Following are two cases for the study in the research

Case-1:

Name: R.M. Gender: Female; Age-20

She was caught roaming on the roads of Kerala, India by an NGO working for the treatment of mentally ill people. On assessment it was found that the patient was unable to respond properly to any question, the clinical diagnosis was found mental retardation. After the patient’s improvement in health she was able to speak-up her name and place from where she belonged. She belongs from state Jharkhand, India. Then the patient was brought to RINPAS hospital

for her restoration. The psychiatric social workers failed to trace her village and family members. In such case the institution has the full right to provide universal rights to the patients, as per the legislations for mentally ill people.¹

Case-2:

Name: (Anonymous). Gender Male: Age-24.

He was brought to hospital for his intolerable behaviour. The chief complaints reported were intake of ganja for since the age of 12 years. For the 3 months the patient was behaving in abnormal way like not taking proper food, moves out of home at any time without any purpose, distributes money and sweets to the community people, sing and dance all the time, claims to have relation with higher authorities and can make other people's work easier if they ask. He would even say that the people are jealous of his power due to which they want to harm him. If the family members challenged his beliefs he would at once showed aggressive behaviour and often abuse and assaults them.

This case illustrates an example of psychiatric emergency where there is threat to harm other people around him. The patient can only be treated in institutional setting. In such case there is a provision to admit the patient in the hospital without his consent.

The rights which both the cases highlight in institutional care are:

- **Right to health:** For mentally ill person, right to health means availability of mental health services, accessibility to the services and quality services with regard to both physical and mental health care.
- **Right to treatment/ access to mental health care:** The patient in this case is unable to take decision regarding her

admission or treatment, in such a case it is the duty of the institution to provide treatment, safety and protection to the patient. The right to treatment holds the issue of informed consent for treatment. It lies in establishing the patient's competence to give consent. If a patient is judged competent to give consent, her or his refusal to accept treatment also has to be protected.

In exceptional circumstances, the legislation may allow treatment to proceed without informed consent. Say if a person with severe mental disorder is found to be lacking competence (capacity) and the treatment is likely to improve the condition of the patient or there is a likelihood of further deterioration of the patient's condition if treatment is not given.

- **Right to life:** It lays down that no person shall be deprived of his life except according to 'procedure established by law'. Hence, in any institution where Right to life is violated by putting the mentally ill in a closed ward, this amounts to violation of his/her fundamental rights. It is considered a serious crime and is punishable under the Indian Penal Code Sec 340, Sec 342, Sec 343 and Sec 344. All these sections deal with wrongful confinement of any person.
- **Right to dignity:** Every person living with a mental illness must be treated with dignity, and accepted by their family and the community. To make dignity in mental health a reality, every person of society needs to work with each other to make mental health visible and not something to be ashamed of. People need to know that mental illnesses are like other physical illnesses. When we think of treating a person with mental illness, we come across many treatment modalities to help the person recover. These would range from hospitalization, medication, skills building, etc. Even after the use of these modalities, if the patient is treated

¹ The 1971 Declaration on the Rights of Mentally Retarded Persons adopts a restrictive view, stipulating that "the mentally retarded person has, to the maximum degree of feasibility, the same rights as other human beings" (UN General Assembly (1971), Art. 1).

without respect and dignity these services become meaningless. Patients should not be subjected to any cruelty or indignity and cannot be used for the purpose of research except when the research is of direct benefit to him.

- **Right to confidentiality or privacy:** here the confidentiality refers to the right of an individual not to have communications that were imparted in confidence revealed to third parties. It guards the individual against a variety of intrusions on an individual's freedom from unwanted attention. Mentally ill persons are considered similar to medical patients, have the right to talk to their therapist in almost complete confidence. Only under a very few circumstances a professional reveal anything about their patients.
- **Rights to basic amenities (food, shelter, and clothing):** In-depth qualitative research shows that many factors are important in promoting well-being and preventing mental ill-health, including medication, relationships with friends, family members and professionals, complementary therapies, religious and spiritual beliefs, self-help strategies, sport and physical exercise, and creative expression (Faulkner & Layzell, 2000). A key factor that is associated with both mental health and diet is poverty (Rogers and Pilgrim 2003). This is closely tied to employment and levels of earnings and these issues also relate to what, why and how people eat.
- **Right to education:** The right of Mentally Retarded individual is to get education on the basis of equal opportunity and for the development of their mental, physical abilities and creativity to their fullest potential. As per the Right to education act (2010) covers two objectives: 1. Provides educational opportunity in a normal school settings, 2. Provides special attention for leaning if it is necessary.
- **Right to protection from harm:** It lays emphasis on the right of patients to be free from any kind of abuse or physical assault. The patients are entitled to be

protected from staff abuse by careful screening of the employees and appropriate supervision. The staffs working at the weekend should be given special attention. The staffs should be given proper training and support to prevent abuse from occurring.

Conclusion:

Earlier in 1970's, the discussion centred on the individual and his/her "functional limitations or psychological losses", current debate locates the "problem of disability within society", insisting that "it is not individual limitations which are the cause of the problem but society's failure to provide appropriate services and adequately ensure the needs of persons with disabilities are fully taken into account in its social organisation" (Oliver,1990).Protection of the rights of individual seeking treatment for mental illness from institution could be successfully applied only by the government effort. It even needs full participation of each individual, not only individuals with mental illness.

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RIGHTS OF INDIVIDUALS SEEKING TREATMENT FOR MENTAL ILLNESS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 22ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Individual with mental illness who either voluntarily or involuntarily involved in mental health treatment system has certain legal rights i.e. entitled to be treated with dignity, decency, equality and freedom regardless of the fact that we are born differently, grow differently, different in our mental make-up, thought processes and life-style.

Keywords: *Mental. Health, Juvenile, Justice, Rights*

“What mental health needs is more sunlight, more condor, more unashamed conversation about illnesses that affect not only individuals, but their families as well.”- Glenn Close

The United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and, more specifically, by the UN Principles for the Protection of Persons with Mental Illness and for the Improvement of Mental Health Care, set forth in 1991. These international documents specify three important points which should be taken into consideration: 1) the right of the person to be treated without discrimination; 2) the presumption of legal capacity, unless incapacity can be clearly proven; and 3) the need to involve users and families in the development of policies which directly affect their lives (*UN Principles for the Protection of Persons with Mental Illness and for the Improvement of Mental Health Care.*). This evolution is characterised as a shift from a so-called ‘medical model’ of disability to a ‘social model’ in which “people are viewed as being disabled by society rather than by their bodies”(WHO 2011). The latter adopts a

rights-based approach to disability, where the person is at the centre of all decisions affecting him or herself (Quinn and Degener, 2002). In 2007, India was among the many countries that ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which includes People with Mental Impairment (*The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, United Nations 2006*).

Following are two cases for the study in the research

Case-1:

Name: R.M. Gender: Female; Age-20

She was caught roaming on the roads of Kerala, India by an NGO working for the treatment of mentally ill people. On assessment it was found that the patient was unable to respond properly to any question, the clinical diagnosis was found mental retardation. After the patient’s improvement in health she was able to speak-up her name and place from where she belonged. She belongs from state Jharkhand, India. Then the patient was brought to RINPAS hospital

for her restoration. The psychiatric social workers failed to trace her village and family members. In such case the institution has the full right to provide universal rights to the patients, as per the legislations for mentally ill people.¹

Case-2:

Name: (Anonymous). Gender Male: Age-24.

He was brought to hospital for his intolerable behaviour. The chief complaints reported were intake of ganja for since the age of 12 years. For the 3 months the patient was behaving in abnormal way like not taking proper food, moves out of home at any time without any purpose, distributes money and sweets to the community people, sing and dance all the time, claims to have relation with higher authorities and can make other people's work easier if they ask. He would even say that the people are jealous of his power due to which they want to harm him. If the family members challenged his beliefs he would at once showed aggressive behaviour and often abuse and assaults them.

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- **Rights to basic amenities (food, shelter, and clothing):** In-depth qualitative research shows that many factors are important in promoting well-being and preventing mental ill-health, including medication, relationships with friends, family members and professionals, complementary therapies, religious and spiritual beliefs, self-help strategies, sport and physical exercise, and creative expression (Faulkner & Layzell, 2000). A key factor that is associated with both mental health and diet is poverty (Rogers and Pilgrim 2003). This is closely tied to employment and levels of earnings and these issues also relate to what, why and how people eat.
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protected from staff abuse by careful screening of the employees and appropriate supervision. The staffs working at the weekend should be given special attention. The staffs should be given proper training and support to prevent abuse from occurring.

Conclusion:

Earlier in 1970's, the discussion centred on the individual and his/her "functional limitations or psychological losses", current debate locates the "problem of disability within society", insisting that "it is not individual limitations which are the cause of the problem but society's failure to provide appropriate services and adequately ensure the needs of persons with disabilities are fully taken into account in its social organisation" (Oliver,1990).Protection of the rights of individual seeking treatment for mental illness from institution could be successfully applied only by the government effort. It even needs full participation of each individual, not only individuals with mental illness.

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HUMAN RIGHTS FOR THE DEPRIVED CLASS OF TRIBAL COMMUNITY: INDIGENOUS AND TRIBAL RIGHTS ISSUES

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties

(Regd: 23ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

This paper deals with the fact that what are the rights of tribal and how they are deprived of it. And how their “Traditional Home” or “Ancestral Land” is being exploited on the name of national development. Therefore the conception of national development should not be based on the theory of “Rich and Poor people” but should be considered on the basis of “Human Rights”.

Keywords: *Human, Rights, Tribal, Indigenous, India*

The Indian sub-continent is known for its vastness and well defined geographical entity. India has the second largest concentration of tribal population, after that of African Continent. The total Scheduled Tribe population in India (as per 2011 Census) is 104, 281, 034, which constitutes 8.6 per cent of the total population.¹ The tribes are the autochthonous people of the land who are believed to be the earliest settlers in Indian Peninsula. They are generally called the *adivasis*, implying original inhabitants.²

The Constitution of India does not specify the tribes which are to be called as the Scheduled Tribes. It leaves the power to list these castes and tribes to the President, i.e., the Central Executive. The Supreme

Court has expressed in *Milind*³ that the words “castes” or “tribes” in the expression “Scheduled Castes” and “Scheduled Tribes” have not been used in the ordinary sense of the terms but are used in the sense of definitions contained in Article 366 (24) and 366 (25). In this view, a caste is a “Scheduled Caste” or a tribe is a “Scheduled Tribe” only if they are included in the President’s Orders issued under Article 341 and 342. Therefore, Scheduled Tribes, according to Article 366 (25) read with Article 342, are those tribes or tribal communities, or parts or groups thereof, as the President may notify. The list has been modified from time to time. In 1950, the list contained names of 212 tribes which in the year 1971 increased to 427 and currently has reached to figure 560.⁴

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tribal.nic.in/WriteReadData/archiveDoc/201410170113319773837STProfileataGlance (Last Visited: October 23, 2015)

² Verma, R C, *Indian Tribes Through the Ages*, Publication Division, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting Government of India, 1995, p-2

³ State of Maharashtra v. Milind, AIR 2001 SC 393: (2001) 1 SCC 4

⁴ Sharma, M.L. and Sharma, D.D., *Sociology*, Sahitya Bhavan Publication, Agra, 2012, p-3

1. Tribal Administrations

The tribal people are associated with a territory and have strong and living tradition of self governance. Accordingly, special provisions have been incorporated in the Constitution relating to the administration of the tribal areas. The relevant areas in the States of Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura and Mizoram have been formally designated as “Tribal Areas” while the other tribal tracts of the country are known as “Scheduled Areas”. The provisions of the Fifth and the Sixth Schedule apply to the administration and control of the “Scheduled Areas” and “Tribal Areas” respectively.

The Fifth Schedule has been described as “*Constitution within the Constitution*”. It gives a lot of autonomy to Scheduled Areas in the matter of administration. In the case of Scheduled Areas, the governor has a special responsibility in respect of administration and control of the area. The Governor has power to direct non-applicable or application with suitable adaption of Acts of Parliament or State Assemblies to Scheduled Areas. Moreover, the Governor can make regulations for peace and good administration of the Scheduled Areas in consultation with the Tribal Advisory Council, subject to their approval by the President. The executive power of the State in respect of the Scheduled Areas is subject to the provisions of the Fifth schedule and the executive power of the Central Government extends to the giving of directives as to the administration of the said areas. The financial outlays necessary for raising the level of administration to that of the rest of the state are not voted but are charged on the Consolidated Fund

of India under Article 275 (1) of the Constitution.

A unique feature of the Sixth Schedule is establishment of autonomous District Councils with legislative, judicial and executive functions, all rolled into one. The legislative functions under paragraph 3 of the Sixth Schedule cover management of land, water courses, forest not being a reserved forest, regulation of *Jhum*, village/town administration including police, inheritance, social customs. No law of the State Legislature shall extend to a District Council Area without its consent. The District Council can modify or adapt with exceptions such laws if it so desire.

2. International Instruments to safeguard the Tribals Interest

Tribes have some International Organizations to defend their rights, The UN, with its tradition of defense of human rights, has been at the forefront of defending tribal right.⁵ The roots of the United Nation’s support for tribes Human Right can be found in the *United Nation Universal Declaration of Human Right (1948)*. Article 15 (1)⁶, states, “Everyone has the right to nationality”, and Article 27⁷, demand specific cultural protection, it states, “Everyone has the right to freely participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits”.

⁵ Viswanathan, V.N., *Human Rights Challenges of 21st Century*, Kalpaz Publications, 2008, p-140

⁶ United Nation Universal Declaration of Human Right (1948)

⁷ United Nation Universal Declaration of Human Right (1948)

The rights of tribals have to be understood in the light of three international human rights instruments/ documents adopted on the rights of indigenous, tribals and semi-tribal people- two ILO Conventions and the UN Declaration. The important conventions that emphasize the tribes (Indigenous people) rights are:

i) *ILO: Indigenous and Tribal People Convention, 1989* (This was the first international convention to address the specific needs for Indigenous Peoples' human rights. The convention outlines the responsibilities of governments in promoting and protecting the human rights of Indigenous Peoples) and

ii) *UN Draft Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People*

In 1954 and 1969, International Labour Organization adopted Convention No. 107 and 169. While the basic premise of the former was 'gradual assimilation' of the tribal people in the national mainstream, the latter underscores the identity of tribal communities and the right of self-definition and self-determination.

On 13th September 2007, the UN General Assembly adopted "*United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples*". This historic Declaration was debated at the UN forums for almost 20 years. The Declaration recognizes⁸

Indigenous peoples' right to self-determination, including their right freely to determine their political status and pursue their economic, social and cultural development;

Right to autonomy or self-government;

The collective right to live in freedom, peace and security as distinct peoples;

They shall not be subjected to any act of genocide or any act of violence;

The right not to be subjected to forced assimilation or destruction of their culture;

The right not to be forcibly removed from their lands or territories;

The right to practice and revitalize their cultural traditions and future manifestations of their cultures, such as archaeological and historical sites, artifacts, designs, ceremonies, technologies and visual and performing arts and literature;

The right to establish and control their educational systems and institutions providing education in their own languages;

The right to the dignity and diversity of their cultures, traditions, histories and aspirations;

The right to their traditional medicines and to maintain their health practices;

The right to the lands, territories and resources which they have traditionally owned, occupied or otherwise used or acquired; and

The right to maintain, control, protect and develop their cultural heritage, traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions, as well as manifestations of their sciences, technologies and cultures.

⁸ Notes on Human Rights in India, Indira Gandhi National Open University School of Law, CHR-12, Module 5, p-71

3. Protection of Scheduled Tribes under Constitution of India

“On the social plane, we have in India, a society based on the principles of graded inequality, which means elevation of some and degradation of others. On the economic plane, we have a society in which there are some who have immense wealth and some who live in abject poverty.”

-Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

The Constitution of India have taken the spirit of Universal Declaration, which can be seen in its preamble and is elaborated in the provisions concerning. The preamble to the Constitution of India provides for securing to all the citizens, social, economic and political justice and equality of status and opportunity. The Directive Principles as contained in **Article 46** of the Constitution provide that “the State shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and in particular of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation”. To facilitate the implementation of the above Directive Principles, the Constitution of India provides for a number of safeguards for the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. These safeguards can broadly be grouped into five categories as mentioned below:

(i) Social Safeguards

Article 17: abolition of untouchabilities

Article 23: prohibition of traffic in human beings and forced labour

Article 24: prohibition of employment of children in factories, etc

(ii) Economic Safeguards

The provisions of article 46, 23 and 24 also form part of the economic safeguards. The specific safeguards for the Scheduled Tribes are:

Article 244 (1): provisions of Fifth Schedule shall apply to the administration & control of the Scheduled Areas and Scheduled Tribes in any State other than the states of Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram and Tripura which are covered under Sixth Schedule, under Clause (2) of this Article.

Article 275 (1): Grants in-Aid to specified States (STs & SAs) covered under Fifth and Sixth Schedules of the Constitution.

(iii) Educational and Cultural Safeguards

Article 15 (4): Special provisions for advancement of other backward classes (*which includes STs*);

Article 29: Protection of Interests of Minorities (*which includes STs*)

Article 350 A: Instruction in Mother Tongue

(iv) Political Safeguards

Article 164 (1): Provides for Tribal Affairs Ministers in Bihar, MP and Orissa;

Article 330: Reservation of seats for STs in Lok Sabha;

Article 332: Reservation of seats for STs in State Legislatures

Article 334: 10 years period for reservation (*Amended several times to extend the period.*);

Article 243: Reservation of seats in Panchayats

Article 371: Special provisions in respect of NE States and Sikkim

Article 371 A, 371 B, 371 C, 371 F, 371 G, 371 H.

(v) Service Safeguards

Article 335, Article 320 (4), Article 16 (4A)

4. Natural Resources and Tribals

In the past, the tribals enjoyed considerable freedom in the use of natural resources. They were virtually lords of water, forest and land (*Jaal, Jungle and Zameen*). They are peace loving people. Their attachment to the land traditionally occupied either for habitation or cultivation is unmatched. They have

gallantly resisted invasions on their territory.⁹ With the introduction of State management of the forests, particularly since the close of the 19th century, the relationship between the tribals and the forests has undergone considerable change. The first national policy on forest was formulated in 1894. It introduced State control over forests in public interest which resulted in the curtailment of rights and privileges of the tribals over the forest resources.¹⁰ The primitive Tribal-Culture is naturalistic-culture. In this culture there is a symbiotic relationship with nature which is based on the ideal of nutrition, not on exploitation. The relation between nature and naturalistic tribal community is of “Mother and Infant”. The tribal ideology is to derive minimum from nature, for the fulfillment of their basic necessities of life. The child has the natural right on mother. So the tribal community believes that they

have the natural right on- water, forest and land- which are the integral parts of their natural habitat. Mahatma Gandhi called them as ‘the Children of the Forest God’.

The recognized rights of the forest dwelling Scheduled Tribes and other traditional forest dwellers include the responsibilities and authority for sustainable use, conservation of biodiversity and maintenance of ecological balance and thereby strengthening the conservation regime of the forests while ensuring livelihood and food security of the forest dwelling Scheduled Tribes and other traditional forest dwellers.¹¹ Whereas the forest rights on ancestral

lands and their habitat were not adequately recognized in the consolidation of state forests during the colonial period as well as in independent India resulting in historical injustice to the forest dwelling Scheduled Tribes and other traditional forest dwellers who are integral to the very survival and sustainability of the forest ecosystem.¹² The British made serious efforts to penetrate into the tribal areas mainly for laying communication network with a view to strengthen their administrative control and their interest was not the development of the tribal areas but they wanted to open up the same for consolidating their position.¹³

The command over resources and other means of production is the central point in all social formations beginning with the primitive communities in the Stone Age to

the most modern age of industrial and post- industrial societies. The tribal people

⁹ *Supra* 2, p-38

¹⁰ *Ibid*, p-79

¹¹ The Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006 (No. 2 of 2007

¹² *Ibid*

¹³ *Supra* 9, p-38

and even agricultural communities have been traditionally associated with a geographical tract, the habitat of the community, on whose resources all members thereof depend for their living.¹⁴

Although, now-a-days in the tribal areas there is no rebellion as far as the authority of the state is concerned but the maoist-ideals regarding water, forest and land are prevalent predominately. Currently in between the exploitation of natural resources for national economic growth and maoist ideals - the security of tribal welfare, the tribal life is passing through a very critical juncture. Hence their slogan is "Human Rights". The tribals do not desire to exploit the natural resources to

establish Industries and Mines but they wish to live their lives as siblings of nature by using only the naturalistic gifts for their livelihood.

For national development excavation and exploitation of natural resources is essential for economic growth which gives employment but the hard-fact reality is that it will uproot and de-establish the tribal community from their traditional livelihood which is their birth-right. Therefore the tribals are psychologically and emotionally attached to their natural rights. The states have the legal rights on natural resources. But the tribal primitive conception is that "God Created the Earth We are Children of God Pray, wherefrom

has the Government Appeared?"¹⁵ During Colonial rule approximately 81 series of

big and small revolts were seen between the year 1778 to 1942¹⁶, where several sections of the tribal people revolted against the British rules and regulations.

5. Resources, National Development and Tribal Displacement

For National development natural resources are essential. On Tribal belts there are vast stocks of various minerals. So keeping in view of the national progress the opening of the tribal belts are considered to be requisite. If in one way the natural gifts are necessary for tribal living then in the other way their exploitation is essential for national development and economic growth. Hence the natural resources are necessary in either way for tribal existence and national

progress. Since independence, development projects of the five year plans have displaced lakh of persons each year primarily as a direct consequence of administrative land acquisition. This does not include displacement by non- plan projects, changes in land use pattern, acquisition for urban growth, and loss of livelihood caused by environmental

degradation and pollution. Hydroelectric and irrigation projects are the largest source of displacement and destruction of habitat. In the scenario of development and displacement the majority of the affected are obviously tribals and other economically marginal rural populations

¹⁴ Sharma, B.D., *Tribals Affairs in India- The Crucial Transition*, Sahyog Pustak Kuteer, 2001, p-116

¹⁵ From the letter of the Chief of Seattle to the President of United States in 1854

¹⁶ Hasnain, Nadeem, *Tribal India*, Palaka Prakashan, 2002, p-558

who have been dependent on the natural resource base for their subsistence.¹⁷

Tribal areas of our country are hydel and mineral rich. Tribals have paid the highest price of national development because their regions are resource rich: 90 percent of all coal and around 50 percent of the remaining minerals are in their regions. Also the forest, water and other sources abound in their habitat. The indigenous/tribal peoples who constituted 8% of the total population of India at 1991 census make up 55% of the total displaced persons due to development projects up to 1990. According to the Ministry of Tribal Affairs (MTA) nearly 85 lakh tribals were displaced until 1990 on account of mega developmental projects like dams, mining, industries and conservation of forests etc. Lakh of tribals have been displaced from 1990 onwards (due to the so-called economic liberalization policies of the Center under pressure from the Western lenders) without proper rehabilitation.¹⁸ And for infrastructural development or damming and mining of the land, this wealth is exploited which results into large scale displacement of the tribal population. And this dire consequence not only affects the tribals but also harm the environment. In recent years this activity has seen to be increased. Mining not only affects the tribal people by displacing them from their natural habitat but also disturbs the ecological balance like forest cover is destroyed, agricultural land is damaged. Displacement from original habitats many times leads to a breakdown of a land based

community organization. Such instances lead to families getting marginalised and morbidity level going up. Cultural and religious practices which are aspects of the social dimensions of displacement are seriously affected. The land-for-land approach adopted for rehabilitation, often does not reflect a holistic perspective.¹⁹ The impact of displacement is that they

lose their house, land, farm, base for earning their livelihood which is gross human right violation.

Displacement from their traditional habitations leaves them under acute trauma and uncertainty – there is institution in India that is interested in alleviating indescribable human sufferings of the tribals left to struggle for survival with any dignity.

The other part of the story of displacement is that when non-tribals come into development project areas, they either permanently settle or settle there for a long period of time which is in the midst of tribal habitation. Many a times when displacement is for state owned small infrastructural work they are not even compensated which make their condition miserable.

¹⁷ *Ibid*, p-222

¹⁸ socialissuesindia.files.wordpress.com/2012/09/tribal-displacement-in-india.pdf (Last Visited: October 25, 2015)

¹⁹ Paswan, Sanjay and Jaideva, Paramanshi, *Encyclopedia of Dalits in India*, Kalpaz Publication, Volume 12, 2003, p-33

6. Initiatives taken by Government

The Government of India has drafted a National Policy for Rehabilitation of persons displaced as a result of acquisition of land, addressing primarily the needs of the disadvantaged communities. Though the Draft was prepared in consultation with NGOs and some prominent activists, forums such as this are required to deliberate on the character and content of the draft policy and examine how it respects the right to a life with dignity for the tribal people. Basic to all the developmental efforts for the uplift of the SCs/STs is a respect for their human rights; respect for their right to equality and equal opportunity; a right to life with

dignity; a right to enjoy the rights guaranteed by our Constitution. Statues and schemes are of course important, but they are rendered meaningless in the absence of a commitment to enforce or

implement them. Projects and programmes for the uplift of the SCs and STs would remain on paper, or they would get derailed unless the agencies charged with the responsibility of implementing them are not only sensitized but also made effective.²⁰

The role of human rights organization and activists in the sensitization of government functionaries is of great significance in this regard. This would also call for according to these functionaries a greater degree of importance and standing in the administrative hierarchy than they enjoy at present. Let the message spread that the ablest and the best are picked up for this

very important task of social uplift and economic development of the poorest of the poor and the weakest of the weak.²¹

7. Conclusion and Solutions

Human Right is the natural right which every human being acquires from the time of birth. The first and foremost duty of the democracy is to make it ensure that this natural right is allowed and enjoyed by everyone of the society. Thus, democracy

safeguards the human rights and strengthens the basic ideal of republic. As the Human Rights are the basis of life and existence. Therefore, they are of primary importance.

The displacement of tribal's which takes place in tribal and scheduled areas for the purpose of development leads not only to them economic problems but also emotional problem as they are psychologically and emotionally attached to their land which is the human right violation. By continuous intrusion of non-tribals in their areas is threatening the sovereignty of tribal communities. And they are also denied their legal right on their land.

The tribal community with their rights resides in the woodlands which are far-off from the formal administrative set up fully ignorant of the complexities of the legal version and its implications. Even the representatives of the formal institutions are not well informed about the human rights. The primitive group is also not well versed of the legal interpretations of the judicial matter. The more tender part of the problem is that the tribals are not in a

²⁰ *Supra* 18

²¹ *Ibid*

position to approach the concerned institutions or officers and get their help and directions in this regard.

I believe that in any democratic set up Right to Information and human right are important but what is more important is that these rights should be availed by each and every citizen residing in different parts of the country. As far as the right of information is concerned relative cells are

opened at various levels, such as (a) Districts, (b) Tehsil, (c) Janpad panchayats and etc, where one can apply and get the information required by him. But the sad part is that no such provisions are made and available to the public in the dimensions of the vital issues, Human birth rights and its utilisation and preservations, without which there is no earthly life. Hence it is urgent and essential.

I would like to underline that the human right institutions should be empowered by judicial endowment. Human Right Organisation and human right activist should be given more power to reach the Janpad (Block) Panchayat level of Scheduled Area. There is need that these institutions and activist should be active.

At present we boast that India is the largest democracy of the world. We will have to keep in mind that the essence of Republic India is manifested with twin approach application of Right to Information and Human Rights directions simultaneously. Therefore while making the tribals conscious of their rights the human rights schools and activist network should also be in a condition to give a

coverage to the tribal belt and make the atmosphere resounded by it. Then only the meaningfulness of the largest democracy will be recorded in history.

RIGHTS OF TRIBALS AFFECTED BY INDIRA SAGAR (POLAVARAM) PROJECT & ROLE OF THE GOVERNMENT

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(Regd: 04ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

After Africa, our country India occupies second position in the world, so far as population is concerned. Report of the Working Group on Tribal Development (1978-83) recommended that the forestry plans may be prepared to satisfy the basic need of the tribal economy and uplift the communities living in the area as the counterpart of commercial forestry and intensive utilization of forest resources. The ownership rights of tribal people, protection of natural resources and the right of the indigenous peoples to participate and give their consent in the use, management and conservation of these resources and consultation in the exploration and exploitation of such resources and in the benefits from them. The Polavaram dam, an earth and rock-filled structure, will displace the largest number of people in India's history of such projects. For every five acres (2.02 hectares) that will be irrigated by the project, one tribal family will be displaced. The project is not only gigantic in size but also in degree of violation of rules and regulations. Village after village certifies that the authorities lied about complying with FRA provisions. The project has also become cause for dispute between Andhra Pradesh and two of its neighbours. The Polavaram project report says the dam will submerge four villages in Chhattisgarh's Dantewada district and eight villages in Odisha's Malkangiri district. The actual numbers are 23 in Chhattisgarh and 10 in Odisha. It urges the government to respect the cultures and spiritual values of the people. Large scale displacement in this very tribal region, submerging 276 villages in AP alone as per official figures, poses serious threat to the ethnic, linguistic and cultural identity of the Koya tribe. Displacement of the scheduled tribes under Polavaram dam is a violation of human rights and is without consent and consultation of the tribal population. Polavaram project is also in violation of the National Tribal Policy which states that "any project which displaces more than 50,000 tribal people should not be taken up". The rights of each individual tribal, his family, his community, lands under cultivation and grazing lands are to be documented along with the traditional customary rights and boundaries of the community and the Govt. should officially accept this.

Keywords: Tribals, Forest, Rights, Projects, Government.

After Africa, India occupies second position in the world, so far as tribal (Adivasi or original inhabitants or primitive or aboriginal) population is concerned. The percent of tribal population to total population is 8.68 per cent in 2011 census. Industrial revolution along with the social and cultural progress of a nation is characterized as economic development. To have an uninterrupted growth of the country's GDP, man has applied Technology to increase production, expand employment opportunities for the rising population. For this, basic and heavy industries were created, hydro electric projects were established, irrigation system were developed, roads and railways, ports were constructed, canals were dug, mines were excavated and power projects were opened in suitable areas. In recent times the large scale industrialization, privatization and globalization for sake of "development" has emerged as the biggest threat to tribal's survival – ironically, the so called "modern civilized society" has become a predator of their age-old eco-friendly, peaceful and harmonious lifestyle. These so called "developmental" activities, which do not confer any direct benefit to the tribals, merely leave them landless and without means for survival. Monetary benefits do not really count when the lifestyle for generations is changed irreparably. Land alienation of the tribals by the powerful entities has become common phenomena. It is most unfortunate that "the freedom to live in their own traditional ways" as guaranteed by the constitution is flouted by those who understand the constitution better.

The Polavaram dam, an earth and rock-filled structure, will displace the largest number of people in India's history of such projects. "For every five acres (2.02 hectares) that will be irrigated by the project, one tribal family will be displaced," says E A S Sarma, former power secretary, who has been tracking the project. It is not only gigantic in size but also in degree of violation of rules and regulations. The Polavaram dam, first proposed in 1941, was revived by former

chief minister of Andhra Pradesh, the late Y S Rajasekhara Reddy in 2004. It is creating heated debate among people from various walks of life ranging from intellectuals, politicians, news analysts, employees and common man. During these debates importance should be given to the basic question - **Who are going to be adversely affected?** Tribals are going to be displaced from their homes. The displacement problem is a very serious problem. According to "Displacement And Rehabilitation Of People Due To Developmental Projects," a document from Lok Sabha secretariat members reference note, around 50 million people have been displaced due to developmental projects over the last 50 years. The situation of the tribes is of special concern as they constitute 52.9 per cent of the displaced population. The need to avoid largescale displacement is felt by all those who are concerned with human rights and who empathise with the problems of tribals. This project is going to displace lakhs of tribals from their homes. Shifting of urban poor from one house to another vastly differs from shifting tribes from their locality. Tribes may not possess the knowledge to adjust to their new locality and even if they are shifted to another forest or other part of the same forest the produce of such a place may not resemble their natural habitat.

1. ROOT CAUSE FOR THE CALL FOR RIGHTS:

As there are number of Protective Land Laws, Legislations, Regulations, Forest Laws, Government Policies, Court Orders and Judgments, and Government Orders (GOs) which prohibit the land transfer in Scheduled Areas. In spite of all these protective and welfare laws made by the government for the welfare of tribals, the Governmental agencies have been acquiring the tribal lands in the name of National interest in contravention to all the Constitutional Provisions. Clearly the protective laws of the tribal areas are being manipulated where the legal access to tribal

lands and resources is denied. In 1990, the Global Constitution on the Realization of the Right to Development as a Human Right underlined that the most destructive and prevalent abuses of indigenous rights are a direct consequence of development strategies that fail to respect the fundamental rights of self determination. The result has been the elimination and removal of natural resources, waters, wild life, forests and food supplies from indigenous lands either through commercial exploitation or incompatible land use; the degradation of natural environment; removal of indigenous people's from their lands; and their displacement or preemption from the use of their lands by outsiders. Above all some of the root causes of protest for developmental projects by the tribals of India are as follows:-

Failure to be consulted and informed

From the inception of planning of most projects, through various stages of displacement and resettlement, it is to be expected that those likely to be negatively affected by the projects would be consulted and kept informed in such a way as to enable them to best rebuild their ravaged lives.

Absence of Advance and Comprehensive Planning for Rehabilitation

In the absence of a statutory rehabilitation law or even a national policy, there is no legal imperative for state governments or project authorities to integrate comprehensive rehabilitation planning into the planning of a project. Indeed, it has been found that even the existence of state and project-specific policies is not sufficient to ensure this. The incremental approach of allowing land acquisition and project construction activities to proceed parallel to displacement and rehabilitation, has led in practice to ad hoc, piecemeal and minimalistic rehabilitation. More often than not, project authorities are interested mainly in the relocation rather than the rehabilitation of project affected persons, in their physical transference from the

submergence zone rather than their long-term welfare.

Undervaluation of Compensation

The only significant reparation for displaced persons guaranteed by law is the payment of monetary compensation for compulsorily acquired individual assets, mainly land or houses. However, the manner in which the law is framed and interpreted ensures that the displaced land-owner or house-owner is always the loser. The practice is to pay compensation for lost fixed assets like agricultural land at the prevailing market rate, calculated as an average of registered sales prices of land of similar quality and location in the preceding three or five years. However, it is an open secret that most land transactions in India are grossly undervalued to evade registration fees. Therefore, the displaced tribal receives a rate which is much below the market rate. Land and houses are paid for at the alleged market value rather than 'replacement value'. Typically land prices shoot up sharply around any large project because of enhanced demand for land and in anticipation for irrigation; likewise houses are depreciated in value for age. In this way, oustees are not compensated for their land or houses at rates which would enable them to buy land or construct houses elsewhere similar to those that are lost.

Failure to acquire alternate cultivable lands

The only recourse for the dispossessed cultivator caught in what Cernea describes as the 'spiral of impoverishment' is typically one of two alternatives. The erstwhile land-owner either migrates to the slums of the cities in search of work, or fans out to neighbouring wastelands or forest tracts or clears them for cultivation.

Problems at Resettlement Sites

Resettlement sites are often inhospitable in a number of ways and their locations are selected without reference to availability of livelihood opportunities, or the preferences of displaced persons themselves.

Traumatic forced and delayed relocation

Involuntary relocation is always extremely painful, but a sensitive project bureaucracy can do much to relieve its trauma. In practice however, it has been observed that the driving objective of project authorities has not been to prepare and assist the families to relocate and to make a gradual and less painful transition to their new habitats. Instead frequently the only objective is to vacate the submergence zone of what are perceived to be its human encumbrances, with the brute force of the state if necessary.

Inability to handle cash compensation

Even more lethal for rural oustees is the provision that whatever compensation is fixed, is paid as a rule in cash rather than kind. Especially tribal people, but to a lesser degree most rural people, have little experience in handling cash. Many studies have recorded how cash compensation is depleted by oustees in short periods, by fraud, for repayment of old debts, in liquor and conspicuous consumption.

Besides all the above some of the other causes are **Dis-entitlement** – a process where by the tribals are gradually denied access to the support system of their livelihood. It meant loss of rights enjoyed earlier by the tribal community over the forest and land sources around them; **Multiple Displacement; Failure to provide alternative livelihoods** and **Problems of host communities**.

2. VIOLATION OF RIGHTS

Rights Related to Land and Resources

The rights of land ownership is guaranteed in the ILO Indigenous and Tribal Populations Convention No. 107 of 1957 concerning the protection and integration of indigenous and Semi-Tribal populations in independent countries, revised ILO Indigenous and Tribals in Independent Countries Convention No.169 of 1989, and UN Draft Declaration on Indigenous Rights.

All these recognizes the ownership rights of tribal people, protection of natural resources and the right of the indigenous peoples to participate and give their consent in the use, management and conservation of these resources and consultation in the exploration and exploitation of such resources and in the benefits from them. It urges the government to respect the cultures and spiritual values of the peoples concerned of their relationship with the lands and territories. It also makes the provision of adequate penalties for unauthorized intrusion upon or use of lands of the peoples.

Rights Related to Culture

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 recognizes the “right to culture” and the Article 15 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966 also recognizes the right of everyone to take part in the cultural life. Article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966 recognizes the cultural rights of minorities, which is more relevant for indigenous peoples. The Declaration of the Principles of International Cultural Cooperation 1966, Declaration on Race and Racial Prejudice 1978, ILO Convention No. 169 and many other laws states that each culture has a dignity which must be respected and preserved.

Rights Related to Development

The Declaration on Right to Development 1986 states right to development as an inalienable human right and the ILO Convention No. 169 declares that the peoples concerned shall have the right to decide their own priorities for the process of development as it affects their lives, beliefs, institutions and spiritual well-being and the lands they occupy or other wise use, and to exercise control, to the extent possible, over their economic, social and cultural development. The Politics of Resistance to Capitalist Development Projects The choices made by the Independent Indian state to follow a capitalist mode of profit oriented development and modern industrial growth has been based on two interrelated process: one unchecked use of earth's natural resources and the transformation of the people, often against their will, into a dispossessed working class. The earth's impoverishment has meant that communities who depend on natural base for sustenance have been deprived of their resources and caused not only alienation, and loss of material livelihood but also most profoundly a wider loss of cultural autonomy, knowledge and power. The UN document entitled 'The Practice of Forced Eviction: Comprehensive Human Rights Guidelines on Development based Displacement' states that evictions constitute prima facie violation of a wide range of internationally recognized human rights. In 1990, the Global Constitution on the Realization of the Right to Development as a Human Right underlined that the most destructive and prevalent abuses of indigenous rights are a direct consequence of development strategies that fail to respect the fundamental rights of self determination. The result has been the elimination and removal of natural resources, waters, wild life, forests and food supplies from indigenous lands either through commercial exploitation or incompatible land use; the degradation of natural environment; removal of indigenous people's from their lands; and their displacement or

Preemption from the use of their lands by outsiders.

Environment, Forests and Human Rights

The Forest Act 1878, which classified forests into three categories: Reserve, Protected

and Village forests makes available only a small portion, i.e. the village forests to the tribals and the National Forest Policy 1894 which declared the forests on the slope of the hills as protected, ultimately led to the process of shrinking tribal access to minor forest produce. Establishing industrial projects, felling trees to supply timber for laying railway tracks, building towns and collecting raw material for industries gave birth to a process of deforestation. This has unleashed a situation where more and more people are being displaced from their communities and traditional ways of life and resulted in an insecure livelihood for the tribal and indigenous communities in the hilly areas and tribal belts. No amount of compensation could be adequate for the loss of the natural habitat and the cultural milieu of the tribals. This process can be characterized as a process of – disentanglement – a process where by the tribals are gradually denied access to the support system of their livelihood. It meant loss of rights enjoyed earlier by the tribal community over the forest and land sources around them.

Rights to Education

The ILO Convention No. 169 on Indigenous and Tribal Peoples 1989, the UN Draft Declaration on Indigenous Rights recognizes and advocates for the right to education of indigenous peoples.

Besides this list of violation of Rights, several Constitutional Provisions like PESA, FRA, were also violated for the said Polavaram Project. The project is in violation of The Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act- 2013, which provides for "land for land" in

command area for the affected people under irrigation projects and protection to ensure that “all benefits, including the reservation benefits available to the Scheduled Tribes and the Scheduled Castes in the affected area shall continue in the resettlement area”. It is also mandatory for obtaining prior consent of concerned Gram Sabha or the Panchayats in the Scheduled Area under Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas Act (PESA) 1996.

3. ROLE OF GOVERNMENT:

In November 2010, Union minister of state for environment Jairam Ramesh issued a show-cause notice to the Andhra government for not holding public hearings for the project even two years after getting in-principle clearance from the ministry. While giving forest clearance in July 2010, the ministry said it was based on the “assurance of the Andhra Pradesh government that there were no forest rights that needed to be settled” under FRA. The Forest Advisory Committee (FAC) of the environment ministry noted in October 2010 that the state had not furnished the mandatory consent certificates from gram sabhas of villages in areas where forests will be submerged. On October 25, 2010, FAC recommended a thorough compliance report from the state government and suggested actions in case of violation. The project has also become cause for dispute between Andhra Pradesh and two of its neighbor Odisha and Chhattisgarh. The Polavaram project report says the dam will submerge four villages in Chhattisgarh’s Dantewada district and eight villages in Odisha’s Malkangiri district. The actual numbers are 23 in Chhattisgarh and 10 in Odisha, say the two state governments. The chief minister, Chhattisgarh Dr. Raman Singh, said the project, is “unacceptable” in any form. Odisha’s appeal against the environmental clearance to the project is already pending in the apex court.

Environmental clearance for the Polavaram dam is based on a 2005

environmental impact assessment (EIA). But the Central Water Commission (CWC) changed its flood situation estimate in 2006 which has not been incorporated in the design. The Polavaram project was designed in 1980s and updated in 2005. It went by the probable maximum flood (PMF) level of 102,000 cubic metre per second (cumecs) for designing the spillway. The CWC, however, did not accept the design; it had originally accepted the spillway designed for a flood level of 102,000 cumecs on the premise that the project was a barrage. When Godavari experienced high flood in August 2006, submerging about 370 villages for days in Andhra Pradesh, CWC made a fresh assessment of PMF at 140,000 cumecs.

Consequently, CWC directed the state government to revise the Polavaram project design to handle 142,000 cumecs flood level for its spillway. However, the National Institute of Hydrology of the Union Ministry of Water Resources estimated the PMF at 169,920 cumecs. The dam break analysis for the Polavaram dam is an essential part of its EIA. The institute found that if the dam bursts, the peak flood will be of 198,200 cumecs. This means the project’s EIA is flawed and downplays the threat of flood. “Based on recent rainfall trends and flood history, a peak flood of 250,000 cumecs is a reality. This will wash away the dam,” says T Hanumantha Rao, former chief engineer with Andhra government. Though CWC changed the maximum flood estimate from 102,000 cumecs to 142,000 for the dam’s spillway design, Andhra Pradesh has not changed the back water level estimates based on the new PMF. Odisha now says that the revised design would lead to very high inundation in Malkangiri.

The Human Rights Society, a registered NGO has voluntarily visited the affected area of the Polavaram on 5th and 6th of January 2015. A fact finding committee consisting Justice A. Gopal Rao, and other members from the field of NGOs, Law, Media etc visited the immediate affected

seven villages which are located in the dam site. The committee preliminarily recommended several points to be useful for the state as well as the central Govt. before drawing to any conclusion on the Polavaram issue the Union and the state Govt. of A.P. must consider the models of rehabilitation of experts, one of the best models of Cernea is below.

Cernea proposes a 'risks and reconstruction' model of rehabilitation. He believes that 'targeted measures – economic, technical, legal and cultural — must be undertaken to orient from the outset the planning of resettlement towards the reconstruction of livelihood, so as to prevent impoverishment'. When the state takes up a project entailing displacement, 'the people who will be displaced are subjected to huge risks, typically without their knowledge, participation or consent'. He identifies the risks as follows: 'landlessness; joblessness; homelessness; marginalization; increased morbidity and mortality; food insecurity; loss of access to common property and services; and community disarticulation'. His hypothesis is that the state can reverse the risks by the following reconstructive actions:

- From landlessness to land-based resettlement;
- From joblessness to re-employment;
- From food insecurity to safe nutrition;
- From homelessness to house reconstruction;
- From increased morbidity to better health care;
- From social disarticulation, marginalization and deprivation of common assets, to community reconstruction and social inclusion.

As Polavaram is not only the life of lakhs of tribals but the question of displacement of livelihoods of several primitive tribes. The following points are to be considered by the Union and the state Govts.

:-

- Justifiability of 'public purpose';
- Establishing that this is the 'least-displacing' alternative;
- Right to information;
- Right to be consulted;
- Social Cost-Benefit Analysis;
- The Goal of Rehabilitation;
- Eligibility for Compensation and Rehabilitation;
- Principles for Assessment and Payment of Compensation;
- Land-for-Land;
- Non-land Based Activities;
- Assistance in relocation;
- Special measures to protect most vulnerable groups;
- No. of Families to be displaced and the no. of Tribal Families;
- Who is going to fund Polavaram Dam?
- The area of land to be irrigated and the area already irrigated;
- Downfall threat of the design;
- Unsafe Embankments;

4. CONCLUSION:

A common man may think why I should concern myself with the problems of tribes across India. The reason is simple. Indifference will harm society as a whole. In this context we should remember a famous poem of Niemoller Pastor Martin, which criticized the German Intellectuals following the Nazis. The poem is as follows:

*"First they came for the socialists,
and I did not speak out - Because
I was not a Socialist.
Then they came for the Trade
Unionists, and I did not speak out - Because
I was not a Trade Unionists.*

Then they came for the Jews, and I did not speak out -Because

I was not a Jew. Then they came for me - and

there was no one left to speak for me.''

Experts have suggested many alternative methods of minimising the displacement of tribes during Polavaram construction. So we must speak for the rights of tribes and explore the methods of minimum displacement.

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WOMEN'S RIGHTS VIOLATION IN DOMESTIC VIOLENCE: A CASE STUDY OF MADURAI DISTRICT OF TAMILNADU, INDIA

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(Regd: 30ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Transgender Domestic violence can be described as the power misused by one adult in a relationship to control another. It is the establishment of control and fear in a relationship through violence and other forms of abuse. This violence can take the form of physical assault, psychological abuse, social abuse, financial abuse or sexual assault. The protection of women from Domestic Violence Act 2005 says that any act, conduct, omission or commission that harms or injures or has the potential to harm or injure will be considered domestic violence by law. Nowadays Domestic violence is increasing tremendously in Madurai District. Many cases were filed against domestic violence against women. Most of the married women are employers and living in nuclear family. Even educated and uneducated women are facing many problems at their homes. The problems are physical abuse, psychological abuse, and financial exploitation and ego problems. So this paper attempts to analyze the domestic violence against women in Madurai District.

Keywords: *Women, Rights, Domestic, Violence, Rights*

Domestic Violence is described as the power misused by one adult in a relationship to control another. It is the establishment of control and fear in a relationship through violence and other forms of abuse. This violence can take the forms of physical assault, psychological abuse, financial abuse, or sexual assault. Abusers use physical and sexual violence, threats, emotional insults and economic deprivation as a way to dominate their victims and get their way. The protection of Women from **Domestic Violence Act 2005** says that any act, conduct, omission or commission that harms or injures or has the

potential to harm or injure will be considered domestic violence by law. Thus, domestic violence in Indian context mostly refers to domestic violence against women.

The term violence against women means “*Any act of gender-based violence that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty whether or occurring in public or private life*”.

Violence against women encompasses but it is not limited to the following:

- Physical, sexual or psychological violence occurring in the family including battering, sexual abuse of female children in the household, dowry-related violence, marital rape, female genital mutilation and other traditional practices harmful to women, non-spousal violence and violence related to exploitation.
- Physical, sexual or psychological violence perpetrated or condoned by the state.
- Violence against women in situations of armed conflicts in the form of murder, systematic rape, sexual slavery and forced pregnancy.
- Violence against motherhood such as Forced sterilization and force abortion. Prenatal sex selection and female infanticide.

Violence, sexual harassment and other forms of gender-based violence constitute the reality of most girls' and women's lives in India. In our society, many women are violently treated by their intimate partners while they suffer in silence. In some cases, domestic violence leads to the death of these women.

Nowadays Domestic violence is increasing tremendously in Madurai District. In 2014, 60 cases were filed against domestic violence against women. Here most of the married women are employed and living in nuclear family. Even though the women in Madurai District are educated they are facing many problems at their homes. The problems are physical abuse, financial exploitation and ego problems. So the researcher took an attempt to analyze the Domestic violence against women in Madurai District.

The objectives of the study are

1. To evaluate the problems faced by the women.
2. To analyze the reason for the domestic violence against the respondents.
3. To find out their attitude after registering complaints against the violators.

This study is based on primary data. Primary data has been collected with the help of interview schedule. In Madurai District 60 cases were filed against various violence faced by the women in 2014. Out of 60 victims 50 per cent i.e. 30 victims were selected by simple random technique for the present study.

The Case of Madurai District: Domestic violence against women increased day by day in Madurai District. When compared to other districts of Tamilnadu Madurai District comprises of more uneducated people still, crimes against women are not decreasing. It is a big question mark for the people of Madurai District. Even though there is good environment circumstance, lot of police stations and peaceful society, domestic violence is increasing. Domestic violence happened mostly in Nuclear family. Major reasons behind it is the husbands are drunkard, illegal contact with other women, ego and greedy to accumulate more material.

1. DIFFERENT FORMS OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN INDIA

UNICEF Reports on Progress of Nations released jointly by Government of India and UNICEF says that more than 60 million women, who should have been alive today, are missing. Responsible factors are from feticide to domestic violence to dowry deaths to physical assaults. Discrimination starts even before women are born and continue till they die.

Domestic Violence against women exists in the form of:

Feticide – Some new forms of Violence have appeared with technological advances as is evident in case of female feticide, rejecting in adverse sex-ratio. Social bias in favour of a male child lead to abortions (Out of 8000 cases of abortions following sex-determination tests, 7999 are female fetus, according to a survey) Sex-ratio is continuously declining all over India except for Kerala. Inefficient and ineffective performance of political, administrative and economic structures and mechanisms failed to stop it.

Infanticide –Thousands of newly born baby-girls die with overdoses of opium. They are abandoned or thrown in rivers or dust bins to die. Out of abandoned children 90 per cent are girls.

Health hazards – According to official argues, there is 10per cent higher mortality rate for girls than boys due to mal-nutrition in infancy and childhood. Health Statistics are equally alarming with 80 per cent of them being anemic.

Physical assaults/rapes/gang-rapes/molestations – According to a Report, there are reported cases of one raps every 54 minutes, a molestation every 26 minutes; and an act of cruelty every 33 minutes. National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) statistics says – every 20 minutes, a women is raped somewhere in India, not to mention the countless number of cases of molestations or rapes going unreported. Child rape cases have increased by 33.6 per cent in the last 10 years. Government data shows crimes by juveniles especially rape and abduction of women has seen exponential rise in the past decade from 48.7 per cent in 2002 to 66.25 in 2012.

Dowry deaths – Number of dowry-deaths is quite alarming in the country- a dowry death every one hour forth two minutes. Dowry- related violence is also in increase. Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan are the states

with maximum number of reported cases. Many cases remain unreported.

Victims of materialistic-culture – Consumerist culture has triggered off increased atrocities, domestic violence and physical assaults on women. Millions of girls live under threat of physical abuse. Employment ratio in organized and unorganized sectors also points out discrimination against women in job-market.

2. CONSEQUENCES OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

There are varied consequences of domestic violence depending on the victim, the age group, the intensity of intensity of the violence and frequency of the torment they are subjected to.

The consequences of the domestic violence in detail can be broadly categorized under

- *Effect on the victim and the family,*
- *Effect on the Society and the*
- *Effect on nation's growth and productivity.*

Effect on the victim and the family
Physical Effect – Bruises, broken bones, head injuries, lacerations and internal bleeding are some of the acute effects of a domestic violence incident that require medical attention and hospitalization. Some chronic health conditions that have been linked to victims of domestic violence are arthritis, Victims who are pregnant during a domestic violence relationship experience greater risk of miscarriage, pre-term labor and injury to or death of foetus.

Psychological Effect – Among victims who are still living with their perpetrators, high amounts of stress, fear and anxiety are commonly reported. Depression is also common, as victims are made to feel guilty for 'provoking' the abuse and are frequently subjected to intense criticism. It is reported that 60 per cent of the victims meet

the diagnostic criteria for depression, either during or after termination of the relationship, and have a greatly increased risk of sociability. The most commonly referenced psychological effect of domestic violence is Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). PTSD is characterized by flashbacks, intrusive images, exaggerated startle response, nightmares and avoidance of triggers that are associated with the abuse. These symptoms are generally experienced for a long span of time after the victim has left the dangerous situation.

to domestic violence include increased aggressiveness, anxiety, and changes in how a child socializes with friends, family and authorities. Problems with attitude and cognition in schools can start developing, along with a lack of skills such as problem-solving. Additionally in some cases the abuser will purposely abuse the mother in front of the child to cause a ripple effect, hurting two victims simultaneously.

Effect on Children – There has been increase in acknowledgement that a child who is exposed to domestic abuse during his upbringing will suffer in his development and psychological welfare. Some emotional and behavioral problems that can result due

3. Analysis of the Primary Data

Domestic Violence

Table-1

Cases of crime against women registered in Tamil Nadu during the years 1999-2009

Nature of Crime	999	000	001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	009
Sexual Assault (Rape)	30	38	32	01	57	18	71	57	23	73	96
Molestation	959	948	773	866	022	861	764	179	540	705	242
Kidnapping and abduction	000	05	59	20	32	92	83	18	097	160	131
Sexual Harassment	316	167	012	766	81	081	65	52	75	74	01
Dowry Death (Sec)	97	91	94	47	20	25	15	87	08	07	94

304B of IPC)											
Cruelty by Husband and Relatives (Sec 498AIPC)	20	37	15	66	565	437	650	248	976	648	460
Offences under the Dowry Prohibition Act	26	87	1	19	75	94	93	1	16	62	07

Table -1 Revealed that many women in Madurai district have faced the problems of Sexual Assault, Molestation, Kidnapping and abduction, Sexual Harassment, Dowry Death , Cruelty by husband and relatives from 1999-2009

Table-2
 Registered Cases of Cruelty by Husband and His Relatives under Sec 498A for the years 2001 - 2008 in the study districts

District	001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	otal
Madurai	3	6	8	4	7	3	73	17	81

Table -2 Women registered cases of cruelty by her husband and his relatives due to ego problems.

Table-3
 Registered Cases of Dowry Death under Sec 304B for the years 2001 - 2008
 In the Study Districts

District	001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	otal
Madurai	7	4	3	2			1	4	14

Table -4 Many dowry death cases were registered and women suffered a lot in the society due to in-laws and the relatives.

Table-4
 Registered Cases for offences under the Dowry Prohibition Act for the Years 2001 - 2008 in the study districts

District	001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	otal
Madurai	A				5	1		A	4

Table -4 Shows that even after the passing the Dowry Prohibition Act, many cases were registered.

Table-5

Disposal of Persons arrested under 304B IPC (Dowry Death) by Courts at different levels including Trial Courts during the period 2003 - 2008, in selected district

Dist		001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	otal
Madurai	Regi s. Cases	7	4	3	2			1	4	14

Table -5 Shows that many persons were arrested due to dowry deaths. Still women are facing lot of problems in the family and outside the family.

4. CONCLUSION

- Immediate solution should be taken to salve the problem.
- In families give and take policy should be maintained especially between husband and wives.
- Traditional culture should be rebuilt in the family.
- The families should follow religion ethics.
- Inequality has to be removed in the family.
- Social relationship has to be opened in the family.
- Wine shops have to be closed in all the area.

A Good family is a university. It is the duty of the people to renew their traditional culture for goodness of their life. Domestic Violence against women happened mainly because of the collapse of joint family system. So joint family system are very much required in this modern world. Every economics knows "How to manage scarce resources" like that people must know how to manage family relationship lifelong. Then our life will be fruitful lifelong.

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RIGHT TO ENVIRONMENT VIS-À-VIS WILD LIFE PROTECTION

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(Regd: 16ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

This is a research essay summarizing various environmental issues of India with prime focus on the Animal Rights with justification to wild life issues, protection and promotion. The thorough of summary begins with Indian mythological context followed by development of society through various stages leading to millennium growth of industrialization and population growth with critical discussion on Indian law.

Keywords: *Animal, Environment, Indian, Rights, Law,*

In a society, there are many individuals playing different roles or jobs so as to ensure smooth running of it. An engineer, a doctor, garbage man, mailman, waitress, farmer, driver etc. all play an important and distinct role in our society. Similarly in an environment each species has a role for the ecosystem to run smoothly. For example, the predators keep population of mice under control, insects help in pollination of flowers etc. Thus, every species is important and help in keeping the ecosystem balanced. According to various online dictionaries the term 'Ecological balance' means "a state of dynamic equilibrium within a community of organisms in which genetic, species and ecosystem diversity remain relatively stable, subject to gradual changes through natural succession." and "A stable balance in the numbers of each species in an ecosystem." The various organisms are not only dependent on the environment for their needs but also on each other. Such a dependency is mainly for food and this in turn results in the existence of food chains or food webs. When a single thread of the ecosystem is broken, the entire ecosystem begins to unravel. The most important point thus is that the natural

balance in an environment should be maintained. But, however this balance is getting disturbed due to various factors like the introduction of new species, the sudden death of some species, natural hazards or man-made causes. Abuse of the natural balance in the environment has long term effects.

Environment is the aggregate of all social, cultural, economical, biological, physical and chemical factors surrounding us to give us necessary protection. All the human beings depend upon the environment in which they live. To ensure full enjoyment of a wide range of human rights, including the right to life, health, food, clean water and sanitation protection of environment is an integral unit. Without a healthy environment it is impossible to even live at a level equivalent with minimum standards. Through a series of resolutions the United Nations Human Rights Council and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) have drawn our attention to the relationship between a safe and a healthy environment and enjoyment of the human rights. Such resolutions have raised awareness of how fundamental environment is as a prerequisite

for the enjoyment of human rights. The Stockholm Declaration and to some extent the Rio Declaration also show the link between human rights and dignity and environment. Earlier the concept of human right including the right to a healthy environment was considered as a novel idea. However, today it is recognized in international law and accepted by almost every country. The first formal recognition of this human right to a healthy environment was given in the *Stockholm Declaration, 1972*:

“Man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being, and he bears a solemn responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations.”¹

It is thus popularly known as the ‘Magna Carta of human environment’. These conventions and programs have helped in deepening our understanding about the direct and the indirect links between the protection of the environment and enjoyment of human rights. It also states the obligations and responsibilities of States for the protection on environment under various multilateral environmental agreements.

There are three important dimensions of the inter-relationship between human rights and the protection of environment: environment as a pre-requisite for enjoyment of human rights (duty of the State to ensure the level of environmental protection for full enjoyment of protected rights); implementation of human rights in order to ensure environmental protection; and the right to safe, healthy and ecologically-balanced environment is a human right in itself. In the recent years, recognition of the link between human rights and the environment has increased to a great extent. This has led to

the rapid growth in the number and scope of international and domestic laws, judicial decisions, academic studies and research on the relationship between human rights and environment.

The deterioration in the environmental protection will eventually endanger life of not only the present generation but also the future generation. Therefore, in the Indian scenario ‘Right to life’ has been used in a diversified manner. This right i.e. ‘Right to life’ in India includes, inter alia, right to survive as a being, right to maintain quality of life, right to live with dignity and right to livelihood. Article 21 of the Indian Constitution states: ‘No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedures established by law.’ The Apex court of India interpreted this negative right in two ways: firstly, any law that affects the personal liberty should be reasonable, fair and just and secondly, the Court recognized many in-articulated rights present in Article 21 in implied form. It is by this second method by which the Court interpreted the right to life and personal liberty to include the right to environment. “Article 21 protects right to life as a fundamental right. Enjoyment of life and its attainment including their right to life with human dignity encompasses within its ambit, the protection and preservation of environment, ecological balance free from pollution of air, water, sanitation without which life cannot be enjoyed”². The ‘Wild life’, which consists of flora (plants), fauna (animals, insects etc.) that are usually found in the forests, is a part of the environment, essential for maintaining the natural balance and hence should be protected. There are numerous laws enacted in India for the protection of wild life for example- The Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 ; Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act 1960 etc. Environment Protection Act of 1986 is considered as Umbrella legislation as it fills many gaps in existing rules. These certain specific Constitutional provisions and the landmark judgments of the Supreme Court

¹ *Stockholm Declaration (Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment), 1972, UN Doc. A/Conf.48/14/Rev.1.*

² IA 670/2002 AIR SC 724

form the bedrock on which conservation and protection of wildlife rests. In spite of the existing laws and rules the environment is deteriorating for the satisfaction of various human needs and comforts, wildlife is being inhumanely exploited leading to extinction of wild species and degradation of the environment.

Indian scenario

The ancient philosophical and mythological scriptures, the Vedas, Upanishad, Puranas of the Hindu religion give a description of plants, trees and wildlife and their importance for the existence of the of human life. The potentialities of the nature in controlling the climate, enhancing the fertility of the land and improving the human life which emphasizes the intimate kinship of the man and nature is highlighted in Rig Veda. Atharva Veda also considers trees as hearth of various gods and goddess. Yajur Veda emphasizes that the relationship of nature and animals should be of mutual respect and compassion, not of dominion and subjugation. Many animals, birds, plants were also associated with different Gods and Goddesses so that they can be protected and preserved for future generations. It is this association of various plants, animals and birds with the supernatural forces that they were preserved and protected for a long period. In the Mauryan empire King Ashoka could feel the necessity for protection of environment and did as much as possible for preservation and protection of resources and the environment including forests and wildlife by making several laws. This same trend continued to the era of medieval India when Mughals ruled over India. Britishers

however, took the strongest steps in the protection of the environment and wildlife³.

It is now pertinent to discuss the constitutional provisions prevailing in India over the period for the protection of environment and wildlife. India was under the colonial rule of British for a large period. The British people over exploited India's rich biodiversity and resources to generate revenue. This revenue orientation of the British government worked towards destructive deforestation, converting forest into desert and denudation of wildlife. The first step taken by the British Government to ensure State's monopoly rights over the forest was the enactment of the Forest Act, 1865. The Act was revised in 1878 and extended most of the territories under the British rule. This empowered the state to encroach the reserved forest to fulfill the immediate needs of the State and also empowered the forest administration authorities to impose penalties for any transgression of the provisions of the Act. The first Forest Policy was declared in 19th October 1884 by the British government. Many other Acts were enacted during the British period for the protection of environment like the Indian Forest Act of 1927. The framers of the Indian Constitution had not foreseen the importance of environmental protection in 1950 when the Constitution of India was adopted. No laws were enacted for the protection of wildlife. However, with the expansion in agricultural sector, industrial and other developments for the satisfaction of multiple human need and greed depletion in forest and decrease in the number of wildlife species could be seen. It is then this aspect gained attention around 1972 in response to the Stockholm declaration. Excessive poaching,

³ Advantage, 'Environment Protection Laws in the British Era' (Legalserviceindia.com, no-date) <<http://www.legalserviceindia.com/articles/brenv.htm>> accessed 6 December 2015

deforestation and mass killing of the animals for trade in the animal articles such as meat, bone, teeth, skin, fur, hair etc. led to extinction of some species and some other were on the verge of extinction. Increase in the population as well as the expansion in the agricultural and livestock raising led to overexploitation of the resources of the environment. Further it could also be felt that the then existing State legislations were inadequate to protect the wildlife. Therefore, the need to protect the wildlife of India was felt necessary and immediate action for it was required. Hence, the parliament of India legislated the Wild Life (Protection) Act, 1972 for the conservation, protection and improvement of wild life. Later in the 42nd amendment in 1976 protection of wildlife and forests was incorporated in the Directive Principles of State Policy. It was also included in the concurrent List, Seventh Schedule, and Article 256 of the Indian Constitution. Now it is also enshrined in the Article 51(g) of the Constitution, making it a Fundamental duty of every citizen to protect, conserve and improve the natural environment including wildlife and forests, rivers, lakes etc and to have compassion for living creatures⁴. Article 48A of the Directive Principles of the State Policy also make it mandatory for the state to endeavor for protecting and improving the environment and for safeguarding the forests and wide range of wildlife of the country. In 2003 further amendments were made and Sections 5A, 5B, 5C were inserted in the Wild Life and Protection Act of 1972 which authorized the Central Government to constitute the National Board for Wild Life (NBWL). NBWL hence, is the topmost scientific body in establishing policies and advising the Central Government and the State government in the ways and means of wild life protection and conservation and to

review the progress in the field of wild life protection and suggest measures for improvement thereto. It is mandatory on the part of the Central Government and the State Government to abide by the suggestions and directions of the NBWL they cannot brush aside its opinion without valid and acceptable reasons. The legislators of India have enacted many laws and rules in order to keep pace with the provisions of various conventions such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and also for ensuring proper implementation of IUCN, CITES etc. The Wildlife(Protection) Act, Bio-diversity Act, Forest conservation Act etc were enacted in the light of Articles 48A and 51A(g) of the Constitution. The Government of India has also laid down various action plans and policies for the conservation and improvement of wildlife and environment such as the National Forest Policy of 1988 (NEP), the National Environment Policy (NEP) of 2006, National Bio-diversity Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) of 2008 and Integrated development of habitats for wildlife in 2009 and development of Wildlife Action Plan (2002-2016). The national animal of India is in the endangered group now. The elephants are also being killed in large scale for their teeth skin meat etc for the making of various ivory products. Thus, the Importance of Wild life could be drawn from the Inference of Project Tiger and Project Elephant. The Panchayats and the Municipalities through the 73rd and 74th amendments have also been given power for protecting the environment and play a vital role at the grass root level.

The High Court and the Apex Court of India interpret that the right to a healthy and wholesome environment is a part of the right to life, guaranteed under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. The slow poisoning caused by pollution that leads to depletion of environment and atmosphere amounts to violation of Article 21 of the Indian Constitution. As a matter of fact, the right to life i.e. guaranteed in Article 21 of the Constitution encompasses the protection and preservation of the nature's gifts without which life cannot be enjoyed to complete

⁴ Durga Das basu , *SHORTER CONSTITUTION OF INDIA* (TWELFTH edn, Prentice Hall of India 1996) 309

extent i.e. to a minimum standard.⁵ Moreover, environmental degradation has disastrous impact on right to livelihood which is a part of the protected rights. The Supreme Court of India in its decisions has rested upon the Directive Principles of State policy to extend the scope and content of the fundamental rights, so as to bring them within the ambit of the justifiable rights. Thus the protection and conservation of the wildlife, ecology and environment, based upon the principles of sustainable development to restore with harmony the conflicting interest for development with the protection of a healthy environment has been recognized as a particular aspect of right to life. This was first seen in the case of *Chhetriya Mukti Sangharsh Samiti v. State of UP*, the Supreme court held “Every citizen has a fundamental right to have the enjoyment of quality of life and living as contemplated by Article 21 of the Constitution. Anything which endangers or impairs by conduct of anybody either in violation or derogation of laws, that quality of life or living by people is entitled to be taken resource of Article 32 of the Constitution.”⁶ The Odisha High Court in the case of *Kholamuhana Primary Fishermen Co-operation Society v. State of Orissa* has held that right to life includes right to pollution free atmosphere. This case was about pollution in the Chilka Lake leading to massive degradation of its ecosystem.⁷ In Indian Council for *Enviro-Legal Action v. Union of India*, the Apex Court of India has implemented right to wholesome environment as a part of the right to life enshrined in Article 21 of the Constitution on behalf of villagers and involves invasion on their right to life because of the pollution caused by private companies manufacturing hazardous and inherently dangerous chemicals like oleum and H acid.⁸ The

Supreme Court of India has also widened the scope of Article 21 in the case of *T.N. Godavardan v. Union of India* (1996) by providing the definition for ‘forest’ so that the Forest (Conservation) Act could be implemented more rigorously. Such landmark judgments might help in taking action against the pollution problem and the destruction of natural habitats for the wildlife.

Need for proper implementation

Though there exists various laws that have been legislated or the protection and conservation of wildlife and in spite of multiple judgments of the Supreme Court and the High Courts to stop excessive poaching and illegal trade in wildlife of India, proper implementation in a strict manner of it is lacking even today. Human being’s voracious greed for resources and his unlimited desires to conquer the nature has brought about the collision course with the natural balance of the environment. The demand for his immensely technical society imposes stress on the state of equilibrium of the ecosystem. Hence to make it more effective these enacted laws, action plans, policies should be implemented with more certainty and with minimum time taken for imposing penalty and the exemplary weight of punishment. The forest authorities and the wildlife protection bodies should themselves stop illegal practices like illegal trading of animal articles and timbers. The participation of local people is essential for proper and effective implementation of the wildlife protection laws and for the conservation of wildlife as these indigenous people and indigenous knowledge about various plants and wildlife can help in restoring the disturbed ecological balance. There is no quick fix solution for this grave problem and just amendment in the laws is not sufficient. Several steps should be taken, first being the reconstruction of investigation process. This requires training, specialized courses and to some extent sensitization of law enforcing personnel. Persons might be appointed in the State Forest Departments and at the

⁵ Durga Das basu, *SHORTER CONSTITUTION OF INDIA* (TWELFTH edn, Prentice Hall of India 1996) 168

⁶ AIR 1990 SC 2060

⁷ AIR 1994 Orissa 191

⁸ Air 1996 SC 446

grassroots level who should be trained in dealing wildlife cases more effectively. It is very well known that the wildlife cannot survive until and unless their habitat is protected. More than 60-70 % of the wild fauna exist outside the protected area networks i.e. national parks and sanctuaries. Almost more than two thirds of the India's tiger population is found outside the protected area of Tiger Reserves with very minimal protection. These habitats outside the protected areas should be assessed and plans should be drawn to safeguard these habitats. Given the close proximity of the human habitation to the protected areas of the wild fauna, conflict between human and wildlife is inevitable but with the rapid growth in the population there is rise in the demand for place of habitation which leaves the State with less choice. The present system of exclusionary model for the protection of wildlife is proving to be ineffective. There is a deep kinship of the human beings with the environment, hence such a approach should no more be encouraged that separates humans from nature.

historical and cultural field but also in the resources and the biodiversity. The wildlife of India is a treasure and we must not lose it in the madness of satisfying our luxury, comfort and needs.

Conclusion

Protection and preservation of wildlife is no more possible by the state Governmental approach alone. Public should cooperate actively and there is a need for committed, educated and active persons in the protection departments for the successful protection of the wildlife. A more participatory approach is required for wildlife conservation. Complete change in the vocabulary of conservation of wildlife is needed. The mode of separation and exclusion of humans for protection of environment should be replaced with the modes of inclusion and integration. We should never forget that all species are created equal and only one species (man) has no right to confer itself with the power that leads to the depletion of resources and environment, extinction of the other species, thereby disrupting in an irreversible way the natural balance of the ecosystem. India has a remarkably rich heritage not only in

“MICROBES OF OUR SOCIETY”: STORY OF MANUAL SCAVENGERS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties

(Regd: 34ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The Paper deals with very important issues of violating human dignity which is widely prevalent in India, ignored, encouraged and accepted, that is manual scavenging. These part of community without them we can't find our streets, villages, towns and cities clean and free from health affect hazards are treated as Microbes, the so called upper class consider them Harijans, untouchables.

Keywords: *Human, Rights, Scavengers, Society, Untouchables*

India is an iconic figure among other nations of the world, known for it's vivid culture portrayed with flamboyance and ethical values. A nation with citizens who value dignity more than their life. Even in this advanced era where people are busy propagating importance on human rights and other socially relevant issues, it is embarrassing to know that some of our fellow beings are still treated as untouchables and are forced to clean the excreta of others to earn their daily bread; i.e. manual scavenging. Hence, we have put forward few questions on the account of this issue:

- How does the system of manual scavenging penetrate into the social life of India?
- How does the act of manual scavenging violate human rights?
- Whether the measures adopted by government to eradicate manual scavenging are effective?
- What is the plight of the community in the present scenario?

Manual scavenging and operation of dry latrines is an infringement of many of the fundamental rights such as Article 14, Article 17 and Article 23 of the constitution. Without any further doubts, here it is evident that their dignity of life is questioned. Also, the health hazards caused by this can't be neglected since the statistics show us that the number of affected ones are pretty high. There is an urgency for strict protection of rights and rehabilitation of manual scavengers all over the nation.

People of India are still unaware about the fact that, there are people in India who involuntarily involve in these abhorrent occupations. This reflects a clear-cut image that India is still suffocating with the evils of caste system. In the recent years this issue has generated widespread recognition in both national and international platforms. Even though there came various legislations and judicial proceedings to curb this act, they all went futile due to the lack of bona fide implementation of governmental policies. In spite of having a legislation to tackle their

issues and give them protection, it is unfortunate see that the law remains as a paper tiger. Through this paper we are narrating the story of a lamentable class of people who are forced to do manual scavenging and, we also wish to discuss the social and legal aspects regarding this issue.

1. HISTORY OF MANUAL SCAVENGERS IN INDIA

India is a country which has been cursed by the evil effects of the caste system. It often arises questions upon us on what basis these discriminating classification were framed among these diverse people of the society. According to Rig Veda each and every person is classified into different classes primarily according to their occupation. It had been believed that the different Varnas (classes), have been created by the supreme power called Brahma. It is said that from the mouth of brahma the Brahminical society (the priestly and intellectual class society) born from and it is from the arms Kshatriyas or the warriors has been originated and there came Vysias (the Bureaucrats and Merchants) from his thighs and finally the ones who took birth from the legs of lord Brahma, the down trodden class or the Shudras were evolved. The Shudras or this downtrodden societies were called as Bhangis which means “broken” or Trash.¹They were forced to remain secluded from the mainstream societies considering them as untouchables. They were forced to do most atrocious jobs of that society. Within Shudras many other sub-castes were made according to their occupation. Since there were no modernised toilets then, human waste had to be collected from dry toilets daily. Thus came the need of manual

scavengers in the society. People who belongs to the Balmiki castes where forced to clean the excreta of their same kinds. Using tin sheet and brooms or even using bare hands they collects human wastes daily. For a very long time their sufferings went unheard. Many of them fell victim to a myriad of diseases due to their unhygienic practices. The ones who wished to go for other jobs where threatened and jeopardised. In the report *Broken People*, Human Rights Watch summed up caste as “the world’s longest surviving social hierarchy, a complex ordering of social groups on the basis of ritual purity” It varies from place to place from one religious interpretation to another. But all over India one thing is common: beneath the castes are the outcastes, the polluted and the untouchables.²

There were various subdivisions within the Balmiki class regionally such as Chauda, Rokhi, Mehatar, Malkhana, Halalkhor and Lalbegi or the Muslim Hela sub-caste. These communities were considered downtrodden and deteriorated even within the Dalit communities. Since they are born for collecting “human shit” and for doing other unsanitary tasks.

In various Ancient religious text books like Narada Samhita and Vajasaneyi Samhitha we could see references regarding manual scavenging. From that period onwards they were denied of all development, social and economic opportunities and even basic human rights. Even Safai Karmacharis and other communities faced discriminations and the upper castes often treat them brutally. Manual scavenging in India has a mixed lineage. Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro civilization of 2500 BC reflects evidence of existence of wet toilets. These cities had toilets which were connected to underground

¹<http://blog.longreads.com/2014/01/28/a-brief-history-of-class-and-waste-in-india> visited on 17th November 2015

²<https://www.hrw.org/report/2014/08/25/cleaning-human-waste/manual-scavenging-caste-and-discrimination-india> visited on 21st November 2015

drainage system lined with burned clay bricks. Excavations from Lothal, one of the prominent cities of the ancient Indus valley civilisation also showed that as in Harappa, people had waterborne toilets in each house, courtesy to a well-planned drainage system made of burned clay bricks. To facilitate operations and maintenance of the drainage systems and manholes and chambers were also made. History says that with the decline of Indus Valley Civilisation science of sanitary engineering held up. During the end of Vedic period, Rig Veda mentions about the Varna system which began to modify into caste system. Hence it can be seen that manual scavenging evolved with the evolution of caste system and now it is continuing in this country from Kashmir to Kanyakumari. Even in the Mauryan period Pataliputra (now Patna) was one of the five ancient cities where the city major termed as “Nagarak”, was the head of the organisation entrusted with the task of looking after the civil affairs of the town. He scavengers and sweepers cleaned the city and disposed the night soil. Some argue that the Mughals are the ones who instituted manual scavenging in the northern provinces of India. Prisoners of war were forced to engage in manual scavenging as a style of torture, and their descents were called as Bhangi. The proof of Research on the medieval sewage system reveals that the bathing rooms of the Mughal forts had small outlets used as toilets. The waste was carried by gravity to the ramparts with water. This mechanism can be found in the Red Fort in Delhi, in the palaces of Rajasthan, in Hampi, Karnataka and in Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. The practice of manual scavenging continued even under the British who came to the 'Orient' on the pretext of a civilising mission³. The British

legitimised and systemised this degrading work while setting up army cantonments and municipalities. Official posts for manual scavengers were created. Every British institution - the army, railways, courts, industries and major towns were equipped with dry toilets instead of waterborne toilets/sewerage. And it has been decades after our country got independence and still this loathing job is continuing. According to my opinion caste system is the most outdated practice of our country and millions of people across the country are suffering as a result of them.

British India tried to establish rule of law and enforcement of equality of without any sorts of discrimination on the basis of caste and religion and in this respect some legislations like Charter Act of 1833 were also instituted. Still they were disinclined to amend the hierarchy in the prevailing social order, as they were interested in this social divisions. This poignant caste system manured the intensions of British in India. Mahatma Gandhi defined “Untouchability means pollution by touch of certain persons by reason of their birth in a particular state or family” and B.R Ambedkar defined “Untouchability is the notion of defilement, pollution, contamination and the ways and means of getting rid of that defilement”. It is a case of irreparable, congenital smear which cannot be purged. Mahatma Gandhi endeavoured to revamp the life of people indulged in manual scavenging. He considered manual scavenging as a sin against god and humanity and quoted “I may not be born again but if happens, I will like to born in a family of scavengers so that I may relieve them from this inhuman, unhealthy, and hateful practice of carrying head loads of night soils.”

³<http://www.hardnewsmedia.com/2008/03/2128#sthash.RHtffExs.dpuf> visited on 29th November 2015

In 1948, the Maharashtra Harijan Sevak Sangh, objected the practice of manual scavenging and eventually announced its abolition. In 1949, several recommendations were proposed to improve the working conditions of the sanitary workers. In 1957, the Scavenging Conditions Enquiry Committee recommended the abolition of practice of carrying human excreta in head loads. In 1968, National commission on Labour set up a committee to study the working conditions of sweepers and scavengers⁴. All these committees recommended the abolition of manual scavenging and rehabilitation of sanitary workers or in other words they are known as Safai Karmacharis, but none of the recommendations were implemented. Although untouchability is legally abolished in India the still prevalent.

2. Manual Scavenging and Violation of Human Rights

The framers of our constitution has adopted equality liberty and fraternity from the French revolution and included in our constitution. The Balmiki class is one set of people who are facing huge discrimination and has been kept ignored by the Indian polity. These illiterate ones are deprived of justice before law hence violating Article 14 of the Indian constitution.⁵

⁴Seema Chowdary, Manual Scavengers|The hands that clean you-a cause close to Mahatma Gandhi's heart this community is yet to be identified and uplifted available at http://www.livemint.com/leisure/fueZ4nUVfDloXSCFanLAXI/The_hands_that_clean_you.html, visited on 11th April 2013

⁵Article 14 "The state shall not deny any person equality before law or equal protection before law within the territory of India."

Violation of Article 17⁶:

India is a country which has been suffered due to the evil effects of untouchability. And the Article says about abolition of untouchability.

Untouchability is abolished and its practice in any form is forbidden. The enforcement of any disability arising out of Untouchability shall be an offence punishable in accordance with law.

But while reading the facts stated before we are able to understand how these communities has been suffering from the evil effects of untouchability.

Violation of Article 19(1)⁷:

Manual scavenging is an unenviable profession and they are doing it only because they are forced to do it by their so-called "superior communities". They are warned and not allowed to go for any other jobs and they are deprived of all other job opportunities. Hence their right to undergo a trade or a profession according to their wish has been infringed.

Violation of Article 21⁸:

India is a country which gives importance to their dignity more than their

⁶Article 17 in The Constitution of India 1949: Abolition of Untouchability; Untouchability is abolished and its practice in any form is forbidden The enforcement of any disability arising out of Untouchability shall be an offence punishable in accordance with law

⁷Article 19(1) in The Constitution of India 1949: All citizens shall have the right(a) to freedom of speech and expression;(b) to assemble peaceably and without arms;(c) to form associations or unions;(d) to move freely throughout the territory of India;(e) to reside and settle in any part of the territory of India; and(f) omitted(g) to practise any profession, or to carry on any occupation, trade or business.

⁸Article 21 in The Constitution of India 1949: No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to the procedure established by law.

life. In such a situation they are forced to live an undignified life by cleaning the excreta. They are not only deprived of a dignified life but also deprived of healthy living conditions. As stated before, they are suffered by a myriad of diseases due to their unhygienic environment and malnutrition. Even in railways the authorities are not giving any precaution to these workers (like glows) and hence caused with various skin disease. The community has been considered as a downtrodden or impure one and has lost their dignity for decades.

Violation of Article 21(A) Right to Education:

According to a field study done at altar of Rajasthan, revealed the children of manual scavengers are not getting proper education. Most of their children are admitted to a government school where the entire students of the school have been occupied into a single class. Mere going into the school doesn't make a child educated but what he requires is quality education and sadly that's what these poor children lack. The families who are involved in these abhorring profession are not willing to send their girl children to school. Since this is a caste based profession which has been practice for decades in the general perception of the people is that there is no use of educating such a girl child who will finally end up doing the same profession.

This practice of manual scavenging also infringes the directive principles of state policies. As per Article 46 of the constitution "the state shall promote with special care, the educational and economic interest of the weaker sections of the people and in particular of the scheduled castes and scheduled tribe and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitations."

3. MANUAL SCAVENGERS AND THEIR HEALTH

Many acts have been passed to curb this undignified occupation, but most of them are getting futile by the lack of proper implementations. Working conditions have got virtually unchanged all over the century. They are exposed to a myriad of hazards despite of various atrocities faced by them. They often get exposure to harmful gases like hydrogen sulphide and methane leading to the diseases like cardiovascular degeneration, musculoskeletal disorders like Osteoarthritic changes and inter vertebral disc herniation. They are also caused with infections like hepatitis, leptospirosis, helicobacter, various skin and respiratory diseases and altered pulmonary function parameters.

4. WOMEN MANUAL SCAVENGERS

Woman working under these barbaric conditions are in great danger of contacting a countless diseases through their daily and closed contact with human wastes. Some of these diseases, in addition to TB, include, campylobacter infection, cryptosporidiosis⁹, giardiasis¹⁰, hand, foot and mouth disease, hepatitis A, meningitis¹¹ (viral), rotavirus infection, salmonella¹²

⁹Cryptosporidiosis: A diarrhoeal disease caused by microscopic parasites, *Cryptosporidium*, that can live in the intestine of humans and animals and is passed in the stool of an infected person or animal.

¹⁰Giardiasis: Infection of the intestine with a flagellate protozoan, which causes diarrhoea and other symptoms

¹¹Meningitis: Inflammation of the meninges caused by viral or bacterial infection and marked by intense headache and fever, sensitivity to light, and muscular rigidity, leading (in severe cases) to convulsions, delirium, and death.

¹²Salmonella: A bacterium that occurs mainly in the intestine, especially a serotype causing food poisoning.

infection, shigellosis¹³, thrush¹⁴, viral gastroenteritis¹⁵, worms and yersiniosis¹⁶.

It is pitiful to hear that, according to the report of TISS (TATA INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES), “Ninety percent of all manual scavengers have not been provided proper equipment to protect them from faeces borne illness,” (Jan 2007). This includes safety equipment like gloves, masks, boots and/or brooms. The use of hands by women manual scavengers, along with the certainty that they will have direct skin contact with human waste, is a very dangerous combination that is contributing to serious health conditions. Chronic skin diseases and lung diseases are very common among women manual scavengers.

This situation is applicable not only for manual scavengers but also for sewage or manhole sanitation workers. The duty of a sewage worker is to remove the clogs in the sewage canal. For this they enter into deep drainage canal often having frequent contact with poisonous gases. Just as manual scavengers they also do this job without any required precautions. Sewage workers have to remove solid substance wastes using their bare hands which are responsible for the blockage of flow of fluid waste in sewage system.¹⁷

¹³Shigellosis: An intestinal disease caused by a family of bacteria known as shigella.

¹⁴Thrush: An infection of the mouth and throat by a yeast like fungus, causing whitish patches.

¹⁵Gastroenteritis: Inflammation of the stomach and intestines, typically resulting from bacterial toxins or viral infection and causing vomiting and diarrhoea.

¹⁶Yersiniosis is an infectious disease caused by a bacterium of the genus Yersinia.

¹⁷Rashtriya Grama Abhiyan: <http://www.mfcindia.org/main/bgpapers/bgpapers2013/am/bgpap2013h.pdf> visited on 25th November

5. LEGISLATIVE ENDEAVOURS AND MANUAL SCAVENGING

Manual scavenging prohibition and construction of dry latrines prohibition Act 1993. This act was primarily made for raising the standard of living of the manual scavengers and to improve the public health and sanitation

According to Section (2) of this act:

- a. No person shall engage in or employ or permit to be engaged or employed for any other person for manually carrying human excreta or construct or maintain dry latrines.

The main objectives of this act are:

- *Time bound phased programme for the conversion of dry latrines into water prone latrines.*
- *Giving provisions of technical/financial assistance for new or alternate low cost sanitation facilities.*
- *Construction and maintenance of community latrines and regulation of their use and pay basis.*
- *Construction and maintenance of shared latrines in slum areas or for the benefits of the Social or Economically Backward Class citizens.*
- *Registration of manual scavengers and their rehabilitation.*
- *Specification and standards of water seal latrines.*
- *Licensing for collection of fees in respect of community or shared latrines.*

Whosoever fails to comply with the act are made to be punishable with an imprisonment up to a term of one year or with a fine of Rs.2000 or both and if this act continues a fine of Rs.100 per day will be levied from the offenders.¹⁸

¹⁸www.downtoearth.org.in News visited on November 12 2015

The main criticism based on this act was it was purely made from the sanitation perspective and was made by the ministry of housing and poverty alleviation. But the actual objective of this act should be to restore human dignity and was liable to talk about rehabilitation and rejuvenation of manual scavengers.

6. THE PROHIBITION OF EMPLOYMENT AS MANUAL SCAVENGERS AND THEIR REHABILITATION ACT 2013

As a result of this case a new act was formulated for preventing atrocities against manual scavengers. Firstly a bill was drafted in the year of 2012 named “prohibition of employment as manual scavengers and their rehabilitation”. It was passed by both the houses on September 7th 2013 and the two main objectives were:

- *Prohibition of employment as manual scavengers*
- *Rehabilitation the existing manual scavengers*

This act gave impetus not only helps to eradicate manual scavenging, it had a wider scope for higher penalties as punishments.

Manual scavenging but also has the provision to provide alternate jobs to these employers and their families. Penalty is imprisonment upto five years according to this act.

The main features of this act are:¹⁹

It prohibits the employers from manual cleaning of sewers and septic tanks without protective equipment and construction of insanitary latrines.

- The definition of manual scavengers has been widened to include a person engaged or employed interalia for manual cleaning of human excreta in insanitary latrines or in open drains or pit.
- Express provisions for identification of manual scavengers and insanitary latrines
- Prohibition of hazardous manual cleaning of septic tanks and sewers, so as to ensure that health and safety of such workers could not be compromised. More stringent provisions for continuation of the new act.
- Vigilance and monitoring committees to set up at subdivisions, districts, state and central levels.
- It tells about the importance of protective gear and safety devices and precautions.
- It also say that every local authority shall carry out within a period of two months from the date of commencement of the act, a survey of insanitary latrines and publish the tests of insanitary latrines of this area for which a time schedule will be drawn.
 - It also say about the importance of awareness campaign that should be carried out at every state, district, subdivisions and town level whenever insanitary latrines are found during the survey.²⁰

Even after all these attempts it is shameful to know that the world’s largest railway network. The Indian railway is also the largest employer of manual scavengers. While the legislative body and bureaucrats officially denies the employment of manual scavengers it is an unambiguous fact that the

²⁰<http://www.prsindia.org/billtrack/prohibition-of-employment-as-manual-scavengers-and-their-rehabilitation-bill-2012-2449> visited on 23rd November 2015

115,000 km track spread across a route of 65,808Km and 7,112 stations, has been kept clean by the hands of these innocent people. This act has the provision to indulge people in cleaning of railways tracks containing human faeces with the help of protective gears but is this what actually we want? Why can Indian railway provide biotoilets instead of these filthy closets where the human excreta is directly thrown outside in these track. Since we could clearly highlight the drawbacks we can't proclaim that this act is a perfect remedy.²¹

7. SAFAI KARMACHARI ANDOLAN CASE

The most landmark judgement regarding this hot topic was laid down in the case Safai Karmachari Andolan and ORS V. Union of India.

The case has been judged by a bench consisting of three judges J.P Sathasivam, J Ranjan Gogoi and N.V Ramana. The main objective of filling this case was to strictly enforce the implementation of the Employment of Manual Scavengers and construction of dry latrines (prohibition act),1993 and also seeking for enforcement of fundamental rights guaranteed under Articles 14,17,21 and 47 of the constitution. The main objective of forwarding this case are as follows:

- To ensure complete eradication of dry latrines
- To declare continuance of the practice of manual scavenging and the operation of dry latrines violate constitution.
 - To direct union of the respondents to adopt and implement the act and to formulate detailed plans on time bound basis, for complete

eradication of practice of manual scavenging and rehabilitation of persons engaged in such practice.²²To direct Union of India and state governments to issue necessary directives to various municipal corporations, municipalities and nagar panchayats to strictly implement the provisions of the act.To file periodical compliance reports pursuant to various directions issued by this court.

Current statistics of Manual Scavengers:

According to the economic caste senses released on July 3rd 2013 reveals that 180657 households are involved in this act for their lively hood. Among the states Maharashtra tops with 63713 manual scavengers from a total population of 1.3 crores, followed by Madhya Pradesh (23,093), Uttar Pradesh(17,619) and Tripura(17332). From the statistics we could understand that the number of manual scavengers have reduced incredibly. In 1961 census there were 3.5 million manual scavenging in our country and roughly 8 lakh people were engaged in manual scavenging.²³

Issue of Manual Scavenging in an International level:

In recent times, this inhuman issue of manual scavenging has also attained an international exposure. Various internationally acclaimed organisations have strived to propagate this issue across the globe, especially United Nations. The special

²¹ www.downtoearth.org.in > News visited on 12thNovember 2015

²²Safaikarmachariandolan v union of indiaindiankanon.org/doc/6155772visited on 24th November 2015

²³<http://www.thehindu.com/news/national/manual-scavenging-still-a-reality-socioeconomic-caste-census/article7400578.ece>

rapporteurs comprises the Sub-Commission on the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights researched upon this subject. Even before this, in 2007, the annual report of the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination of the UN conveyed consternation about the callous conditions of manual scavengers in India. It stated, “The Committee notes with concern that very large numbers of Dalits are forced to work as manual scavengers”.

In its 1999 and 2007 reports, eminent international NGOs like Human Rights Watch have scrutinized the difficulties of manual scavengers, connecting these to untouchability and caste-based discrimination. In 1999 report, Human Rights Watch recommended that the government should ensure effective fulfilment of the Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines Prohibition Act, 1993, including the judicial proceedings against the officials accountable for prolonging the practice and for not reintegrating the affected manual scavengers.

8. CONCLUSION:

Even in this advanced era where people are busy propagating importance on human rights and other socially relevant issues, it is embarrassing to know some of our fellow beings are still treated as untouchables and are forced to clean the excreta of others to earn their daily bread. This reflects a clear-cut image that India is still suffocating with the evils of caste system. In the recent years this issue has generated widespread recognition in both national and international platforms. Even though there came various legislations and judicial proceedings to curb this act, they all went futile due to the lack of bona fide implementation of governmental policies.

Before raising developmental propaganda, its high time government should implement fast track actions to completely wipe off these stain, which have affected the backward classes of our society. Government should also ensure that, there shouldn't be absolutely no control for people belonging to any so-called “apex” classes over them. A drastic alteration especially in the Indian Railway is consequential. Dry latrines should be substituted by bio latrine technology.

One of the major remedy lies within us, people should erase their barbaric attitude towards the people belonging to these socially backward classes. An individual should pledge to create a socially committed attitude to bring about pragmatic changes in our society. Young minds should enlighten the void and dark minds of people with proper awareness. So that with fraternity people of diverse classes hands and walk together to carve a better and brighter India.

DISABILITY RIGHTS IN INDIA AND INTERNATIONAL CONVENTIONS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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(Regd: 37ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The concept of human rights is used by public at large. Often the concept varies from person to person. A theologian member of Christian denomination may have a different understanding than that of a philosopher. Similarly always' view is based on logical premises. Therefore, concept of Human rights differs from person to person. Human rights attached itself with human dignity and integrity which his an integral part of human freedom and enjoyment

Keywords: *Human rights, disabilities, International Conventions*

The concept of human rights is used by public at large. Often the concept varies from person to person. A theologian member of Christian denomination may have a different understanding than that of a philosopher. Similarly a lawyer's view is based on logical premises. Therefore, concept of Human rights differs from person to person¹.

We are citizens of interwove global community. This global community or society is seen closely together by the process of globalization. The various unknown tribes, communities, migrants have come together through globalization. This global connection makes us realize how we are connected to one another. Human right is also a part of this process of globalization

which makes us realize not only one's own need but also the needs of others².

Human rights simply mean one's rights and freedoms. A person has certain rights and freedom simply because he/she is a human. It not only affects oneself but also the surroundings i.e. friends, family, co-workers, colleagues etc. The controversy of universality of human rights, like other intellectual debates, has created a conceptual confusion. Human rights are universal as a concept but the scope of application when combined to *ratione loci*³ to *ratione personae*⁴. Applicability means it applies to

² Philips A Douglas, "Global Connections: Human rights", Chelsa House Publication (2009), pg 7-9

³ A court will consider whether it has jurisdiction *ratione loci* and will assess that jurisdiction where the item of property in dispute is within their territory, though the parties are not. Similarly, where the contract was accepted within the territory covered by the court or where an alleged tort which gives rise to the claim before it, occurred on the territory covered by the court though one or both of the parties reside elsewhere

⁴ Jurisdiction of a judge in a case which has international elements may depend on the whereabouts of the plaintiff or, as in most cases, the defendant. In certain cases, jurisdiction will depend on the whereabouts of the object of the

¹ Brems Eva, "Human rights: Universality and Diversity", Martinus Nijhoff Publishres, Netherlands, (2001) pg 3-8

all persons regardless of place. Universality simply justifies that there is no barrier of times place, nationality, race, gender, language, religion, political opinion, birth, property etc. for applicability of Human rights⁵.

Human rights attached itself with human dignity and integrity which is an integral part of human freedom and enjoyment. The intellectual center of entire culture of human rights is based on human dignity. It is a part and parcel of legal order⁶.

But the question remains the same, what are human rights? Human rights are as basic as the human existence. Those rights which are enjoyed just because of the fact that he/she is a human, is a Human Right.

The human rights developed after the Second World War wherein atrocities were committed against people resulting in adoption of Universal Declaration of Human Rights by United Nations General Assembly in 1948. But the basis of UDHR lies in United Nations Charter, the preamble of which reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the equal rights of men and women" and Article 1(3)⁷ of the United Nations charter, for the first time used the words "Human rights" so as to encourage respect and freedom for all human beings. Similarly Article 55⁸ provides that human

being should enjoy a good standard of living, employment opportunities and universal respect for human rights.

Of particular importance is Article 56⁹ of the charter, all the members take joint and separate pledge to co-operate with each other to achieve the purpose set forth in Article 55. UDHR is a non-binding resolution, which has acquired the force of international customary law can be entreated by national and other judiciaries when needed¹⁰. The UDHR strive to promote civil, economic and social rights, as part of the foundation of freedom, justice and world peace. The declaration was the first international legal effort to limit the behavior of states and press upon them duties to their citizens following the model of the rights-duty duality. The Preamble of UDHR¹¹ recognizes the dignity and inalienable rights of human beings and to give them justice and freedom.

The UDHR was framed by members of the Human rights Commission, with former First Lady Eleanor Roosevelt as Chair, who began to discuss an *International Draft bill of Rights* in 1947. The members of the Commission did not immediately agree on the form of such a draft bill of rights, and whether, or how, it should be enforced. The Commission proceeded to frame the UDHR and accompanying treaties, but the UDHR quickly became the priority. The document was structured to include the basic principles of dignity, liberty, equality and brotherhood. Some of the UDHR was researched and written by a committee of international

litigation (i.e. real estate); in others, jurisdiction will depend on whether or not the defendant is within the territory of the court or is a citizen of that court's nation.

⁵ Ibid 1.

⁶ Tomuschat Christian, "Human rights: Between Idealism and Realism", Oxford University Press, (2008), 2nd Edn

⁷ Article 1(3) of United Nations Charter states that one of the purposes of UN Charter is to "achieve international cooperation in solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character, and in promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion".

⁸ Article 55 of United Nations Charter shall promote:

a) higher standards of living, full employment, and conditions of economic and social progress and development; b) solutions of international economic, social, health, and related problems; c) international cultural and Educational cooperation; d) universal respect for, and observance of,

human rights and fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion

⁹ Article 56 of United Nations Charter states that "All Members pledge themselves to take joint and separate action in co-operation with the Organization for the achievement of the purposes set forth in Article 55."

¹⁰ Ball, Olivia, Gready, Paul, "The No-Nonsense Guide to Human Rights New Internationalist", Oxford University Press (2001).

¹¹ Preamble of UDHR states that, "Recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world".

experts on human rights, including representatives from all continents and all major religions. The Universal Declaration was later on divided into two important treaties, a Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and another on social, economic, and cultural rights¹².

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), 1966 were Adopted by the United Nations, between them making the rights contained in the UDHR binding on all states that have signed this treaty, creating human-rights law.

When we talk about Human rights, disability becomes a very important issue which needs to be dealt with in the context of Human rights. Social Values, norms and attitudes are not static and are liable to change depending on a wide range of factors are forces that operate at macro and micro level. The formal notion of disability has undergone revisions to accommodate changes in social norms and attitudes. What a society at a particular time in its history considers to be a disabling conditioning reflects its conception of a normal and socially functional human being and hence in a way it reflects society's self-image¹³.

Disability is a Human rights issue. Disabled people deserve the same rights. The disability movement identified Human rights as a major issue in the fight for equal rights and participation of Disabled people. International human rights treaties are needed to set a global framework and direction for the equal rights of Disabled people worldwide. The populations who live with a disability continuously encounter barriers to their full participation in society. People with disabilities are often denied

access to basic services such as primary health care and Education. Employment opportunities are extremely limited, hindering economic self-sufficiency. Exclusion and abuse of people with disabilities are violations of their Human rights¹⁴.

A Human rights approach to disability acknowledges that Persons with Disabilities are right holders and that social structures and policies restricting or ignoring the rights of PWD's often lead to discrimination and exclusion. A human rights perspective requires society, particularly governments, to actively promote the necessary condition for all individuals to fully realize their rights¹⁵

In spite of being one of the most detailed and voluminous constitutions in the World, Indian Constitution does not incorporate specific provisions for Education and rehabilitation of Disabled persons¹⁶.

There are various legislations in India regarding disabilities but its implementation has not been seriously taken by our government. The PWD Act 1995 was drafted with a vision of giving employment opportunities and barrier free environment has failed in providing so. With the ratification of United Nations Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2007, the various social activists were of the view that it would bring changes regarding the perspective of people and create opportunities for Disabled persons. Since then, there has been no effort by the government to implement the ratification through an act. Recently, it has been reported by The Hindu Newspaper that Activists of the Disabled Rights Group protested against the non-passage of the

¹² Glendon, Mary Ann, "A world made new: Eleanor Roosevelt and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights", New York: Random House (2001).

¹³ Disability: Definitions, Estimates and Causes, Disability Manual, National Human rights Commission, (2005) pg 9

¹⁴ Dr. Kaur Prithpal, "Disability Issue: An New Strategic Alliance for the Disability Rights Movement", RGNUL law Journal, Punjab, Jan- Jun (2011) Vol. 1 pg. 1

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Dr. Palande Jayshree, "Rights of Disabled Children: Need for Practical Implementation of Legislative Provisions in India", Bharti Law Review, Pune Jan-Mar (2013), pg100

Rights of Persons with Disabilities Draft bill. The he version tabled in the Rajya Sabha had been approved by the Union Cabinet on December 30, but disability rights activists opposed it, saying it was a diluted version. The activists, led by Javed Abidi, then launched a major campaign for bringing amendments in the draft of the proposed law and met senior Ministers in the government. As a result 14 new amendments were added and then tabled in Rajya Sabha¹⁷. Amita Dhanda in her Article in India Express Newspaper has posed two questions as regard to first, can the government enact the Draft bill of 2014 through the Ordinance route after it had been referred to the House Committee; and second, should the government take this route? The Draft bill was sent to a House Committee and not passed by Parliament because it was accepted that it needed more work. There is no urgency to enact the Draft bill¹⁸.

Though, presently, the government has made efforts to draft a draft bill on Rights of Persons with Disabilities with amendments (2014) in 2011 but it has not been accepted by Rajya Sabha. Hence, the draft bill stands lapsed. The PWD Act of 1995 stands as a basic Act to deal with issues related to Disabilities. Not only has this, but also the other disabilities laws like The Mental Health Act, the Rehabilitation Council of India Act and The National Trust Act etc. needs amendments too¹⁹

1. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The history of disabilities prior to the 17th and 18th centuries has been referred to as a time of confusion, lacking in understanding of, and services for, persons with disabilities. However, the 17th and 18th centuries witnessed a more constructive, scientific

approach to individuals with disabilities. The earlier efforts of Sir Isaac Newton and Galileo contributed to an understanding of the physical world, while philosophers of the time tried to understand human nature.

1. **Mahabharatha:** Dhritrashtra, the blind Kaurav king was not found worthy of throne due to his blindness. Similarly, prince Shakuni, brother of Dhritrashtra's wife Gandhari and king of Gandhar, was handicapped but proved to be a very good politician in the kingdom of Kaurvas.

2. **Mughal Period:** Institution established for the welfare continued to thrive since zakat (a system of charity) was strictly adhered to. Mughal instituted special department with a head (sadar) to supervise charities and endowments. Facilities were opened to all citizens regardless of caste and class. Mughal Emperor Akbar took special care for maintaining social harmony and order²⁰

3. **Charity:** Introduction of special school by Christian missionaries. First school for hearing impaired was established in 1884 by the Roman Catholic missionaries at Mumbai. Ms Annie sharp started the first school for blind in 1887 at Amritsar Punjab.

4. **Pre-Independence:** The first school for the disabled persons, i.e., the deaf, was established in Mumbai 1884 by a Roman Catholic mission. First school for the blind was set up at Amritsar in 1887. In Calcutta 1893 followed by Roman Catholic mission. In palam cottash 1896 in Tamil Nadu followed by Roman Catholic mission 32 institutions for the blind in 1947. Limited arrangement for vocational training or other forms of economic rehabilitation Traditional craft- re-caning, weaving, doormat making etc. Absence of a common Braille Code for

¹⁷ Dhar Aarti, New Draft bill to strengthen definition of disabilities, The Hindu Newspaper, February 9, 2014.

¹⁸ Dhanda Amita, Disability Rights on the Ordinance Route, Indian Express Newspaper, February 24, 2014

¹⁹ ¹⁸ Mandal Sangeeta, "Rights of Disabled Persons: A Human rights Approach", Indian Human rights Law Review, December, (2010) Vol 1 pg 2.

²⁰ Eraly, Abraham, "The Mughal Throne: The Saga of India's Great Emperors Phoenix", Orion Publishing Group Ltd. (2004) pg. 115.

Indian Language No Braille Printing facility,²¹

5. Post-Independence: 1951, Bharti Braille came to be accepted as the National Code for the country. The central Braille Press and the workshop for the manufacture of Braille appliances established in Dehradun 1950s. RCI recognize first teacher training programmed in deaf blindness. National Institutes/ apex level institutions conduct long and short term specialized courses to train professionals in physiotherapy, occupational therapy, prosthetic and orthotic engineering, and mental retardation, special education, audiologist, speech rehabilitation, orientation and mobility etc²²

2. DISABILITY JURISPRUDENCE

Charity Model

Driven largely by sensitive appeals of charity, this model treats people with disabilities as helpless victims needing care and protection. As the term handicap implies, derived as it is from the image of a beggar with a 'cap in hand', this model relies largely on the goodwill of benevolent humanitarians for 'custodial care' of the disabled²³.

The charity model shares a common feature with the bio-centric model that there is a similar imperative of social responsibility that is derived from charity and benevolence, rather than justice and equality. The notion of charitable privilege has its roots in the laws, which primarily protected drain on social resources and created criteria to limit

claims to rights. In other words, the charity model was based on an assumption that claim to rights is valid on certain grounds and invalid on certain others. Disability was perceived as a disqualification and perhaps for this very reason the expression 'invalid' became synonymous with persons with disabilities²⁴. The charity model justified the exclusion of disabled from mainstream Education and employment, and other rights and privileges enjoyed by citizens who fitted into the criteria of valid holders of rights²⁵.

Bio-Centric Model/ Medical Model

The bio-centric model of disability is linked ideologically to a trend in Western thought that can be traced to the biological sciences and to a period referred to as the 'Enlightenment' era in Europe. In their struggle to grapple with apparent differences between groups of people, like disabled and non-disabled, the rich and the poor, men and women, western people and non-western people, the Europeans of this period tended to reduce social phenomena to their supposed natural biological roots. Similar construction based on biological and intellectual characteristics have also been deployed by lawmakers of ancient India who classified people into various caste categories. These scientists and philosophers were inclined to find scientific justifications for social inequality that fit into a mechanical world-view based on natural laws and natural causes at the level of biology²⁶.

On this basis, under the bio-centric model, persons with disabilities are positioned as

²¹ Inclusive Education in India: A Country in Transition available at <http://int1dept.uoregon.edu/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/INTL-UG-Thesis-Kohama.pdf> visited on May 4th, 2015.

²² Verma, Gajendra K, Christopher Bagley, and Madan M. Jha, "International Perspectives on Educational Diversity and Inclusion: Studies from America, Europe and India", London: Routledge (2007) pg 126.

²³ The charity model available at <http://www.making-prsp-inclusive.org/en/6-disability/61-what-is-disability/611-the-four-models.html> visited on April 4th, 2014.

²⁴ Siebers Tobin, "Disability Theory", University of Michigan, Michigan, (2008), pg 211.

²⁵ Fleischer Z. Doris and Zames Freida, "The Disability Rights Movement: From Charity To Confrontation", Temple University Publications, (2001), pg 11-13

²⁶ Disability and health available at

<http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs352/en/index.html> visited on April 4th, 2015

‘Abnormal’ in comparison to the established norms of a normal human being. In its harshest forms, the bio-centric model treats disabled persons as undeserving and dangerous.²⁷

Human Right Model

- Diversity
- Equality and Non Discrimination
- Accommodation
- Convenience
- Equal Participation and Inclusion
- Private and Public Freedom

Disability Right Model

The disability rights movement led by individuals with disabilities began in the 1970’s. The self-advocacy is often seen as largely responsible for the shift toward ‘independent living’ and ‘accessibility’. The term ‘independent living’ was taken from 1959 California legislation that enabled people who had acquired disability due to polio to leave hospital wards and move back into the community with the help of cash benefits for purchase of personal necessities for their normal subsistence. However, the movement and its philosophy have spread to the other countries after the US civil rights and consumer movements of the late 1960, and started influencing peoples’ self-perception, their ways of organizing themselves and their countries themselves²⁸

3.INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

The International recognition of human rights emerged in response to atrocities committed to human beings during World War II (1939-45). After World War II efforts were made to codify those rights that had been infringed earlier. Subsequently, the International draft bill of human rights instruments acknowledged that there are

some groups (women, children, disabled, minorities, migrants) which are identified as vulnerable and need protection²⁹. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948, is another important document which affirmed the rights of all people without any discrimination. The Preamble enumerated the basic postulates and principles of human rights in most comprehensive manner. Pursuant to this the General Assembly Adopted the Declaration on Social Progress and Development in 1969, reflecting an international awareness about the right of the persons with disabilities. The declaration proclaimed the necessity of the rights of the physically and mentally disabled people and assuring their welfare and rehabilitation. UDHR provides that all human beings are free and possess inherent dignity and rights³⁰. It also states that all persons have right to adequate standard of living for himself and his family in the circumstances which is beyond his control³¹.

*Hamilton v. Jamaica*³² provides solid evidence that the HRC³³ realizes the potential of the ICCPR in the disability context. So far, the complaint procedure has not been used to a great extent in the context of disability. But it is highly likely that the number of disability communications will

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Bagenstos Samuel, “Law and the Contradictions of the Disability Rights Movement”, Yale University Press,(2009)

²⁹ Indian Scenario, Disability Manual, National Human Rights Commission (2005), pg.25

³⁰ According to Article 1 of UDHR, All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

³¹ According to Article 25 of UDHR, Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or According to Article 25 of UDHR, Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or

³² *Hamilton v. Jamaica* CCPR/C/60/D/616/1995.

³³ Human Rights Committee.

increase in the years ahead as awareness of its existence spreads throughout the disability community.

The ICESCR rights from the peculiar perspective of disability can be grouped under: (a) Overarching right to non-discrimination

- The right to non-discrimination (Article 2)
- The right to equality between men and women (Article 3)

The Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10 December 1984 it came into force on 26 June 1987. The convention deals with the protection against discrimination from torture of inhuman conditions or treatment to any human being. Torture means any act by which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on a person for such purposes as obtaining from him or a third person information or a confession, punishing him for an act he or a third person has committed or is suspected of having committed, or intimidating or coercing him or a third person, or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or suffering is inflicted by or at the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official or other person acting in an official capacity. It does not include pain or suffering arising only from, inherent in or incidental to lawful sanctions³⁴

National Scenario:

A large section of disabled people live in India, which is an issue of great concern so far the availability and enforcement of their human rights is concerned. They being the most marginalized section of the society suffer from a number of complex problems deserving comprehensive legislation to cover

³⁴ Article 1(1) of CAT

all aspects of their lives. Although, legislation cannot alone radically change the fabric of a society but it can make a beginning by giving a socio- human consideration towards the needs and requirements of the disabled.

In essence, the human rights perspective on disability means viewing people with disabilities as subjects and not as objects. Importantly, it means locating problems outside the disabled persons and addressing the manner in which various economic and social processes accommodate the difference of disability, or not, as the case may be. The debate about the rights of the disabled is therefore connected to a larger debate about the difference existing in societies.

4. CONSTITUTION OF INDIA

A Constitution is a document having a special legal sanctity which sets out the framework and the principal function of the organs of the government of a state declares the principles governing the operations of those organs. Constitutional law is a rule which regulates the structure of the principal organs of the government and their relationship to one another, and determines their principle functions. The rules consist of both of legal rules in the strict sense and of usages, commonly called conventions, which without being enacted are accepted as binding by all who are concerned in the government

The Constitution of India incorporates the principles of social justice and human rights. The preamble, fundamental rights and directive principles of the state policy enshrined in the Constitution reflects the commitment of the state to its people. Disability as the ground of discrimination is not prohibited expressly in the Constitution. However, the state could initiate programmes in favour of the disabled on the basis of 'reasonable classification', which permits different person should be treated differently.

Any differential treatment which helps the disabled to overcome the disadvantage of disability is permissible under Article 14, 15 & 16 of the Constitution. Article 21 guarantees 'Right to life and personal liberty' which includes right to live with human dignity and extends to disabled persons as well. The Constitution of India gives an assurance in the form of directive principles of the state policy for the right to work, to Education and to public assistance in cases of unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement, and in other cases of undeserved want³⁵.

Mental health Law

In the recent decades, mental health and human rights have emerged as converging field of research and practice. The relationship between the two i.e. that health is human rights issue, whereas, mental health constitutes part of health itself³⁶. Therefore, both are interrelated. Mental disorders not only produce an enormous impact in their own right but through their interaction with physical conditions resulting in complex patterns of reciprocal causality.

People with mental health conditions including schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression, epilepsy, alcohol and drug use disorder, child mental health problems and intellectual impairments; have been largely overlooked as a target of development work. The economic impact on families and communities lead to social stigma, discrimination and exclusion. The need for development for people with mental health conditions is required in mainstreaming of

disability issues into strategies for sustainable development

Mental health legislations were initially drafted to safeguard the public from dangerous patients by isolating them from the public. A paradigm shift from custodial care to community care has occurred due to (i) Advances in medical technology in assessment and treatment of mental disorders; (ii) the human rights movement; (iii) World Health Organization's (WHO) definition of 'health' ; and (iv) Promotion, preventive, curative, rehabilitative approaches and mitigation of disability. This shift has given a new perspective to the care of mental disorders and has led to the review of mental health legislations worldwide.

In *Raj Kumar v. Rameshchand and Ors*³⁷, Raj Kumar, is a mentally retarded person. An application through next friend was filed on his behalf for eviction of the respondents from the premises which was owned by Raj Kumar, In reply to the Eviction Petition, it was inter alia stated that the appellant was a man of unsound mind and was not capable of doing any business and as no guardian has been appointed by the District Judge, the father could not act as a guardian. Regarding the Judicial inquisition alleged mentally ill person possessing property, custody of his person and management of his property. An application for appointment of a guardian in accordance with the said provisions was filed. An application to this effect was filed before the Rent Controller and the father was appointed as the guardian. The Appeal was allowed and the impugned order of High Court stating the non- maintainability of eviction petition was set aside

³⁵ Article 41 of the Constitution states that, the State shall, within the limits of its economic capacity and development, make effective provision for securing the right to work, to Education and to public assistance in cases of unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement, and in other cases of undeserved want.

³⁶ Dudley Michael, Silivi Derrick and Gale Ran, "Mental Health and Human Rights: Vision Praxis and Courage", Oxford University Press (2012), 1st Edn., pg 2-3.

³⁷ *Raj Kumar v. Rameshchand and Ors*, 1999 Supp(3) SCR 345

Rehabilitation Council of India Act 1992 (Amendment 2002)

The objectives of the RCI³⁸ are to:

- To regulate the training policies and programmes in the field of rehabilitation of persons with disabilities.
- To bring about standardization of training courses for professionals dealing with persons with disabilities.
- To prescribe minimum standards of Education and training of various categories of professionals/ personnel dealing with people with disabilities.
- To regulate these standards in all training institutions uniformly throughout the country.
- 5. To recognize institutions/ organizations/ universities running master's degree/ bachelor's degree/ P.G.Diploma/ Diploma/ Certificate courses in the field of rehabilitation of persons with disabilities.
- To promote research in Rehabilitation and Special Education.
- To maintain Central Rehabilitation Register for registration of professionals.
- To collect information on a regular basis on Education and training in the field of rehabilitation of people with disabilities from institutions in India and abroad.

Judicial Interpretation

In *Delhi Transport Corporation v. Rajbir Singh and Sadh Ram*³⁹, the respondents Rajbir Singh met with an accident on 12.8.1996 as a consequence whereof his left femur bone was fractured. He remained under treatment till 16.2.1997. He was advised rest by his doctors for three months initially. They were prematurely retired on the ground of medical invalidation.

³⁸ Sundar S., "Textbook of Rehabilitation", Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers Ltd, New Delhi (2007), pg. 1.

³⁹ *Delhi Transport Corporation v. Rajbir Singh and Sadh Ram*, (2003) ILLJ865Del.

Questioning the said orders, writ petitions were filed by the respondents praying that they be reinstated in service with full wages. The respondent allegedly filed a fitness certificate. However, he was directed to appear before a medical board, which declared him medically unfit and pursuant to and in furtherance thereof, the appellant passed an order on 10.7.1998 retiring him prematurely on medical grounds. Before a learned Single Judge, a question was raised that in a situation of this nature the appellant herein could not have terminated the services of the respondent in view of the provisions of PWD 1995.

National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy and Mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities Act 1999

- To empower the independent living of persons with disabilities in the community⁴⁰.
- To provide support and facilities to persons with disabilities⁴¹.
- To support those organizations which provide facilities to persons with disabilities and their families⁴².
- Address problems of the disabled persons⁴³.
- Care and protection of the disabled in the event of death of parents or guardian⁴⁴.
- Evolve procedures for appointment of guardians and trustees for people requiring a supported lifestyle⁴⁵.
- To facilitate equal opportunities, rights protection and full participation for disabled persons.

⁴⁰ Chapter II Section 10 (a) of National Trust Act, 1999

⁴¹ Chapter II Section 10 (b) of National Trust Act, 1999

⁴² Chapter II Section 10 (c) of National Trust Act, 1999.

⁴³ Chapter II Section 10 (d) of National Trust Act, 1999

⁴⁴ Chapter II Section 10 (e) of National Trust Act, 1999

⁴⁵ Chapter II Section 10 (f) of National Trust Act, 1999

Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995

- To spell out the responsibility of the state towards the prevention of disabilities, protection of rights, provision of medical care, Education, training, employment and rehabilitation of persons with disabilities.
- Create a barrier free environment.
- To counteract any situation of abuse and exploitation of persons.
- To make special provision of the integration of persons with disabilities into the social mainstream

Obligation Government

1. Undertake surveys, investigations and research concerning the cause of occurrence of disabilities
2. Promote various methods of preventing disabilities
3. Screen all the children at least once in a year for the purpose of identifying “at risk” cases
4. Provide facilities for training to the staff at the primary health centres
5. Sponsor awareness campaigns and disseminate information on general hygiene, health and sanitation,
6. Take measures for pre-natal and post-natal care of mother and child;
7. Educate the public through the pre-schools, schools, primary health centres, village level workers and anganwadi workers;
8. Create awareness amongst the masses through television, radio and other mass media on the causes

5. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The international community began to pay increased attention to the issues and conditions surrounding persons with disabilities (PWDs) after the United Nations proclaimed 1981 as the International Year of Disabled Persons, and the years 1983 to 1992 as the UN Decade of Disabled Persons. In

1992, the General Assembly of the UN Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP) Adopted the resolution that the period from 1993 to 2002 should be declared as the Asian and Pacific Decade of Disabled Persons and that ESCAP should adopt the Proclamation on the Full Participation and Equality of People with Disabilities in the Asian and Pacific Region and the Agenda for Action for the Asian and Pacific Region⁴⁶.

Comparative Analysis of 1995 and UNCRPD

The PWD 1995 was enacted as India was signatory to the ESCAP. The Act spells the responsibilities of the state towards the development of persons with disabilities, medical care, rehabilitation, training, employment etc. It also states that the state should create a barrier free environment and to remove any discrimination against PWDs

The preamble of the UNCRPD provides for the state parties to recall, recognize and reaffirm the principles laid down in UN Charter which recognizes the dignity of all persons and equal and inalienable rights of all persons. The Preamble also provides that the state parties to recall the principles of ICCPR, ICESCR, CEDAW, and Convention against Torture etc. The preamble of the UNCRPD provides for the state parties to recall, recognize and reaffirm the principles laid down in UN Charter which recognizes the dignity of all persons and equal and inalienable rights of all persons. The

⁴⁶ ESCAP adopted the Agenda for Action at its 48th General Assembly, which was held at the Beijing Conference in December 1992. The Agenda for Action identified 12 areas for action: (i) establishment of a national coordination committee on disability matters; (ii) enactment of legislation for PWDs; (iii) collection and analysis of data on the disability situation, and facilitation of access to information; (iv) public awareness building; (v) guarantee of access to build environments and communications; (vi) guarantee of integrated Education for children with disabilities; (vii) vocational training and employment of PWDs; (viii) prevention of causes of disability; (ix) expansion and improvement of rehabilitation services; (x) production and supply of assistive devices; (xi) promotion of self-help organizations of PWDs; and (xii) regional cooperation through networking.

Preamble also provides that the state parties to recall the principles of ICCPR, ICESCR, CEDAW, and Convention against Torture etc.

General Principles

Article 3 of the UNCRPD provides for principles for the present convention which the state party shall keep in mind while drafting legislation. These principles provides for inherent dignity, non-discrimination, equality of opportunity and equality between men and women.

1. There are no such general principles in the PWD Act 1995 that specifically provides for dignity, equality between men and women etc. as it does in UNCRD under Article

3. These principles are explained in detail under the Convention itself regarding the implementation by state party and obligations thereof.

2. There is no provision in the Act which provides for inherent dignity whereas the preamble of the convention starts with recalling the principles of UN Charter which recognizes inherent dignity⁴⁷. Also para (h) states that, 'discrimination against any person on the basis of disability is a violation of the inherent dignity and worth of the human person'. The purpose of the convention is to protect the dignity of persons with disabilities.

⁴⁷ The Preamble of UNCRPD, (a) *Recalling* the principles proclaimed in the Charter of the United Nations

which recognize the inherent dignity and worth and the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family as the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world

Judicial Interpretation

- With respect to discrimination faced by persons with disabilities in government employment and the scope of such employment, the Supreme Court in the case of *Dalco Engineering Private Ltd. v. Shree Satish Prabhakar Padhye and Ors*⁴⁸ held that the definition of 'establishment' under Section 47 included within its ambit government companies set up under the Companies Act, 1956. Hence, Section 47 is applicable to any person who acquires a disability during service in a Government company. However the section would not apply to private companies.
- While considering the question of discrimination in the promotion of persons with disabilities in government employment, the Hon'ble Supreme Court held in the case of *Union of India (UOI) v. Devendra Kumar Pant and Ors.*⁴⁹, that under Section 47 of the PWD, promotion of a disabled employee with disability shall not be denied to a person on the ground of his disability if the disability does not affect his capacity to discharge the higher functions of a promotional post.

Comparative Analysis of UNCRPD and Draft RPD Draft bill

The United Nations Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities consists of some important general principles which every state party who is a signatory to the convention needs to comply with. These general principles are incorporated in Article 3 of the convention.

Keeping in mind these general principles, the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Draft bill was drafted in 2011. Efforts have been made to incorporate all the general principles and

⁴⁸ *Dalco Engineering Private Ltd. v. Shree Satish Prabhakar Padhye and Ors*, AIR 2010 SC 1576.

⁴⁹ *Union of India v. Devendra Kumar Pant and Ors*, AIR 2010 SC 1253

give persons with disabilities all the rights irrespective of socio-economic or civil political rights. The draft bill gives equal opportunities to persons with disabilities without discriminating on the ground of disability.

- The preamble of the draft bill itself provides for protection, promotion and ensuring that persons with disabilities have a right to integrity, dignity and respect with full participation and inclusion⁵⁰ Similarly, Article 3 (a) of UNCRPD provides for respect of inherent dignity, autonomy and independence.
- The appropriate government shall take necessary measures to ensure the protection of woman and girl with disabilities from all form of abuse, violence and exploitation and shall provide such an environment to protect the dignity, self-respect and autonomy of the person⁵¹. The Convention provides for protection of dignity of persons with disabilities. It provides for protection against abuse, violence and exploitation of persons with disabilities and provides protection to women with

Drawbacks of draft bills of 2012

- Article 1 of the Convention seeks to promote, protect and ensure the full and equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by all persons with disabilities. The definition of “persons with disabilities” is an

⁵⁰ Preamble of RPD draft bill states that, Persons with Disabilities have a right to integrity, dignity and respect with full participation and inclusion; to live a life free of shame, ridicule, or any form of disempowerment and stereotyping; and to be entitled on an equal basis with others to all civil-political and socioeconomic rights guaranteed by international and national law.

⁵¹ According to section 9(2) (c) of RPD draft bill, the government shall ensure such a Provision of gender, disability and age sensitive protection services, assistance and support for victims of abuse, violence or exploitation, for physical, cognitive and psychological recovery and development, rehabilitation and social reintegration, in an environment that fosters the health, welfare, self-respect, dignity and autonomy of the person

inclusive definition, and include those “who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.

- According to Article 4 of Convention, state party is obliged to adopt all appropriate legislative, administrative and other measures for the implementation of the rights recognized in the present Convention. Section 64 of the Draft bill 2012, lays down the Functions of the Central Advisory Board on Disability, which is to “advise the Central Government and State Governments on policies, programmes, legislation and projects with regard to disability.” Another function is to “review and coordinate the activities of all Departments...dealing with persons with disabilities”.

Comparative Analysis of Draft bill and PWD Act 1995

The Preamble of the RPD draft bill provides for the promotion, protection and ensures the rights recognized in UNCRPD. It states that the persons with disabilities have right to integrity, dignity and respect, live peacefully and free from shame and guarantees the equality with other non-disabled all civil, political and socio- economic rights.

The PWD Act of 1995 does not guarantee any of the above. The preamble states that the PWD law is enacted to give effect to the Proclamation on the Full Participation and Equality of People with Disabilities in the Asian and Pacific Region.

The RPD draft bill includes many important definitions like Abuse, Augmented and Alternative Communication (AAC), Barrier, Care Giver, Communication, Disabled Persons Organizations (DPOs), Discrimination on the basis of Disability, Language, Reasonable Accommodation and Universal Design. Under section 2 of PWD none of the aforementioned definitions are provided.

Child Rights

Chapter 5 of the PWD 1995 provides for Education for children with disabilities. The appropriate government and local authorities to provide the children with disabilities free Education till the age of eighteen years. The government shall also take measures to ensure that the children with disabilities are integrated in normal schools. If needed, the government may run such schemes and programs beneficial for the children with disabilities. According to section 27(a), the appropriate Governments and the local authorities shall by notification make schemes for connoting part-time classes in respect of children with disabilities who having completed Education up to class fifth and could not continue their studies on a whole-time basis. According to section 30 the appropriate governments to prepare a comprehensive Education scheme providing for transport facilities, supply of books, etc. The RPD draft bill provides for the rights of children with disabilities. It states that the children with disabilities have quality before law and equal rights and it cannot be denied on the basis of age or disability.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Disability has been a major issue in our society since ages. Disability affects similar transformations on racial, sex and class identities not only because they also rely on ability but also because disability appears at first glance to be so individualizing that it overwhelms any sense of group identity. Disability affects many aspects of day-to-day life. Many disabled people lack the health to hold full-time employment, affecting their economic well-being. Still others can hold full-time employment, yet face discrimination from employers who may choose healthier employees or discount the ability of someone with lesser problems, such as a limp, or hearing difficulties. There is a stigma which is often associated with disability. The people without any disability many a times fell uncomfortable when they are around people with disabilities. They are more likely to be

isolated from the society than the people without disability.

Society often acts blindly to the ongoing violation of when it comes to the treatment of persons with disabilities. Rehabilitative programs offer a bridge to full-time employment, but even in that realm, the person with disabilities must overcome his share of discrimination, and prove that he can do the same duties as everyone else. This attitude can be changed through awareness and empowerment. The purpose of the present Dissertation is to convey that disabled people are also human beings.

The human rights approach acknowledges that persons with disabilities have equal rights but they are often lead to discrimination. The major changes were when disability was recognized internationally with the establishment of UN Charter. There were many International Convention and National Legislations which came into existence for purpose of human rights protection i.e. UDHR, ICCPR and ICESCR etc. The legislations, then, legally protected and promoted the rights human being in many aspects like employment, Education and reservation etc. This gave awakening to many other groups like women, children and migrant etc. to fight for their rights. With this awakening, CEDAW, CRC, CAT and CERD were established provides right to the people who were discriminated. Along with the recent growing national and international recognition of the need for equal enjoyment of all human rights by people with disabilities, the Non-Governmental Organizations are increasingly incorporating disability rights into their advocacy agendas. There are increasing opportunities to bring together the human rights movement and the disability movement. Increased awareness of disability rights as human rights is essential to acknowledge the disability rights violations that are occurring and to add to the effectiveness of work to eliminate disability discrimination.

ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE OF THE RIGHTS OF A HOUSEWIFE IN INDIA: CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 18ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The Human Development Report 1995 suggested that the System of National Accounts (SNA) should become more inclusive and encompassing in the criteria of defining the economic activities; for the reason that the people performing work for societies remain invisible. The type of tasks and conditions under which the tasks are performed by the women at the household level differ widely. The burden of unpaid work and paid work respectively are distributed unequally among men and women. Most of women's work remains unrecognized and underestimated; which are often unpaid. A few research studies have tried to analyze and quantify the valuation of the household works. Issues identified are lack of knowledge on economic value of tasks performed by housewives leading to deprivation of human rights amongst women and increase in vulnerabilities among this segment viz. social insecurity, financial insecurity, lack of recognition, domestic violence and other psychological problems.

The history of sexual division of labour affirms men as hunters and women as gatherers. Women contribute substantially to economic welfare through large amounts of unpaid work, such as child-rearing and household tasks, which often remains unseen and unaccounted for in the GDP (Katrin Elborgh- Woytek et al. 2013). Women's ability to participate in the labor market is constrained by their higher allocation of time to unpaid reproductive work. On average, women spend twice as much time on household work as men and four times as much time on childcare (Duflo, 2012).

One of the major segments of women was those who belong to the groups of the homemakers or the housewives. The average housewives don't seek employment outside because of family responsibilities and hence are termed to be '*unproductive*' or '*economically inactive*' and '*the household is not a productive enterprise*'; according to the national accounting system at global level.

Therefore, it must be noted that neither the government; nor the social scientist or the economist are interested to know the contribution of labour made by the women at household level which remain to be unrecorded, unpaid and often remain unacknowledged. This had led to the severe gender inequality in distribution of economic power. Ever since 1960's the period of Second Wave of Feminism where patriarchy system was questioned highlighting the neglect of women and dominance of male oriented society. The struggle for gender equality had its early origin at the inception of the United Nations in 1945. The UN Women's Conference (1980), at Copenhagen in New York revealed the myth of the 'non-working' women. Based on the insights of the conference Marilyn Waring had prepared a theoretical paper on UN System of National Accounts for the Women and Food Conference in Sydney, Australia in February 1982.

Some research studies have shown that there are structural limitations to illustrate the importance of keeping accountability of domestic household work for labour to be valued in particular ways. The predominance of unpaid work can become a constraint on economic development as well as on poverty reduction. (Catherine Hoskyns & Shirin M. Rai, 2007). Amartya Sen in 1987 had established 'bargaining models', which stressed that have advantage over standard models of 'household production', or 'family allocation' or 'equivalence scales' designed to capture the household conflict and cooperation.

Women still face discrimination on several issues related to intra-family bargaining power¹ for subsistence within the family which also included resources even land property (Bina Agarwal, 1994). Mutual cooperation is one of the determinants of well-being related to gender relations; the other factors influencing the person's fall-back position. There are several levels of fall-back position of women in the household bargaining power; the notion of legitimacy needs to be broader than as captured by Sen's 'perceived contribution response'.

Most United Nations publications use the term Gender, Empowerment, and the Care Economy "unpaid care work" quite broadly, synonymously with terms such as "nonmarket work" or the work of "social reproduction." While it is tempting to call attention to the importance of social reproduction as a process of meeting the needs of individuals and

¹ The bargaining power of an individual depends on a range of factors which influences the person's fall-back position. Bina Agarwal (1997), stressed upon the critical aspects for intra-household dynamics from a gender perspective which was missed out by the existing household models. Also tried to analytically explain how household models get constructed and point out the complexity and historic variability of gender relations not only at intra-household level but also at extra-household level. As a consequence of undervaluing of the household works performed by women and leading to deprivation from the human rights and increase in hostility against women including social insecurity, financial insecurity, lack of recognition, domestic violence and other psychological problems.

families, it is difficult to think of any activities that do not indirectly fall under this general rubric. Unaccountability of unpaid domestic work by women had been a subject of debate at different levels by the UN Statistical Commission, by the authors of the World Bank Living Standard Measurement Series, by researchers at Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and by conferences of International Labor Organization (ILO).

Furthermore, Waring suggested that the national income statistician must decide how far the imputation process of national income which includes rate of growth of national income and GNP. The rate of growth of national income and GNP is significantly influenced by social habits, working hours, retirement ages and unemployment change.

According to the UNSNA, the unpaid work performed by women within the households is not employed. Income saved within the household is invisible as both production and consumption i.e. a woman baking cake at home rather than purchasing.

The two major reasons cited by economists and statisticians for global invisibility of the housewives as follows:

1. Conceptual difficulties
2. The difficulties in collecting data

Worldwide the society is undergoing a period of transition which is under the situation of turmoil across the globe where the entire world is pondering and debating on equal economic right of housewives for rendering the selfless unpaid care works. Despite a recent flurry of attention, no clear consensus has emerged regarding accounting conventions for the care economy. Even definitions of care work vary widely (Nancy Folbre, 2006). While some countries like Ukraine and Venezuelan government began paying stay-at-home housewives, recognizing their work at the home as valuable economic activity (Sakuntala Narasimhan, 2008). The society is undergoing a period of transition

which is under the situation of turmoil across the globe where the entire world is pondering and debating on equal economic right of housewives for rendering the selfless unpaid care works.

In 1982 the International Labour Organization (ILO) identified the total labour force, or currently active population, comprising all persons who fulfill the requirements for inclusion among the employed or the unemployed during a specified brief reference period. Therefore we can conclude that labour market influences economic growth of the country which has its reflection on the Human Development Index (HDI), Gender Development Index (GDI), and Human Poverty Index (HPI) etc. A major chunk of these populations belong to 'unpaid labour' contributed by the homemakers or the housewives a population of the society. But still the efforts made by housewives towards household often go unrecognized.

Mynul Islam (2012); described household work time means how much time a person doing household work. Most of the household works are done by women no matter what her position is; whether it is employed or unemployed. Cultural construction of our patriarchal society makes housework as women's work and outside work as men's work. He further elaborated that women contribute a lion share towards household work, but since these works remain invisible, even though they spend a longer time to household work and yet their works go unrecognized.

The contributions made by the housewives towards the household economy are generally considered under care economy. The concept of care work also encompasses work within the paid economy, particularly jobs that provide market substitutes for services women once provided in the home (Nancy Folbre, 2006). Care work is labor that contributes to the well-being or development of other people that is often face-to-face and requires skills in interaction and communication (England 1992). Ever since

the ancient period of human civilization; housewives are often considered as agent of reproduction and growth of family. Women as housewives are laden with both the sexual and non-sexual components as duties. The sex component of housewife's duties and her attractiveness may be considered as important components needed for the job (Barbara R Bergmann, 1981).

The tasks performed by housewives are standard unpaid and quite often unrecognized and unpraised. As a consequence of this non-recognition of the household works results to deprivation of their rights leading to scarcity and poverty.

Therefore Marilyn Waring (1997); stressed upon concrete steps should be taken to quantify the unremunerated contributions of women to agriculture, food production, reproduction, and household activities. The UN Women's Conference (1980), at Copenhagen in New York has exploded the myth of the 'non-working' women, and also referred to the conditions under which large numbers of women were living in the rural areas of developing countries. In India though women are being considered as the wealth and the glory of the house or the family yet the irony lie in the fact that out of 136 countries India ranks 124th position on the criteria of economic empowerment to women and 120th on educational attainment of women according to *Global Gender Gap Index* 2013.

Housewives work for approximately 15 unpaid working hours a day. These over-worked and unpaid women neither have the money to spend, nor the time to spend. As a result of this leading to dual deprivations resulting to neglect, injustice and even injury inform of domestic violence. Gender discrimination – the theme of HDR 1995 – gave special illumination, an enlargement of the issue of inequality through the gender-lens (Devaki Jain, 2012). In spite of the fact that the UN Charter of Human Rights and the provisions of the Indian Constitution, women continue to be victims of exploitation. Gender inequality was defined by Amartya Sen (2001)

as not one homogeneous phenomenon, but a collection of disparate and inter-linked problems. According to NCRB report 2012, there has been an increase in cases against cruelty by husbands or relatives has doubled itself from 49237 during 2002 to 99135 during 2011. In Odisha context 2638 cases and 178 cases in Khordha have been filed against cruelty by husband or his relatives (Sec. 498A IPC). One of the basic reasons behind this state of crime is assumed to be financial and social insecurity attached with the household works performed by the housewives (female homemakers).

The paper at hand is based on empirical research conducted in the district of Khordha of Odisha in India. The main objective of this study was to measure economic contribution of the unpaid tasks performed by housewives to the household economy. This research was an exploratory empirical study. The study was piloted in the different locations including urban state capital Bhubaneswar and areas within the proximity to urban vicinity from Bhubaneswar; one village Padanpur in Jatni block which is located near to the state capital Bhubaneswar 23km and Ratanpurpatna in Tangi block which is 40 km away from the city in Khordha district of Odisha state.

According to the Census 2011, the sex ratio of Odisha is 978 per 1000 male population. The literacy rate of Odisha is 73.45% which is lower the national average 74.04 %. For the present study it is assumed that the literacy rate, proximity from the urban location and economic status of the family has a strong influence on the value of the unpaid care works of housewives.

Multi-stage sampling was incorporated in this research study; where the samples were selected based on different strata to collect information from both rural and urban localities equally so as to avoid any biasness in the sample collection.

The study was an attempt to understand the status of housewives in context

of both rural and urban localities. Out of total sample of 160; 50 percent of the representative sample was covered from the three different strata of high, middle and low income groups in the urban locality of Bhubaneswar the state capital of Odisha. Around 25 percent of the rest was interviewed from Ratanpur is a village with high literacy primarily inhabited by Brahmins; whereas Nuagaon is low literacy village which is inhabited by scheduled caste community in Tangi block.

Time-use studies typically have a single focus: to study the frequency and duration of human activities (Linda L. Stinson, 1999). Therefore, time use survey technique was used to collect empirical data to estimate the total working hours of housewives in each category of tasks identified such as:

1. Child care Cleaning, decorating and provision of clothing
2. Eldercare
3. Food-related Health care and companionship
4. Keeping up with finances, daily household items, and expenses

Economic status of the household plays a significant influence the social status of the women particularly the housewives. Nuagaon a village in Tangi block which was far away from the capital city was economically more backward and predominantly inhabited by the people belonging to the scheduled caste community. Supplementing to their vulnerable condition; the literacy rate of Nuagaon village is as low as 56.1 % much below the literacy rate of Tangi block 68.6%; which is one of blocks with lowest literacy rate even lower than the literacy rate of the Odisha state 72.9%. As a consequence of which housewives have low social status due to lack of education and social taboo.

As an outcome of this study it was found that a major share of housewives, themselves don't know the economic value of the tasks performed by them. As she (*referred to housewives*) herself is not able to see her

work as value-producing work, she subscribes to devaluation of this work as non-work, as purely supplementary to her husband's work, she is not able to bargain for just a wage Maria Mies (1982). The percentage distribution of the head of the family reveals that 96.7 percentage of the households were male headed; whereas only 3.3 percentage households were headed by female.

Subsequently, most of housewives (respondents of the study) had a common response that their financial dependence is one of major cause of social insecurity and social taboo. It is worth mentioning that housewives belonging to the middle and low income groups; are more of common consensus that their livelihood dependence on their husband and in-laws results to financial and social deprivation.

This study had taken reference from the work of Ann Chadeau (1985); and had tried to analyze and estimate the value of the tasks performed by housewives if outsourced. Different tasks performed were assigned with estimated market costs of getting the service delivered and an effort was made to estimate the economical value of the tasks performed by the housewives and contributing to the household economy in Indian context. In other words it was tried to find the contribution of housewives towards the economy. Putting a money value on unpaid household work is a way of showing its economic importance, and also of expressing this part of human activity in terms which enable comparison with market activities (Ann Chadeau. 1985).

Attempt was made to investigate the influence of female education and economic status of the family on the valuing the works performed by housewives. It was found that the economic contribution made by the housewives subsequently increased with the increase in their educational status. With the social development the women strata of the society have been empowered and have excel in different fields of life. The study proves that educated housewives are more adoptable and adaptable to multi-situations at a given point

of time and education makes them more competent to be better decision makers. The multi-tasks handled by these housewives include taking care of both indoors vis-à-vis maintaining of quality family life; social cohesion and outdoors activities vis-à-vis shopping, bank related tasks. Subsequently looking after the household budget care and household savings; contributing towards the household economy.

Around 89 percent of the housewives responded that in a day the maximum number of hours they spend on child care around 3 hours a day; followed by the housekeeping activities average 4 hours and health care average 2 hours a day. However the time taken to perform these tasks may over lap each other. Therefore it was estimated that the working hours of these housewives is much more than the maximum work for any labour after reduction of the time spent on leisure and personal care activities. Still the paradox is that the contributions made by housewives are not accounted into System of National Accounts (SNA) activities. These unrecorded economic activities which essentially generate goods and services produced and consumed by the households without undergoing monetary transactions and which are not recorded in labour statistics and in national accounts. These activities could be termed as 'non SNA activities (A.C. Kulshreshtha & Gulab Singh 1999).

Since every individual of aged 18-40 years is considered as potential labour; therefore housewives belonging to that age group could be considered as "Concealed Employment"; as person is engaged in tasks or employment having economic value without any valid appointment, remuneration and employment agreement; with special reference to unpaid care works. In order to estimate the value of tasks performed by housewives; important to calculate the output per hour or productivity of labour contributed by housewives. The real GDP is the product of total hours of work in the economy times the amount of output produced per hour; which is

known as labor productivity (output per unit of labour).

Further these housewives do add value to household savings by undertaking the household duties which if outsourced would

More to the point it was very shocking to find that even the housewives belonging to high income groups and having educational attainment of post graduate level were not aware of their value contribution and furthermore consider the tasks performed by them of no economic value.

A number of labour laws have been enacted catering to different aspects of labour. Both the Central and State Governments have recognized labour as a subject competent to enact legislations by Constitution of India. The Constitution of India accepts the responsibility of the State to create an economic order in which every citizen finds employment and receives a 'fair wage'. This made it necessary to quantify or lay down clear criteria to identify a fair wage. However, it did not take into consideration the household works performed by the housewives; which on the other still question the economic contribution made by the household duties performed by the housewives and their social security.

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augment the household budget. During this study a small exercise was tried out to estimate the approximate value of the household savings contributed by the housewives (respondents of the study).

There is dearth of research that focuses on 'unpaid care work' evident from the review on research provides a strong case for new research to be conducted on this issue (Lopita Huq, 2013). Research plays a vital role in generating evidence to change the perception and understanding of policymakers regarding 'unpaid care work'. This study has been an empirical evidence of the fact that this is the call of the hour to address the need of recognizing the tasks performed by the housewives and should account in the System of National Account (SNA). Recognition of the household labour by women in economic terms may stand as a catalyst in better bargaining power position and ensured the deliverance of the human rights to women; more specially the segment of housewives. Nevertheless, UNDP during 2008 responded to the urgency of addressing unpaid care work. There is a need for the government and civil societies to intervene and help to empower those housewives who are predominantly engaged in household chores

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HUMAN RIGHTS: AN ETERNAL CALL FOR HARMONIOUS CO-EXISTENCE

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 25ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Human beings by nature possess a mind for research after hidden principles and truths, which made him master on the earth. The concept of human right is one of his great discoveries. It has been evolved gradually through centuries through Charters, Bills and Declarations. Universal Declaration of Human Rights reflects the culture of the civilized man. Human right is the common moral language of modern man. Human rights implied human duties. Doctrines on duties are as old as the history of man. Human rights are implicit in religious as well as rational precepts. As a rational animal and as a social animal man embraces human rights for maintaining peace, prosperity and wellness. Virtue or vice, is not instinctive, but culturally inherited by man. Man has choice in his life. It is his responsibility to choose what he learns and what becomes. There are two types of men: those who violate human rights and those who promote human rights. Empathy is the core from which justice and fairness springs. The heart of human relationship is mutual gratification which is a harmonious co existence. The message of human rights have been imparted to man throughout the ages. It is an incessant process.

Keywords: *Human, duties, Responsibilities, harmony, peace*

In the long trail of evolution man surpassed all the fellow beings by the merit of his brain which made him superior race and master on the earth. Man exercised the power and enjoyed the rights of a master conveniently ignoring the fact that mastery always goes with responsibility. Devoid of accountability authority is ineffective and even dangerous; for, then, masteris just a monster! Monstrous exercise of power warrants devastation and loss. The signs of devastation are being visible: man-induced climatic change, pollution, violence,

disorder, disease, miseries and death spread across the 21st century and beyond. Human interference has disrupted peaceful life and even put the survival of living being at risk on this planet.

Unlike other species, human beings possessed a mind for research after hidden principles and truths. With his spirit of inquiry man discovered the secrets of creation, and even secured the 'key' to unleashing the energy inherent in nature. However, he is slow to discover himself- his own nature. Though man enjoys dominance over earth subjugating all forms of life, he failed to conquer himself; consequently, he is

dangerously driven by instincts. In course, man became alarmingly aware that unless he manages his personal power, he will not be able to manage, beneficially and fruitfully, the energy in the nature. The so called progress, developments and conquest are nothing but a process of slow suicide. This awareness made him pause to ponder on himself. New ideas and concepts emerged, initiated from different corners, successively through different ages. The greatest discovery warranting wellbeing and survival of man is the concept of human rights, which evolved over many centuries. Along with his battles for world conquest, man is gradually being weaned to this concept as a means for self conquest, not with swords, but words, in the form of invocations, proclamation and declarations; most of which are epoch making.

1. Evolution of Human Rights

The story of Human rights is also the story of human culture, evolved over several eras. First recognition and declaration of human rights can be traced from the archeological evidences of Cyrus the Great (600 or 576 – 530 BC) who freed slaves, declared that all people had the right to choose their own religion, and established racial equality (Barbara, S. 2013). His declaration goes: “I announce that I will respect the traditions, customs and religions of the nations of my empire and never let any of my governors and subordinates look down on or insult them until I am alive”. A document inscribed in Akkadian cuneiform on a clay cylinder, the declaration has come to embody the hopes and aspirations of many (Nagel, A., 2013; MacGregor, 2013). However, this was never the intention of the document, because the modern concept of human rights hardly existed in the ancient world.

Later in 1215, plea for the rights of man was documented when the Archbishop of Canterbury, in order to make peace between the unpopular King and a group of rebel barons, drafted what came to be known as Magna Carta or "the Great Charter of the Liberties" (Carpenter, D. A., 2004). The Great Charter promised the protection of church rights, protection for the barons from illegal imprisonment, access to swift justice, and limitations on feudal payments to the Crown. Neither side, the king nor the barons, stood behind their commitments by the Charter (Black, C.,1999). But Magna Carta became a frame of reference for voicing rights in the years to come.

The Petition of Right, 1628, written by Parliament was an English document that helped promote the civil rights of the subjects of King Charles I. This document, though served only to intensify hostility between the both parties- the king and parliament, it reflected the common man's cravings and entreaty for justice and rights (Kemp, R. L., 2010).

Bill of Rights in 1689 was an Act of the Parliament of England to lay down limits on the powers of the monarch and to set out the rights of Parliament. (Horwitz, H.,1977). The Bill granted freedom from taxation by royal prerogative, freedom to petition the monarch, freedom to elect members of parliament without interference, freedom of speech and of parliamentary privilege, freedom from cruel and unusual punishments and freedom from "fine and forfeiture" without trial. The Bill of Rights was a milestone in the recognition and affirmation of human rights (Amar, A. R., 1998).

US Declaration of Independence on July 4, 1776, announced that the thirteen American colonies, were no longer a part of the British Empire but a new nation—the United States

of America (Armitage, D. 2007). The statement of the Declaration runs: "...that whenever any form of government becomes destructive of these ends, it is the right of the people to alter or to abolish it, and to institute new government".

References to the text of the Declaration had invigorating effect on many later events. It has become a celebrated statement on human rights, particularly its second sentence: 'We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights, that among these are Life, Liberty and the pursuit of Happiness'. This has been called "one of the best-known sentences in the English language", containing "the most potent and consequential words in American history" (Wills, G. 1992; Boyd, J. P.,1945/1999).

French Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen passed by France's National Constituent Assembly in August 1789, is a fundamental document in the history of human and civil rights. (Gregory, F. B.,2007). The Declaration, emphasizing the "the natural, unalienable, and sacred rights of man", was a core statement of the values of the French revolution and had a major impact on the development of liberty and democracy in Europe and worldwide (Kopstein K., 2000). The declaration stated that: "Men are born and remain free and equal in rights. Social distinctions may be founded only upon the general good. The aim of all political association is the preservation of the natural and imprescriptible rights of man. These rights are liberty, property, security, and resistance to oppression". The French declaration, together with the American Declaration of Independence, inspired many later uprising for freedom and rights.

The Declaration of the Independence of India or Purna Swaraj in India on 26 January 1930 was the recognition and affirmation of human rights for freedom. The decree, "Freedom is my Birth Right" by Balaangadhara Tilak inflamed the hearts of millions of Indians. The Purna Swaraj declaration aimed to have for Indians complete self-rule independent of the British Empire. The declaration stated: "The British government in India has not only deprived the Indian people of their freedom but has based itself on the exploitation of the masses, and has ruined India economically, politically, culturally and spiritually.... Therefore...India must sever the British connection and attain Purna Swaraj or complete independence (PareL,A.,2006). Gandhiji's vision of Poorna Swaraj was broader than political freedom: he wanted to eradicate social, religious, cultural and all superstitious practices that have been traditionally violating human rights in India.

Similarly, the South African freedom struggle which began in 1652 and continued until 1994 is a compelling story of the sacrifices made by the natives in overcoming the oppression of colonialism and apartheid for establishing their rights. Meanwhile, the invocation by Karl Marx for equality of right stirred especially the working class in different parts of the world.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10 December 1948 at the Palais de Chaillot, Paris. The declaration proclaimed that "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights"(Morsink, J., 1999). This Declaration represents the first global expression of rights to which all human beings are inherently entitled. The concept of right became clear and convincing to everybody. The idea of human rights has become the

common moral language of modern man across different cultures.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights reflects culture of the civilized man. The Declaration evoked several individual and organizational initiatives on the issues of human rights in the contexts of civil wars, religious and racial clashes, natural calamities etc..Its message spread across boundaries and incited many political movements- for example Palestine, Vietnam etc... In many states monarchy and theocracy were dethroned establishing power of the people. For modern man, the philosophy of democracy came to be synonymous with human rights.

2. Duty Left is Right Left

The concept of the rights of man at first appeared under the name of natural rights. As such, it depended upon the doctrine of natural law, which itself represented a confluence of stoicism, of Roman law, and of the Judaic-Christian tradition. The idea of natural law, as of any law, involves both duties and rights. The traditional theorists of natural law gave more emphasis to the duties. The shift of emphasis in natural law from duties to rights took centre of the stage for certain theorists of the seventeenth century, notably Hobbes and Locke.

The idealistic conception of right by modern man is commendable; however, the implementation of these rights in full, demands a society which is yet to emerge. Therefore, in many instances, they did not grow beyond being mere idealistic statements and concepts serving the purpose of high level discussions. That is why, though the Declaration has had wide acceptance among a large number of nations, a single nation is scarcely found where this article is adhered to, without reservation and

condition, outside the strictly legal context. Various States recognized only the rights of a citizen rather than rights of a man. They gave importance to his political, economic and social rights as a member of a particular civil society than as a member of human race. Positive obligation to assist an individual regardless of his caste, nationality, religion or region is missing. Thus, the proclamation of human rights turned to be but a negative obligation of others to acknowledge the rights of a man and to leave him alone to do the best he can for himself. A shift of emphasis from passive awareness to active response to human right alone will bring productive results.

French Declaration of the Rights states: "... the ignorance, neglect, or contempt of the rights of man are the sole cause of public calamities and of the corruption of governments,...." Those instances of denial of rights are but negligence of one's duty. Each deprivation endured by underprivileged rightly points to the duties of the privileged. All the declarations and assertions of human rights witnessed in history are but exhortation for duties. It is categorically stated in the Preamble of the Declaration of Human Duties and Responsibilities (DHDR) that the effective enjoyment and implementation of human rights and fundamental freedoms is inextricably linked to the assumption of the duties and responsibilities implicit in those rights. A man's rights normally correspond to the duties of others towards him. 'Rights necessarily imply duties; for whatever is due to one man, or set of men is necessarily due from another' (Beeton, I. M., 1861).

Much prior to the emergence of human rights, precepts on the duties and responsibilities of man had been prevalent. Doctrines on human duties are as old as the history of man. Every age produced

visionaries and leaders who would remind man of his duties. For no other cause, in the history, blood, sweat and wealth have been spilt profusely, than to educate man of his duties.

3. Divine Precepts

Concepts of human rights are implicit in most of the religions of the world. Human rights are embedded in religious principles. God commands devotees to obey divine law, and their obedience guarantees the protection of human rights for everyone. The essence of the doctrines of all religions is the same; the moral responsibility of man. Long before the age of reason, religion was the only means to convince man of his obligations. The question asked by Dostoyevsky's Ivan Karamazov, "If God did not exist, would all be permitted?" indicates how the fear of god keeps man in self control.

Stories of creation are but clever attempts to convince man that he is not the superior being, but a subject, and that he has obligations. God created man, out of clay or out of His own physique- as per the versions of scripture. God permitted man to subdue and conquer the world, but that the conqueror has responsibility over the conquered. As man was so immature he required Divine support for decision making, and he got it too. God forbade him not to eat fruit from the tree of Knowledge, implying that man cannot become the Master who decides right or wrong. But man disobeyed and consequently assumed the role that he was not fit for. For his disobedience man was sent out of Paradise, to live on his own. Now, man has to act out of choice, and every wrong choice fetched trouble, putting him in a grave condition. All the religious precepts are to support man in this predicament.

Holy Quran reminds: "Surely Allah commands justice and the doing of good (to others), and giving to the kindred, and He forbids indecency and evil and rebellion. The Quran stresses that all humans are equal in the eyes of God, regardless of gender, class and race: "O mankind, indeed, We have created you from male and female and made you peoples and tribes that you may know one another".

Love your neighbor as yourself is a simple but profound precepts by Christ on protection of human rights. The golden rule in New Testament is "Do unto others that you want them to do unto you". "It is more blessed to give than to receive" (Acts 20:35) emphasizes man's obligation and duty than his right.

In Buddhism human duties include the fundamental principles such as the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. In Jainism duties refer to the teachings of Jinas. For Sikhs, the word duty refers to the path of righteousness. Sikh Scriptures highlight human rights and human dignity: Dharma or duty is born of compassion; through contentment, it creates harmony.

The heart and very definition of the Hindu society is varnashrama-dharma model. Every member of each caste is written in the Rig Veda (X.90.1-3) to be derivative from God: "The Brahmin was his mouth, Of both his arms was the Kshatriya made. His thighs became the Vaishya, From his feet the Sudhra was produced". The story of creation implies that man is not master of himself, nor he is an independent entity.

While lower species are bound by instinct, man has to take moral decisions in his life. His free choice makes him accountable and human life is a life of responsibility. The incarnate Lord Krishna states that although he has absolute authority over the universe,

human beings must perform Dharma themselves and reap the benefits.

Dharma signifies behaviors that include duties, rights, laws, conduct, virtues and “right way of living. Dharma promoted individual security and happiness as well as the stability of the social order. The fear of anarchy led to the elevation of Dharma to divine status and this in turn gave it even higher status than the king and the government. The contexts which gave rise to the Declarations, Petitions, Bill, and Charters in history are implicit instances of the attempts to reinstate Dharma when anarchy prevailed.

4. Rational Ability and Social Affinity

The concept of Human right and duties affirms that there is an instinctive human ability to distinguish right from wrong. Apart from falling in line with Divine law man can also act using his ability for reasoning. Dharma or one’s own duty can be an empirical and experiential inquiry for every man and woman. Man has, as Albert Camus holds, an impulse to seek the purpose and meaning of life, and, without adequate answer to it he is in absurdity (Solomon, R. C., 2001). Hence, by nature, man looks for a ‘right, sensible cause’ for doing things and he avoids what does not appeal to his reason and conscience. Man is a rational animal: he shares his appetitive desires with animals, but controls them with reason. Man constitutes a distinct species, with species-specific obligations which springs from his social affinity: He is a social animal. “Human beings”, claims Article 1 of Universal Declaration, “are endowed with reason and conscience” and they should “act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood”. It indicates that brotherhood is related to reason and conscience.

Immanuel Kant, the modern philosopher, observes that human beings are “free” and “dignified” in the sense that they are “endowed with conscience capable of setting a world of freedom, justice and peace” (Uleman, J., 2010). The classical Greek philosopher Socrates, had attributed the same when he stated reason and conscience as inherent in man (Donald, K. 1987). Socrates observed that it is not in human nature for someone to go after what he thinks is bad in place of the good. But human only out of ignorance goes after what is harmful to him. It implies that what ultimately motivates any action is some cognitive state: if you know what is good you will do it. All errors committed in human choices are due to ignorance.

The Charters, Declarations and Protocols are the vivid signs that man is gradually coming out of the veil of ignorance. Modern man started to reason out that whether created by God or by a series of chemical reactions, everybody has the same origin and everybody has the same end. All are equal with all life forms. Hence, have equal rights and duties.

The ancient philosophers, referred to rights but not in the way it is understood today. However, behind the apparent differences, they share same soul. Almost two millennia prior to the emergence of rights Greek philosophers argued that human excellence include the moral virtues practiced. Human right was inherent in virtues. Plato used the analogy of a person for an ideal city. The order and harmony of the soul is attained by providing what is good for each of the parts and the whole, and so makes the parts function well, for the benefit of each and of the whole person. The order and harmony in the soul are paired with order and harmony in the city (Debra, N., 2002).

Greek term eudaimonia means living well and doing well, i.e., virtue, together with its active exercise, is identical with happiness. Practice of virtues is essential for a just society. Living well includes looking after the welfare of others, which implies the recognition of human rights. The negligence of Eudaimonia is aptly represented by the Universal Declaration in the phrase, “whereas disregard and contempt for human rights have resulted in barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind.”

Marcus Tullius Cicero, a Roman philosopher and politician identified human nature with being both self-aware and socially conscious (Cowell, F R: (1948). To Cicero it is the nature of man to engage in activities useful for others. Being a social animal, respecting other’s rights is quite natural for man. Cicero also views that human reason uses duties and moral obligations as guidelines for practical purpose. Respecting the rights of others is, therefore, a practical way to establish peace and justice in the society, which ultimately ensures happiness and human excellence. All the declaration and charters are indeed practical wisdom for the progress of man.

Aristotle believed the reason we do things is to pursue an end, a *telos*, which for man is the good. In Nicomachean Ethics Aristotle posits supreme good as the aim of human actions. The supreme good, as Epicurus means, is pleasure which he defined as body's health and the soul's freedom from disturbance. The universal declaration is just an invocation for man to pursue what is good for man.

5. The Passion for Power

In Plato’s Dialogue Callicles thinks that moral convention is designed by the numerous weak people to intimidate the few strong ones, only to safeguard their rights. Against this Thrasymachus (in Republic) argues that moral precepts is set up by the powerful, i.e., rulers to contain the subjects against their self-interest (Debra N., 2002). Both arguments are in accord that the end of morality is personal interest. In ‘Will to Power’(1968) Frederik Nietzsche means the same: ‘there are no truly altruistic actions, all human beings are ultimately and exclusively egoistic by nature’. Everybody has the will to power. When power is the prime aim human right is neglected.

Nietzsche’s opinion is interestingly similar to one of the political views which Noam Chomsky has professed, that “states are fundamentally violent institutions and a state's internally espoused values have no bearing whatsoever on its external behavior” (Posner, R. A.,2003). Social institutions and social structure have been set up for maintaining order, and guarding the rights of every member in the society. But, when the interest of the State comes against the interest of the individual, statutory violence results. John Stuart Mill who feared society as one that cared nothing for individual liberty, puts forward the “harm principle” that “the only purpose for which power can be rightfully exercised over any member of a civilized community, against his will, is to prevent harm to others” (Rosen, F., 2013). The men in power violate human rights. Francis Bacon has succinctly explained the reason why power produces violence: “Men in great place are thrice servants: servants of the sovereign or state; servants of fame; and servants of business”. When they are servants to position, pomp and profit, they cannot serve human. Holocaust and World Wars are examples of statutory violence organized by these great ‘servants’ who are

egoistic and self-centered. They fail to see human beings in the world of business. To all ambitious men Albert Einstein pleads: "Try not to become a man of success, but rather try to become a man of value."

6. Unlearning the Undesirable Learning

While leading the freedom struggle Gandhiji sensed violence residing in man. So he equated freedom with self-rule, and the notion of self-rule, to Mahatma Gandhi, implies the voluntary internalization of our obligation to others. Gandhi had to shed his blood to teach man such principles and values, because basically people had already been formed for violence. The basic nature of man is a subject of interest over centuries. Ancient Stoic school emphasized that the mind starts blank, but acquires knowledge as the outside world is impressed upon. This concept, known as 'Tabula Rasa' or blank slate is popularized by many in the later centuries, most notably John Locke who holds that individuals are born without built-in mental content and that all knowledge comes from experience or perception (1689/1996).

The studies in neuro psychology refute the theory of 'blank slate' suggesting that the entire cerebral cortex of human being is already programmed and organized to process information and some other functions. Hence mind is not blank by birth. This innate programmed mechanism in the brain subsequently acts to learn and refine the ability of the organism (Busan, T., 2005). Eagleman (2011), a neuroscientist, noted that babies inherit a great deal of problem-solving equipment and arrive at many problems with solutions at hand. Babies, have neural programs specialized for reasoning about objects, physical causality, numbers, the biological world, the beliefs

and motivations of other individuals and social interactions.

Neuro psychology, though disputes 'tabula rasa' does not confirm innate violent nature of man. Nor there is any contest on the factors of information processing such as intelligence, attitude, experience and perception as strongly correlated with culture. The nature of man whether peaceful or violent, is socially inherited. Jean-Jacques Rousseau argued that humans must learn warfare because warfare is an advent of society, rather than something that occurs from the human state of nature. Peace or violence, is learned. A major challenge in the promotion of human right is to unlearn the undesirable learning rather than to induce desirable learning. It calls for pain, sweat and sufferings to teach man; Socrates, Jesus, Gandhi, Abraham Lincoln etc... were such teachers who taught human right at the expense of their lives.

The Preamble to the Constitution of UNESCO declares that "since wars begin in the minds of men, it is in the minds of men that the defenses of peace must be constructed". Virtue, as stated in Plato's *Republic*, resided more in the person—in one's soul—than in the political structure of the state. For the ancient philosophers, virtue is to be cultivated by each person as well as the community. The cultivation of virtues, is the responsibility of man. Where this responsibility is neglected, there human right is violated.

7. The Ultimate Choice

In the *Republic*, the term eudemonia refers to a state of the soul as well as the active life it leads; which means both one's activity and its result on oneself is the same (Debra N., 2002). This is echoed in the Existential conceptualization of human right as an act of

duty and its benefit. Human right exists when it is practiced, meaning that source and result of the practice is the same and it has no external factors. Jean Paul Sartre views that “Humans are the source as well as the end of categorical imperatives”. The end of all what he does is himself, with no external factors. Man creates his own human nature through free choices. Human beings are radically free to act and mould themselves independently of outside influences. (Aronson, R.,1980; David, B., 2006). It is up to a man if he should practice human right or not, and ultimately, he is what he practices.

To be or not a champion of human right is ultimately one’s own decision. “It is the choice one makes: Man is born only as a potential. He can become a thorn for himself and for others, he can also become a flower for himself and for others”, opines Osho. All the declarations, protocols and precepts by the philosophers, prophets and leaders down through ages are the recurring efforts, in one form or other, to counsel man for right choice. Accordingly, there are two types of men: those who violate human rights and those who promote human rights. If human history is coloured by blood, tears and murder, it is also gleamed by models of moral conduct, altruism and love. In the words of Tagore: “Civilization must be judged and prized, not by the amount of power it has developed, but by how much it has evolved and given expression to, by its laws and institutions, the love of humanity”(Marie, S., Aruna, J., 2010).

8. Rights, an Experience of Love

In violence one is blind to one’s fellowmen, but human right opens the eyes to have a concern for the fellowmen. Empathy is the core from which this concern springs, and it qualifies the relationships with justice and sense of fairness. Relationship is the

awareness of interconnection between people in physical, psychological and spiritual environment, without which there is no existence. “To be is to be related”, says J. Krishnamurthy, and the heart of this relationship, according to him, is “mutual gratification”. This is the experience of love, a harmonious co-existence, the culmination of all values proclaimed by theists or atheists alike.

The very structure and nature of human being makes it impossible for him to remain isolated. Only when he consciously keeps himself in harmony with his surroundings, he will be experiencing in fullness, what it means to be a human being. This experience is not obtained from obedience to laws, nor from observance of rituals but it is a life style adopted with deep seated conviction.

The call for harmonious co-existence is eternal, every age producing it profusely in different voices. The Bills, Charters or Declarations coming in succession promise nothing new or different. Summits, Conferences and Conventions will ensue endlessly until man internalizes the wisdom being imparted to him in various forms and means since the days of ‘creation’.

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EDUCATION RIGHTS AND THE ROLE OF MOBILE LIBRARY

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Delegation to the **1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties**
(Regd: 07ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The knowledge access and education is a fundamental right of every human. The mobile library exclusively gives us the information in multifarious area and its offered variety of services to the users. Today, library is open to all public so that they can search their reference thereby, fulfilling their requirements. The mobile library is an appropriate learning tool, that includes e- readers loaded with actual required resources of books, journals, documents, database, maps and others reading materials etc. In this context, trained and skilled professionals of library have been engaged in solving the problems not only at school level but also till college level. Thus it should help in the various fields of science and technology, information communication and management through electronic media. It has extended the services towards networking, literacy programme and also development of awareness to protect the human right in rural area.

A library on the vehicle is to provide service even at places far from the city and is open for all users without restriction. The mobile library is an extension of public library that is provided by all services to the users.

- It is a library carrying their resources by van to outside users.
- Public library is providing mobile library services through mobile vans.
- The mobile library provides services in rural area mostly.

2. History

It has been observed that the first mobile library services started in African and Arabian countries. India had started this service in 1953 with a specially designed vehicle. At that time mostly the said services were especially visually and physically handicapped peoples. After some time because of its demand and popularity for readers it started for common people.

Before the beginning of services needed to selection of place by the library professionals did a brief survey of the concerned place on various parameter and requirements.

1. Geographical feature
2. Local Administration: Head of Area, MLA, Panchayat Pradhan etc
3. Population: Male /Female ratio
4. Education label: School: Primary, Higher Secondary label, Co-ed College: Degree or Post graduate label Subject Study, Training Centre or Institution
5. Economic condition: Cultivation, Industry and employment
6. Hospital and Health Care Centre
7. Population
8. Distance from the nearest library
9. Interest of Local People
10. Suitable Timings of local peoples
11. Social Activities
12. NGO Service available
13. Shortest Route of the selected service place
14. Arrangement of Electricity or lighting source
15. Security and softy of service peoples.
16. Available of Networks

After observation of the above parameters they proceeded to the next steps which are most important of mobile library service.

Arrangement of vehicle

The prescribed standard size of van is 5x12.5 feet with both side sliding doors and a pilot who must have a basic mechanical knowledge of vehicles and needed to check windows, doors and other parts of glass should be fixed properly to avoid the dust particles, sunlight, rain water and jerks.

Next steps of the service

After consulting of the local authority/in charge of the concern place like Principal of school / Panchayat Pradhan/Councilor officially seeks the permission; settles the schedule, time and date before providing the services as convenience.

2. Selection of Man powers

Normally about two or three professionals are required in a team. The qualification of the library professional should be maintained accordingly.

1. The professionals must be qualified in the field of library and information science, also they should have sound knowledge of computer works.

2. The professionals should also have basic operating knowledge of electronic equipments like LCD projector, laptop, reprography, scanning and audio-video and sound systems etc.

3. Professionals should be well prepared to interact with the local people's knowledge of current affairs, capability to conduct seminars, workshop, exhibition and films show individually as per requirements and demands..

4. Children education programme: The principle objective of mobile library is the extension of education in rural areas, increase of literacy ratio of adult and women and provide the library services those who are not able to come at the public library due to long distance, transport problems, financial hardship or physical disabilities etc.

Through the mobile services people can get information from their required reading materials, employment, information of govt.scholarships,development programme, higher education scopes, skilled training and guidance for professional jobs etc.

3. Advantage of mobile services

There are so many advantages available in this service out of which the most helpful services is to remove the darkness of illiteracy and insist the people for developing reading habits. Comparatively this service is very cheap and more convenient as there are no administrative

complexities, requirements of infrastructures, more manpower and funds, furniture plus these equipments are more convenient to the readers as they get the books/reading materials as per their actual demands and interest .The users can also spare their time according to themselves.

It has been observed that the utility of mobile library is more helpful to convey the current awareness , information of new technology , research progress in agriculture , cattle, governments plans and programme, and employment related information, etc. to extend the service in rural areas as well as connect with the Country. In some time such a service shall be provided by the non government organizations also.

Comparison of Membership & Lending of Books for the Year – 2013-14

IN PUBLIC LIBRARY: -

New Membership 2014

Male-77/Female88

No. of Users

Male-27/ Female-18

No of Users

Male-27/ Female-18

Books to Aware to Rights

IN MOBILE LIBRARY

New Membership-2014

Male-43/ Female-77

No. of Users

Male-39/ Female-68

Consequently the mobile library services are too helpful with respect to remote access, common programme, education and development in rural areas.Thus, the access of library to enhance of knowledge should be a significant right of all.

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STATUS OF CIVIL (LIFE AND LIBERTY) RIGHTS OF TRIBALS IN ANTI-NAXAL OPERATIONS: A CASE OF JHARKHAND

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 26ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

This article seeks to find out the extent, causes, and suggest remedies on human rights violations of tribals particularly the right to life, and personal liberty guaranteed under Part III of the Indian Constitution. With ratification of various covenants like the ICCPR and ICESCR, India is duty bound for its compliance and domestic adherence. The naxal violence in Jharkhand throws up a number of cases of the violations of human rights in its anti-naxal operations which puts the innocent civilian's life at peril. The study primarily analyses the situation using doctrinal methodology, methods and tools. The literature is varied and diverse picking the important incidents and assessments on the life and liberty in the back drop of the anti-naxal operations. The study questions the kind of approach taken by the state and maoist which put the constitutional safeguards at bay. It takes up the cases of civilians, tribals, who are caught between two guns, and are victims of collateral damage in anti-naxal war. Hence, a reality check on how democratic are the means to ends in world's largest democracy.

Key words- Human rights, Jharkhand, Life, Liberty, Naxal, Schedule tribe

Right to life and personal liberty encompass almost all conceivable human rights. They are the natural rights of the most basic type without which life is unimaginable. Both life and liberty have depth and width in its coverage of the elements which sustains life like, food, water, clothes, shelter, clean environment etc. But today, life is understood to be much beyond these. Right to life does not mean an animalistic existence rather a dignified life. It incorporates all such facets which make lifeworthy. Hence, beyond the basics of food, one would need, right to peaceful environment, marriage, education, privacy, livelihood, family, legal aid, and much more, for dignified human life. The Indian State is constitutionally obliged not to violate the right rather create favorable conditions for its enjoyment. So, it is both a positive and a negative right.

Personal liberty is cherished by all. Liberty does not mean unrestrained freedom to do what one wants. In legal parlance it means enjoying one's freedom without causing inconvenience to others. Liberty prefixed with 'Personal' narrows the scope of the term. It relates to liberty relating to or concerning the person or body of the individual.

Fundamental Rights (Part III), Article 21 of the Indian Constitution states, "*No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.*"¹ It is both for the citizens and non-citizens. The Constitution of India, specifically Part –III, Fundamental Rights (Art. 12-32) and Part IV (Directive Principles of State Policy) consist the best of

¹Bakshi, P.M., *The Constitution of India* 46(Universal Law Publishing co., New Delhi 8th edn. 2008)

human rights jurisprudence. The former is fundamental thus enforceable and the citizens can approach the courts by way of writs (Art. 32 and Art. 226), while the latter are guidelines for the state, non-justiciable and non-enforceable. The Directive principles are the positive obligations requiring the state to conform when formulating and executing policies and principles.

The fundamental rights acknowledge the contribution of various human rights jurisprudence. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948 mentions the Protection of life and personal liberty under Art. 3. Similarly International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), 1966 under Article 6(1) & 9(1) mention of protection of life and personal liberty. The right to life and personal liberty can only be deprived "by the procedure established by law". So, if at all these fundamental protections are taken off, they must be in conformity with the procedures laid down in law.

In *Maneka Gandhi* case, the Supreme Court has given the widest possible interpretation to the word 'personal liberty'. A valid law interfering with personal liberty must satisfy a 'triple test' (i) it must prescribe a procedure (ii) the procedure must withstand the test prescribed in Art. 19 (iii) it must not infringe Art. 14. Thus, the procedure must be fair, just, and reasonable. The court created a protective shield against any type of arbitrary unreasonable and unjust actions, which seeks to violate the individual freedom and liberties of people, by inter-mixing and correlating the provisions of Arts. 14, 19, and 21.²

The other part of which can be helpful in protecting life and liberty are in the procedures. These procedures are laid down in Art. 22 which provides safeguards against arbitrary arrest and detention. It provides the minimum procedural requirements that must

be included in any law enacted by the legislature in accordance with which a person may be deprived of life and personal liberty. Art. 22, thus, sets out certain limitations upon the powers of the legislature. If a law contravenes the conditions or limitations prescribed by Art. 22 the law would be nullity. Art. 21 has to be read supplemented by Art. 22. Thus law relating to ordinary arrest or a law relating to preventive detention must satisfy requirements of Arts. 14, 19 and 21. They have to be just, fair and reasonable. Art. 22 (1) and (2) guarantees four rights to the persons arrested under ordinary law.³

The UDHR, 1948 provides the Right against arbitrary arrest and detention (Art. 9), which correlates to Indian const. (Art. 22). In the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) these are provided in Article 9(2)(3) & (4). The Indian Government has ratified ICCPR, 1966 but not the two Optional protocols. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights entered into force on 23 March 1976. Thus, India is under the obligations to ensure that the domestic legislations are in tune with the International Covenants.

Jharkhand the rich land of mineral and natural resources is plagued with the Naxal terror. 18 out of 24 districts are affected by this menace. A sizeable tribal population consists of the naxal base, which are operating from the remote villages, heavily forested and hilly terrain. They project themselves as the protector of the interests of tribals, dalits, farmers, labourers from the exploitative mechanisms of the state. Contrary to their ideology, they have themselves indulged into forcible recruitment, mass killings of both police personnel and innocent civilians for being

² A. K Jain, *Constitutional Law of India* –II 139, 143 (Ascent Publications, Delhi, 2nd edn. 2009).

³ *Ibid.* (The right of (a) information of the ground of arrest, (b) to consult and be represented by a lawyer of his own choice, (c) to be produced before a Magistrate within 24 hours of his arrest (excluding the time of his journey) and (d) no detention beyond 24 hours except by the order of the Magistrate. These are available to both citizens and non-citizens. Clause (3) makes an exception with respect to enemy alien and those detained under preventive detention laws).

informers, blowing off development infrastructure, torture, instituting *janadalat* (kangaroo courts). The innocent people for the fear of Naxal backlash, and fear of death, dare not raise voice against them. The government has started various anti – “anti-naxal operations”⁴. Amidst the exchange of hostilities between the state and the Armed Opposition groups (AOGs), (the Naxalities or Maoists), it is the innocent tribal and non-tribal civilians who become target of suspicious killings from both sides. The constitutional rights guaranteed to every citizen like right to life and liberty are constantly violated by the state and the AOGs. Therefore, the study focuses on a reality check on the enforcement of such constitutional guarantees during the anti-naxal operations.

1. Extent of violation of right to life and personal liberty.

According to a report by Jharkhand Human Rights Movement (JHRM), since the creation of Jharkhand a total of 4,372 people have been arrested on the charge of being Naxalites. Of these, 315 are hardcore Naxals for whom the government had announced prize money. The remaining 4,057 have no record of any criminal offence; even the police have been unable to establish their Naxal involvement.⁵

In other instances, countless innocent people (mostly tribals) have been killed during anti-Naxal operations. The incident that occurred on April 15, 2009 at Latehar, Jharkhand, exposed the dark side of these operations. Five tribals were picked up from their homes by the CRPF and district police, taken to a nearby place and shot dead. The initial police investigation tried to cover up the act, claiming the tribals were Maoists. Following protests, the Jharkhand police finally

accepted that they were ordinary villagers who had no links with Naxalites. So much so that, the recent exposure of anti-Naxal operations in the Saranda jungle, home to over 125,000 tribals, is even more disturbing. Central and state forces deployed here under Operation Monsoon and Operation Anaconda destroyed homes and killed innocent people, not sparing even the food the tribals had. As revealed by JHRM, during Operation Anaconda, 33 villagers were arrested on charges of Naxal involvement. The police have been unable to provide any evidence to support this claim.⁶

While the Jharkhand government has been initiating measures to make sure Naxals surrender and are given handsome rehabilitation packages, the police have been framing hundreds of innocent villagers as Naxalites and putting them in prison. Across prisons in Ranchi, Khunti, Saraikela, Chaibasa and some other districts of Jharkhand, many villagers are hoping to be free one day. Even after being freed, however, hardly any of them will be able to lead a normal life.⁷

According to the Human Rights Law Network, there are 39 villagers lodged in Chaibasa jail against whom the police have not been able to prove charges of them being Naxals. Similarly, KalyanBarjo, Gonda Nag, KujurGargi and many such people have been in jail for almost three years now despite the fact that the police have not been able to prove charges against any of them till date. There are 49 people lodged in the Khunti jail under similar charges, more half of them arrested in 2010-11. There are 20 such people in the Ranchi jail and 16 in the Saraikela-Kharsavan jail against whom the police have not been able to prove the charges.⁸

Besides these, Father Stan Swami, a social activist who has been working on the issues

⁴ Operation green hunt, Operation Monsoon, Operation Eagle, Operation X, Operation Sikhar, Operation Hill Top, and Operation Black Thunder

⁵ Available at: <http://infochangeindia.org/human-rights/analysis/jharkhand-the-failed-promise-of-an-advansi-state.html> (Last Visited on Nov. 26, 2015).

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Available at :<http://gulail.com/author/jacinta?print=pdf-page> (Last Visited on Nov. 26, 2015).

⁸ Ibid.

of tribals in Jharkhand, says there are almost 6,000 youths from tribal, Scheduled Castes (SC) and Other Backward Communities (OBC) who are in jails across Jharkhand for many years on various charges and there is nobody to pay for their bail. In an RTI application he filed in 2010, he asked for the number of people who had been arrested for being Naxals in the state. The reply, which came after a year, said that 441 people had been arrested in such cases, out of which 168 were tribals, 77 Dalits, 161 OBCs and 35 from the upper castes. Many of them had been arrested under charges of helping Naxals. Father Swami says that many have also been jailed for keeping Naxal literature despite the fact that the government and various district administrations have not specified what kind of literature would classify as Naxal literature. He says that the police have also not followed instructions given by the Supreme Court in the D.K. Basu judgment. "The police should have the instructions painted on the walls of the police stations," he says⁹

The NHRC revealed in July 2007 that there were as many as 84,000 cases of human rights violations under consideration of the NHRC out of which 3,000 were from Jharkhand. However, Jharkhand government failed to establish a State Human Rights Commission then. The state human rights commission came into existence on 19.01.2011 vide notification no. 195 on 15.01.2011. In the gap years, The Adivasis continued to face serious human rights abuses. According to the National Crime Records Bureau, a total of 332 cases of crimes against Scheduled Tribes were reported in Jharkhand during 2006. Tribals have been arrested under false charges when they tried to access minor forest produce in Jharkhand. About 12,000 cases have been filed by the state's Forest Department against tribals as of 12 August 2007 for claiming land rights by tribals guaranteed under the Scheduled Tribes (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act. The NHRC received two cases

⁹*Ibid.*

of illegal arrest, two cases of unlawful detention, one case of disappearance and 128 cases of other police excesses in Jharkhand during the period of 1 April to 31 March 2007. The police failed to take action in 144 cases.¹⁰

The police often tortured the accused persons during interrogation. State security forces, frustrated by their inability to track Maoist fighters who slip into the forests in the adjoining states, often direct their attacks against "soft" targets—villagers from areas that support the Maoists and activists who criticize police abuses and state policies.¹¹

On the part of the Non-State Actors

The violation of life and liberty is effected by the naxal or Maoists both against the state forces and the innocent civilians.

Against the state

The police and other paramilitary forces are always at the target of the Left- Wing Extremism. The non- state actors are also involved into the gruesome killings, which include, beheading, public hanging, shooting, etc. of the innocent civilians who they allege to be police informers or anti-maoists. The life and liberty is thus cut short by means not falling under any law, causing grave human right violation. For example, (i) Beheading of an IB officer Francis Induwar in Khuti District (Jharkhand, October 2009)¹²(ii)

¹⁰Available at:

<http://openspace.org.in/book/export/html/826> (Last Visited on Nov. 25, 2015).

¹¹Available

at: <http://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/reports/india0712ForUpload.pdf> (p. 28 Last Visited on Nov. 25, 2015).

¹²Available

at: <http://www.hindu.com/2009/10/07/stories/2009100757800100.htm> (Last Visited on Nov. 26, 2015). Maoists beheaded Jharkhand police inspector Francis Induwar, who was abducted by them a week ago. Naxalites abducted him, demanding the release of three of their arrested leaders, including Kobad Ghandy, in exchange for him. The Union government condemned the killing and termed it unacceptable. Induwar's body, along with the severed head, was found in the early hours of Tuesday near Raisha Ghati under the Namkom police station area, about 12 km from the spot, Superintendent of Police (Ranchi Rural), Hemant Toppo, said.

CRPF IED incident (Jharkhand, on January 7, 2013)¹³ (iii) Attack on Police Van carrying prisoners: On November 9, 2012.¹⁴ Besides other attacks on the state and paramilitary forces the naxals have also perpetrated attacks on the innocent civilians, civil society members, by executing them in *janadalats* (people's court).

Atrocities against Civilians

Jan Adalat, beheading, killing on ground of being police informer, forcible abduction and recruitment (including female and child soldiers) etc. are some of the worst forms of the human rights violation committed by the Maoists against the civilian population. In one incident, Friday, 12 November 2010, Maoists kill man at 'kangaroo court' in Jharkhand- Pronouncing "death sentence" against a man at its "kangaroo court", members of the CPI (Maoist) chopped off his head and legs at the Naxal-infested Giridih district, police The Maoists claimed responsibility by pasting a poster on the distorted body and said he was killed after being branded a supporter of "reactionary forces at a *janadalat*" staged by the guerrillas at Beluaghati. The Naxalites have perpetrated several crimes at Beluaghati, including massacre of over twenty people about five years ago.¹⁵

¹³ Available at: <http://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/india/maoist/Assessment/2014/Jharkhand.htm> (Last visited on Nov. 26, 2015). (The Maoists sent shockwaves across the country at the very beginning of 2013, when they killed nine Central Reserve Police Force (CRPF) personnel and one Jharkhand Jaguars trooper in an ambush near Amawatar village in Latehar District, Jharkhand, on January 7, 2013, and then surgically inserted Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs) inside the abdomen of two dead CRPF troopers).

¹⁴ Jharkhand Assessment, available at: http://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/india/maoist/data_sheets/Major_incidents_2012.htm (Last Visited on Nov. 28, 2015). (Three Policemen and a prisoner were killed when about 100 armed CPI-Maoist cadres, including women cadres, attacked a Police van carrying 32 prisoners from Giridih Court to the Divisional Jail, at MahadevChauk in Giridih District. The Maoists succeeded in freeing eight of their comrades from the prison van)

¹⁵ Available at: <http://www.dnaindia.com/india/report-maoists-kill-man-at-kangaroo-court-in-jharkhand-1465536> (Last Visited on Nov. 28, 2015).

In the same breath, the Naxals have also committed worst human rights violations by ordering public execution, on their own, for example - on 5 July Naxals beheaded three members of the *Shanti Sena* (peace squad), a group campaigning against the Naxals, in Khairpani village in Gumla District. Four persons from Turudi in Latehar district died on 31 August following an attack by Naxals belonging to the Jharkhand Sangharsh Jana Mukti Morcha.¹⁶ The number of *Jan Adalats* reported in 2011, 2012 and 2013, were 54, 23, 41.¹⁷ These are few cases of the many that goes unreported, just to highlight the unseen and unheard cases that might have occurred but not noticed.

Attacks on civil society - In Jharkhand in particular there have been repeated allegations that some Maoists, or groups claiming to be Maoists, are engaged in corruption. In the case of Niyamat Ansari, an activist who exposed corruption in the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS), was killed by Maoists on March 2, 2011.¹⁸ Another incident was of Killing of Sister Valsa John, Jharkhand¹⁹.

Child rights

As per UN Committee report, there have been mass scale recruitment of children in the Maoist cadre under fear. Insurgent groups reportedly used children in militant activities. Insurgents trained children as spies and couriers, and gradually in the use of arms, in planting land mines and bombs, and in intelligence gathering.²⁰ There have been

¹⁶ Available at: http://www.satp.org/satporgtp/sair/Archives/4_11.htm (Last Visited on Nov. 28, 2015).

¹⁷ *Supra* note 13.

¹⁸ *Supra* note 11 at 25 (Last Visited on Nov. 26, 2015).

¹⁹ *Id.* at 27 (Valsa John, a nun with the Sisters of Charity, had been involved for many years working on behalf of tribal people in Jharkhand, particularly those displaced by mining operations. On November 15, 2011, in Pakur district, a group of about 50 people that reportedly included about 30 Maoists broke into her home and murdered her.

²⁰ Available at: <http://www.state.gov/documents/organization/220604.pdf> (Last Visited on Nov. 26 2015)

cases of forcible recruitment as per cases of Pathari²¹ village of Lohardaga district in Jharkhand, and Mahuatand village of Latehar district.²² There have been umpteen cases of blowing off the school buildings across the state which are used by the security forces as camps in the anti- naxal operations. This is violation of the right to education as guaranteed under Art. 21 A, of the Indian Constitution as fundamental right.

2. Causes and Remedies of violations of life and liberty.

Both the state and the Left wing extremists are causing loss of life and liberty of their warring parties. In the case of the Naxals, there is inter and intra rivalries simply to claim control over economically remunerative territory, and overall hegemony. The splinter groups now clash among themselves which is another aspect where fratricidal deaths are common. The causes for violating right to life and liberty stand differently for the state and the naxals.

For the state

3.1.1. Internal security aids development: The former P.M, Mr Manmohan Singh, declared that Naxalism (Maoism), and left-wing extremism poses the “greatest threat to our national security”, (The Hindu, October 22, 2010). The Union Home Ministry then accepted that 125 districts spread over nine states in central India and adjoining areas have come under the influence of Left radical groups, loosely called Naxalites. Jharkhand is famous for its rich mineral resources²³. The government for the sake of development and mineral resources entered into no. of MOUs with the corporates, which has and would result into displacement if executed. Given the fact, that the tribals constitute 40 per cent of the entire displaced population so far, the tribals vehemently opposed any such repetitions. The maoists came as the messiah of the tribals championing their cause under the derailed ideology. Left forces resist the entry of the government, while govt. insists on. The naxals care nothing about the life and liberty of the citizens and hence would resort to kill and terrorize any one to enforce their dictates. The govt. is on the spree to sanitize the area off naxalism, and would not care less to ascertain maoists form the innocent civilians, as long as that would help in larger goal of capturing the naxal bases. No doubt, the government sees naxalism as the internal security problem, and a hindrance to the development process. In this, the larger issues of poverty, land alienation, displacement, and rehabilitation are left out. In such a hostile situation life and liberty of both the parties, along with the civilians continue to be at stake.

A shadow report to the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict released by the Asian Centre for Human Rights (ACHR) in March stated that state governments in Odisha, Jharkhand, and West Bengal recruited thousands of youths as special police officers.

²¹In Pathari village of Lohardaga district in Jharkhand, which remains a stronghold of Tiritiya Prastuti Committee (TPC), a Naxal outfit, school going children remain their main target. The villagers disclosed that TPC cadres compel the children aged 13-14 years-old to join their outfit and strengthen their cadres. The red rebels also exploit them as human shields against security forces and use them to transfer their consignments. Ganesh Lal, a villager, confirmed the truth by saying: “The Naxals are targeting children as they can be easily influenced to join the outfits. There are many instances where rebels are recruiting children to prepare them for anti-national activities”. Poor villagers who have seen their children being snatched away are reluctant to lodge any complaint with the police. They fear they will be attacked by the Naxals

²² In Mahuatand village of Latehar district, the rebels have ordered each family to offer one teenager for their cause. Experts believe that illiteracy and poverty have forced many villagers to silently follow the orders of the Naxals. “The Naxals offer a monthly income and food to the poor children and their families to convince them that what they are doing is in their favour. It is highly condemnable

²³Available at: <http://www.jharkhand.gov.in/about> (Last Visited on Nov. 27, 2015) Like Uranium, Mica, Bauxite, Granite, Gold, Silver, Graphite, Magnetite, Dolomite, Fireclay, Quartz, Feldspar, Coal (32% of India), Iron, Copper (25% of India) etc. Forests and woodlands occupy more than 29% of the state which is amongst the highest in India.

3.1.2. GDP centric Development models: A large part of mineral resources reside in tribal belts of the country.²⁴ Jharkhand accounts for 32% of India's Coal, 25% of India's Copper and Forests and woodlands occupy more than 29% of the state which is amongst the highest in India. India in order to give its GDP (Gross domestic Product) a boost, looks forward to the mineral rich resources to run large industries. For example, The Jharkhand Govt. till Nov. 2007, had signed sixty-six. MOUs with companies, including MNCs for exploiting mineral resources and setting up mineral – based plants in Jharkhand, of which forty-one were in West Singhbhum district alone. No doubt, development is the slogan of the Globalized world. In a race to attain a higher GDP, need we trample the secret of inclusive and sustainable development, the practice of harmonious co- existence by the tribal people. Thus, the forces of pro- development without sustenance would further jeopardized the life and liberty of the tribals who are sandwiched between state and LWE elements.

On the part of the tribals

The problems of unrest in the tribal heart land are related to the exploitation of the land, natural and mineral resources, as well as non-adherence of the protective laws fully.

3.2.1. Land Alienation- B.K Roy Burman (2009) considers systematic dispossession of the tribal people from their land resources which they have been holding for generation to be the most important fact which has pushed them to political extremism in central

India. Here he is referring to the dispossession which is very different from development related displacement. As against involuntary displacement, there are evidences to show that in the predominantly tribal areas the people have been deliberately disposed of their lands and resources in a meticulously planned manner.²⁵

Non-adherence of the legislation: Various legislations and judgments having the traditional right over their land (Samantha v. State of Andhra Pradesh), Provisions of Schedule V of the Constitution, Nehru's Panchseel, Chotanagpur Tenancy Act, 1908 (CNTA), Santhalparagna Tenancy Act, 1949 (SPTA), Forest land, traditional and customary rights, inadequate resettlement and rehabilitation measures, require compliance. Moreover, the International legislations like, ILO Resolution 169, 107, UNDRIP, 2007 etc. have not been acted upon. The Jharkhand Panchayat Act, 2001 (JPA), has not fully incorporated certain sections of the revolutionary Panchayat Extension to Schedule Areas (PESA), 1996 Act. The Forest Right Act 2006, also needs to be complied with.

3. Remedies:

All the stake holders should have to act in accordance to the procedure established by law. The state, the Maoists, tribals, and the civil society etc. have to make sustained efforts to win each other's trust and find a peaceful solution towards ending the menace of Naxal terrorism.

The state

There has been violation of human rights by the State machinery in the forms of arbitrary arrest, unlawful detention, torture etc. This is the gross violation on the part of the State.

²⁴ Available at: <http://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/comment-on-issues-faced-by-tribal-communities/article6749215.ece> (Last Visited on Nov. 27, 2015)

(Sixty per cent of the forest area in the country is in tribal area. Fifty-one of the 58 districts with forest cover greater than 67 per cent are tribal districts. Three States — Odisha, Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand — account for 70 per cent of India's coal reserves, 80 per cent of its high-grade iron ore, 60 per cent of its bauxite and almost 100 per cent of its chromite reserves. Forty per cent of those displaced by dams are tribal peoples)

²⁵ J.J. Roy Burman, "Factors of Maoist Movement among the Tribes of Central India" *Mainstream*, November, 26-30 (2013).

(i). Effort should be made to investigate the role of senior police officials and administrative officials to prevent the human rights abuses. Strict and appropriate actions needs to be taken against those responsible (disciplinary measures, suspension, removal and criminal prosecution etc). All this should be done transparently and fairly.(ii). Enforce the Supreme Court guidelines of D.K Basu judgement on arrest and detention, and take disciplinary actions in case of violations.(iii). End filing malicious and politically motivated criminal charges and there should be no detention without evidence. (iv). Guidelines for both the national and state officials not to treat the civil society groups as being Maoist supporters without any concrete evidence and make not generalization. (v). Repeal the colonial-era sedition law used to silence peaceful political dissent in violation of Supreme Court rulings. Drop all pending sedition cases.(vi). State government should enforce the Guidelines mentioned in the Gopinath Ghosh v. The State of Jharkhand and others W.P. (PIL) NO. 2584 of 2011.(vii). Spread awareness on the protective laws among tribals, speed up the grievance redressal mechanisms at all levels, conduct trust building programmes, and address the root causes etc. can be some of the immediate steps taken by the govt.

The Maoist/ Naxalites should

(i). Make a public commitment to respect international human rights standards, such as the rights to freedom of association and expression, in areas under Maoist control.(ii). End attacks on schools and hospitals.(iii). Cease all reprisals against people who work on government development projects and their family members(iv). End obstruction of development efforts, since this only harms marginalized and deprived communities.

Rather they should

(i). Encourage the participation of the tribals in the development related work, and enforce the constitutional guarantees in a democratic way.(ii). Make people aware of the rights and bring to the appropriate authority in case of any violations.. **The tribals and civil society** should.

Channelize the learnings and education towards spreading awareness among his/her tribesmen about the rights available and seek remedies through proper channels. Refrain from ultra-left ideologies, and not get drifted by the lofty ideals. Take up the atrocities committed on them to the right forum rather than entrusting them to the Naxal justice system.

4. Conclusion

Life and liberty are cherished by all sections of the people worldwide. There cannot be a greater cause than safeguarding, and preserving these rights in the human history. On the contrary these are also the most violated rights. It is to be understood that the life of human beings sustain on the elements of nature, like food, oxygen, environment, natural and mineral resources etc. There is another aspect for our existence that is the life of the nature itself. These are dependent on our ability to strike a harmonious correlation between development and destruction if any for larger development. No doubt, development is essential, but the cost has to be minimized in a way that the section paying the cost becomes part of the development progress and are not weeded out or crushed in the developmental journey. History has been testimony to the fact that as long as there are social inequality, inequitable distribution of the resources, there would be conflict. The case of Jharkhand, is no different. With the vast mineral resource and the deep seated social inequality this has become a case for the Maoists field for representing the cause of the tribals. In process, of sharing the development pie, the state and naxals have sustained their agendas causing massive loss of life and liberty to the common masses.

The civilians are caught between this mess, and the constitutional, judicial guarantees are forgotten. The anti – naxal campaign by the security forces and the mindless violation of life and liberty is detrimental to tribal welfare and for the country as a whole. The insecurity of life, livelihood, of the people caught in the crossfire needs to be respected and restored. Besides, physical security from being the cannon fodder, the community sustenance, needs to be also secured. The insecurity of life, livelihood are the real causes of violations. Therefore, there is a need to start the campaign against poverty and dispossession. One's Life and liberty can be thus secured if we secure others in a democratic manner and by rule of law.

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THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN DIGNITY AND ITS APPLICABILITY TO NON-HUMAN ANIMALS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 08ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

This paper seeks to examine both historical and prevalent notions surrounding the nebulous term, 'dignity', and establish that the understanding of this quality as something only humans possess and are entitled to is problematic. Given the recent advancements in scientific inquiry into various fields – from genetics to neurosciences – the very definitions which have hitherto delineated aspects that make certain animals 'human' have begun to blur, leaving behind the moral quandary surrounding the way we view and treat other, nonhuman animals. Once the present paper ascertains that nonhuman animals are indeed entitled to a certain level of dignity, it delves into questions surrounding the key precepts of dignity, to see how far these may be applied to nonhuman animals.

Keywords: *Animal, Rights, Environmental, Dignity, Human society, Environment*

The concept of human dignity, seemingly based on the very essence of humanity, has been widely embraced in international law. Still, the very meaning of the term remains shrouded in mystery, devoid of objective consensus and dependent upon cultural opinions. The etymological roots of dignity can be traced back to the German term 'würde', which means both 'worth' and 'to become',¹ and the Latin term 'dignitas', which could mean 'dignity' but also various other things such as 'grace', 'decorum' and 'position'.² These meanings give little indication of what dignity might mean, which is consistent with its varying lexical meanings today – including self-respect, gravitas, honourable position, or just simply worthiness.³ Going by lexical definitions alone, it is impossible

to say exactly what dignity means as a term. Throughout early Western tradition, the term was used only to signify hierarchy in society, and not as inherent worth demanding respect or recognition.⁴ Even today, while most societies do have their own conceptions of human dignity, they are often unidentifiable and certainly not based on ideas of inalienability or social equality.⁵

It is then no surprise that the question of including animals within the ambit of 'dignity' is strongly divisive. Despite the leaps made in the scientific understanding of animals and humans, the law confusedly lags behind.⁶ This paper will critically evaluate the meaning of dignity, and analyse the reasonability of arguments seeking to accord it exclusively to humans. It

¹ 'Würde' (Oxford Dictionaries) <<http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/translate/german-english/wurde>> accessed 01 April 2014.

² 'Dignitas' (Latin Dictionary) <<http://www.latin-dictionary.org/dignitas>> accessed 01 April 2015.

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⁴ Jack Donnelly, 'Normative Versus Taxonomic Humanity: Varieties of Human Dignity in the Western Tradition' (2015) 14 *Journal of Human Rights* 1.

⁵ Rhoda Howard, 'Dignity, Community, and Human Rights' in Abdullahi An-Na'im (ed), *Human Rights in Cross-cultural Perspective* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 1991) 81.

⁶ Andrew McLaughlin, *Regarding Nature: Industrialism and Deep Ecology* (SUNY Press 1993) 148.

will then attempt to assess the extent to which the universal principles of dignity may be applied to nonhuman animals.

1. DIGNITY AS A HUMAN QUALITY

Religion

Most religions consider all humans to be sacred. The Quran has accorded dignity to 'all sons of man'.⁷ Christianity proclaims that man is made in the image of God and consequently bestowed with a dignity that places him above all other animals of the world.⁸ Despite its acceptance of Darwin's theory of evolution, the Catholic church maintains that the true source of human dignity, the soul, was created by God, hinting at an ontological leap made sometime during evolution itself.⁹ Other Eastern religions, such as Hinduism and Buddhism, accord dignity to all beings as they all work to maintain the cosmological balance, all though humans are accorded greater dignity than others, poised as they are to achieve spiritual liberation.¹⁰ Because these religions have accorded a modicum of dignity to animals, viewing them as friends and family from past lives,¹¹ they also stipulate better treatment of these animals, going as far as forbidding the slaughter of cows.¹² Ultimately, using religious philosophy that has little grounding in science as the basis for granting or denying dignity to any species can be a dangerous proposition, especially

⁷ Jerome J Shestack, 'The Philosophic Foundations of Human Rights' (1998) 20 Human Rights Quarterly 201.

⁸ *ibid.*

⁹ 'Truth Cannot Contradict Truth: Address of Pope John Paul II to the Pontifical Academy of Sciences' (*New Advent*, October 22, 1996)

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¹⁰ Dipti Patel, 'The Religious Foundation of Human Rights: A Perspective from the Judeo-Christian Tradition and Hinduism' (*Human Rights Law Centre*)
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¹¹ Neil Dalal and Chloë Taylor, *Asian Perspectives on Animal Ethics: Rethinking the Nonhuman* (Routledge 2014) 155.

¹² Marvin Harris, 'The Cultural Ecology of India's Sacred Cow' (1966) 7 Current Anthropology 51.

considering the fact that these religions themselves do not hold a unanimous stance on the meaning and vessels of dignity.

Human Nature

Cicero, one of the earliest writers on the subject of dignity, tautologically defined the *dignitas* of human beings as a virtuous quality which made human beings worthy of being respected.¹³ Dignity was, to him, both a person's intrinsic worth and external decorum. It could be achieved only once humans learned to cleave themselves from the sensual pleasures of the world, which he deemed animalistic. Cicero's definition of dignity would clearly exclude animals (as they remain irreverently animalistic), but it also specifically excludes most of humankind itself, and he himself considered some men as men in words alone and not actions, and deemed them unworthy of possessing dignity.¹⁴ His conception of dignity, therefore, would not satisfy the requirement of universality, and becomes irrelevant to postmodern discussions of human and animal rights.

Human Rational Capacity

Rather than basing dignity on metaphysical aspects such as man's nature, Kant, whose theory exemplified the age of enlightenment, declared that humans possessed dignity because they had reason and autonomy. It was this capacity for moral choice that meant that they must be the end and never the means.¹⁵ More recently, autonomy was used as a cornerstone of dignity by the prominent bioethicist Browns word, who based it on the respect for the ability of humans to override their natural inclination of survival and end their

¹³ Scott C Shershow, *Deconstructing Dignity: A Critique of the Right-to-Die Debate* (University of Chicago Press 2014) 53-63.

¹⁴ *ibid.*

¹⁵ Mette Lebeck, 'What is Human Dignity?' (*Maynooth University*)
<http://eprints.maynoothuniversity.ie/392/1/Human_Dignity.pdf> accessed 05 April 2015.

lives.¹⁶ Ash rightly criticised this particular line of thought by bringing up evidences of animals harming and even killing themselves when they undergo trauma inflicted upon them by humans.¹⁷

An even greater reason exists to refute the use of human autonomy as the basis of dignity, however. Recent neurological experiments are beginning to destroy notions of free will and autonomy, by proving that choices emanate from the unconscious, not the conscious, sections of humans' brains, affecting both the action to be performed¹⁸ and the time of its performance.¹⁹ Taking this a step further, electromagnetic theories of free will declare that consciousness is nothing but the firing of neurons in particular regions of the brain.²⁰ While these studies have been heavily contested, they have nonetheless added some fresh perspective – namely, that human decisions could be the result of evolutionary responses to environmental stimuli, a concept that is not dissimilar to animals' decisions with regard to their own environment. And if exceptions have already been made for children and the mentally disabled despite their lack of complex thought processes and moral culpability, ought the same not be done for other sentient beings?

The idea, that human intelligence is somehow in an entirely separate category, has also suffered from recent scientific knowledge of animal intelligence – with scientists supplying proof of various

nonhuman animals not just committing facts to memory to utilise in future planning, but displaying proficiency in basic arithmetic, crafting tools out of their environment, and even reflecting upon their knowledge to come up with unique solutions to problems.²¹ The human mind may be intelligent and capable of rational thought, but it is not the only mind capable of both. It is merely the most complex of all species, but that fact in itself does not sever the evolutionary connection between human and nonhuman animals.

Human Emotions

Having failed to establish that dignity is a solely human quality in light of scientific proof of the similarities between the natures and rational capacities of human and nonhuman animals, and in the absence of any actual proof of an ontological leap that resulted in the implanting of a soul (and with it, dignity) in humans by a divine entity, those adamant on denying the dignity of animals are resting their case on the entirety of a human being's complex intelligence and emotions, arguing that the sum is greater than the parts.

Fukuyama, a proponent of this line of thinking, defines human consciousness as the 'full gamut of human emotions' and called it at least as important as human reason and moral choice. He feels it is this gamut of human emotions that engenders every human need, desire, goal, purpose, fear, aversion, and the like, and consequently it is the source of 'all human values'.²²

While this is an admirable attempt to work towards a non-speciesist definition of dignity, it remains insufficient, if only because of the fact that he did not offer up any explanation as to why a line ought to be drawn in the sand, separating animal

¹⁶ Roger Brownsword, 'Bioethics Today, Bioethics Tomorrow: Stem Cell Research and the "Dignitarian Alliance"' (2003) 17 Notre Dame Journal of Legal Ethics and Public Policy 15, 21.

¹⁷ Kyle Ash, 'International Animal Rights: Speciesism and Exclusionary Human Dignity' (2005) *Animal Law Review* 195, 210.

¹⁸ Chun S Soon and others, 'Unconscious Determinants of Free Decisions in the Human Brain' (2008) *Nature Neuroscience* 543.

¹⁹ Benjamin Libet, 'Do We Have Free Will?' (1999) 6 *Journal of Consciousness Studies* 47.

²⁰ David Talbot, 'Searching for the Free Will Neuron' (*Technology Review*, 17 June 2014) <<http://www.technologyreview.com/featuredstory/528136/searching-for-the-free-will-neuron/>> accessed 07 April 2015.

²¹ Thomas R Zentall, 'Animals Represent the Past and the Future' (2013) 11 *Evolutionary Psychology* 573.

²² Francis Fukuyama, *Our Posthuman Future: Consequences of the Biotechnology Revolution* (Farrar, Straus and Giroux 2002) 169.

emotions from human ones. Emotions do not fall exclusively in the human domain. Experiments on animals have proven that they feel pain and pleasure,²³ sexual desire,²⁴ jealousy,²⁵ and even empathy.²⁶ It is not unreasonable to then expect that animals be accorded dignity as well, even if they cannot experience emotions the way humans do. If Fukuyama's assertion is indeed that someone who cannot experience every human emotion is unworthy of being accorded dignity, then this might also strip the dignity of people with mental abnormalities that affect their ability to feel emotions, in the case of psychopaths, or recognise them, as in the case of autistic people,²⁷ as both situations could leave the humans in question unable to possess 'all human values'.

Human Genetics

A purely scientific objection to according dignity to animals is genetic. It finds expression in Article 1 of the Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights, 1997, which states that '[t]he human genome underlies the fundamental unity of all members of the human family, as well as the recognition of their inherent dignity...' The genetic ground is arguably the most speciesist, and for good reason. While it might be possible to one day understand everything about the nature and minds of animals so that their differences from humans dwindle even further, and while it might even be possible to find extant species that have human-like intelligence and

emotions, it would certainly never be possible to find a nonhuman animal that shares a human's exact genetic makeup.

Certain species do come close, however. The biologist and geneticist, Walter Bodmer, considered the genetic sequences of chimpanzees and human beings to be 99 per cent similar.²⁸ He believed this dissimilarity of 1 per cent was enough to create a complex notion of a human being that was separate from all other creatures in his identity, autonomy and responsibility. However, close scrutiny of the genetic sequences of males and females reveals that they differ by as much as 2 per cent, which is greater than the gap between those of humans and chimpanzees. Indeed, Willard has said that 'there is not one human genome, but two: male and female,'²⁹ which itself runs contrary to the wording of Article 1 of the Universal Declaration above. Males and females are not the only members amongst human animals who display this genetic difference. Humans that suffer from Down's Syndrome, the disorder that leads them to have an extra chromosome 21 instead of the usual pair, could differ by 1 to 1.5 per cent from other humans.³⁰ While recent studies are now stating that the difference between humans and chimpanzees are far greater, up to 5 per cent in fact,³¹ consensus is far from achieved, leaving enough scope to question, once again, the arbitrariness in making exceptions for some beings and not for others.

The very term 'family' in the Declaration requires some careful

²³ Marian Stamp Dawkins, 'Animal Minds and Animal Emotions' (2000) *American Zoology* 883.

²⁴ Joseph H Manson, Susan Perry and Amy R Parish, 'Nonconceptive Sexual Behavior in Bonobos and Capuchins' (1997) 18 *International Journal of Primatology* 767.

²⁵ CR Harris and C Prouvost, 'Jealousy in Dogs' (2014) *PLoS ONE* 9(7)
<<http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=101371/journal.pone.0094597#abstract0>> accessed 08 April 2015.

²⁶ Jennifer Viegas, 'Dogs Sense When Humans Are in Distress' (*ABC Science* 2012)
<<http://www.abc.net.au/science/articles/2012/09/03/3581696.htm>> accessed 08 April 2014.

²⁷ Molly Losh and Lisa Capps, 'Understanding of Emotional Experience in Autism: Insights From the Personal Accounts of High-Functioning Children With Autism', (2006) 42 *Developmental Psychology* 809.

²⁸ Walter Bodmer, 'Foreword' in Charles Pasternak (ed), *What Makes Us Human?* (OneWorld Publications 2007) ix.

²⁹ Robert Lee Hotz, 'Galaxy Of Genetic Differences Between Men & Women: Latest Research Into X Chromosome Brings Startling Discoveries' (*The Scotsman – UK* 2015)
<<http://www.rense.com/general63/galaxyofgeneticdifferences.htm>> accessed 09 April 2015.

³⁰ Based on the estimates of the genes that chromosome 21 contains in proportion to the total genes in the human body, in 'Chromosome 21' (*Genetics Home Reference* 2013)
<<http://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/chromosome/21>> accessed 09 April 2015.

³¹ RJ Britten, 'Divergence between Samples of Chimpanzee and Human DNA Sequences is 5% Counting Indels' (2002) 99 *Proceedings National Academy Science* 13633.

reconsideration, bearing in mind that the Linnaean classification of living organisms now features many extant species of great apes alongside humans in the family-level classification, *Hominidae*.³² These apes also have the distinction of being descended from the same ancestors as we, making Richard Dawkins absolutely right in stating that, but for ‘the accidental extinction of the intermediates’ that link us genetically to other great apes, the very concept of humanity would have to be deliberated upon in courts that would have the burdensome task of pronouncing judgment over whether intermediates could pass for human or not.³³ Dawkins likened this situation to apartheid, and while the analogy might appear harsh, the element of arbitrariness, in including certain animals within the definition of the human family and excluding others, cannot be denied.

The speciesist argument of human genes establishing their superiority is wrong on another ground as well. The exact extent to which genes can determine the personality and traits of any human is unclear and provokes fiery debate. The scientific consensus lies in acknowledging that it is not just the genes of human beings that determine their natures and personalities, but also these genes’ interaction with the environment.³⁴ The concepts of both ‘nature’ and ‘nurture’ play important roles, and it would be unwise to reduce all of humanity to either one aspect and use that as a ground to discriminate against nonhuman animals.

2. DIGNITY OF ANIMALS DISTINCT FROM HUMAN DIGNITY

It is evident that there is no logical ground for denying animals the dignity that they deserve, other than the archaic notions of human uniqueness that people obstinately cling to. Philip Allott was right in declaring the reality of the human world to be a ‘species-specific reality made by human beings for human beings’, an *istopia* where the objective truth is merely what human beings, after coming up with the answers in their minds, say it is.³⁵ This is evident in the reasoning of the famous Swiss Expert Report,³⁶ which talks about a ‘minimal conception’ of human dignity, arguing that humans have a self-awareness to them that spawns self-respect and the capacity for feeling humiliation.

The concept of self-awareness is, itself, very highly debated. David De Grazia has argued that there are, in fact, many different types and levels of self-awareness – a *personal self-awareness*, which stops the animal from eating itself and informs it of the body’s movement and position, a *social self-awareness*, which allows the animal to know its place in the hierarchy of its pack and informs its interactions with other animals, and an *introspective self-awareness*, which informs the animal of its feelings, wants and desires. Different animals may hold different types of self-awareness. Certain animals are complex enough to hold memories of their pasts and be able to anticipate their immediate futures, since both skills are imperative for survival in a variable environment.³⁷ Furthermore, if self-awareness is considered synonymous with self-

³² ‘Hominidae’ (*Encyclopaedia Britannica* 2014)

<<http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/270333/Hominidae>> accessed 16 February 2015.

³³ Richard Dawkins, ‘Foreword’ in Justine Burley (ed), *The Genetic Revolution and Human Rights* (Oxford Amnesty Lectures 1998).

³⁴ Robin Headlam Wells and John Joe McFadden (eds), *Human Nature: Fact and Fiction: Literature, Science and Human Nature* (Continuum 2006) 15-17; Fukuyama (n 22) 131-37.

³⁵ Philip Allott, *The Health of Nations: Society and Law beyond the State* (Cambridge University Press 2002) 3-5.

³⁶ Philipp Balzer, Klaus Peter Rippe and Peter Schaber, ‘Two Concepts of Dignity for Human and Non-human Organisms in the Context of Genetic Engineering’ (2000) 13 (1-2) *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 7.

³⁷ David DeGrazia, ‘Self-awareness in Animals’ in Robert W Lurz (ed), *The Philosophy of Animal Minds* (Cambridge University Press 2009) 201-217.

recognition, then many species of nonhuman animals have passed the popular mirror test that is used to gauge self-recognition,³⁸ and at least with the great apes, the data produced by multiple tests remains consistent.³⁹ In fact, research has proven that children up to the age of six years can remain stumped by the mirror test and be unable to recognise themselves.⁴⁰ If this is the case, then self-awareness can hardly be used as a valid excuse for viewing dignity as an exclusively human attribute.

Acknowledging that studies have proven the existence of self-awareness in animals, the Swiss Expert Report reasoned that this quality in itself was not important; rather, the nonhuman animal must also possess 'some conception of how it should live',⁴¹ thereby invalidating the dignity of those humans who were unable to have this conception. It added, however, that humiliation could be both felt by the victim and perceived by outsiders, and that society as a whole would ascribe an inherent human dignity to even those members who were not capable of feeling degraded. This ascription would arise out of 'social-psychological considerations', because other humans felt "some special connection to young children and the mentally challenged".⁴² This complicates things somewhat for people who domesticate animals and feel an affinity to them, and rests on its own assertion of a myth that can be perpetuated by nothing other than social conditioning. The Supreme Court of Israel did, in fact, put an end to a television show that featured human battles with alligators to entertain viewers. The Court, comparing animals with children, called them innocent, weak and unable to

defend themselves from human brutality. It called upon humans to protect animals and refrain from treating them cruelly or humiliating them.⁴³ The Court also said that it did not know if the alligator could feel humiliation, but the people could certainly feel that they were humiliating these alligators, and for this reason, their treatment was inhuman.

In light of this, it would perhaps be better, as Dunja Jaber suggests,⁴⁴ to conceptualise dignity as the inherent worth of all living organisms, and to differentiate the level of moral obligation to protect this dignity on the basis of *species-specific capabilities* (which for humans would include the ability to feel humiliation).⁴⁵ This concept would be in keeping with the doctrine of *intrinsic value* of all living beings. If this is done, dignity will easily apply to nonhuman animals, but in not quite the same way as it does to humans. The extent to which it can be applied to an animal would depend on not just the species-specific capabilities of the animal, but also the very conception of dignity in international law.

3. THE POTENTIAL EXTENSION OF DIGNITY TO ANIMALS

Dignity in Law

The term dignity has been used in international law rather intuitively, its meaning implicit and not explicit.⁴⁶ Human rights instruments attempt to define neither dignity nor its relationship with human rights.⁴⁷ This raises the question of whether

³⁸ Monique V De Veer and Ruud Van Den Bos, 'A Critical Review of Methodology and Interpretation of Mirror Self-Recognition Research in Nonhuman Primates' (1999) 58 *Animal Behaviour* 459.

³⁹ Gordon G Gallup Jr, 'Self-Recognition in Primates' (1997) *American Psychologist* 329.

⁴⁰ Tanya Lynn Broesch, 'Cultural Variations in Children's Mirror Self-Recognition' (2011) 42 *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 1018.

⁴¹ Philipp Balzer, Klaus Peter Rippe and peter Schaber (n 36) 14-15.

⁴² *ibid* 13-14.

⁴³ A Reis Monteiro, *Ethics of Human Rights* (Springer Science and Business Media 2014) 247.

⁴⁴ Dunja Jaber, 'Human Dignity and the Dignity of Creatures' (2000) 13 (1-2) *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 29, 30.

⁴⁵ *ibid* 39.

⁴⁶ Oscar Schachter, 'Human Dignity as a Normative Concept', (1983) 77 *American Society of International Law* 848, 849.

⁴⁷ Louis Henkin, 'Human Dignity and Constitutional Rights' in Michael J Meyer and William A Parent (eds), *The Constitution of Rights: Human Dignity and American Values* (Cornell University Press) 211.

dignity is a separate human right, a catalogue of human rights,⁴⁸ or the very philosophical basis of all human rights.⁴⁹

Defining dignity may well be a futile task, as it is one concept but has many conceptions and many roles to play in international law. In fact, as Andorno has stated,⁵⁰ its primary meaning may merely be intrinsic value, but it has 'multiple functions, which operate at different levels'. McCrudden suggests that while scholars could continually debate the philosophical meaning of dignity, judges have, for the most part, overlooked philosophy and settled upon a case-by-case approach to determine if dignity has been violated. They come to different conclusions by emphasising different interpretations of dignity.⁵¹ In such circumstances, dignity might easily be extended to animals by favouring those interpretations that grant them dignity.

Universal Tenets of Dignity that May Apply to Animals

Christopher McCrudden has proposed a 'minimum core' of dignity by way of universal consensus, and lists its three components – firstly, every human being has an intrinsic worth; secondly, this intrinsic worth must be recognised and respected, necessitating an alteration in treatment that is inconsistent with respect for this intrinsic worth; and finally, the State exists for the sake of the individual human being and not vice versa.⁵² Thus, when applied to animals, the minimum core would simply say that they have an intrinsic worth, which must be recognised by everyone, and which must be respected and protected by the State.

A more detailed attempt to strip the concept of dignity of culture-specific context and distil it to a globally acceptable notion is made by Andrew Clapham, whose four postulates of dignity are further elaborated upon by McCrudden.⁵³ They are the prohibition of inhuman, degrading or humiliating treatment of a person by another; the autonomy accorded to individuals to freely pursue their choices and attain self-fulfilment; the protection of group identity and culture; and the creation of conditions so that individuals can meet their essential needs. Each of these has some bearing upon the way animal dignity can be perceived.

Freedom from torture and degrading or inhuman treatment is one of the most basic and inviolable human rights, considered non-derogatory even in times of emergency.⁵⁴ Its applicability to animals would go a long way in assuring their dignity and welfare. Demonstrating this approach, the Indian Supreme Court recently upheld a Governmental ban on the practice of *jalikattu* – a tradition where bulls were starved, beaten and forced to participate in races – saying that all living creatures possess an inherent dignity and an accompanying right to live peacefully, which encompasses their protection from physical abuse of various kinds. The Court has also stated that while it is common practice to distinguish human life from mere animal existence, that practice stems from an anthropocentric bias and disregards the intrinsic value of nonhuman animals.⁵⁵

Animals form a big part of human life at different levels – acting as pets and companions, beasts of burden, sources of entertainment, providers of food, and involuntary subjects of scientific experiments and genetic meddling. There is an urgent need to revolutionise the processes dealing with animals in order to minimise their pain

⁴⁸ Oscar Schachter (n 46) 853.

⁴⁹ Joel Feinberg, 'The Nature and Value of Rights' (1970) *Journal of Value Inquiry* 243, 252.

⁵⁰ Roberto Andorno, 'Human Dignity and Human Rights as a Common Ground for a Global Bioethics' (2009) 34 *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy* 223.

⁵¹ Christopher McCrudden, 'Human Dignity and Judicial Interpretation of Human Rights' (2008) 19 *European Journal of International Law* 655.

⁵² *ibid* 679.

⁵³ *ibid* 686.

⁵⁴ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976) 999 UNTS 171 (ICCPR) art 4.

⁵⁵ *Animal Welfare Board of India v A Nagaraja and Others*, Civil Appeal No 5387 of 2014, Decided on 07 May 2014.

and suffering. Temple Grandin has conducted excellent research in the field of domesticated animals' welfare, and her extensive proposals of reform include effective solutions to make living conditions for these animals more humane, training staff to sensitively handle animals, and ending practices that cause unnecessary physical harm and death. The goal is to minimise not just the physical suffering of animals, but also any mental distress.⁵⁶

This also in with Clapham's fourth postulate of dignity, namely, the creation of conditions so that *animals can meet their basic needs*. Most animals have a basic litany of goals in life – to be adequately fed, to be of robust health, and to be able to reproduce. Animals in captivity are often stripped of these basic rights, forced to live in cramped conditions that cause an abundance of health problems, and often malnourished.⁵⁷ In order to preserve these animals' dignity, their environment must allow them at least a modicum of movement and their diet should be sufficient to keep them healthy.

The second and third meanings of dignity as defined by Clapham do not have as clear an application to animals as the ones already mentioned, but scientific progress in understanding nonhuman animals could help expand the area in the future. While studies have proven the *existence of culture* in animals,⁵⁸ there has been no evidence so far linking its presence or absence to the intrinsic worth of the animals.

The *dignity in animals' autonomy*, on the other hand, could exist, albeit in a crude fashion. It can be simply understood as their freedom to live their lives and perform their species-specific functions, while

keeping human intervention in their daily affairs minimal. Since animals have, so far, not been found to have very complex thought processes, it would not make sense to accord them the rights that are given to humans capable of complex thought processes – such as the right to vote. Indeed, even children, who possess similarly low cognitive abilities, do not have such rights.

Oscar Schachter has, in his own conception of dignity, made mostly the same points as Clapham above. However, he added *another element to human dignity – responsibility*, which can mean both respect for a person's autonomy as well as consequences for his autonomous actions.⁵⁹ Humans' dignity may well stem from their responsibility, but this does not apply to the mentally disabled and children, whom the law absolves of responsibility in most criminal and civil situations. It would therefore not be a far stretch to extend the same exception to animals as well.

Dignity and Nonhuman Animals' Right to Life

Perhaps the most widely debated aspect of animal dignity would be its potential effect on animals' right to life. Ruth Cigman, in an attempt to assess the morality of animal slaughter, has proposed that human suffering and animal suffering are unequal, and that death is a misfortune for humans alone.⁶⁰ She claims that while animals feel pain and therefore must be protected from cruelty, they do not feel their life as strongly as humans do. They do not hold any fear of death or illness and consequently, their painless killing would not be immoral. Kyle Ash, however, dismisses her view as being steeped in metaphysical privilege and lacking any objective criteria for conferring such a legal right to humans alone.⁶¹

⁵⁶ Temple Grandin, 'Animal Welfare and Society Concerns Finding the Missing Link' (2014) 98 Meat Science 461.

⁵⁷ *ibid.*

⁵⁸ Michael Balter, 'Strongest Evidence of Animal Culture Seen in Monkeys and Whales' (*Science* AAS 2013) <<http://news.sciencemag.org/brain-behavior/2013/04/strongest-evidence-animal-culture-seen-monkeys-and-whales>> accessed 10 April 2015.

⁵⁹ Oscar Schachter (n 46) 851.

⁶⁰ Ruth Cigman, 'Death, Misfortune and Species Inequality' (1981) 10 Philosophy and Public Affairs 47.

⁶¹ Kyle Ash (n 17) 210-11.

It could be argued that the animal kingdom is structured in a way that the predators hunting the prey forms a part of nature's cycle. If the animals' dignity is maintained throughout their existence and their death is painless, then the taking away of their life need not be considered immoral, so long as the animal was not killed to serve no purpose. This does not relate to species that are on the brink of extinction, as certain legal measures will certainly have to be implemented for their protection, but that would not in itself grant them an inherent right to life.

It can also be argued that nonhuman primates, who are much closer to humans than other animals in the Linnaean classification system, can be accorded a right to life. The beauty of the dynamic nature of law is that this has already been done in Argentina, where a Court of Appeals ordered the release of an orang-utan languishing in a zoo with the writ of *Habeas Corpus*.⁶² A similar case has been heard in the New York Supreme Court, where the fate of two chimpanzees used for research by the Stonybrook university was decided with the filing of a *Habeas Corpus* writ. While the judge ultimately ruled that she was bound by an earlier precedent denying a nonhuman primate personhood, she urged an appeal on the matter to a higher court, saying that public policy and principle play a greater role in determining 'personhood' than mere biology. She also ordered the release of the two chimpanzees and clarified that humans could bring cases on behalf of nonhuman animals without showing any proof of personal injury.⁶³ While the case achieved a modest amount of success, the ultimate question of the chimps' personhood, to be

determined in a future appeal, will either establish the Argentinean court's ruling as a lone exception, or mark it as the beginning of a new era in animal rights.

4. CONCLUSION

Science has not yet managed to answer all the questions surrounding human and nonhuman existence, but its advances so far have helped bring the two closer than philosophers and legal scholars could have ever imagined, in terms of genetic makeup, intelligence and emotions. The concept of dignity, however, has been unable to evolve in keeping with our new understanding of life. The idea that humanity alone possesses dignity is an entirely theoretical concept, paralleling other theoretical notions that have enjoyed widespread popularity in the past – such as those alleging the inferiority of women and 'savages'. Much like those previously popular notions, it also rests on a fundamentalist idea rather than any actual scientific grounding, leaving plenty of scope for detractors of animal dignity to produce new grounds to preserve the *status quo*. But every reason supplied for this speciecism fails either because it is purely metaphysical, like religion's reliance on an ontological leap, or because of its inability to find any one trait or ability that is exclusive to humans. Exceptions are inadvertently created for children, the mentally disabled, sufferers of genetic abnormality, and yet these exceptions are not extended to nonhuman animals.

But when dignity is condensed to its most basic, universally accepted core, it becomes as crucial to the existence of animals as it does for those of humans. It is notable that some legal systems are already beginning to recognise animal dignity, in so far as it relates to minimising their suffering and ensuring that they are not ill-treated for amusement. This has generated hope that, once humans are able to cast off the shackles of their anthropocentric view of rights, dignity and life, they will finally be able to

⁶² 'Argentine Appeals Court Rules Orangutan Has Right to Habeas Corpus' (*Non Human Rights Project* 2014) <<http://www.nonhumanrightsproject.org/2014/12/22/argentine-appeals-court-rules-orangutan-has-right-to-habeas-corpus/>> accessed 26 April 2015.

⁶³ Steven M Wise, 'That's One Small Step for a Judge, One Giant Leap for the Nonhuman Rights Project' (*Non Human Rights Project* 2015) <<http://www.nonhumanrightsproject.org/2015/08/04/thats-one-small-step-for-a-judge-one-giant-leap-for-the-nonhuman-rights-project/>> accessed 04 October 2015.

recognise and respect the dignity of nonhuman animals.

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GENDER PARADIGM OF SOCIAL CHANGE: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 27ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Women confront segregation and constant gender disparities. This paper will cast light on how women strengthening will prompt improvement in the economy and further what are the present boundaries which are preventing the same to happen. Marriage, multiculturalism, destitution and stratum assume a critical part in giving restricted access to women around the world. The paper will be centered towards the present day status of women and solutions to the same.

Keywords: Economy, Gender disparities, Multiculturalism, Women, Marriage.

Gender is the fascinating subject of social conflict. Across the division on the basis of language, caste, religion and creed, gender is a common horizontal basis of division among all of them. Women played a vital role in the development of the country, but still they had suffered throughout the history. The contributions of women have been evidenced by sacrifices and pains.

due to which one sex becomes inferior to another. The concept of gender issues is not confined only to the roles allocated to men and women but it also covers the problem of homosexuality. Gender issues emphasizes on the idea of development of the women in every aspect. It requires providing opportunity to women over economic and social resources.

2. SEX AND GENDER

The State is an important concept which led to emergence of all the institutions. A person, either in the capacity of an individual or a citizen, led to the emergence of the State. It is the State through which the notion of gender has been evolved. A person constitutes a family which turns into the clan and later, the clan turns into tribe and hence the conflict between tribes led to the emergence of the State. The abstraction of matriarchal theories and patriarchal theories led to the emergence of the issues of gender.

Sex and Gender are the two words that are often confused with. The biological idiosyncratic which makes the distinction between male and female is called as sex. The term biological in the definition directly shows that the term “sex” emphasizes on reproductive system, hormones, *et cetera*. Gender underlines on social, mental and social characteristics that are connected with sex as per the social standards. It can be concluded that sex makes us male or female; gender makes us masculine or feminine.¹ According to the social norms, the role of

The concept of “gender issues” focuses on the problems which arise due to the allocation of roles to the respective sexes

¹ Chapter 1-Sociology of Gender, Gender Roles: A Sociological Perspective, ISBN -13: 9780132448307.

male and female are determined according to their sex.

Gender relations are generally experienced as “natural” rather than as something created by cultural and social processes. Throughout most of history for most people the roles performed by men and women seem to be derived from inherent biological properties. Gender relations are the result of the way social processes act on a specific biological categories and form social relations between them. From an egalitarian point of view, gender relations are fair if, within those relations, males and females have equal power and equal autonomy. This is what could be termed “egalitarian gender relations”.² The distinctions based on biological difference can be controlled but it is not easy to remove the differences based on the socially constructed ideas. We cannot consider a thing to be desirable or untransformable just because that thing is natural. These social norms are the tools used by males to protect their interest by making females to suffer so that males can protect their interest.

Justice demands something to be just and reasonable. Justice is related with the concept of liberty, equality and fraternity. Social justice demands for the equal treatment without any discrimination on the basis of race, sex, caste, religion, *et cetera*. Women cannot get their status until and unless they are not provided with economic justice. Economic justice is the sole factor due to which there is inequality between the two genders. Civil liberty deals with the liberty at individual level and it is the urge for power. It also refers that all people must have equal right to develop their personal abilities and free to make personal choices. Women are not provided with economic justice and hence they cannot attain civil liberty. If women would attain civil liberty, then they will become independent and hence superior to men. Economic justice gives rise to issues such as women cannot get

² Chapter 15: Gender Inequality, American Society: How it really Works, Erik Olin Wright, Joel Rogers, ISBN: 978-0-393-93067-2.

their share in property, inadequate medical facilities, unequal pay for work, *et cetera*. Many religious practices such as devdasi, dowry, *et cetera* also affect the rights of women. The laws are also inadequate to provide protection to the women.

2. FEMINISM

Feminism is an important term associated with gender issues. Feminism is a term aimed at ending the oppression of women.³ Feminism is a range of movements and ideologies that share a goal to define, to establish, and achieve equal political, economic, cultural, personal and social rights for women.⁴ This includes seeking to establish equal opportunities for women in education and employment.⁵

Multicultural feminism focuses on the specific cultural elements and historical conditions that serve to maintain women’s oppression. In Latin America, for instance, military regimes have devised specific patterns of punishment and sexual enslavement for women who oppose their regimes.⁶ Multicultural feminism emphasizes difference among women (race, ethnicity, class, *et cetera*); focus on coalition-building among different groups of women; emphasize international and global programs of reform.⁷ “Feminism and multiculturalism might find themselves as allies in academic politics; but as political vision in the larger world they are very apart.” Multiculturalism urges towards respect for all cultural traditions but feminism questions the same. Global feminism is a feminist theory closely aligned with post colonial theory and post colonial feminism. It concerns itself primarily with the forward movement of women’s rights on a global scale.⁸

3. WOMEN AND CUSTOMS

³ Supra note 1.

⁴ Globalization and Feminist Activism, Hawkesworth, M.E. (2006), ISBN 9780742537835.

⁵ Feminism is for everybody: Passionate Politics, Hooks, Bell (2000), ISBN 9780745317335.

⁶ Supra note 1.

⁷ <https://www2.cnr.edu/home/bmcmanus/classnotes.html>.

⁸ <http://www.mainstreamweekly.net/article3236.html>.

Part III of the Constitution assures development of all the individuals irrespective of their race, sex, caste and religion. The very words of the Constitution form the backbone of all other laws in the country. The framers of the Constitution were well aware of the conditions of women and discriminatory practices against them due to which specific provisions have been inserted in the Constitution in order to provide protection to the women. Article 14 provides protection for all the people irrespective of their condition. The Constitution provides Article 15 as specific instance of Article 14 to enable the protection of women. Article 15 empowers the State to make special provision for the women.⁹ Women's control and participation in economic processes is important for their advancement and through this, they would be able to exert their control and influence in the society.

Due to limited access to women over the resources, they are dependent on men throughout their lives. The major reasons behind the inequality in the status of the women are poor knowledge, illiteracy, lack of confidence, custom and usages, *et cetera*. The patriarchal setup is the major reasons behind the status of the women. The birth of boys is celebrated, whereas birth of a girl is considered to be a movement of sorrow. The practice of Azan in Muslim community illustrates such practice. According to this practice, a prayer is called at mosque after the birth of a male child. The birth of a female child is not recognized as such. This negligence leads to gender based health disparities among the young age population. This negligence results into insufficient nutrition, less preventive care, and irregularity in seeking health care during illness for female children.¹⁰ The practice of *Purdah* system hinders the participation of women in society and they cannot become economically independent. The problem of

gender issue is also observed when the funeral rites are carried by male child.

Hindu social practice allows the parents to absolve themselves from honoring the daughter's inheritance right at par with their sons with the alibi of paying dowry at the time of the daughter's marriage. Dowry as a substitute of land and other properties in inheritance is one key way the patriarchal beliefs are deeply anchored in social practice, denying the women social and economic equality within the family. The practice of dowry is so entrenched that women themselves do not feel that it is their moral or legal right to claim inheritance rights in their parents' property.¹¹

Women are the direct victim of the curse of poverty. It is seen that among the poor, women seldom can have basic needs like the health care services, education, *et cetera*. One of a consequence of poverty is child marriage which is embedded so deeply in the social and cultural setting that it could be a leading cause of women discrimination and deprivation of access to all opportunities and benefits in family and societal life.¹²

4. WOMEN, LAW AND PROPERTY

Women's access over economic resources is an important factor in the field of gender issues. Women's rights over economic resources include jobs, education, control over property, *et cetera*.

Property is the essence of the concept of rights. Rule of law and gender plays the vital role towards the development of the country. Women are not able to receive legal support especially in terms of property rights. Due to lack of education, they are unaware of the laws meant for their protection and current judicial mechanism.

⁹ Article 15, The Constitution of India, 1950.

¹⁰ Khandaker, Mu. Mizanur Rahman, The University of Tokyo, "Gender discrimination in healthcare spending in the household and women's access to resources: perspective of Bangladesh".

¹¹ Report on The Formal and Informal Barriers in the Implementation of the Hindu Succession (Amendment) Act 2005, Landesa Rural Development Institute, <http://www.landesa.org/wp-content/uploads/hsaa-study-report.pdf>.

¹² *Ibid*.

When property is concerned, the position of women determines her share in the property. Women get different share in the same property in the capacity of mother, widow, daughter, *et cetera*.

Since ancient times, there has been inconsistency in property rights pertaining to the gender. Earlier, women were considered to be of low status and they were always considered to be inferior to men. According to Mitakshara Law, only son were given rights over the properties. According to it, the coparceners included only male members, females were excluded from this group. The Hindu Law of Inheritances, 1929 was the earliest legislation which improved the status of women and gave them rights over the property. Hindu women's Right to Property Act XVIII, 1937 gave widows right to share in property same as that of the son.

As far as women under the Hindu Law is concerned, prior to the enactment of Hindu Succession Act,¹³ women were not given equal rights as that of men but now Section 14¹⁴ of the Act improved the conditions of the women. Under the Muslim Law, women inherit their property as widow, daughter, *et cetera* on the basis of their positions in the family.

Property rights had been denied to Hindu women just to exercise control over them and to make them subjugated and

dependent on men.¹⁵ Prior to Hindu Succession Act, 1956 'Shastric' and 'Customary' law that varied from region to region use to govern the Hindus. According to this Act the hitherto limited estate given to women was converted to absolute one, the principle of simultaneous succession of heirs of a certain class was introduced, the principle of testamentary succession was applied so as not to exclude women, remarriage, conversion and unchastity were no longer held grounds for disability to inherit and even the unborn child, son or daughter, has right if s/he was in the womb at the time of death of the intestate.¹⁶

Some of the special laws for the protection of women are as The Equal Remuneration Act, 1976, The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956, The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961, The Medical termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971, The Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987, The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006, The Pre-Conception & Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Regulation and Prevention of Misuse) Act, 1994 and The Sexual Harassment of Women at Work Place (Prevention, Protection and) Act, 2013.

The definition of rape under Section 375 of IPC defines an act to be concluded as rape if and only if the victim is less than 18 years of age.¹⁷ The exception to the Section 375 of IPC explicitly says that the act would not amount to rape if the victim is wife of the person committing rape.¹⁸ Even though the Section protects female from wrongs committed by men but it does not offer any protection to the wives. The Section offers protection to the wife less than 15 years of age. It is violation of human rights as it does not offers protection to the wife more than 15 years of age. The definition of rape under the Section is not adequate as it uses narrow approach to define an act as rape. It defines

¹³ Hindu Succession Act, 2005.

¹⁴ 14. Property of a female Hindu to be her absolute property—
(1) Any property possessed by a female Hindu, whether acquired before or after the commencement of this Act, shall be held by her as full owner thereof and not as a limited owner. Explanation.—In this sub-section, "property" includes both movable and immovable property acquired by a female Hindu by inheritance or devise, or at a partition, or in lieu of maintenance or arrears of maintenance, or by gift from any person, whether a relative or not, before, at or after her marriage, or by her own skill or exertion, or by purchase or by prescription, or in any other manner whatsoever, and also any such property held by her as stridhana immediately before the commencement of this Act.

(2) Nothing contained in sub-section (1) shall apply to any property acquired by way of gift or under a will or any other instrument or under a decree or order of a civil court or under an award where the terms of the gift, will or other instrument or the decree, order or award prescribe a restricted estate in such property.

¹⁵ Law Commission of India, 174th Report on "Property Rights of women: Proposed Reform under the Hindu Law".

¹⁶ <http://socialregenerationandequity.blogspot.in/2013/10/womens-property-rights-in-india.html>.

¹⁷ Section 375, Indian Penal Code, 1860.

¹⁸ Exception to Section 375, Indian Penal Code, 1860.

an act to be rape if an only if there is penetration of penis into vagina, mouth, urethra or anus. It does not include others kinds of acts which may have the same consequence as that of rape. The priority given to penetration by the penis over all other forms of penetration or sexual assault is historically based on the need to defend the rights of the legitimate father rather than the woman's integrity.¹⁹

Men found in situations of illicit intercourse do not suffer either a social stigma or a psychological scar, as it is acceptable behavior given the assumptions about the nature of male sexuality. But women lured into such situations will perhaps end up being prostitutes due to the social and psychological repercussions of illicit intercourse with them. That also explains the inclusion of prostitution, and illicit intercourse in the same sections.²⁰

5. WOMEN AND SOCIETY

It is accepted by the society when we see a man peeing on the road, but at the same time, we do not accept a woman peeing on the road. It again shows that these social norms are again restricting the freedom of the women. Men having sexual relations outside the marriage are considered to be more masculine, whereas a woman having sexual relations outside her marriage is considered to be a sin. It is considered to be to duty of women to protect her virginity and protecting her virginity means protecting the status of her tribe whereas men having sexual relations with other women and rape the women of other tribe characterizes his masculinity.

A woman makes all the efforts to maintain her married life. There are two purposes behind the marriage, the primary and the secondary. The primary purpose behind marriage is to fulfill sexual desires. The secondary purpose behind marriage is to get psychological support and economic dependency. The purpose of economic

dependency makes women inferior to men. The decline in the stability of marriage concludes that women cannot receive the financial support from her husband. Due to this, females even after violence, do not seek divorce. If they do so, their life will become more miserable. Women are not respected and given equal rights even if they married in an educated family.

Earlier, women were not allowed to get share in the property. The social practices such as sati, dowry, child marriage *et cetera* made the life of women more miserable. The attempts made by reformists such as Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Swami Dayanand Saraswati and other social reformers improved the conditions of women. In India, women are considered to be goddess (e.g. we call Bharat Mata) and in the Vedas, women are considered to be goddess. We pray many goddesses such as Durga, Sarawati, *et cetera* but still in today's society women are ill treated by men in the patriarchal setup. A bride is ill treated by her family if she does not bring adequate dowry.

The problem of gender issues was highlighted in 1950s. During the period of 1980s and 1990s, it became an important issue in management and organizational studies.²¹ In the field of employment, gender discrimination may exist in various forms such as discrimination in employee hiring, difference in salary and wages, discrimination in promotion *et cetera*. Employee is a back bone of the organization that performs critical tasks for the survival of the organization and employee productivity is also affected by gender discrimination. Organizational productivity and performance affected by employee performance and employee performance affected by gender discrimination. Equal pay for equivalent work would go much further in eliminating gender inequality in labor market earnings because it would directly undermine the strong tendency for jobs that are associated

¹⁹ Gender Analysis of the Indian Penal Code, Ved Kumari.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* Vol. 1 No. 15 [Special Issue – October 2011], Gender Discrimination & Its Effect on Employee Performance/Productivity, Dr. Qaisar Abbas, Abdul Hameed, Amer Waheed.

with "women's work" to be less valued than traditionally male jobs.²²

6.CONCLUSION

The advantage of providing opportunities for the women is that an educated girl would postpone marriage. Furthermore, they would raise a smaller family and hence send her children to school without discrimination. An educated female has more chances of earning and she would help in the development of the countries due to her participation in the political processes. Women face problems while searching for jobs and the consequence of this is that they face more harassment while searching for work. Uneducated women are more prone to divorce due to which they die because of unbearable problems.

The guaranteeing of rights to girls and women will provide them with the opportunities to reach their full potential. But apart from this, it offers wide range of international development goals. If females are empowered, it would ensure productivity of their health and hence will assure the fulfillment of international development goals. Furthermore, it would provide for the productivity of the country. Gender equality aims at ensuring equal power to both the sex to attain economic independence, education and hence personal development. Attitude of males towards females plays a vital role in the development of females and hence in removing gender disparities.

Women are also facing lack of nutritious food, negligence to medicine and proper checkup, lack of educational opportunities, sexual abuse of girl child, rapes, forced and unwanted marriages, sexual harassment at public, home or work place, unwanted pregnancies at small intervals, bride-burning, wife-battering,

negligence of old women in family, *et cetera*.²³

Law and order enforcing agencies along with both marriage registrars and birth registrars should be more efficient and sincere in order to end violence against women and girls at home and in the communities. Early marriage and dowry, which are two root causes of gender discrimination, are deeply embedded in the improvised and traditional cultural settings in the world. No single solution is available to prevent and protect such kind of social diseases. Gender issues, especially social and cultural education regarding early marriage, sex biasness, dowry system etc should be incorporated in school curriculum in order to build gender awareness among the young generation.²⁴

To conclude it can be said that "*It is not easy to eradicate deep seated cultural values or to alter traditions that perpetuate discrimination. It is fashionable to denigrate the role of law reform in bringing about social change. Obviously law, by itself, may not be enough. Law is only an instrument. It must be effectively used. And this effective use depends as much on a supportive judiciary as on the social will to change. An active social reform movement, if accompanied by legal reform, properly enforced, can transform society.*"²⁵

We should make all possible efforts to improve the conditions of the women otherwise we will be destroyed by the monster of our own creation.

²²Supra note 2.

²³<http://www.indiacelebrating.com/essay/social-issues/women-empowerment/violence-against-women-in-india/>.

²⁴Supra note 10.

²⁵ Justice Sujata V. Manohar of Supreme Court of India.

TRIBAL'S COMMUNITY FOREST RIGHT: A PIONEERING SUCCESS STORY IN MAHARASHTRA

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 24ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

On 15th August 2009 a history was rewritten by the marginalized, ridden with Naxalite menace and remotely placed tribal's of Mendha (Lekha) scheduled village fighting with draconian forest laws, officials along with revenue department with a tool of conviction, knowledge and consensus decision making mechanism. This historic event was boasted as first of its own in India since independence. Proposed paper is endeavor to enumerate a unique story of struggle movement to get legal entitlement of community forest right for their village, from the clutches of government officials under the aegis of "The Scheduled and other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Forest Rights) Act 2006". The main highlight of this story was the application of rights based approach of Social Work Intervention.

Keywords: *Tribal, Forest, Rights, Maharashtra, Displacement*

The Indian Constitution is supposed to protect tribal interests, especially tribal autonomy and their rights over natural resources, through Fifth and Sixth Schedules. Scheduled Areas of Article 244(1) are notified as per the Fifth Schedule and Tribal Areas of Article 244(2) are notified as per the Sixth Schedule. Village level democracy became a real prospect for India in 1992 with the 73rd amendment to the Constitution, which mandated that resources, responsibility and decision making be passed on from central government to the lowest unit of the governance, the Gram Sabha or the Village Assembly. A three tier structure of local self government was envisaged under this amendment.

Since the laws do not automatically cover the scheduled areas, the PESA Act was enacted on 24 December 1996 to enable Tribal Self Rule in these areas. The Act extended the provisions of Panchayat to the tribal areas of nine states that have Fifth Schedule Areas.

Most of the North eastern states under Sixth Schedule Areas (where autonomous councils exist) are not covered by PESA.

The salient feature of the Panchayat (Extension to the Scheduled Areas) Act, 1996 (PESA) and the modalities worked out to grant rights to tribal's in the country are:

(i) Legislation on Panchayat shall be in conformity with the customary law, social and religious practices and traditional management practices of community resources;

(ii) Habitation or a group of habitations or a hamlet or a group of hamlets comprising a community and managing its affairs in accordance with traditions and customs; and shall have a separate Gram Sabha.

(iii) Every Gram Sabha to safeguard and preserve the traditions and customs of people, their cultural identity, community

resources and the customary mode of dispute resolution.

(iv) The Gram Sabhas have roles and responsibilities in approving all development works in the village, identify beneficiaries, issue certificates of utilization of funds; powers to control institutions and functionaries in all social sectors and local plans.

(v) Gram Sabhas or Panchayat at appropriate level shall also have powers to manage minor water bodies; power of mandatory consultation in matters of land acquisition; resettlement and rehabilitation and prospecting licenses/mining leases for minor minerals; power to prevent alienation of land and restore alienated land; regulate and restrict sale/consumption of liquor; manage village markets, control money lending to STs; and **ownership of minor forest produce**. Ownership over minor forest produces under the PESA, was the main contention to claim community forest right as envisaged in Forest Rights Act 2006. Hence, these two legislations were more relevant in this context.

We need forests for our survival, each passing day the forest lands in India are under a big threat not necessarily for the tribal people who live in the forest but from developers who want the land, minerals, water and other resources. The infrastructure imperative will take away forests, which have become the only free and available resource at the time of scarcity there are estimates of what forests generate for the economy but no valuation of the minor forest produce, which provides livelihood to the poor tribal's, if we take into account the enormous potential of growing wood and non timber produce and their impact on livelihood.

31st December 2006 was the historical day in the life of marginalized tribal's of India, who were residing in the forest areas whose livelihood totally depends upon natural

resources but these people are grossly deprived of their traditional rights over the ages. Tribal has sensed the second freedom of their life when the "Scheduled Tribes and other forest dwellers (recognition of forest rights) Act 2006" was notified in the Gazette of India. For the first time tribal's were given the community ownership rights over forest land in which they're residing and toiling for generations, though they were always labeled as encroachers and always been husking away forcibly from their homeland. The basic philosophy of this act was worded that:

1. We need to value the economic potential of forests in which forests provide livelihood support to the dwellers,
2. We need steps to pay for the standing forests. This money must go to the local communities who bearing the burden of forest conservation. And
3. The economic value of keeping forests has to be paid to the custodians, it will build local economies and local support for forest protection and most importantly, we have to increase the productivity of the remaining forestland.

In the introduction of the said act it candidly confesses that, the historical injustice has been done on the tribal's regarding forest rights which they have deserved by virtue of traditional rights, another sea change in the policy was that Indian forest Act had over time categorized bamboo as timber which meant that the forest department had the monopoly over it. In 2006 Forest Rights Act "vested the right of ownership, access to collect, use and dispose of minor forest produce" it has also defined bamboo as a grass (minor forest produce) which means direct access to tribal people, now industry directly source bamboo from small tribal landholders with community forest rights. They have to pay market value, the buyer - seller relationship will put money directly in the hands of tribal people. The world is desperately looking for this new green growth model.

1. SILENT MOVEMENT OF MENDHA VILLAGE:

Paving the way for the lakhs of deprived sections of the society, this historical golden opportunity grabbed by the two tribal villages namely Mendha (Lekha) and Marda of Gadcholi district of Maharashtra which is the notified scheduled area, Naxalite ridden, surrounded by the 80% forest coverage, full of minerals, natural resources but the paradox is 84% of tribal's are still under below the poverty line and at the same time at the bottom of human development index in Maharashtra. These two villages had created a history when they got community forest rights over 4528.82 acres and 2278.82 acres of forest land respectively on 15th October 2009 by the hands of Governor of Maharashtra and became the first villages in India. What is so special about these villages? To get the answer to this question one should know the background about these villages.

Village Profile:

These villages emerged as out of the box thinking villages when they took part in Padmashree Baba Amte's movement '*Save forest, Save Human*' due to this movement only one mercurial local leadership have emerged in the form of Shri. Devaji Tofa, this illiterate simple looking person came up with some imaginative ideas for village development. He infused a lot of motivation and confidence among the villagers while he was a Mukhia, his slogan "*Delhi, Mumbai hamari Sarkar, Hamare Gaon me hum hi Sarkar*" have created a sensation and '*we can do it*' spirit in the minds of villagers. These villages were the first who knows the importance of Panchayat Act in the scheduled areas of 1996 and formed a tribal self rule in their villages, they acknowledge the importance of the institution of 'Gramsabha' and emphasized the 'consensus decision making rather than

majority decision making' in the Gramsabha, they ensured the fullest participation of

womenfolk without them no Gramsabha was held, this rule makes a lot of difference in community well-being and they saw the fruits of this mechanism. They always have faith in their own capabilities, believed in philosophy 'for own problems, find own solutions' without depending on others. These village's came into limelight again on 15th April 2004 when they prepared their sustainable management of natural resource record called 'Peoples Biodiversity Register'(PBR), nobody is ever thought of. It is evident that villagers were very curious about every developmental thing pertaining to the common benefits.

2. BASIC ASSUMPTIONS FOR CLAIMING COMMUNITY FOREST RIGHT:

1. Village is eligible being comes under PESA Act.
2. Rather than individual forest rights it is in the larger interest of the village to claim Community forest rights, which are the integral part of it.
3. Got legitimate ownership over forest land and no one labeled them as encroachers in their own homeland.
4. Free themselves away from the shackles of the forest and revenue officials.
5. The village is the caretaker of the entire forest, which they have owned.
6. The government should ask village Gramsabha for any development projects in their area and not by the village.
7. Development, Conservation, and Regeneration of the forest is the sole responsibility of villager's. Which are their bread and butter?
8. Auctioning and sell of minor forest produce including bamboo is the discretion of village Gramsabha.
9. So, the income belongs to the villagers.
10. Unity is the only weapon to fight against all socio-economic odds.

Chronology of events:

- **Get Act translated** in vernacular language. **Formed a Study group** to decode each word in the Act. Took help of the like-minded people.
- **Networking** among NGO's.
- **Persuasion** with officials.
- **The extensive use of RTI** to get relevant information.
- **Prepared eligibility certificate:** Since villages are, 100% scheduled Tribe villagers.
- **Form forest Rights Committee:** Called Gramsabha and formed an independent forest rights committee with consensus decision, comprising of six males and three female members.
- **Fill up the application form** and submitted to the forest rights committee.
- **Verification of claim** in Gramsabha attended by govt. Officials as well.
- **Verification report** handed over to the village development officer.
- **Submission of records** i. e. Nistar register, Revenue map, Forest map, Settlement survey to show village boundaries, Peoples Biodiversity Register etc. With Sub-Divisional Office.
- **A claim accepted by the office (28th Aug 2009)** and land record handed over to the villagers in a public function (15th December 2009)
- **Acknowledgement by the central government, then minister** who personally visited the village.

3. SOME UNIQUE INITIATIVES BY THE VILLAGE

- First scheduled villages who implemented Tribal Self Rule under PESA 2006
- Strong belief & effective use of Gramsabha'
- Women participation in 'Gramsabha made compulsory.
- Practiced 'Consensus Decision Making' rather than Majority Decision Making'
- First Tribal villages who prepared 'Peoples Biodiversity Register' (PBR) also known as 'Sustainable Management of Natural Resources Record.'
- Every person contributes 10% of his/her income in cash to the Village Fund.
- Each family contributes 2.5% of its production in the Grain bank.
- Members from 4 families do the forest patrolling every day to record the observations.
- 80% households used Deenbandhu Bio Gas plant.
- Women's SHG is running Fair Price Shop & got Kerosene license & managing Stone mine & Brick Production.
- Youth SHG is involved in non destructive honey collection & recently started full fledged Honey Processing Unit also involved in Bamboo value addition activities.
- Youth SHG is acquiring technical skills to become 'Barefoot Engineers' to implement MGNREGA through Gramsabha.
- A team of village youth is trained in video shooting, script writing & editing etc. with this they made a documentary films on 'Honey Collection' & 'FRA Struggle'.

- Gramsabha has established computer training centre. functioning, campaign, lobbying, advocacy, use of right to information act, maximum use of internal resources, help to help themselves, believe in their own capacities, effective use of constitutional institutions,
- Last year rate of Bamboo was Rs.33/ per pole , labor charges were Rs.13/ & Rs.20/ diverted to the 'Gram Nidhi' creating pressure group, local techniques of problem solving, networking, co-ordination among CBO's, NGO's, trained social workers, advocacy groups has played the bigger role in this success story, without that the emancipation process could not see the light of development.
- Per family now earned up to Rs.25,000/
- Recently gram sabha has taken a decision regarding 10% of families income contributed towards 'Devrai Fund' (Contribution to the God

5. Impact

This event was one of its own kinds and first ever in India, has far-reaching impact for claiming community forest rights on the footprints of these villages. After this, there are over 5245 CFR claims were submitted and 2371 community forest rights titles have been distributed in Maharashtra (2014). 1.23 lakhs of rupees they have collected by direct auctioning of minor forest produce including bamboo and use it for the village development.

Recent past, National Advisory Council (NAC) of last government has taken a cognizance of this event and finally decided to strengthen its Forest Rights Act; they have laid down procedure to claim the Community Forest Rights. NAC had given 59 suggestions; this would remove procedural obstacles in the act.

Summary:

For knowledge community's point of view this pioneering success story has demonstrated many theoretical aspects and execution of tribal rights into action. The entire process of awareness creation, conscientization, capacity building, participatory mode of

6. REFERENCES

This paper has been based on the firsthand account with Mr. Devaji Tofa & recent personal visits to the Model villages.

1. www.tribal.nic.in
2. <http://fra.org.in>

HUMANTATWA- A PARADIGM SHIFT FROM HUMAN RIGHTS TO HUMAN DUTIES

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(Regd: 28ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

We as humans dream to live in a utopian nation with equity principles as the base but fail to even acknowledge the obligations we are born with. Any incident for that matter, be a dog bite, shall be enough to start a whole new parade for human rights violation. It is very essential that the rule of last antecedent is applied before we start interpretation of our human rights. In the middle of the fight of superior rights, the existence of duties has been negligible. This paper shall try to put forth the picture, where, in the hunger of our rights, we as a nation have never paid heed to our duties, causing the root reason of our stagnancy.

Abstracts: *Humantwa, Human, Rights, Duties, Principles*

The word TATWA in Sanskrit means the core essence. Prefixing the word human to it emphasizes more on the virtue of being a human, which brings, onto a quote by a wise man-

“There is only one basic human right, the right to do as damn you may please, and with it comes the only basic duty, the duty to take up the consequences.”

This article entitled ‘human-tatwa’ is an attempt to stretch our conscious focus from ‘**the rights**’ to ‘**the duties**’- with a much wider approach to achieve the former in a more sheer form. *‘I have the right to come home and have some peace’ – said the husband. The wife replied- ‘I have the right to tell how I feel’.* A very familiar squabble we shall find in almost every house. This argument ends up with an endless debate on ‘mine’ and ‘your’ rights¹

In its analytical perspective, “right” has two parts (form and function). One is the internal structure of right (their form); and the other is what rights do for those who hold them (function). Accordingly, right is a combination of claim and duty. This means a right confers certain liberties or privileges and imposes duties upon individuals to exercise while claiming their rights. A number of jurists define the concept of exercise of rights with duty as positive and negative rights. Accordingly, the person who is entitled of positive rights shall be the claimant of some goods or services. A holder of negative right is entitled to non-interference. In the eyes of law, Right confers on a person certain amount of liberties and privileges. At the same time impose obligations to discharge.²

Liberation of a society by granting rights without taking up the due cognizance has ever since always failed. Starting from Louis xiv of France, absolute czars in Russia to Nazis in Germany, Mussolini in Italy, the

¹ <http://www.humanrightsdefence.org/index.php/articles-sp-724795164/370-enlarging-the-scope-of-democracy-by-changing-our-interpretation-of-human-rights.html> accessed on 9/10/2015

² http://www.unipune.ac.in/pdf_files/Final%20Book_03042012.pdf accessed on 15/10/2015

world has seen it all.³ Although in today's world we do not have absolute monarchy, but it is essential to see that we should not end up just by declaring or assigning rights to individuals, groups and having a mere enforcing body to support it.

1. Rights- an overview

In the time line of evolution of the concept of grant of rights, to provide better nourishment to the humans, irrespective of their citizenship, there has been several efforts to enforce the basic rights and has also succeeded to a considerable extent. Rights from being authoritative and hierarchical, to divine rights of the king, to the modern concept of being liberalized, to the revolutions - that has brought in storm of changes in the concept.

In the contemporary concept of rights, the inception can be told as the formation UNITED DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS (UDHR) during the 20th century which had set standards for individuals, groups, governments to maintain the behavior towards each other, which was followed by the international covenant on civil and political rights and international covenant on economic social and cultural rights. India has been a signatory to the United declaration of human rights and has followed up by setting up a national board known as NATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS COMMISSION (NHRC).

So when the nation already has propounded so much when it comes to establishing the rights, then one could probably expect huge uplifting change of the genus atleast in regard to the basic rights, but the reality picture seems to be far from this vision. *People's watch*-a magazine on human -their rights and violation, had recently published '*From Home to Despair*' which is a balance sheet of the work is done by the National

Human Rights Commission. They have come to the conclusion that the National Human Rights Commission has not been effective to tackle the human right violation. Of all the complaints the commission has not replied to 1/3rd of the complaints. The acknowledgment for the receipt of the complaint and progress in the case has not been informed to the complainant. It is inhuman not to inform about the progress for two to three years to the complainant. The disappointing reality is that the people working in the Human Rights Commission are waiting for the death of the complainant who is waiting for a response. Those who receive a reply from the Commission cannot understand the order passed by the Commission because these replies are short. There is necessity to train the members of the Human Rights Commission to send reply in a language, which can be understood by the people.⁴

The social welfare nature of the state that we have has the positive duties to provide welfare to the individuals, it is here where the bill of rights came into play emphasizing on civil political rights. It is the responsibility of people to awaken and bring some constructive changes in the sleeping Human Rights Commission because such machinery is an insult to the citizen's human rights.

The skeleton of any right has the soul of being liberalized. As the famous quote by Jhon Dalbough Acton goes, '*liberty is not the power of doing what we like, but right of being able to do what we ought*'. Since recognition of the rights has been already established, it is important that there is recognition of positive duties that is important while re shaping the fundamentals of the welfare state we dwell in. The state's responsibility is no longer conceived as the sole unconditional provider of package of benefits, but instead it is in terms of

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<https://humanrightsindia.wordpress.com/2008/02/21/the-hard-facts-of-the-bad-functioning-of-the-human-rights-commissions-in-india/> accessed on 15/10/2015

³
<https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Human&action=history/acc> essed on 9/10/2015

empowering the individuals. The right bearer is characterized as an active agent instead of being a passive recipient.⁵ It is essential that there should be interrelation between positive duties within the sphere of human rights and welfare state.

Every freedom or rights is to be fed by the competency of the seeker. A simple example would be- the not privileged in the society has the right to be given the basics of the life, the vulnerable of the society have the liberty to claim security to their vulnerability. The social welfare state on the other hand needs to have enough resources to allocate this necessities. Thus as Mr. Sen demonstrates *“countries with accountable leadership do not suffer famines because leaders know if they are to remain in power, they must take action to protect the population.”* Moreover he argues, *“political rights, including freedom of expression and discussion, are not only pivotal in including political responses to economic needs, they are also central to conceptualization of the needs themselves”*.⁶

Every recognition to a right also acknowledges the necessary obligation along with it. However these obligations unlike the rights have been divided into categories like the primary secondary and tertiary. This also involves positive duties to provide and negative duties to restrain. This kind of model is what we have in our constitution under part IV- directive principles of state policy but again these are not judicially enforceable.

2. Jurisprudential views

The Jurisprudential aspect has a rather expansive form of this concept. Talking about the rights and duties, the core fundamental concept was broadly put forward by Hohfeld's Jural co relations matrix. The whole concept could be summarized as one who is in a capacity to claim rights has a co relative duty attached. However Hohfeld identified each kind of right (claim liberty authority and immunity). Therefore claim rights has co relative duties, liberty rights co relate with absence of claims, authority rights co relate with liabilities, immunities correlate with absence of authority. The same could be applied onto moral rights.⁷

In the words of Paton 'An obligation is that part of law which creates rights in personam'. Since the central point is to justify human rights, it's very important to keep in mind that the concept of human rights as not been derived out of thin air, but it is a byproduct of the society we as humans have been dwelling in. Prof. H.L.A. Hart divided the system of law into two kinds of rules- viz:

1. Primary
2. Secondary.

The reason that he gave was that, these regulate the conduct of the member of the society and that they are derived from human practices. When these rules are magnetized with societal practices then, the sociological domain is infused within. According to a dimension of analytical positivism- these primary rules consist of duties which are binding in nature. And then the secondary rules come into their actual play which confer powers to the individuals.

Another jurist of early 20th century had a more precise explanation of the concept of

⁵P Jones, universal principles and particular claims: from welfare rights to welfare states”(sage London 1990)

⁶ Sandra Fredman “human rights transformed : positive duties and positive Rights” www.ssrn.com/link/oford-legal-studies.html accessed on 15/10/2015

⁷ ibid

human obligation. Leon Duguit in his theory of 'social solidarity'. This theory defines the human relation as interdependent. As no man can ever be self sufficient solely depending on thyself. Therefore A society provides us the support system, in return of which every individual has certain indispensable duties to be fulfilled. Failure of which, rights of the human shall be grossly violated. To quote him 'Justice as a social reality has its root in the society itself and not in the will of the sovereign'.

The conclusion would be that at the very outset to secure right, the obligation corresponding needs recognition. It is also necessary to formulate a non doctrinal method that could give quantitative results; such that any discrepancy could be sorted. Human right in its holistic form and approach essentially involves incorporation of THE DUTIES.

3. Duties- magnified

Human rights have ever since been recognized has been into one of its expanding horizon. This makes its difficult to prioritize human rights and understanding its approach. Then how do we ensure that the rights in favor of humans are protected. Metastudy in one of its researches have concluded that in order to know the rate of growth of the subject , the indicators of the subject should be closely studied. They reveal out the actual loopholes in the graphs, for example to know the probability of production both demand and supply serve as indicators .

Possibly one of the indicators in case of human rights could be 'Duties'. Duties arise in several ways and means, such as moral duties, legal duties, parental duties, societal duties, and civil duties etc. Here is an example- the citizens have the beautiful right to enjoy in amusement parks in the city, the state has the responsibility to provide the same. This does not stop here. The citizens

have the utmost duty and obligation to not to destroy or litter anything in the park.

One of the housing society in Oslo, Norway (which also lists in the top 10 clean cities in world) devised a unique way to ensure that every family in that society received the necessities. They made a booklet mentioning about the amenities like water, maintenance, garbage, noise, etc and circulated to all. They were directed that every time any of these duties failed, they had to put up a red sticker on that column for one month. By the end of the month that had statistics as to where was the failure. Well this could be applied to almost all material failures.⁸

Mere existence of human rights commissions is not adequate. Human rights programmes needs to be devised and it needs to be ensured that theses programmes form a integral part of the educational curriculum. This is extremely important, to sensitize the society at large from a young age to resent and resist human rights violation. The awareness regarding human duties ought to create a new ray of hope for all.

In India, although the law is dynamic in nature but right now its important that the duties shall be in par with the rights. The irony is, fundamental duties are not enforceable as the rights are. This duties are not only in regard to the government but for one individual to another. High time that we make this duties judicially enforceable and along with it penalize the violation of any. In such a situation where one has a right and has also complied the corresponding duty still is being deprived of justice, judiciary shall interpret laws for the best purpose fit.

On International level, the draft 'bill of duties' should be notably taken into contemplation . A body similar to UDHR known as the UNITED DECLARATION OF HUMAN DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES(UDHD) had been

⁸DR. M.H. khandagle, Dialectics and dynamism of human rights(2011) p.90, Asia law house

proposed in Valencia Declaration in 1998. However there has not been any further progress in this respect. The countries ratified for UDHR should come forward willingly to get this into action . This could be started from and by us as Indians forming a National body as “national human duties commission” which shall regulate all of the important aspects and most importantly shall regulate transparency.

- To pay the taxes established by law for public purposes.
- To Protect the property and culture of the state.
- Not to discriminate or advocate anything on communal, linguistic and religious

Or any other ground that affect the liberty of other individuals

- To respect the rights and responsibilities of others.
- Not to make false allegations or complaints against others.
- Not to misuse the laws and regulations

There are innumerable duties that an individual has towards state and the society. But so were the rights when the country started with its constitution, Now we have an non exhaustive clause to the lists of rights The above stated duties few are only illustrative in nature. The strict adherence of the duties prescribed by each state and society contributes for the sustainable development. In the modern context, many people think of their rights without acknowledging that they have a duty to protect the rights of others. This degradation of duty perspective has brought in a number of upheavals in the contemporary area. If people are duty conscious, automatically the country and its institutions also follow the duties without any deviance. The sincere practice of duties and exercise of rights

certainly will create a society or state that is equitable in its pure form.⁹

4. CONCLUSION

In the light of the above discussions it could be said that the concept of human duties is in a nascent stage in India. Existing laws put emphasis on protection of human rights but its relatively more important that we start giving importance to duties. Its urgent to start progressing in this direction for wholesome growth.

Firstly campaigns regarding awareness of duties needs to be started.

Secondly education system should be given much importance to the human duties serving's human rights

Thirdly a body should be formed for enforcement and supervision of the human duties.

⁹ supra .2

PATRIARCHY VS REPRODUCTIVE EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN: A FEMINIST APPROACH

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(Regd: 09ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Reproductive health and reproductive rights are life time concerns which are essential to women's empowerment and gender equality, nevertheless within patriarchal society women don't have control over their reproduction, or to use contraception, terminate pregnancy and prefer to girl child. Further patriarchy not only forces women to be mothers of sons, it also determines the condition of their motherhood. The scripting of reproductive rights into International Human rights law is a foremost achievement. The struggle over reproductive and sexual rights led to a progressive feminization of theory and practice of governance, development, human rights and global justice.

* In the presentation first I want to explain that what is the role of feminist groups regarding sexual and reproductive rights of women?

* Secondly it will be discussed that after implementation of PCPNDT how Indian mothers combat against patriarchy to save their girl child, which has been strengthening their reproductive choice

Keywords: *Women, Health, Reproductive, Human, Rights*

1. INTRODUCTION

The scripting of reproductive rights into International Human rights law is a foremost achievement. The struggle over reproductive and sexual rights led to a progressive feminisation of theory and practice of governance, development, human rights and global justice. It has also invented extraordinary patterns of global social action. It is remarkable that in the beginning of twenty first century women's movement is generated in a constructive way. One hand women movement energetically hypothesize the lack of concern with women's rights and as wellbeing in prior human rights diction and find to redress it by innovating general specific norms. Apparently women's movements also strengthen the presence of human rights formulation, the logic and the language of reproductive rights. Feminist

movement tries to establish the categories of right to live, invulnerability from torture or ill treatment, the rights to the highest attainable standards of health education, information privacy and dignity.¹

Primarily in 1968, at Teheran Conference of human Rights, documented the requirement of basic human right to decide independently and responsibly the number and spacing of children, right to enough education and information in respect.²

In 1970's with the spread of second wave of feminism in West the issue of reproductive rights of women was emerged. In the part of Europe and North America reproductive rights and abortion were

¹Connecticut journal of International Law 1999, p-83

² Final Act of International Conference on Human Rights at 14-15, UN Doc A/ Conf.171/13 para 7.2

merged in the political legal and cultural movements of women. In the mid of seventies the waves of the movement has stimulated the feminist interpretation in India. In the mid-seventies UN focused on the women issue. Asian countries also took part along with European and American countries. There was an increasing visibility in the presence of activists from the South at international conferences and as part of informal transnational frame work. They emphasized on four issues which were reproduction related oppression faced by women. Women from south Region highlighted oppressive family planning policies which were barriers of their reproductive freedom.

There pointed out that women's health movement associated with the philosophy of the reproductive rights. There pointed out that women should have the right to decide 'whether' 'when' and 'how' to have a children regardless of nationality, class, ethnicity, race, age religion, disability, sexuality or marital status in the social, economic, and political conditions that make such decision possible'. (WGNRR: 1993)³

From the feministic viewpoints in the conference it was explained that reproductive health has four dimensions. 1) The ability to enjoy sexual relations without fear of infections, unwanted pregnancy or coercion. 2) The ability to regulate fertility without the risk of unpleasant or dangerous side effects. 3)The ability to bear healthy children.' In the conference it was declared that reproductive health⁴ is the central to the idea of reproductive rights. The international women's movement emphasized the notions of rights of woman to have control over her own body, sexuality and reproductive life. The international Women's Year Conference 1975 noted that "...it should be one of the

principal aims of social education to teach respect for physical integrity and its rightful place in human life. The human body whether that of man or woman is inviolable and respects of it's a fundamental element of human dignity.'" (United Nations: 1976)⁵

The language of reproductive rights first matured in Cairo Programme which expanded the notion to include a right to reproductive health defined as a state of complete physical mental and social wellbeing.⁶ 1992 in Cairo conference the women's health movement was drafted. The declaration was planned to promote women's health movements stand on a variety of issues around development and reproduction in the third world countries. Between 1992 and October 1993 the declaration was modified and finalized by 100women's organization from 23 countries. Those organizations avowed that "[w]omen's fertility has been the primary objective of both pro-nationalist and anti-nationalist population policies. Women's behaviors rather than men's has been the focus of attention. Women have been expected to carry most of the responsibility and risks of birth control...but have been largely excluded from decision making "in personal relationships as well as in public policy... [p]opulation policies must be based on the principle of respect for the sexual and bodily integrity of girls and women..."⁷ The declaration was finally adopted in January, 1994, the singular achievement of the Declaration was that women from all over the world deliberated over it and supported the values and agendas it embodied. Apparently in the Beijing Platform had declared the notion reproductive health to women's right "to have control over ...matters relating to their sexuality...free of coercion discrimination and violence."⁸ In the Beijing Conference reproductive rights

³ WGNRR news letter, 1993

⁴ The Women's health movement adopted the WHO definition of reproductive health which was defined not in the negative as the absence of disease or infirmity. But as a condition to aspire to that is 'a state of complete physical, mental and social well being. WGNRR new letter, 1993

⁵ United Nations 1976: cited in Freedman Isaacs 1993, p-23

⁶ United Nations, Report of the international Conference on Population and Development, UN DOC.A/Conf. 171/ 13 para, 7.2

⁷ Cited in GermainNowrojiec and Pyne, 1994,p-32

⁸ United Nations Report of the Fourth World Conference on Women, UN DOC.A/Conf.177/20 para 96

entitled for all sections of women in society. It declared that a revolutionary transformation assuring equality of relationship between men and women.”⁹

After Cairo and Beijing conference feminist groups were advocated a set of principles regarding reproductive rights, their steps were undoubtedly revolutionary. Cairo and Beijing conference have made enormous effect on feminist movement in India. Feminist activists demand that with the strengthen of Reproductive and sexual rights it have also challenged to the artificial segregation between ‘public’ and ‘private’ spheres by implementing obligations on fathers, husbands, kin groups and local communities to respect women’s integrity and self-determination in aspect to their bodies, sexuality and fertility. Firstly, the definition of “‘privacy’” is always contestable, and feminists have defined it, for example, not as the familial or domestic sphere, but rather as the imaginary sphere of personal identity and self-realization.¹⁰ Nancy Fraser has argued that the feminist project is aimed not at the collapse of the boundaries between public and private, but rather “‘to overcome the gender hierarchy that gives men more power than women to draw the line between public and private,’” while also taking account of other dimensions to that power imbalance, not least those of race, ethnicity, and class.(Fraser: 1997)¹¹Kandiyoti emphasizes the major difference between privacy and patriarchy, arguing that feminists should be wary of ethnocentric definitions of the private and the public, and should acknowledge that the “‘private’” is often

problematically defined by the state. (Kandiyoti: 1991)¹²

Within the arguments of feminist organization it has reflected that ‘control over reproduction is a basic right for a woman. It is linked with women’s health, social status and as well as the powerful social structures of religion, state control and administrative apathy and private profit, it is from the perspective of the poor women thus this girl can best be understood and confirmed. With the influence of feminist movement women have tried to break the patriarchal obsessions and have explained that bearing of child is not social it is purely personal. Women have started to justify her reproductive rights thus women have carried foetus for 10months in her womb so they have primary right over their babies. They have also justified that if a woman cannot give birth of child then patriarchy is marked them as barren but men would not be responsible for that. With the influence of feminism also women have raised the issue that a man would also be a barren.

Feminist scholars and activists have fought to consider reproductive and sexual rights as individual’s right. According to the concept of Petchesky and Judd it has explained that for women of developing societies where an individualist concept of reproductive rights is contrary with their concept of body and self, and their alliance to their community and family the social rights perspective resonate closer to their understanding of their reproductive needs.¹³

Feminist arguments in support of abortion rights have necessarily engaged with broader debates over how to produce rights claims which minimise the risk of application or interpretation in unjust and unequal ways. This has, in turn, led to

⁹ ibid

¹⁰ Jean Cohen, for instance, offers the following definition: “Let me formulate the standard that underlies this aspect of privacy as the right not to have an identity imposed upon one by the state or third parties that one cannot freely affirm and embrace.” (original emphasis) (Cohen, 1996, p. 201).

¹¹ Fraser, Nancy (1997). Justice interrupts: Critical reflections of the “post socialist” condition. London: Routledge.p-119

¹²Kandiyoti, Deniz (1991). Identity and its discontents: Women and the nation. Millennium: Journal of International Studies, 20(3), 429– 443.

¹³Petchesky R. Judd K (1998), edsNegotiating reproductive rights: Women’s perspectives across countries , Zed Books, London, p-45

debates over whether rights claims can ever be a sufficient remedy for inequality and injustice. Petchesky(1986), in her influential consideration of its limits, defines choice as “a woman’s right to control her own body,” a version of bodily and decisional autonomy, while also arguing that such autonomy should be limited, because, as she puts it, recognizing women as the source of decision making over pregnancy “let’s men and society neatly off the hook” (Petchesky, 1986, p. 7). Specifically, the complex contexts of abortion decisions is left unexamined in making a claim for abortion access as an issue of “private” choice (Davis, 1981; Himmelweit, 1988). In other words, the emphasis on privacy prevents any consideration of the socio-political forces which produce both involuntary pregnancies and calls for abortion access, and constrain the “choices” of different women in different contexts. This construction of abortion as an issue of private choice trivializes abortion decisions, as well as endorsing the very mind/body dualism which feminism has consistently contested (Cornell, 1995, p. 33).¹⁴

The second problem with claiming abortion as a privacy right, however, is that this construction does not oblige the state to ensure access to abortion services (Petchesky, 1986). Treating abortion as a right to privacy is therefore insufficient to prevent the state from actively obstructing access (Cornell, 1995, p. 33).¹⁵ If the private sphere were officially defined not in the usual terms of possessive individualism, but in terms of personal identity and self-realization, then perhaps the state would be obliged to support abortion access (a point which will be considered in section three, on Feminist Rights Theory, below).

¹⁴ As Cornell puts it, “[t]he rhetoric of choice and control assumes the much criticized dualistic conception of the subject as the king who reigns over the body” Cornell, 1995, p. 33.

¹⁵For example, the current Irish Government’s policy of allowing women to travel abroad for abortions which are not available in Ireland, leaving those women without the means to travel who don’t have any recourse to the state, unless their lives are at risk from their pregnancy (Brennock, 2001).

Rights theory is based on the assumption of competing recognition claims. As already mentioned, the second major problem with the “right to choose” discourse has been that it has enabled the successful lobbying for both cultural and official recognition of foetal rights (McNeil, 1991). To evoke rights in the context of abortion would seem to affirm the construction of pregnancy in adversarial terms, between foetus and woman, rather than between woman and the state, or between women and men. In other words, constructing abortion access as a rights issue would appear to inevitably generate opposing claims on behalf of foetuses, as well as on behalf of men as fathers (Porter, 1996; Steinberg, 1991, p. 280). Foetal- rights advocates have necessarily constructed women in terms of the potentially dangerous foetal environment, in need of regulation.¹⁶

The example of this uncertainty over the advocacy of reproductive rights claims as a substantial alternative to the “right to choose” can be seen in Susan Himmelweit’s (1988) attempt to elaborate the parameters of that alternative. Her aim, as she describes it, is to work within, while also transcending the limits of, individual rights politics. She defines what she refers to as a ‘humanitarian’ alternative, which should enable the provision of abortion on demand to all women without medical authorization, a goal which, unlike Petchesky, she advocates unequivocally. However, her determination to avoid “individualizing” abortion decisions leads her to recommend a form of welfares as the basis upon which such decisions should be made, a move which seems to suggest a community-level interest in the making of those decisions: A recognition of the active involvement and interdependence of mother and foetus would provide a secure foundation for a humanitarian claim for abortion on demand,

¹⁶ Barbara Duden argues that women are present in this iconography only as the delicate and possibly dangerous ecosystem necessary for the survival of the usually male foetus (Duden, 1993, p. 2). Sally Sheldon (1997) provides an analysis of the foetal discourse legitimizing medical practice in cases of multiple pregnancy.

based on the welfare of both mother and foetus. (Himmelweit, 1988, p. 53) It seems to me that the uncertainty and limitations these articulations of “reproductive rights” exhibit suggest a confusion between providing explanation and producing political principles.

With the influence of feminist movement MTP act has implemented in India which has primarily strengthened to abortion choice of women. Act 1971(hereafter MTP Act) to control abortions and strategies like keeping a track of pregnant women. These are dangerous strategies as they seek to control all abortions even when no sex-selective diagnosis has taken place. The MTP Act allows abortion on several grounds, including failure of contraception.¹⁷ “A prospective mother who does not want to bear a child of a particular sex cannot be equated with a mother who wants to terminate the pregnancy not because of the foetus of the child but because of other circumstances laid down under the MTP Act.”¹⁸ Some feminist groups have demanded that these grounds should be expanded to allow abortion to a woman if she chooses not to have a child.

Social activist SudhaSundaraman has explained that if women’s powerlessness can increase their urge for having children (especially sons), then steps towards their empowerment could most probably have the opposite effect. Now women can understand that if they will educated, financially independent then they will control over their reproduction. The physical hardship of repeated pregnancies, closely spaced, can

exact a terrible toll on a woman’s health, especially if she is undernourished. In developing countries as estimated 20 to 45 percent of women of child bearing age does not consume. They are suffering anemia due to frequent pregnancy and iron deficiency. Though MTP has negative effect nevertheless it is terminated unwanted pregnancy and to be empowered women’s reproductive choice.¹⁹

Though MTP Act has strengthened the reproductive rights of women nevertheless due to son phobia and pressure of patriarchal families, medical professionals have miss used to MTP as license of sex selective abortion. After Nairobi conference in1968 Indian social activists and feminist organization have fought to legalise Medical Termination of pregnancies but when it would use as profit earning methods and female sex ratio is gradually decline due to practice of female foeticide, then women activists and feminist organization have moved to prevent illegal practice of sex selective abortion. They have argued that Sex-selective abortions of female fetuses should be sharply distinguished from the right to abortion, which every woman should have, as it is a blatant and extreme form of discrimination against the girl child and is fuelled by and fuels further discrimination. After long term battle of social activists and women organization Prohibition of Sex Selection Act has introduced in India (after it is well known as PCPNDT). After implementing PCPNDT Indian mothers get legal strength to save their girl child, which has been strengthening their reproductive choice. Indian parallel films have also visualized the battle of women against female foeticide.

The 1994 Act has proceeded by the Maharashtra PNDT Act in June 1988 by which time it has become clear that pre-natal sex determination tests to abort female fetuses had become an easy way of getting

¹⁷ Vijay Sharma v UOI AIR 2008 Bom 29

The Bombay High Court in this case dealt with the MTP Act and observed that “It (MTP Act) seeks to liberalize certain existing provisions relating to termination of pregnancy as a health measure - when there is danger to the life or risk to physical or mental health of the woman, on humanitarian grounds - such as when pregnancy arises from a sex crime like rape or intercourse with a mentally ill woman, etc. and eugenic grounds - where there is substantial risk that the child, if born, would suffer from deformities and diseases . It does not deal with sex selective abortion after conception or sex selection before or after conception.”

¹⁸ Ibid, Para 17

¹⁹SudhaSundaraman Former General Secretary of All India Democratic Women’s Association has given me the interview on 11.7.2014 at AIDWA office, New Delhi-7

rid of daughters²⁰. The fact that the central legislation has come about six years later than the state Act showed the lack of political will in controlling this dangerous trend. Even though the law has been enacted in 1994, it “came into force” only on first January, 1996. This lack of political will has continued till date and has manifested itself in the manner in which the PCPNDT Act has, or rather has not, been implemented and enforced by the Central and State governments. In some states the Act did not get notified till very recently.²¹ In one case conviction could not take place as the Act has not even been notified in the gazette²².

The PCPNDT Act is a comprehensive and strict legislation. Though earlier this Act had only dealt with pre-natal diagnostic techniques it was amended in 2003 to also prohibit pre-conception diagnostic techniques as well. The introduction to the Act acknowledges that pre natal diagnostic centres had sprung up in the urban areas in the country and stated that the law has been proposed “to prohibit pre-natal diagnostic techniques for determination of the sex of the foetus leading to female foeticide.” The law therefore provided for the following;

- 1) Prohibition of the misuse of pre-natal diagnostic techniques for determination of the sex of the foetus, leading to female foeticide.
- 2) Prohibition of advertisement of pre-natal diagnostic techniques for detection or determination of sex.
- 3) Permission and regulation of the use of pre-natal diagnostic techniques for the purpose of detection of specific genetic abnormalities or disorders.
- 4) Permitting the use of such techniques only under certain conditions by the registered institutions; and
- 5) Punishment for violation of the provisions of the proposed legislation.²³

²⁰PatelVibhuti, A Long Battle for the Girl Child, Economic and Political Weekly, VOL XLVI NO 21, 18

²¹Maharashtra, Haryana, etc.

²²GauravGoyal v State of Haryana; in the High Court of Punjab and Haryana at Chandigarh; Civil Writ Petition No.15152 of 2007

²³Statement of Objects And Reasons (Act No57 of 1994)

The first landmark case to highlight the non-implementation of the PCPNDT Act is the CEHAT v UOI²⁴ in which the Supreme Court lamented the fact that the law to prevent the practice of sex-selection has not been implemented and that Appropriate Authorities at State and district levels had not been appointed. The CEHAT’s petition has also pointed out that the Central Supervisory Board is not meeting as stipulated and that no action has been taken against advertisements about facilities for pre-conception determination of sex or pre-natal sex-selection. The Court has observed that it is “apparent that to a large extent, (that) the PNDT Act is not (being) implemented by the Central or the State governments.” It has issued detailed directions to the Central and State governments, including directions to hold regular meetings, review and monitor the implementation of the Act and to see that Appropriate Authorities furnish regular quarterly reports on the registration of clinics and on the action that is taken against non-registered clinics and other complaints received by them. It has stated that these quarterly reports The Court also has directed the Central and the State governments to create public awareness against the practice of sex-selective abortions of female foetuses. The Court has issued pointed directions to Appropriate Authorities to take prompt action against advertisements in violations of the Act; against persons who are, and bodies which are operating without a valid registration and to give reports on actions taken by them. The Court also has pointed out²⁵ that they has learnt that Appropriate Authorities were only issuing warnings to unregistered clinics and that this is not proper as the AAs should take actions as per Section 23 of the Act. It further has stated that AAs are not only empowered to take criminal action but are supposed to search and seizes documents, records and objects, etc. according to Section 30 of the Act.²⁶

²⁴ (2003) 8 SCC 398

²⁵ Order dated 19.09.2001

CPIM Politburo Member Miss. Brinda Karat has pointed out the women organizations like AIDWA, NFYW, CWDS, YWCA, FORCES, Jagori etc they have found in the aspect of female foeticide that the PCPNDT Act is not being implemented by the Centre and by the State Government and the strong lobbies of medical professionals who justify the female foeticide in the name of free choice as the good way to control population like many Medical Association have used their influence to ensure the criminal cases are not field against those violating Act. It is common experience of the activists of women organization that because of the collusion between family members and doctors it has very difficult to identify cases of female foeticide. Further the collusion is not limited to doctors alone. The Indian medical Association should issue a circular calling for a strict action against those who violated PCPNDT act. There should be general sensitization courses for the medical community and coordinated country wide campaign must be launched against unscrupulous practitioners.²⁷

Justice K.S. Radha Krishnan and Deepak Mishra have also given emphasize to proper monitoring of PCPNDT Act for prohibiting sex selective abortion. The bench has said that “we have gone through the court as well as the data made available by various states, which depict a sorry and alarming state of affairs. Lack of proper supervision and

²⁶The Court issued directions to Central government to frame rules so that no ultrasound machines were sold to unregistered clinics. An important issue which has arisen in various fora including in courts is how to safeguard a woman’s right to abortion while campaigning and fighting for an end to sex-selective abortions of female fetuses. This is because some groups and individuals who support the prohibition of sex-selective abortion are against all abortions and are “pro-life” supporters.

VinodSoni&Anr. v UOI 2005 (3) MLJ 1131

A Division Bench of the Bombay High Court in this case held the PCPNDT Act as constitutionally valid and held that “The right to personal liberty cannot expand by any stretch of imagination, to liberty to prohibit coming into existence of a female foetus or male foetus which shall be for the Nature to decide... Right to bring into existence a life in future with a choice to determine the sex of that life cannot in itself to be a right.”

²⁷Brinda Karat’s interview is published in AIDWA’s Commission paper, 2006-07

effective implementation of the Act by various states is clearly demonstrated. ...cases have booked under the Act are pending disposal for several years in many courts. Nobody takes any interest in their disposal and hence seldom do those cases end in conviction and sentences a fact well known to the violators. Many of ultra-sonography clinics seldom maintain any records as per the rules and in respect of the pregnant women, no records are kept for their treatment, and the provisions of the Act and the rules are being violated with impurity.”²⁸ (Hindu: 2013)

Nawanshahr campaign was the one of important high profile women’s movement against female foeticide. The rebounding accusations between medical, social activists and a government for enforce the law after the ratification of the PNDT Act resulted in a series of responses ranging from indifference to an almost militaristic style of operation in eliminating the of menace of female foeticide. Nawanshahr represented the latter response. Primarily the district administration was criticised in the media for what was characterized as a misdirected approach in the manner of which it targeted women undergoing sex selective abortions rather than the Medical personnel who conducted the procedures. Soon after the launch of the campaign, cases were filed against six women who were arrested for undergoing the ultrasound scan and then having abortions. The outcome and message that spread was that women whether under conditions of duress or choice who undergo sex selective abortions were punishable.

Government of India also takes progressive and effective steps to save girl child and to prohibit sex selective abortion. In 2006-07 women and Child Development Minister Renuka Chaudhury first introduced ‘Palna or cradle scheme in rural part of South and North India. Under the proposed ‘palna’ or cradle scheme, the government plans to open a centre in each district where parents

²⁸ Hindu, 5.3.2013

can leave their girl children if they do not want to bring them up themselves. "We want to put a cradle or 'palna' in every district headquarters. What we are saying to the people is have your children, don't kill them. And if you don't want a girl child, leave her to us," Minister of State for Women and Child Development RenukaChowdhury said in an interview.²⁹

*The 'palna' scheme has been proposed to be put in place during the 11th Five Year Plan as part of a slew of measures to fight the menace of female foeticide. Now at least the unwanted girl child will have a chance to live and perhaps some lucky ones will even find a new home and a new life somewhere else rather than ending up in the garbage dump in the backyards of hospitals across the country. In spite of all this and other problems that we fear might bedevil this scheme going forward. This scheme is WORTH it. And it deserves to be fully supported. Because it gives these unfortunate children the most basic right of any human being that is being denied to them most often in the wombs of their mothers itself- **The Right to Live.***³⁰

After published of 2011 provisional Census Report the Government has recognized that the problem of declining child sex ratio in India is not an isolated phenomenon but must be seen in the context of the low status of women and the girl child as a whole, within the home and outside. While its immediate reasons can be traced to increasing son preference as well as advances in technology that has encouraged sex selective abortions, concern of safety and security of the girl child along with the practice of dowry are no less responsible for it.

Accordingly, the Government has undertaken a number of measures to improve survival and status of girl children in the country. While programmes for improvement of nutrition benefit all children

including girl children, like the Integrated Child Development Scheme, National Rural Health Mission, Mid-day meal scheme etc., specific interventions for girl children include implementing the Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Prohibition of Sex Selection) Act, 1994, pilot cash transfer scheme of 'Dhanlakshmi', setting up a Sectoral Innovation Council for improving child sex ratio, and the pilot scheme 'Sabla' for a comprehensive Intervention for adolescent girls in the age group of 11-18, with a focus on out of school girls in select 200 districts of the country. Of the above, 'Dhanlakshmi' provides cash incentive, and the scheme does not discriminate on the basis of caste and creed.

I have completed the chapter with reference of the case study of Indar Singh who has fought against patriarchy to save her girl child. Indar Singh Bharti and his wife, who initiated a change before twenty seven years, when they literary gifted life to their new born baby girl. While everybody instructed them to kill their daughter, the couple decided to let their child live. He told "I don't remember what we were thinking them but it was my wife who took this decision. I only supported her. ...we were often taunted people talked in front of our babies. We have fought a lot...at last we are won. One of my daughters is civil servant and one of them is doctor. Now villagers told to us that they have to feel proud for our daughters..."³¹

²⁹ Times Of India. 2.7.2007

³⁰ ibid

³¹TOI-6.5.8

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION AND INFRINGEMENT OF ANIMAL RIGHTS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 29ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Environmental Degradation is one of the largest threats to the world today. The effects of degradation have been seen in long term ecological imbalance till date. This has led to extinction of various species and in-turn infringements on their rights. This paper examines International Conventions and Indian Laws to assess their adequacy providing safety for the same.

Keywords: *Environment, Degradation, Ecology, Rights, Climate*

The environmental degradation has become one of the largest threats of the present era; which disintegrates the earth and deteriorates the environment. It occurs when earth's natural resources are depleted and environment is compromised in the form of extinction of species, pollution to air, water and soil and deforestation. This effect of degradation can be seen in ecological imbalance till date. While environmental degradation is mostly associated with anthropogenic activities and has its impact on wildlife by infringement on Animal Rights has been caused in two ways such as Natural and anthropologic activities. The former happens due to landslide, tsunamis, hurricanes, and wildfire which completely decimate animal community. The latter is caused due to environmental degradation, loss of bio – diversity, ecological imbalance, deforestation and land use change and population. Infringement is also caused by illegal hunting, poaching, domestication of wild animals and birds, using animals for entertainment and experiments and pollution.

Chapter III of the Constitution of India dealing with Fundamental Rights does not have any direct bearing on environmental degradation and animal rights. But the judicial pronouncement of the Supreme Court of India and various High Courts of States of Indian Union have significantly contributed in giving a fresher and finer view to environment protection in the form of fundamental rights. The Courts, while dealing with environmental cases, have referred and based their judgment on Right to Equality (Article 14), Right to Life (Article 21) and Right to Freedom of Trade and Commerce (Article 19(1) (g))(Shastri, 2002).

The environmentalists give lesser importance to humans are defined as a recent addition to the livestock and are considered to have been a wholly disruptive influence on a world which was a paradise before their arrival(Malcolm, 1994). In this context, this paper attempts to describe the violation of rights of animals due to environmental degradation and infringement and to provide an overview of legal provision for protection of animals.

Environmental Degradation

The human transformation from hunter – gatherer to agriculturalist and pastoralist, led to change the environment to suit their living conditions (Bharucha, 2005). The environmental problems such as deforestation, extinction of species, acid rain, air, water and soil pollution, ozone layer depletion, over population and climate change (Chauhan, 2008) which affects life of all organisms. Natural forces like earth quake, wildfire, avalanche, storm and tsunami which not only affect the environment but also affects nearby flora and fauna.

Fossil – fuel power plants, refiners, and paper and pulp mills are major source of Sulphur Dioxide emission, which mix with Nitrogen Oxides emitted by automobiles and other vehicles causes Acid Rain. Acid deposition affects lake, forests, agricultural production, buildings, human health etc. (Visgilio & Whitelaw, 2007). The five basic ecological variables such as energy, matter, space, time and diversity are sometimes combined as natural resources. (Chauhan, 2008). The depletion in natural resources has become major focus for governments and UN which is considered to be a sustainable development issue (Baofu, 2013). Ozone layer depletion did not receive any international attention till 1974. It was first discovered above the Antarctica Circle by the British team in October 1984 and it was confirmed by NASA. For every 1% depletion of ozone layer, between 1 – 2 % more of harmful UV rays reach the earth's atmosphere (Jurgielewicz, 1996), become a global issue leading to implementation of Montreal Protocol (1987) on curtailing the production and phasing out the use of CFCs on the global scale which became the unique basis for the protecting of ozone layer was signed by more than hundred and fifty countries including India (Gupta, 2000). Human population was approximately 0.6 million in 1700 was increased to 6.1 million by the end of twentieth century. (Misra, 2009). The current massive degradation of habitat and extinction of species is taking

place because of human ingenuity (Sinha & Choudhary, 2008). Each individual requires space, energy and resources to survive. which results in environmental losses. If the human population is maintained at sustainable level, it would balance the environmental loss (Sinha, 2006).

Animal Rights

According to critics the word use is abuse and it has been suggested animal use to be made more animal friendly (Aaltola, 2012). Since the dawn of history, humankind has depended upon animals for survival. Considerable portion of the society have begun to exploit animals and activities such as circus and hunting, which use animals for entertainment and sport. While, people deny that animals should have rights beyond protection from abuse, activists believe that animals should have same rights as of humans (Hile, 2004). In 2002, Germany - the first EU member, included animals in the constitution and has the right to be respected and protected with dignity by the State. Switzerland a non EU member included in their constitution in 1992 which acknowledges animals as beings rather than things (The Guardian, 2002). However, animals that are the predecessors of humans, who use, own or exploit animals, face a number of challenges and infringements when it comes to their rights.

Animal Entertainment

The animal entertainment is historically deep rooted. Over a span of 700 years of the Roman circus, hundreds of thousands of elephants, lions, leopards, tigers, rhinos and many other species had been slaughtered, to entertain volatile citizen (Curnutt, 2001). The category of entertainment animals includes non-human animals trained to perform acts, fights and even to kill, animals in exhibition in circuses, movies, racing and many other forms of fighting. Use of animals for entertainment raises animal protection issues because taking animals out of their natural community and environment is always

harmful. Even more harmful is when they are prompted to perform actions which are not part of their natural lifestyle (Waldau, 2011). Animals show the evidence that they are natural performers, but the business of animal entertainment is synonymous of abuse (Bekoff, 2010). The forms of entertainment often cause animals great sufferings and over a century animal entertainments have become multi-billion dollars global industries (Grant, 2006).

Animal Experiments

Animal experiment is not an experiment in EU sense if it does not imply that the animals suffer. In technical sense experiment is an experiment even if animals do not suffer (Nordgren, 2010). When an animal becomes a subject of experiment, their interests are compromised or obligated (Orlans, 1993). The extremes in animal experiments are unrestricted support or radical rejection. These two positions, in all likelihood, are taken by only minority of the population. Majority of the population believes in animal experimentation principle so as to preserve human life (Fox & Mickley, 1986) and to do away with animal lives. More than 100 million animals – including mice, rats, frogs, dogs, cats etc., are killed in laboratories for biology lessons, medical trainings, curiosity – driven experimentation and chemical, food and cosmetic testing every year. In a welcome move the Govt. of India banned animal-tested cosmetics from being imported to India via a notification in The Gazette of India (PETA India, 2014). In 2013, 1.04 million animals were used for experiment in United States. In 2013, 4.12 million experiments on animals and 2.94 million without anesthesia in United Kingdom. In 2011, 3.33 million animals used in experiments and 128,873 animals were subjected to severe pain near, at, or above pain tolerance (Collins). In India, the National Centre for Laboratory Animal Sciences (NCALS) supplies approximately 50,000 animals to laboratories every year to 175 institutions including pharma companies and educational institutions (PETA India).

Hunting and Poaching:

Hunting and Poaching are activities associated with illegal killings of animals either for sport or entertainment or for other purposes. The use of animals in agriculture has a long history, hunting animals for their hides, meat and fur goes back to the very beginning of human race. It is 10 years before Hunting has become purely a sport or for entertainment and for the thrill of the hunt (Hile, 2004). It is a violent form of entertainment which rips animal families apart and leaves countless animals orphaned or badly injured (PETA). Poaching on the other hand affects local communities, wildlife population and environment. It is a crime fueled with black market transaction on animal parts (One Green Planet). Considered valuable Traditional Chinese Medicine recommends formulae containing tiger bones, antelope, and buffalo or rhino horn etc. Bear gall bladders is used in making Chinese herbal remedies which cures hepatic and biliary disorders (Feng, et al., 2009). Elephants are poached for ivory and tigers are poached for their skins. In 2012, 668 rhinos were poached in South Africa and the number increased to 946 in 2013. The existence of wild animals is severely affected by poaching and hunting which resulted in a deep reduction in their numbers. At the beginning of twentieth century the African elephants and Asian elephants are in few millions and a lakh approximately and presently it is around 405 lakhs to 7 lakhs and 35,000 to 45,000 respectively (Do Something). Illegal hunting and poaching increased the risk of the life of animals and made some of them as endangered species. The notification of endangered species makes them legally protected ones.

Illegal Trade:

Wildlife trade is a sale or exchange of flora and fauna by people for the pet or for horticultural trade or trades in diverse range in wildlife. In all, Southeast Asia contains 64,800 known species of which 2 percent are endangered species and it also accounts for

25 percent of the global value of illegal wildlife trade (Caballero-Anthony & Cook, 2013). It results in severe environmental and human impacts including extinction of species, a reduction in biodiversity and the spread of diseases (Liddick, 2011). The trade in wildlife and plants estimated to be worth billions of dollars involved. Simultaneously, when there is depletion in a targeted species, they also develop new smuggling methods and routes to avoid detection (Oldfield, 2003). In United Kingdom over one million plants, live and dead animals and their parts and medicines were produced from endangered species. The United States is also a major consumer of illegally trafficked animals and China is the largest market in the world for tiger bones, rhino horn, ivory and sea horse. The illicit wildlife trade in India amounts to \$ 1 billion (Liddick, 2011). The current regime to control wildlife trade is built upon Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora with an objective that the international cooperation is essential for the protection of certain species against over exploitation through international trade. It was signed in 1973 to control the trade of wild species listed in three Appendices. Appendix I – Species brink of Extinction, Appendix II – Danger of Extinction if trade is not prevented and Appendix III – subject to regulation by one country (Adams, 2004) (Shastri, 2002).

Climate Change

Climate change one of the paramount issues of present era, with potential devastation to biodiversity as well as disruption to human societies (Brodie, Post, & Doak, 2013). A change in temperature makes it warmer or cooler than normal which in turn permits species to increase or decrease in their population (Hardy, 2003). Climate change damages wildlife and causes certain species to lose ground, migrate or decline. Animals are living in a fragile ecosystem and slight changes can have far – reaching effects. Nevertheless, climate change marches hand in hand with loss of habitat to human

settlements and numerous ecological blunders of mankind causing stress on wildlife (Godrej, 2001). The atmospheric concentration of Green House Gases especially Carbon Dioxide increases the risk of climate change. Nearly eight billion tons of Carbon Dioxide is added every year (McNall, 2011), in the atmosphere.

Deforestation:

It is believed that 10,000 years ago 85 percent of the earth was covered with forest (Tripathi, Srivastava, & Pandey, 1993). It becomes a cause of degradation and infringement on animal rights when forest resources are depleted and exploited. In the tropics and sub-tropics, maximum reduction happens in Asia and Pacific because of population explosion. Deforestation is caused by forest fires, timber extraction, overgrazing of cattle, shifting cultivation, tourism, natural causes and land degradation (Joshi & Joshi, 2009). Apart from the causes, disappearance of vegetation in India is also caused through encroachment of forest land for agriculture and other purposes (Chandra, 2004). In India, deforestation affects two interest groups namely commercial and subsistence group. Commercial interest group has used forest to generate capital and on another hand subsistence interest group view forest as their basic support of their life and destruction of forest means the end of those benefits (Montagnin & Jordan, 2005). The rapid rate of environmental changes has led to loss of plants and animals, on a scale never before experienced in human history (Bee, 1993). It has been estimated that without the effects of deforestation, ten to fifteen species of the world are lost in a year. It is also estimated that nearly 40,000 species are lost each year due to deforestation and if it continues at same speed within fifty years the majority of plants and animal species will be eliminated (Horsman & Flowers, 2007). According to World Bank report as of 2012, in India, 687 sq.km thousands covers forest area and only 5.2 percentage of total land area is terrestrial protected area. As of 2014, in India, there are 712 threatened species

which includes mammals, birds, fishes and higher plants(The World Bank, 2015).

Loss of Biodiversity:

Human beings are dependent on biological resource for food, shelter, cloth, health, enjoyment of life and well-being therefore depleting natural resource is of great concern. Unfortunately there has been an unprecedented loss of biodiversity worldwide and it is mainly attributed to human population explosion(Kala & Silori, 2013). The loss of degradation of natural resources associated with loss of biodiversity is now widely recognized as one of the global environmental concern (Newton, 2007). The habitat loss is one of the main losses of biodiversity. This is due to clearing of forests, diversion of forest land to non-forest use, mining activities, construction of dams and transportation facilities in forest, overgrazing of domestic cattle population etc. The loss of marine biodiversity is caused by man-made factors (pollution due to industrial effluents and oil spills).The loss of aquatic biodiversity is due to over fishing, toxicity and industrial pollution.The habitat losses have vastly reduced and have fragmented population of several hundred species(Belsare, 2007).The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Forest Principles and Chapter 11 of Agenda 21, the United Nation Forum on Forests (UNFF) and many other international conventions and declarations are indicators for sustainable forest management(Newton, 2007). In spite of,many positive and encouraging developments that have arisen over the years, the approaches and responses have failed to stem the loss of biodiversity (Wood, Edwards, & Mang, 2000).High rates of forest loss and degradation are still occurring in many areas and are considered as major contributor to biodiversity loss which has been referred to global extinction crisis (Newton, 2007).

Environmental Pollution:

The actual livable space covering the earth is a thin layer of air, water

and soil called the Bio-sphere interact with each other to maintain a mutual balance called Ecological balance(Mathur, 1998). The human interference in the bio-sphere caused changes in chemical, physical and biological conditions in the environment affecting ecological imbalance has led to environmental pollution. The pollutions that affect environment are air, water, and soil, and noise, thermal, radioactive and maritime pollution. Air is the first and foremost susceptible component of our environmental pollution. It is a mixture of gases and the gaseous components of unpolluted air which has been polluted for thousands of years because of which even at remote location the air may be best described as a dilute polluted air (Agarwal, 2009). Water one of the most important source of human life has been exploited by man than any other resource for sustenance of his life. Pollution of water has emerged as one of the most significant environmental problems of the recent time. The gross pollution of water has its origin in urbanization, industrialization, defecation and increase in human population (Goel, 1997). Soil pollution, a global problem, is the accumulation of substances, native or introduced in soil at a level harmful for the growth of organisms, including microorganisms, plants, animals and humans. Hazardous substance find their way into the soil from domestic, industrial, municipal, mining and agricultural wastes like fertilizers and pesticides (Osman, 2014). Noise pollution, created by humans is no less hazardous than the toxic chemicals. It has added fuel to fire and has added greater consequences on human mind, animals and other living creatures. As soon as a being is born it comes in contact with noise pollution. This pollution is adversely affecting all walks of life, accelerating the environmental degradation(Mahandiyan, 2006). Radioactive pollution is the pollution caused due to blast of atoms. The radiation which is emitted from radioactive substance is a part of man's environment. Natural radiation arises from three sources: cosmic rays, environmental and internal radiation. Apart from natural radiation, man-made or artificial radiation such as x-rays, radioactive fallouts, atomic

explosion etc., causes pollution(Mathur, 1998). River receives huge amount of sewage, garbage, agricultural discharge, huge amounts of plastics etc., which ultimately ends upon sea causing marine pollution. Discharge of oil and petroleum products and dumping of radionuclide's waste into sea also causes marine pollution. In marine water major contributor of pollutants are oil and petroleum products, particularly when afloat on sea. Nearly 285 million gallons of oil are spilled (Joshi & Joshi, 2009). This environmental pollution poses a serious health issue for man as well as animals. Animals have been observed to suffer from eye and respiratory problem (Shafi, 2005). In 2012, it is estimated that 9 million people died from air, water and land pollution. World Health Organization reported that 7 million people die from air pollution alone, 24 percent of global disease and 13 percent of preventable deaths every year is caused due to air pollution (The World Bank, 2015).

Environmental Law:

The Constitution of India is amongst few in the world that contains specific provisions on environment. The Directive Principles of State Policy (DPSP) and Fundamental Duties explicitly enunciate the national commitment to protect the environment. Article 48A in DPSP declares, 'the state shall endeavor to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forest and wildlife of the country'. Article 51A (g) in Fundamental Duties imposes similar responsibility on every citizen, 'to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life, and to have compassion for the living creature'. These provisions in the constitution highlight the importance of environmental protection (Divan & Rosencranz, 2001).The term environment does not have any direct bearings in the constitution but the judicial interpretations have given significantly new dimensions for its protection under the ambit of Fundamental Rights. Article 21 of the Constitution of India which provides Right to

Life and Personal Liberty has been interpreted by Supreme Court and included healthy environment as a Fundamental Right. Various High Courts too, have considered that environmental degradation is a violation of fundamental right (Divan & Rosencranz, 2001).The material resource of community like forests, mountains, etc., is nature's bounty. They maintain ecological balance and they need to be protected for healthy environment (*Hinch Lal Tiwari v. Kamla Devi*).Any activity which pollutes the environment and makes it unhealthy, hazardous of flora and fauna is violative of Article 21 of the Constitution. It also guarantees Right to Equality under Article 14 to all persons without any discrimination. This indicates that any action of the State relating to environment must not infringe upon the right to equality(Shastri, 2002). The courts on various occasions have struck down official sanction in environmental matters (*Ajay Hasia v. Khalid Mujib Sehravardi*), which does not jeopardize the wildlife and natural wealth of the nation. It has been found that tanneries, acid factories, dye factories etc. are contributing to environmental pollution. It all relates to fundamental right to freedom of trade and commerce under Article 19 (1) (g) (Shastri, 2002). Some of the trades are carried on in a manner which endangers vegetation cover, animals, aquatic life and human health. But, time and again, it has made clear that this right has reasonable restriction (*Abhilash Textiles v. Rajkot Municipal Corp.*). In *Indian Handicrafts Emporium v.Union of India*, court held that, "animals play a vital role in maintaining ecological balance". A trade dangerous to ecology could be either regulated or totally prohibited. The right to trade should be balanced with demands of social interest (Leelakrishnan, 2005). A survey of the cases related to environment pollution and ecological imbalance reveals that most of the cases are filed under Article 32 and Article 226 of the constitution to the Supreme Court and High Courts of Indian Union respectively for the protection of fundamental right(Shastri, 2002).If anything endangers or impairs the quality of life, a citizen has a right to move to Supreme Court

under Article 32 (*Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar*). Any disturbance of the basic environment elements like air, water and soil, which are necessary for life, would be hazardous to life. Thus courts can levy fine and damages under Article 32 (*M C Mehta v. Kamal Nath*). Apart from constitutional provisions the Parliament of India has passed many other legislation such as: The Environmental (Protection) Act, 1986, The Air(Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981, The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974, The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980, Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972, The Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act, 1960, The Biological Diversity Act, 2002, etc. The International forum has taken resolutions on environment protection. 'The first ever declaration which is also known as 'Magna Carta of Environment', the Stockholm Declaration formulated 26 Principle to defend the environment for present and future generations with a fundamental goal of peace and social and economic development'. The Rio Declaration also known as Earth Summit was declared with the goal of establishing a new and equitable global partnership through the creation of new levels of cooperation among States, key sectors of societies and people (Nanda, 2015). Agenda 21 was one the instrument held at Rio. The Agenda 21 has various provisions for the management of toxic-chemical hazardous waste, solid and sewage waste and radioactive wastes. It also deals with the protection of oceans, seas, coastal areas, etc. and management of land resources, deforestation, sustainable development etc. The Bonn Convention recognized that wild animals are an irreplaceable part of the earth's natural system and it's an obligation of the mankind to take forward this legacy to future generations. There are many other conventions and declaration adopted by United Nations namely Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 1992, Vienna Convention on Ozone layer, 1985, Kyoto Protocol, 1997(Shastri, 2002), The Universal Declaration on Animal Rights (2011) REDD and REDD+ are the latest one and there is a

proposal to implement to Universal Declaration on Animal Welfare by United Nations.

Discussion:

A little meaningful effort, more care and friendly attitude towards up-keeping of ecological balance by each individual in the society could to sufficient to eliminate intricate environmental problem (Shafi, 2005). The Constitution of India with wide judicial interpretations has included Right to Life for animals as well. The Supreme Court recognized five fundamental principle including right to live with dignity for animals. It contended that all forms of life including animal life, come under Article 21 of the constitution. Right guaranteed under The Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act are statutory rights and it has to be elevated to fundamental right as done by other countries for animal honor and dignity (*Animal Welfare Board of India v. Nagaraja*). The Parliament of India should take initiative to include animals under the realm of Fundamental Rights. The golden triangle of fundamental rights which are Article 14 – Right to Equality were animals are also allowed to live with equal prominence as that of human beings, Article 19 (1) (g) – Right to Freedom of Trade and Commerce doesn't mean that environment should be compromised and there should be trade on animals for the greed of money, Article 21 – Right to Life where humans live with dignity, should also include animals and rights to be guaranteed as that of citizen of India.

The Precautionary Principle which says that in case of any possible threat to the environment, the foremost requirement is to take precautionary measure so as to prevent the environment being attacked and degraded. The Polluter Pays Principle (PPP) was first time used by Organizations for Economic Cooperation and Development which says that polluter has to bear the expenses for the damage caused by him to the environment and its victims (Nanda, 2015). The Supreme Court of India took bold

decision and evolved the rule to Absolute Liability in *M C Mehta v. Union of India* (Oleum Gas Leak case) as part of Indian Law overthrowing the rule of Strict Liability laid down in *Rylandv. Fletcher* and declared that new rule was not subject to any exception (Bangia, 2014). To evade from the consequences of PPP, the plans, projects and other developmental policies should be examined by Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) before they are executed. EIA examines the consequences and predicts the future changes in the environment by foreseeing and avoiding potential dangers (Leelakrishnan, 2005).

Conclusion:

The significant cause about environmental degradation and animal rights shows nexus between the two. It also shows how infringement is caused upon such animal rights. There is a need for Sustainable Development which was adopted in Rio Declaration with a goal of economic and social development in terms of sustainability of the country so that the present generation doesn't compromise the ability of future to meet their needs (Shastri, 2002). Therefore the concept of intergenerational equity which says that humans hold the nature and culture environment of the earth in a common both with other manners of the present generation and with other generation of past and future (Weiss, 1992) should be used so that our future generations enjoy the environment what we are enjoying today.

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SOCIAL DISCRIMINATION AND VIOLATION OF SCHEDULED CASTES HUMAN RIGHTS IN INDIA

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties

(Regd: 20ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Indian constitutional provisions guaranteed human values for its all subjects, but Scheduled Castes never permitted to enjoy such provisions by dominant caste society. In India, whenever Scheduled Castes tried to get such values have been attacked by so-called upper castes in the name of socio-religious sanctions.

Keywords: *Social, Discrimination, Human, Rights, castes*

The Dalits are Caste traditional India's principal category of social ordering and control is the most exhaustive and of noxious of all known exclusionary systems. The Hindu social order, particularly its main pillars, the caste system, and untouchability presents a unique case. As a system of social, economic and religious governance, it is founded not on the principle of the liberty (or freedom), equality and fraternity, the values which formed the basis of universal human rights, but on the principle of inequality in every sphere of life. The social order is based on three interrelated elements, namely, predetermination of social, religious and economic rights of each caste based on birth; the unequal and hierarchical (graded) division of these rights among castes; and provision of strong social, religious and economic ostracism supported by social and religious ideology to maintain the order.¹ Among the Backward Castes, Scheduled Castes are socially, economically, politically, religiously, and culturally oppressed. In the past many Scheduled Castes embraced Christianity during the British rule in India, these converts were given free food, clothes and education by the missionaries. Many of them got good educations and jobs.² Some made an attempt, in the 19th century, to disassociate themselves from the traditional callings of the community. They began to

imitate the dress and rituals of the Upper Castes³ in order to avoid ill-treatment, Scheduled Castes have often preferred to change their religion.

With the legacy of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar, the Indian constitution guaranteed to all citizens the fundamental rights and equal protection before the law. It provides a number of safeguards to Scheduled Castes to ensure their all-round development and protection against all kinds of the discriminations in India. But most of the provisions of the constitution have remained only on paper because their implementation has been faulty, half-hearted and inadequate and inequality, discrimination, exclusion and stigmatization can jointly contribute to the utter marginalization in India. No doubt, Scheduled Castes were never given in human rights or treated with dignity; hence those cannot be restored to them as such.⁴

The conflict or social conflict is a process in which a dispute takes place between two or more persons or groups or even communities on certain issues. Phenomenological, conflict is a state of mind in which an individual starts behaving in an abnormal way on certain issues. Conflict is not simply as a domain in itself but also a manifestation of the inherent properties of culturally based behavior in its continuing interaction with

the environment.⁵ Atrocities are to be given viewed as social and physical violence committed collectively or individually by those groups, castes and communities or their members who try to have more access to the existing resources and monopolize their status-superiority over others. The targets of such atrocities are those who have traditionally been degraded and deprived and who try to find a place other than that prescribed to them in the social structure. Such efforts are likely to disturb the status-quo and intercept the unlimited chances of the privileged one. Hence, violence and atrocities happening against them.⁶

The Scheduled Castes are subjected to various types of atrocities due to the caste Hindu's resentment against a number of government policies in general and the provision of reservations in education and jobs in particular adopted in their favor though the immediate causes involved in the commission of atrocities might be something else. Equally important in

this regard are a number of inherent social contradictions between caste Hindus and the Scheduled castes. However, very little is said about the growing resentments and protests shown by people of the schedule castes towards atrocities perpetrated on and various types of discriminations practiced against them. Such course of action is adopted by them more in self-defense or to gain self-respect and protect their dignity than in pursuing their social and economic development through the constitutional measures and other means. However, Scheduled castes are satisfied with the present level of their socio-economic development. They are in reality more interested in achieving their freedom from traditional bondage and liberation from the economic dependence on the upper castes and classes. These obviously attract the convulsing acts of the upper castes which are resented by the Scheduled castes. Thus, the desire and action of the Scheduled castes,

reaction to that of caste Hindus and others and then counter reaction of the Scheduled castes placed in the sequence of chain-responses are such that ultimately take the form of the human rights violations against Scheduled Castes.⁷ Since the days of the society formation people were confronted by different types of values in the form of intellectual values, religious values, moral values, economic values, and aesthetic values⁸ but in Indian Scheduled Castes have to lead their lives without many values of them in caste dominant society. The atrocities have increased during all the years because among the caste Hindus here grown increasingly jealous, intolerant and vindicate even to the little progress made by the Scheduled castes. In this context, this paper discloses about experiences of the Scheduled Castes in Indian caste dominant society towards socio-cultural, economic and political values.

The Republic of India(1950) ratified the International covenants on civil and political rights and on economic, social and cultural rights with certain declarations. A careful reading of these instruments would reveal the concern of the United Nations for Human Rights(1948)⁹as follows.

Subject	Indian Constitution	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
Equality before law	Art 14	Art 7
Prohibition of discrimination on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place or birth or any of them	Art 15	Art 2 (Para 1)
Equality of opportunity in matters of public employment	Art 16 (1)	Art 7 (sentence 2) Art 21 (2), Art 19
Freedom of speech, assembly association etc.	Art 19 (1)	Art 20 (1), Art 23 (4)
Protection in respect of conviction for offences	Art 20 (1)	Art 20 (2), Art 12 (1)
Protection of life and personal liberty	Art 21	Art 11 (2)
Prohibition of traffic in human beings and forced labour	Art 23 (1)	Art 3, Art 9
Freedom of conscience and free profession, practice and propagation of religion	Art 25 (1)	Art 4
Protection of interests of minorities	Art 29 (1)	Art 18
Rights of minorities to establish and administer educational institutions	Art 30 (1)	Art 22
Right to constitutional remedies (right to right)	Art 32 (1)	Art 26 (3)
		Art 8

- Beyond these provisions in the Constitution of India some special provisions are made for the Scheduled Castes. Article 17 has abolished to practice of untouchability. Article 330 and 332 gave provided for the reservation of seats to appointments, Article 338 has made provision for the special officer to investigate all matters relating to the safeguards for the Scheduled Castes and Article 46 relates to special care about the educational and economic interest of the Scheduled Castes.¹⁰
- National Commission for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes: Article 338 of the constitution requires constitution of the National Commission for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes for better protection of the rights of the members of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes.
- Caste Disabilities Removal Act 1950: The Act provides that when in a civil suit the parties belong to different persuasions, the laws of the religions of the parties shall not be permitted to
- operate to deprive such parties of any such parties of any property to much but for the operation of such laws, they would have been entitled.
- Protection of Civil Rights Act 1955: By this Act, enforcement of any disability arising out of untouchability has been made an offence punishable in accordance with the relevant provisions.
- The Bonded Labour System (Abolition) Act, 1976
- Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act 1989: An Act to prevent the Commission of atrocities against members of the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes for Constitution of special courts for trial of such offences, and to provide relief and rehabilitation to the victims.
- Protection of Human Rights Act 1993: The Act provides for the Constitution of a National Human Rights Commission, State Human Rights Commission, and Human Rights Courts for better protection of Human Rights.¹¹

The image of Dr.B.R. Ambedkar entered every Scheduled Castes colony and his philosophy spreads over the villages and became as philosophical foundation for Scheduled Castes lives. They have been asserting for their rights through democratic process. As long as there was no threat to their economic and social harmony, the

Upper Castes put up with the little changes that were visible in the village. Whenever the Scheduled Castes assert their rights, the Upper Castes attacked them.¹²

1. Social Rights Violation

a) Karemchedu

Karemchedu is a village of socially, politically dominated by the Upper Castes in Prakasam district of Andhra Pradesh. In Karemchedu, Scheduled Caste man Venkateswarlu was beaten by Upper Castes who questioned minimum wages and attacked on Scheduled Castes woman who tried to fetch water from village tank and tried to beat her but she escaped with the help of Scheduled Caste man. For that, they attacked Scheduled Castes in the eve of general elections in 1985. Karemchedu incident tells about Scheduled Castes have no Economic Rights and Social Rights.¹³

b) Chundur

Chundur is a village of socially egoist minded Upper Castes against Scheduled Castes in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh. In 1991, Scheduled Castes' student, Ravi entered cinema theatre and took seat upper row to Upper Caste boys. Upper Castes felt guilty and attacked Scheduled Caste boy and Upper Castes expelled from the village but Scheduled Castes people opposed such incident and it leads to attack on¹⁴and killed 13 Scheduled Castes.¹⁵Chundur incident showed the social ego of Upper Castes against the Scheduled Castes.

c) Suroth

Suroth is a village of social prejudices of Upper Castes against Scheduled Castes in Karauli district of Rajasthan. In Suroth, the scheduled caste youth Dayal visited hotel with his friends for tea but hotel proprietors belong to Upper Caste and served them tea without milk. It was questioned by Dayal and also complained against village Sarpanch for

not solving the problems. With these two incidents Upper Castes decided to attack the Dayal with their social power. They complained against Dayal in the pretext of theft of bicycle and organized caste panchayat and fined for Rs.3,000/- and sent to Jail. Suroth incident discloses about the question of Scheduled Castes self-dignity and self-respect against Upper Castes.¹⁶

d) Natham

Natham is a village of left oriented place which converted into casteist Manu minded village in Dharmapuri district of Tamilnadu. In Natham, Adi-Dravidian boy and Vanniar (OBC) girl love each other got marriage. But this is not digested to girls' father and he filed case against Scheduled Caste boy. By the dire witness of Divya her father got failure in the court and he felt ashamed and committed suicide. By this incident, Vanniar caste people attacked the Scheduled Castes three colonies and burnt houses for five hours and police personnel enjoyed that incident with castiest mind. Natham incident reveals that Scheduled Castes have no marriage rights against Upper Castes and Other Backward Castes.¹⁷

2. Economic Rights Violation

a) Belchi

Belchi is a village of Kurmi landlord's dominated place against Scheduled Castes in Bihar. In Belchi, in 1978, 11 Scheduled Castes were burnt alive by the Kurmi landlords for minimum wages. In 1985, again it had witnessed for massacre of Scheduled Castes by Upper Castes in the cause of fluking of leaves in disputed land. In this incident, 6 Scheduled Castes were killed and 5 were along with the 2 women seriously injured in order to get economic rights. Belchi incident speaks about the economic domination of Upper Caste landlords against Scheduled Castes who asked for the minimum wages and about extraction of forced labour.¹⁸

b) Golana

Golana is a Darbar Rajput Landlords dominated village since imperial British in Gujarath. In Golana, early stage, Scheduled Castes were worked with Darbar Rajput Upper Castes for agricultural works. In course of time, Scheduled Castes, Vankars achieved some skills and settled in textile companies. It resulted in deficiency of labourers in agriculture works of Upper Castes. Then it leads to aggression of Upper Castes and 5 Scheduled Castes were attacked to death. Golana incident reveals about the no rights for Scheduled Castes against economic tyranny of Upper Castes.¹⁹

c) Audatpur

Audatpur is a village of economically dominated by Upper Castes in Medak district of Andhra Pradesh. In Audatpur, the Scheduled Castes left village for better economic life to nearest city. It was resulted in deficiency of labourers for Agricultural works of Upper Castes landlords. So they imposed sanctions on the entre of Scheduled Castes into the streets of Upper Castes. Scheduled Caste workers who working for landlords entered main village attacked by landlords. There by, Scheduled Castes filed complaint against landlords. For that, landlords looted, and arson the colony. Audatpur incident speaks about no Scheduled Castes have right to work for their livelihood.²⁰

d) Laximpet

Laximpet is a village of socially dominated and Manu Minded Other Backward Castes against other weaker sections. In Laximpet, Scheduled Castes got some land along with the Other Backward Castes in the process of re-habitation.²¹But it was not digested by the Other Backward Castes and they tried to take over of that land. But Scheduled Castes opposed such activities. In this cause Other Backward Castes attacked and killed 5 Scheduled Castes. Laximpet incident tells

about no Scheduled Castes have right to possess of any kind of land against Upper Castes and Other Backward Castes.²²

e) Kairlanji

Kairlanji is village of Upper Castes has economically domination and weak Neo-Buddhists from Scheduled Castes in Vidarbha region of Maharastra. In Kairlanji, the Scheduled Caste man from Bhotomange family bought land. It was remained uncultivated for a longtime and used as passage by the villagers.²³The dispute was raised when Roshandaslal want to cultivate his land where Upper Castes want to laid road through his land. For some time, it was trailed in court. For that, Upper Castes had attacked the Roshandaslal family and murdered four members and two women were paraded in naked, and brutally murdered. Kairlanjiincident discloses about the Scheduled Castes have no economic and legal rights.²⁴

3. Political Rights Violation

a) Main, Barsimha, Chunibiga and Jahirbiga

Main, Barsimha, Chunibiga and Jahirbiga are the villages of East Bihar where Private Army, Savarna Liberation Front of Upper Castes against Moist Communist Centre which had been working for Poor Rights. MCC had been filled with the Scheduled Castes in cadre. So SLF want to take revenge against the Scheduled Castes by mass raping the women. According to SLF Commander in Chief, Ranabheer Singh, the rape of the Scheduled Castes women shows great effect on women and her family, throughout their life than the murder of Scheduled Castes men. Main, Barsimha, Chunibiga and Jahirbigaincidents discloses no Scheduled Castes have Rights in the Political/Ideological sphere.²⁵

b) Paramakudi

Paramkudi is a village of Upper Castes dominated and left awareness and Dalit concept among the Scheduled Castes in Ramanthapur district of Tamilnadu. In Paramkudi, Immanuel Sekaran was involved himself in revolutionary activities against caste oppression and organized Pallar youth in Ramanthapuram district. In course of time, Depressed Castes of Tamilnadu forced state for celebration of Immanuel Memorial. But it was not digested to Upper Castes, Thevars and they want to spoil the memorial of Immanuel Sekaran and removed the banners which were prepared by the Scheduled Castes. There by, Upper Castes spread over the rumors about arrest of SC/ST employees and John Pandian, MLA from PuthiyaTamilagam. The Scheduled Castes organized protest at five point junction with demand of release of arrested. But police personnel rounded the site and opened fire without any provocation from the protesters. It was resulted in killing of 3 and injuring of 30 Scheduled Castes. Paramakudi incident messaged that the no Scheduled Castes have Political/ Ideological Rights.²⁶

c) Vempeta

Vempeta is a village of factions which mixed with Left revolutionaries and Caste egos in Andhra Pradesh. In Vempeta, the Scheduled Castes youth organized RytuCooliSangam and it distributed government land for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes and Other Backward Castes but it was not digested to the Upper Castes and they tried to stop the distribution. Meanwhile, Naxalite group warned Upper Caste man BommaShivaiah and killed him. Then Upper Castes under the leadership of BuddaVengalareddy attacked Scheduled Castes colony and killed who supported RytuCooliSangam by accusing to death of BommaShivaiah. Vempeta incident speaks about no Scheduled Castes have Political/ Ideological Rights against Upper Castes.²⁷

4. Religious Rights Violation

a) Konalam

Konalam is a village of dominated fundamentalist Upper Castes and asserted Scheduled Castes in North Arcot district of Tamilnadu. In September, 1982 one Scheduled Castes women died and they want to move new burial ground for funerals though the streets of Upper Castes. Instead of old burial ground which was occupied by the Upper Castes. With the help of the Tahsildar, the Scheduled Castes succeeded in their efforts towards passage to burial ground. There by, Upper Caste Raddiars, stopped to give work for the Scheduled Castes and managed for their agricultural activities from neighboring villages and one Scheduled caste women and her three children were abducted and raped. The Scheduled Castes are fled for neighboring villages for continued attacks. Konalam incident tells about no Scheduled Castes have Right to perform death rites Rights as caste Hindus.²⁸

b) Papili

Papili is a village of social ego which is under the rule of Manudhrama in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. In Papili, Scheduled Castes tried to manage procession of Vinayaka idol to immerse along with the main streets of Upper Castes and Other Backward Castes. But Other Backward Castes objected the procession. Then Scheduled Castes complained to the police and organized immersion programme. Other Backward Castes attacked to Scheduled Castes houses, shops and looted all belongings in the pretext of those who not voted for Upper Caste candidate in local body elections. Papili incident tells about no Scheduled Castes have Religious and Political Rights against Upper Castes and Other Backward Castes in Indian society.²⁹

5. Conclusion

Traditionally, the different Scheduled Castes were employed in the various types of occupations and with their varying social and economic positions, were assigned different ranks in the overall ritual and social hierarchy of the caste system. One might think of these castes not as part of the organization of a village society contrary that the Scheduled Castes were associated in certain ways with social organization but their touch either with a person or a commodity belonging to a Caste Hindu was avoided as far as possible. Thus, there existed strata of castes on the basis of their farness from the clean castes. What governs the daily life of a Scheduled Caste is discrimination on the basis of caste manifests itself through visible practices such as a separate drinking water wells, segregated housing colonies, separate burial grounds, segregated places of worship, separate seating of children during mid-day meals at school, denial of taking food from scheduled caste cooks in mid-day meals at schools, prohibition of dressing like others do, prohibition of inter-caste dinning and marriages, or mounting a horse during a wedding, amongst scores of other forms. Discrimination also manifests itself through non-visible forms in the shape of caste prejudices that can be heard in the spoken language through idioms and phrases. The failure of the Indian state and its instruments to cope with the problems arising in the process of socio-economic change in a society with adult suffrage and equality of opportunity and status, among other similar objectives provided in our constitution, has led to rising expectations on the one hand, and growing consciousness of the exploitation and indignity in social relations, on the other. Such a combination has inevitably led to strong resentment expressing itself in violence. Unless these infirmities are removed and progress made towards the creation of a truly just society and non-exploitative social order, violence is not only likely to continue but may get aggravated.

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RIGHTS TO REFUGEE: JUSTICE FOR ALL

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 31ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

One day you wake up and find you have to leave your home because of some civil war. How helpless it is! This paper shall deal with theoretical and practical refugee rights, considering emotional aspect and laws of different countries. Dealing issues of asylum; concluding needs of change in law.

Keywords: *Human, Rights, Justice, Refugee, India*

We love our lives so much, isn't it! And the lives of near and dear ones are also so precious to us. We wake up in morning get ready for our work places, earn our lives and in the evening when we return back, we feel so relaxed that we are going back to our homes. Home, the safest place where we can do anything and everything we want. But just imagine if you don't have that home or you got no way to get back home? Thinking such situation even makes us so restless. That restless feeling is what a refugee feels every day. This is the biggest reason that makes it an issue of concern.

This paper shall deal on emergence of the "refugee" and current scenario of refugee under 3 heads, first, history and development of refugee law, this topic shall deal with league of nation and United Nation Organization; second various international agencies; third situation in India, finally concluding the paper.

Laws are made by us, we the people. They are made just for our convenience, so that we could live our lives in peace. So the nature of law should be such that it suits majority and should do just for all. Fundamental rights are the only thing that are enforceable in courts worldwide and protects us from unjust

situations. And the basis of all fundamental rights comes out of the principle of right to equality. And that's the biggest issue for refugees that they are discriminated.

A state is not free to treat its nationals as it please despite the fact that it's sovereign. The greatest impact of human rights law has been to erode the absolute control which a state has in its classic period¹. International human puts a check that in exercising its sovereignty any state do not takes away the fundamental rights of the individuals. Refugee law is a matter of 'municipal law'² as well as to international laws, as refugees flee from one country to another so it's to scratch out any confusion as to what laws should apply on him (i.e. origin country law or laws of the country where he is residing) refugee laws are made.

According to Article 1 of the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees, a refugee is someone who has fled his or her country "owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a

¹ Agarwal H. O, international law and human rights, central law publication, Allahbad; 4th edition(2014) ISBN 978-93-81292-51-8; page:

² Here the word municipal is used and not state because municipal has some other meaning in strict sense

particular social group or political group opinion.”³

The term ‘Refugee’ has a particular meaning in international law and its legal definition is laid down in the United Nations 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees⁴ (to be referred to as “1951 Convention”) and its 1967 Protocol⁵. Article 1 paragraph 2 of the 1951 Convention defines the ‘refugee’ as “A person who owing to well founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country.”. Therefore, the need to give due importance to humanitarian and human rights aspects in dealing with refugees cannot be over-stressed.

“Thus, it may be noted that there are well-defined and specific grounds, which have to be satisfied before a person can qualify to be a ‘refugee’. These grounds are *well-founded on fear of persecution* and considerations of a number of factors which may operate individually or collectively”⁶.

History and development of refugee law

Refugees are victim of gross violation of human rights from a long time. The reason for same is that they don’t have any security any of state. So to check on their basic human rights international conventions and protocols came into picture. International action for Refugee did not start until 1920. Assistance to Refugee was provided by Dr.

³ Definition as per UNO

⁴ J.Fitzpatrick, “Revitalising the 1951 Refugee Convention”, *Harvard Human Rights Journal*, vol. 9 (1996), pp.229-53.

⁵ See Goodwin Gill, note 1; Pirkko Kourula, *Broadening the Edges : Refugee Definition and International Protection Revisited* (Hague, 1997)

⁶ The Refugee in International Law Third edition Guy S. Goodwin-Gill, Professor of International Refugee Law, University of Oxford, ISBN 978-0-19-928130-5 Guy S. Goodwin-Gill & Jane McAdam

Nansen. His contribution helped in creation of the world public opinion in favor of creation of international machinery for the protection and assistance of Refugee. League of nation on June 27, 1921 established the office of high Commissioner for Russia refugee. Doctor Nansen was appointed the first high commissioner on August 20, 1921. He devised a so call League of nation passport commonly known as Nansen passport; give the owner the right moves freely across Nation boundaries. Nansen passport was adopted by more 50 states. He was awarded leadership, vigor and spirit in the service of refugee. League of nation could not stop another world war and the problem of refugee even increased by Second World War.

United Nations relief and Rehabilitation administration (UNRRA)

The problem of Refugee started after Second World War. Many people after world war became Refugee. United Nation organization formed after world war formed UNRRA on 9 November 1943 signed by 44 Nations. Main objectives of this agreement included the release, maintenance, rehabilitation and repatriation of United Nation nationals who had been displaced as a result of war. However many of them were reluctant unwilling to be repatriated, either because they had lost all ties with their countries of origin or because of change political conditions. UNRRA concentrated on distributing relief supplies, such as food, clothing, fuel and medicines. It also provides relief services with train personal and aided agricultural and economic rehabilitation.

International agencies

International Refugee organization

The International Refugee Organization (IRO) was founded on April 20, 1946 to deal with the massive refugee problem created by [World War II](#). This Special committee on Refugee and displaced persons was established by economic social council. A Preparatory Commission began

operations fourteen months previously. It was a United Nations specialized agency and took over many of the functions of the earlier United Nations Relief and Rehabilitation Administration. In 1952, its operations ceased, and it was replaced by the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)⁷

United Nations high Commissioner for refugees

The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees was established on December 14, 1950 by the United Nations General Assembly with a three-year mandate to assist Europeans displaced by World War II. The following year, on July 28, the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees was adopted. It still constitutes the key legal document in defining who constitutes a refugee, their rights, the legal obligations of states, and the basic statute guiding UNHCR's work. The Convention entered into force on April 22, 1954, merging previous international instruments relating to refugees, and still presents the broadest codification of the rights of refugees at the international level. Unlike former international refugee instruments, which concerned specific groups of refugees, Article 1 of the 1951 Convention approved a single definition of the term "refugee," which accentuated the protection of persons from political or other forms of persecution. Accordingly, a refugee is someone who is unable or unwilling to return to his or her country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political⁸.

The general assembly on December 3, 1949 adopted the Statue of the office of the United Nation high Commissioner for refugees. UNHCR came into existence on January 1,

1951. UNHCR was set up in Italy for a period of 3 years. Later general Assembly decided to prolong the mandate for the period of 5 years. Made it renewable beginning from January 1, 2000 in the year 2000, general assembly resolved to continue UNHCR for a period of 5 years.

The most important International instruments related to problems of Refugee and the convention relating to status of Refugee of 1951 which was adopted after considering that the charter of United Nations and Universal Declaration of Human Rights have affirm the principles that human beings enjoy fundamental rights and freedoms without discrimination. The convention came into force on April 22, 1954 on June, 15; the convention had 136 state parties.

According to Para 2 of article 102 those persons who have become decision support January 1, 1950 in order to widen scope of convention, status of refugees was completed in 1967 which is under Para 2 of article 1 omitted the expression " as a result of such events." legal status of Refugee has been defined in the above two international treaties also define rights and duties of Refugee and make provision for various aspects of the everyday life including desire to work, education and social security and the right to travel documents, since not in position to use their own National passport. Main provisions of the convention of 1951 are as follows:

- Personal status of Refugee
- Movable and immovable property
- Civil rights
- Treatment of refugees
- Illegal entry of refugees
- Expulsion of refugees
- Travel documents
- General applications
- Prohibition of expulsion or Return
- Access to courts

⁷ Holborn, Louise Wilhelmine; *the International Refugee Organization, a specialized agency of the United Nations: its history and work, 1946-1952*. London: Oxford University Press, 1956.

⁸ Sert, Deniz Şenol. "United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees." *The Encyclopedia of Global Human Migration* (2013)

Present international scenario

Talking about the most recent case of Paris, people of Paris faced a traumatic Attack by terrorist. Many people were killed in this attack on 14th November 2015. The reason which is guessed behind attack is religious. Three-year-old Aylan Kurdi, found dead in Turkey near the beach this incident got viral on Twitter with hash tag humanity shore away. Famous artist Charles made cartoon sketches of this incident in which he spoke controversial about Islam religion. Many Muslim youngsters over there are under training of IS, and this pictures of Charles seems to be the reason behind Paris attack. Why people puts religion on the one side of the balance and basic human rights of others on the other side. No doubt right to religion if one of the fundamental rights but every right has its importance and one must have a clear decision as to which right should dominate which. Taking someone's life is it justifiable because someone out of a huge population has said something about your religion. Such intolerance is increasing these days which is not acceptable neither could be control single handedly by any international agency. Till the time the mentality thinking approach towards others right changes no one of us can do anything.

The main motto of United Nation organization is to prevent the conversion of cold war into physical war and such attacks by a few terrorists is declining the motive of UNO. It is the need of hours for UNO not only to make laws for Refugee but also to prevent the causes which let the persecution occurs in the country. UNO is the most important and most powerful international Organization and should positively take steps to cure search situations that may lead to the problem of Refugee.

People have to leave their origin country due to fear of persecution and to travel some other country in search of basic needs of human, another country where he is not

welcomed. Condition of Refugee pathetic and very pity, due to some riots or attack, they become homeless and helpless

Situation in India

India is neither the party to the refugee convention of 1951 nor protocol of 1966. Parties to the refugee convention have not been considered by the government of India from time to time standards in 1967 and 1992-94, history of external affairs considered conventions and protocol and a ' particular design for Refugee protection drafted in euro heightened centric context.' dJ instruments according to ministry and design family Steel with individual cases in contrast situation of Mars influx which country has been facing. Similar argument has been given by the other developing countries as well. Not being a party to convention is not legally bound to provide right to refuse explain down in about instruments. India in the past has not connected any domestic legislation in relation to Refugee despite the fact that it has invalid please provide it refuse to the people link from countries like Tibet, Bangladesh and Afghanistan. That is fairer approximately 1, 76 000 refugee is in India, epass maturity of home innocence of any law is not clear as to what shall be legal status of refugees and to be properly identified . The legislation is likely to have enriching impact on the refugee issues but no serious am tired anil opposite the drafting and adoption of such loss is essential. legislation is also essential to safeguard the security of the country.

India in Past has not enacted any domestic legislation in relation to refugee despite the fact that it has invariably provided Refugee to the people fleeing from countries like Tibet, Bangladesh Shri Lanka Afghanistan. It has been estimated that they are approximately 1, 76, 000 Refugee is in India, the vast majority of whom are Afghans. Absence of any law it is not clear up to what shall be the legal status of refugees and what light shellac your to them.

The constitution provides that some of the fundamental rights under part 3 of the Constitution shall be available to 'all person' and consequently, there's a will able to Refugee as well.

INDIA'S MEASURES FOR FULFILLING INTERNATIONAL OBLIGATIONS:

India has taken numerous steps and measures to fulfill its international obligations in respect of refugees. Some of the more important ones merit detailed mention.

Entry into India

The Government of India have followed a fairly liberal policy of granting refuge to various groups of refugees though some groups have been recognised and some other groups have not been, often keeping in view the security concerns of the nation. However, the emerging trend of past refugee experiences bear testimony to the fact that entry into India for most refugee groups is in keeping with international principles of protection and *non-refoulement*. Further, such entry is not determined by reasons of religion or any other form of discrimination.

Work Permits

There is no concept of work permits in India, although refugees who are granted residence permits do find employment in the informal sector, without facing any objection from the administration. In fact, Tibetan refugees have been granted loans and other facilities for self-employment. Similarly, most Sri Lankan Tamils have been granted freedom of movement within the camp areas, enabling work facilities for them as casual labour. Similarly, Chakma and Afghan refugees have also been engaging in gainful, even if it is in minor forms of employment.

Freedoms

Generally, refugees are allowed freedom concerning their movement, practice of religion and residence. In case of refugees whose entry into India is either legal or is subsequently legalised, there is limited interference by the administration regarding these basic freedoms. However, those refugees who enter India illegally or overstay beyond permissible limits, have strict restrictions imposed upon them in accordance with the statutes governing refugees in India i.e., The Foreigners Act, 1946, Foreigners Order, Passport Act etc.

Detention

A refugee may face detention as soon as he/she illegally crosses the international border into India. It is pertinent to appreciate that the refugee has at that moment just entered an unknown country, after fleeing to save his/her life from his/her own country of origin. He/she may have undergone severe trauma of loss of family and friends in his/her homeland or en route India. The refugee in such situations may be unable to explain his/her background during initial interrogation, giving rise to apprehension on the part of local authorities regarding the genuineness of his/her subsequent refugee claim. He/she may be suspected to be a spy or infiltrator in the light of inconsistent statements that may have been made by him/her to the authorities. This is bound to be further compounded if the refugee is not in possession of the usual 'travel documents'. In fact, it would be very unreasonable to expect him/her to possess valid travel documents, considering the background of his/her having to escape from his/her own country. The same may result in further interrogation and continued detention pending registration of FIR (First Information Report, which is usually the basis of the start of 'investigation').

Lack of Medical Aid in Detention

While in detention the refugee may be suffering from some physical ailment requiring immediate medical attention. In the event that the detaining authority does not provide the requisite medical aid, the same may result in devastating consequences. In some cases court's directions can be obtained and appropriate medical attention and treatment given to the refugee. Here again, NGOs can play a very useful role. In the case of a Palestinian refugee who was detained at the international airport in New Delhi consequent to a deportation order pending against him, a writ petition was filed to obtain the Delhi High Court's order that the refugee be provided at least the basic necessities like food and medical care. Knowledge of such cases would help security personnel to foresee and where necessary, seek the help of an agency like the UNHCR or a local NGO to render necessary help to the refugee.

Right of asylum

This part of the paper examines how extradition and asylum interrelate "where the person whose extradition is sought is a refugee or asylum-seeker, or if an asylum application is filed after the wanted person learns of a request for his or her extradition. While international refugee law does not in itself stand in the way of extradition, its principles and requirements impose certain conditions on the lawfulness of extradition, which need to be taken into consideration by the requested State. Conversely, information which comes to light in the extradition process may affect the credibility of an asylum application and/or give rise to the application of an exclusion clause in the asylum procedure. Such information may also cast doubt on the validity of a refugee status determination, which in turn may result in its cancellation or revocation."⁹

⁹ <http://www.unhcr.org/3fe84fad4.pdf> (page 10 ¶2)

The word asylum is Latin and ride from the Greek word 'asylia' which means inviolable place. Asylum and refugee status are special legal protections available to people who have left their home country for their own safety and are afraid to return. the term refers to those cases where the territorial state declines to surrender a person to requesting state, and provides shelter and protection in its own territory. Asylum Involves two elements firstly, shelter, which is more than a temporary refuge; and secondly, degree of active protection on the part of authority in control of the territory of asylum. These two elements distinguishes asylum from immigration

‘The right of asylum falls into three basic categories: territorial, extraterritorial, and neutral. Territorial asylum is granted within the territorial bounds of the state offering asylum and is an exception to the practice of extradition’¹⁰.

Extraterritorial asylum refers to asylum granted in embassies, legations, consulates, warships, and merchant vessels in foreign territory and is thus granted within the territory of the state

Conclusion

It can be easily seen from the foregoing paragraphs that India notwithstanding its own security concerns, particularly in the last couple of decades, and pressure of population and the attendant economic factors, continues to take a humanitarian view of the problem of refugees. Even though the country has not enacted a special law to govern ‘refugees’, it has not proved to be a serious handicap in coping satisfactorily with the enormous refugee problems besetting the country. The spirit and contents of the UN and International Conventions on the subject have been, by and large, honored through executive as well as judicial intervention. By this means, the country has evolved a practical balance between human

¹⁰ Smith, G. "Right of Asylum." *LQ Rev.* 27 (1911): 199.

and humanitarian obligations on the one hand and security and national interest on the other. It is in balancing these interests, which may sometimes appear to be competing with each other, that the security and law enforcement agencies face day-to-day challenges. If and when a separate 'Refugee Law' for the country is enacted, it is important that this aspect is given due consideration. It is important that security and enforcement officials do not overlook both the legal as well as the underlying human angles inherent in the 'refugee' situation, especially the latter.

few who wants to create fear and spread terrorism amongst people.

Basically, the problem on refugee issue is not that we lack of basic laws somewhere. If that would be the issue, it would not be a great deal for UNO to make some international agency to seek ways out. The situation is that we are flooded with endless number of international agencies and protocols but the problem is that following or going by that norms are not really easy. Let's assume that following protocol we deal with the problem of refugees but what about limited resources present in our country. India is not a part of IRO, it has not sign the agreement and the biggest reason for same is that the India is already trying to deal with huge population of 121 cores of its own how can it handle some more immigrating every year. When someone is not given the title or status of citizen than what should be his rights being in territory of India. Before going into the problems of asylum or basic human rights we have to look into our own problems like population, security etc.

Sometimes right of asylum is compromised by some missing travel documents and national security. Its time when we should not only provide facilities to refugee but to take strict action on international level and make every country so strong that no one can take away sovereignty and create situation of fear that let to refugee to leave their own country and roam to any other country. Let's make UNO such a strong organization that no one could force anyone to leave their country. After all the rule should be of majority who wants peace and not of those

ECONOMIC INJUSTICE, VIOLENCE AND VIOLATIONS

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 13ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The Paper is an essay where different land allotment policies of Odisha Government studied in the context of Human Rights Violation. In a simple line People's Land rights in terms of economic injustice and different kind of violence arise out the government policies and infringement of state, local and illegitimate powers.

Keywords: *Revenue Acts, Social Problem (Servitors), Violence and Violations*

Economic injustice is a violation of human rights that causes violence, although the preamble of the Constitution of India guarantees economic justice to all its citizens and the Constitution (Forty second amendment) Act 1976 enshrines Socialist feature in its Preamble for the weaker sections of the society. The fundamental concept of Human Rights dates back to the doctrine of natural rights founded on natural law. Man born free and he aspires a life of free thought with a decent life. Right to personal security, personal liberty and all other rights by the by conceived were appended to the basic concept of human rights. Man gradually progressed so as to reach the height of civilization that has been the world culture of the present day, although it lacks rationalization in equitable distribution of the limited resources bestowed upon the living being for its use as yet. Human rights not merely circumscribed to cater justice to an individual or a group of individuals by lessening the loss or damage caused, but it was thought of to be indispensable to place a check for further deterioration so that on that base one should have a healthy and peaceful life. Thus social and political justice pledged by the preamble

of the Constitution to be secured to all citizens will be incomplete unless first economic justice is guaranteed to all.

From a nomadic life man reached a settled life based on agriculture and now in a position to make use of the advanced science and technology. Human rights as a part of social sciences are supplementary to material sciences for equitable distribution of the limited resources all around. Development in agriculture builds the economic infrastructure for industrial growth of any country. But matter of concern land titles in India are in mess. Most of the criminal offences are the outcome of the civil irregularities. D.C. Wadhwa, emeritus professor of the Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics says, "India's land records are fiscal in nature and presumptive in character. The title to land is only incidental"(1). Giving his views on McKinsey's estimate that 1.3 per cent growth is lost every year because of land and property market distortions. Professor D.C. Wadhwa says, "India could be losing 1.3 per cent economic growth a year, if you consider the productive man-hours lost in litigation proceedings, and the fact that doubts over

ownership inhibit supply of capital, thus raising the cost of credit for agriculture”(1).

Vulnerable groups according to Human Rights- Rights of Tribals/Indigenous rights: Rights of indigenous people, Ethnic groups who are natives to a land or region (2). India basically being an agricultural one and most of its people depend upon agriculture for their living, naturally study and analysis on land laws need be systematic to achieve the Socialistic feature of the Constitution. Inadequacy in land related and socio-religious laws and lack of due care in interpretation and application of the Acts extant worsen the plight of some ethnic groups, who are a minority making them economically handicapped and loss of livelihood.

1. Revenue Acts

We may read the following Acts to make the point lucid.

Odisha Land Reforms Act 1960: Whereas it is necessary to enact a progressive legislation relating to agrarian reforms and land tenures consequent on the gradual abolition of intermediary interest (3). The Act makes clear provision for conferring higher rights on the real cultivator. The Act, therefore has come with time schedule for effecting these reforms with a view to conferring higher rights on the true cultivators, put an end to absentee landlords fix ceiling units in respect of agricultural holdings determine surplus lands and settle the same with landless people (3).

Odisha Estate Abolition Act 1951:Whereas in pursuance of the Directive Principles of State Policy laid down by the Constitution of India, it is incumbent on the state to secure economic justice for all (4).

Section 8 (3) of the OEA Act reads as: Any person who immediately before the date of vesting held land under an intermediary on favorable terms for personal service rendered by him to such intermediary shall, from the

date of vesting, be discharged from the conditions of such service and the land may be settled with him in such manner and under such terms and conditions as may be prescribed (4).

Provided that nothing in sub section 3 shall apply to a trust estate which is vested in the state on or after the date of coming into force of the Odisha Estate Abolition (Amendment) Act, 1970(4).

2. Social Problem (Servitors)

Making an analysis of the position of the traditional temple priests and their allies, we may read the Odisha Hindu Religious Endowments Act 1951 as:

Any jagir or inam granted to an archaka, sevak, service holder or other employee of a religious institution for performance of any service or charity in or connected with a religious institution shall not be deemed to be a personal gift to the said archaka, service holder or employee but shall be deemed to be a religious endowment (5).

Traditional servitors, basically from the OBC, ST and SC communities of Odisha, associated with the religious concerns since the pre-vedic era have been earmarked some landed property in course of time by the ex-feudal state chiefs in shape of remuneration for the services they render hereditarily to the Deity. These people have been the real agriculturists and tillers of the land for earning their livelihood. As per the statute interpreted so far by various authorities, Section 8 (3) of the OEA Act is not applicable to the traditional servitors and their allies engaged in the services to the Deity, as they do not render personal services on favorable terms to the intermediary. Sevapuja etc to the Deity are not considered as a personal service to the Deity as the status of the Deity as an intermediary in that respect is different from that of the mortal ex-intermediaries. Unlike, servitors any person who holds the land under an intermediary for rendering personal services to the

intermediary shall be discharged from the conditions of his service and the land may be settled in his name. A traditional servitor tenant and other than a traditional servitor both possess the land for rendering personal services to the intermediary. They both developed the land since their forefathers to the present cultivable state of the land putting their personal hard toil. The land in question has been in shape of remuneration to both the tenants because that was the procedure of payment of remuneration or wages then. Unlike other tenants, land title for the servitors is highly fluctuous and elastic and it is ambiguous to a common man's understanding. It is very difficult to establish in the court of law, the title extant in the present scenario, as the land grabbers are tactful to transfer the ownership in a camouflaged fashion to establish their rights over the land.

Below are mentioned some of the villages where the servitors have been forcibly ousted from their lands of possession unauthorizedly either partially or wholly. There are cases where servitors are rendering their services but no land title maintained as it was initially; inelasticity of the land title incidentally eroded. Often the matter is subjudice for pretty long period. And there are cases where Government is not responsive to accord protection to these vulnerable ethnic groups for their just cause. Village Pantikharisasan, Kaibalyapur, Haripur, Hatiasila, Badhisahi, Golagaon, Gothabana, Damasahi, Gamei, Gotisahi, Puania, Natugaon, Saluni, Nagamunduli, Itamati, Melama, Balugaon, Sampada, Khuntupada (Khandapara), Jogiapalli, Kanchanabelli, Malisahi, Bhaliadihi, Panchumu of Nayagarh district and many other villages of Odisha witness disturbances and violence over the issue. It may be worth noting, there is not a single village in Odisha where land disputes more or less not arisen and because the servitors could not fight the situation, the matter closed ex parte in some cases. Servitors in some places have to sell their own recorded land to meet the expenses

of Court cases for the lands litigated by the land grabbers.

Huge common property and funds created out of the landed property taken away by the land grabbers from the servitors and due to lack of proper management of the property so taken and the funds so raised leads to severe violence that causes wastage of precious productive man hours and loss of life mostly in the rural Odisha. Servitors in their dwelling villages are prone to be litigated concerning their cultivable land. It is presumed by most of the common people that the servitors can only use the land in question and can be ousted any time as they like, even though the servitors have been cultivating the lands ancestrally. Traditional servitors have got no voice in the locality. Their right to freedom of speech and expression under Article 19 (1) (a) are infringed. Their identity in the locality is trivial and unaccountable, though their contribution to the society is age-old. Land grabbers and their associates may be accused of snooping of the servitors.

Traditional servitors have been engaged in their priestly work since the prehistoric era diffusing a healthy socio-religious atmosphere in the society. They work for maintaining brotherhood and a peaceful environment in the society and inculcate people to maintain a life, free from worries and anxieties with an ethically justifiable way of life. They are the cradle of the aggrandized temple culture, we come across now. They never leave the temple even if the temple's income falls for some reason. As hereditary functionaries they are the most depended upon. Sevyatas would not hesitate to lay their lives for the cause of temple. They visualize an ideal society which could show the path of redemption to all. It advocated an egalitarian principle of devotion and a different concept of ritual pollution (6). If Odisha Government could conduct an impartial enquiry or any philanthropic Agency could make a detailed study and bring out a report, the real picture about the plight and predicament of the

innocent servitors would come to light. In order to make the mission a success an atmosphere of fearlessness be enliven among the servitors to get a realistic response from them.

3. Violence and Violations

3.1. Fundamental Rights

Article 14- Right to equality before law: the state shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India (7). Section 8(3) of the OEA Act is not applicable to the trust estate of the religious shrines, whereunder the servitors and other concerned hereditarily render seva-puja to the Deity, even though they discharge their duty and remunerated in shape of landed property since long. The wages or remuneration procedure here may be contemplated similitude to the minimum wages Act now, but the Act is not applicable to them as the religious and the charitable institutions are not coming under the purview of a farm/factory or a shop or commercial establishment, either. However, minimum food, health care, shelter, education for their children and all other basic and dire needs for them and their family members are an inevitability. Traditional servitors do not desire more than the existing land already earmarked to them defeating the law extant, section 8 (3) of the OEA Act, but they contravene the fact that misinterpretation i.e. with an evil intent of designing to establish that these people are deficient to the task assigned and in the process the lands in their possession made litigated, unnecessarily drags them to violence. State being the guardian to these vulnerable and minority groups, need to stand by them for justice and their rescue, in order that these socially and economically weaker people do not suffer, but we do not feel such a sympathetic and judicious gesture from the state government. Traditional servitors as poor agriculturists and the real cultivators of the land if evicted from their agricultural holdings, it amounts to deprecation of their source of livelihood.

Article 21- protection of life and personal liberty: no person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law (7). The servitors are deprived of their right to livelihood established according to law, i.e. section 8(3) of the OEA Act, comes under the purview of violation of Article 21 of the Constitution. The Supreme Court in its decision rendered in *Raja Vir Kishore Deo v. State of Odisha* held that the Act so enacted has not taken away the right of Raja of Puri as *sewaka* and also it does not affect religious rights of Raja (8). We can analyze the situation in the context of the traditional servitors that as *sewakas* in the various temples of Odisha, their right to enjoy the title and possession of lands cannot be alienated from them. In the state of Himachal Pradesh *v Umed Ram*, the Supreme Court further elaborated that right under Article 21 embraces not only physical existence of life but the quality of life and denial of that right would be denial of the life as understood in the richness and fullness by the ambit of the Constitution (8). Right to live with dignity is a fundamental right as held by apex Court in *Menaka Gandhi v Union of India* AIR 1978 SC 597. Article 21 advocates protection of life which is embodied with the guarantee of livelihood. Even though the servitors engaged in a religious charitable activity, they have every right to live with dignity and decency. The lands in the question under their possession for offering *seva-puja* to the Deity though belongs to the religious institution as per the statute, in the name of religious activities or any other malafide intent of some unruly and undisciplined people, it cannot be withdrawn from them for common use making the servitors economically crippled. It amounts to snatching away of the rice bowl from them. As citizens of India, servitors have got the basic right to earn their livelihood for a decent living free from malnutrition and unhealthy environment. The lands in the question withdrawn from the servitors tantamount to making them loss of livelihood leading to a miserable, meaningless and incomplete life. With the expansion of the

number of families, lands allotted to them initially have been portioned even to approximately half an acre or below in most of the families. The homestead lands where these people stay in are also not of theirs and they have to manage themselves in one thatched house, (bed room-cum kitchen) about four members of a family. Charitable institutions not being the commercial establishments, Minimum Wages Act not applicable to them, but servitors who have been remunerated in the shape of landed property hundreds of years ago cannot be deprived of their rights of livelihood guarantying right to life under Article 21 of the Constitution. Their humble submission is that there should not be any deviation from the statute; government is only to initiate steps and be watchful for application of section 8(3) of the OEA Act in letter and spirit. In order that the servitors even if a vulnerable group of the society can make use of their valuable time in a constructive way toward progress and prosperity and can be free from mental distress and languish and this shall be an auxiliary to the progressive momentum of the human society as a whole.

Right to freedom of religion : Article 25-Freedom of conscience and free profession, practice and propagation of religion (7) is infringed in the case of traditional servitors who are made to be deprived of their age-old routine cal scheduled duty consequent upon being evicted from their ancestral possession of land as remuneration and humiliated. And this is in no way contravention to Article 25 (1), excerpted as-Subject to public order, morality and health and to the other provisions of this part, all persons are equally entitled to freedom of conscience and the right freely to profess, practice and propagate religion (7). It also does not affect any existing law, i.e., section 8(3) of the OEA Act, or prevent the state from making any law as directed in Article 25 (2) of the Constitution.

3.2. Directive Principle of State Policy

We may discuss the Directive Principles of State Policy enshrined in part IV of the Constitution which have got relevance to the subject.

Article 37-Application of the principles contained in this part-The provisions contained in this part shall not be enforceable by any Court, but the principles therein laid down are nevertheless fundamental in the governance of the country and it shall be the duty of the state to apply these principles in making laws (7). Directive Principles are not the rights but the principles as it connotes. Rights are enforceable but principles are applications. Courts initially used to deliver judgments emphasizing on part III of the Constitution that contains the Fundamental Rights. But after the (twenty fifth Amendment) Act 1971, Courts have been taking a different view point. While delivering judgments they consider Directive Principles of State Policy as directives and both part III and part IV are complementary and supplementary to each other for achieving the Socialist objective of the Constitution. Directive Principles of State Policy under Part IV of the Constitution empower the state to frame schemes to secure economic justice to the weaker sections of the society. Where in worst case, the state fails to comply to the fundamental rights of the citizens; it could supplement the same through suitable schemes framed. But as we observe for the traditional servitors across the state no such tentative scheme framed by the state as yet.

Article 38- State to secure a social order for the promotion of welfare of the people-(1). The state shall strive to promote the welfare of the people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may a social order in which justice- social, economic and political, shall inform all the institutions of the national life (7).

(2) The state shall in particular, strive to minimize the inequalities in income and

endeavour to eliminate inequalities in status, facilities, and opportunities, not only amongst individuals but also among groups of people residing in different areas or engaged in different vocations (7).

Article 39. Certain principles of policy to be followed by the state- The state shall in particular, direct its policy towards securing – (a) that the citizens, men and women equally have the right to an adequate means of livelihood (7).

(e) that the health and strength of workers, men and women and the tender age of children are not abused and that citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter avocations unsuited to their strength (7).

(f) that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity and that childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment (7).

Article 39 (A)- Equal justice and free legal aid- The state shall secure that the operation of the legal system promotes justice, on a basis of equal opportunity, and shall in particular provide free legal aid by suitable legislation or schemes or in any other way, to ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason of economic or other disabilities (7). In the context, the state may consider to frame a scheme to extend legal aid to the traditional servitors.

Article 41. Right to work, to education and to public assistance in certain cases- The state shall within the limits of its economic capacity and development, make effective provision for securing the right to work, to education and to public assistance in cases of unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement, and in other cases of undeserved want (7).

Article 47. Duty of the state to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living and to improve public health (7).

3.3. Universal Declaration of Human Rights

It is very important to note that Article 1,3,5,7,8 and 22 which have got a unique and unparalleled echo of humane approach of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights are violated in case of the most primordial traditional servitors of Odisha.

4. Conclusion

It is mostly during the post-independence era, the lands bestowed to the traditional servitors by ex-feudal state chiefs and even prior to that they had been in possession and could develop the land to a cultivable stage as agriculturists for rendering seva- puja in the religious shrines have been litigated. Consequently they are dragged to court cases incurring unimaginable expenses and violence. Cases of death and physical assault are abundant. They are demoralized, pressurized left in a fearful ambience and not able to draw the attention of the higher authorities. They lead a miserable and pathetic life. Their socio-economic position is in a pitiable stage. Odisha Government as a mark of compliance to the Socialistic feature enshrined in the Preamble of the Constitution of India may take the following steps for upliftment of their socio-economic standard-

1. A survey on the socio-economic, literacy, position of the traditional servitors be made and a report published by the Odisha government.
2. Land records' position as before 1917 settlement be rectified and possession given to the traditional servitors evicted.
3. Traditional servitors engaged in their priestly work not enjoying the land, be allowed to possess and recorded in their names.
4. A cell in the state Secretariat be constituted to monitor the tasks assigned

and suitable suggestions communicated to the state government regularly.

5. Government may design suitable schemes and implement the same for upliftment of the socio-economic and literary standard of the traditional servitors.

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GENDERED INHERITANCE AND ITS CHALLENGES AS PORTRAYED IN ARUNDHATI ROY'S "THE GOD OF SMALL THINGS".

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 32ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Patriarchal societies the world over prefer sons to carry on the family business. Inheritance belongs to sons by virtue of their gender. The protagonist Ammukutty – a divorcee of a non-endogamous marriage is portrayed by Arundhati Roy to show how she challenges a predominantly patriarchal Syrian Christian culture of Kerala. This is a Research Essay, discusses the patriarchy, male gender favoritism by rejecting the daughter importance in the Authoress portrayed families.

Keywords: Domestic, Violence, Arundati, Family, Inheritance

The Preamble of Universal Declaration of Human Rights¹ upholds the family values in the Article 16(3) as "family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection of society and the State." Followed by its further claim for gender equality by Article 17(1) which states *everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others* and Article 17(2) further states that *no one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property*. Article 22 states *everyone has the right to social security and is entitled to realization.....of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality*. Article 25 (1) says that *everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health & well being of himself and his family*

including food, clothing, housing & medical care and necessary social services and right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control. Article 25(2) further states that *Motherhood & Childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock shall enjoy the same social protection*.

Many of the Philosophical texts have captured/foreseen this before the legal laws with certain depth of vision and this has been reflected in their text. Though Human Rights also have been guaranteed, the plight of women especially in Oriental countries like India and here in this paper specifically the condition of women of the Syrian Christian community of Kerala is highlighted to show that these human rights have been violated consistently through the generations in spite of cent per cent literacy and highly educated professionally qualified women in this community. A greater clarity and specific laws keeping in mind the socio-

¹ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is generally agreed to be the foundation of International Human Rights Law.¹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10 December, 1948 was the result of the experience of the Second World War.¹

cultural background will go a long way in ensuring that Human Rights is not only guaranteed but also practised in the true sense of the Declaration of Human Rights as formulated and as in the spirit of its founding fathers.

Arundhati Roy, who is a trained architect, has worked as a production designer and written screenplays for two films. She is a political activist who voiced her support strongly in the Narmada Bachao Andolan led by Medha Patkar. She lives in New Delhi.

This is her first book and it won her the 1997 Booker Prize – it is believed to be partly autobiographical. This novel is a truthful portrayal of the plight of women in society and their marathon struggle for seeking a sense of identity in a male dominated conservative framework. The central character of the novel, Ammukutty, yearns for pleasure and happiness and for a life that is free from the shackles of constraints. As a child, she was beaten by her father; her escapist marriage landed her from the frying pan to the fire literally who had to live with a drunkard husband willing to give her away to his boss to clear his debts. The rejection she faced from her own family and the discriminatory treatment by the family members towards her and her children drove her to love the man by night her children loved by the day. The subsequent class conflict and violence left her family scattered and she died an obscure death. The subsequent rebellious lifestyle of the twins – Rahel and Estha depict a contrast to Ammukutty's life. Arundhati Roy flings a harsh irony on man's domination over woman in this novel.

The protagonist Ammukutty of the Booker Prize winning novel *The God of Small Things* by Arundhati Roy dares to defy the existing norms of endogamy of the Syrian Christian community that she belonged to by marrying outside the community and religion. Endogamy (marrying within the community) is strictly followed by the Syrian Christian Community of Kerala. Any

deviation from the norm is heavily frowned upon and those defying it are ostracised. After an abusive and violent marriage that produced a set of twins Rahel and Estha, Ammu walks out of her marriage and returns to her ancestral home (Taravat) in Ayemenem, a small town in Kottayam District of Kerala. She is treated as an outcaste by her mother and brother Chacko, an Oxford educated jobless womaniser who returns back to India once his British wife deserts him. "... An Oxford avatar of the old zamindar mentality – a landlord forcing his attentions on women who depended on him for their livelihood (pg. 65) Taravat is the symbol of one's ancestry and high social standing. Marriages alliances are made based on the Taravat one belongs to. This community is highly patriarchal in nature. All inheritance in terms of property is distributed amongst the male siblings and the youngest son inherits the Taravat since he is responsible to take care of his parents in their old age. The Syrian Christian community of Kerala is a mercantile community that deals with trading of spices and are land owners. Chacko though a silent partner in his mother's business still bosses over all the women in the house and is autocratic. He blatantly tells Ammu that "what's yours is mine and what's mine is also mine." (pg. 57). The patriarchal nature of the Syrian Christian community is reflected here. Also the manner in which boys are preferred over girls in all aspects of life right from birth to education to marriage and finally inheritance from parents reflects the hegemonic masculinity prevalent in this community. "Though Ammu did as much work in the factory as Chacko, whenever he was dealing with food inspectors or sanitary engineers, he always referred to it as *my* factory, *my* pineapples, *my* pickles. Legally, this was the case because Ammu, as a daughter, had no claim to the property" (pg. 57). Chacko by virtue of his sex and gender i.e. physiological and psychological conditioning gains preference over Ammu in matters of education – he is Oxford educated whereas Ammu has local school education, Chacko is allowed to marry a British lady but Ammu's

marriage to a Hindu Bengali man is unacceptable. Chacko's daughter Sophie Mol gets preferential treatment whereas Ammu's children are labelled as hybrids. Even Chacko's divorced wife Margaret gets preferential treatment over his sister Ammu. "There would be boiled water for Margaret and Sophie Mol, tap water for everybody else." (pg. 46) Even after Chacko comes back from Oxford he is accorded high respect in the ancestral home and in the society whereas Ammu is shunned by the society and in her own ancestral home. The very women who have experienced suppression, domestic violence and ill treatment turn into perpetrators of these crimes once they become old. This process of emphasized femininity was practised by the community then and is prevalent even now and hence these reiterate the patriarchal mode of governance. A number of such case studies in research findings show how disparity with siblings ends up in the sisters giving in. Though the Indian Supreme Court's ruling on Christian inheritance was made on 24 February, 1986 stating that a daughter has rights to equal share with male siblings, the daughter is unwilling to get into legal squabbles with siblings fearing the jeopardizing of their future relationship with siblings. Hence there continues to be an unequal distribution of father's property amongst siblings in this community. Mary Roy and et al successfully repealed the Travancore Act and brought relief to the present daughters of the Syrian Christian community. But the Act has not brought relief in terms of prestations which has over time become pathological prestations and the demand for dowry in the name of *stridhanam* (woman's wealth) still continues.

The research findings to analyse the social and cultural behaviour of the Syrian Christian community of Kerala has used Cultural Materialism as a theoretical approach. Jonathan Dollimore and Allen Sinfield made current and defined Cultural Materialism as designating a critical method which has four characteristics – Historical context i.e. what was happening at the time

the text was written, Theoretical Method i.e. incorporating older methods of theory like structuralism, post-structuralism etc, Political commitment i.e. incorporating non-conservative and non-Christian frameworks such as Feminist and Marxist theory and Textual Analysis i.e. building on theoretical analysis of mainly canonical texts that have become "prominent cultural icons"¹ This approach of Cultural Materialism is important to understand the nature of gender conflicts which is centred to the core identity of materialism that this community practises.

Some of the major assumptions of Cultural Materialism are that all subjects live and work within the culture constructed by ideology, through discourses. The ideological constructions in which the authors live and have internalized, inevitably become a part of their work, and therefore their works are always political and always vehicle of power. Since literature plays an active role in the creation and consolidation of power, a literary text does not merely reflect the culture in which it is produced, but also actively contributes to the constitution of that culture. Cultural materialism tries to bring to light how ideology and thus existing social order tries to maintain itself through literature without losing its grip..... Cultural Materialists follow Foucault in their interest in the insane, the criminal, the exploited and all those who over the course of history have been marginalized. More than that, Cultural Materialists follow Raymond Williams in his adaptation of Gramsci's view of hegemony. For Williams, the dominant culture is never the only player in the cultural field, although it is the most powerful. There are always residual and emergent strains within a culture that offer alternatives to hegemony. In other words, the dominant culture is always under pressure from alternative views and beliefs. So analyses of the literary texts by the Cultural Materialists bring to light how these texts while being the instruments of the dominant socio cultural order, also demonstrate how the apparent coherence of that order is threatened from the inside, by

inner contradictions and by tensions that it seeks to hide. Focusing on the cracks in the ideological façade that texts offer, Cultural Materialists offer readings of dissidence that allow us to hear the socially marginalized and expose the cultural machinery that is responsible for their marginalization and exclusion.ⁱⁱ

According to Dr. Pips of TRS (The Student Room website) *Patriarchy is defined as the dominance of men in social or cultural systems.*²

Socio biologists sees patriarchy arises more as a result of inherent biology than social conditioning. In 1973, Goldberg published *The Inevitability of Patriarchy*, which advanced a biological interpretation of male dominance. *Patriarchy* is a social structure in which men are considered to have a monopoly on power and women are expected to submit. Patriarchy developed in the society during the Vedic period (ca. 1750-500 BCE). Patriarchy is very evident in all aspects of the Syrian Christian culture – whether at home, workplace, religious institutions and in the society.

Marriage is a parting of ways for a girl and her natal family; she moves to her husband's home and her visits back to her own home begin to decrease over time, especially when she lives a distance away. This is a patrilineal, patrilocal society. Inheritance passes down the male line and girls are considered transitory members of their natal home, 'guests' who go away after a while and therefore cannot be given a share in paternal landed property. Instead, the rights of girls are limited to receiving 'dowry', consisting of jewellery, clothes and items

that might be useful in their new homes. The stress on the male line combined with minimal rights accorded to daughters remains among most caste- based agrarian Christian communities, where land is the main inheritable property.

In Syrian Christian culture, the birth of a male child brings in lot of joy and celebration and is viewed in terms of the monetary benefits he would bring into the family in the future. The birth of a female child on the other hand brings in a lot of anxiety to the parents and the tendency to hoard for the daughter's future begins with her birth. This is evidently seen in the Ipe household where the birth of Chacko is celebrated and Ammukutty is always admonished to behave as she is a girl. This was not the case when the tradition of dowry was instituted in the first place. A dowry was given to the bride at the time of her marriage according to the inheritance that the bridegroom would receive from his father's property. But nowadays it has taken an ugly turn since the bride's party is required to pay for all the expenses related to the marriage and giving of dowry (whether in cash/kind) and also an equal share of her inheritance from her father's property. This has created gender conflicts in this community on a scale unparalleled before.

*Money's impersonal power replaces personal definition with competition and grounds relationships in predation. The result is a sense that human interaction is a function of commercial contracts and mistrust.*ⁱⁱⁱ

The Community encourages the increase of wants of the grooms family at the risk of the bride's family going bankrupt. Syrian Christians are described as materialistic and money minded people, who demand large dowries for their sons and hold rigidly conservative attitudes towards the behavior and expectations of women.^{iv}

The research findings dwell on the social and cultural norm of the Syrian Christian Community called *Stridhanam*. What is

² As such, rather than working to destabilize the historical notion of *patriarchy*, much literature assess the origins of *patriarchy*, or a social system in which the male gender role acts as the primary authority figure central to social organization, and where fathers hold authority over women, children, and property.

Stridhanam? *Stridhanam* (female wealth) is the sum of money that a Syrian Christian woman brings with her at the time of marriage. It is not seen as a gift but falls under the category of prestations. Symbolically, it must be seen as the severing of economic ties for a woman from her natal home and her incorporation into the conjugal household.

Stridhanam is generally a very large sum of money (often running into lakhs of rupees) given by the father of the bride to the groom's father. The woman no longer has a share in her father's property.....In the Orthodox/Jacobite Syrian Christian case, *stridhanam* ideally comes under the category of pre-dominant and money is used in order to contract marriages with desirable families. The 'spirit' of prestation however demands that there be no questions regarding its expenditure once money has changed hands. The woman has no control over her wealth and while there is often suppressed violence, in the majority of cases women tend to accept the entailed subjugation.^v Not only is the marriage looked at by the men as a barter system to form alliance with desirable families, but also that women have no say in the entire process because the head of the family makes all decisions regarding the girl's marriage. This obligation to provide *stridhanam* for a daughter at marriage is frequently a strain on her parents. The prestations have to continue, although varying in nature, even after the birth of her first child. A daughter was therefore seen as a burden. The staking of conjugal rights and privileges is the function of this payment. The old values attributed to the family name and individual character are being replaced by the idiom of which one can get for the amount one has in hand. So *stridhanam* now begins to look more like groom price than dowry. There is a conflict in the gender here because much as the girl is supposed to give *stridhanam*, why is the boy not interested in giving *purushadhanam* (men's wealth)? In order to enjoy conjugal rights and privileges why are only the men deprived of giving *purushadhanam*? Gender preference is very

evident when parents tend to view daughters as a burden and sons as profitable. The old values attributed to the family name and individual character are being replaced by the idiom of which one can get for the amount one has in hand. So *stridhanam* now begins to look more like groom price than dowry. So gender differences bring in cultural materialism into the picture.

The Indian Supreme Court ruling on Christian inheritance which was made on 24 February, 1986 stated that a daughter has rights to equal shares with male siblings. Prior to this, the Travancore Act of 1916 stated that a legitimate equivalent to the daughter for the payment of her *stridhanam* was a sum of five thousand rupees as against the concomitant settlement of estate for the daughter. This resulted in unequal distribution of the father's property amongst the siblings. Mary Roy and *et al* successfully repealed the Travancore Act and brought relief to the present generation daughters of the Syrian Christian community. But the Act has not brought relief in terms of prestations which has over time become pathological prestations and this demand for *stridhanam* has left many women and their families in a piteous condition. The present generation uses *stridhanam* as a platform to exhibit their status quo and also wield it as a weapon in their marital home to consolidate their superiority in the marital home. These prestations have caused a sort of reversal of roles now with the daughter-in-laws having a greater say in the households compared to their counterparts earlier. They have a say in all the major decision making process of the family unlike the earlier tradition wherein the father-in-law was the sole and ultimate decision maker in all family and business matters. The daughter-in-law brings in an equal income and so this has changed the scenario in their relationship with her. So here also materialism comes in as the ruling factor in the maintaining of relationships.

With the expansion of the urban Christians middle class, educational qualifications,

earning power and jobs in the urban employment sector, and ownership of urban property have become essential requirements for both men and women in the marriage market. The financial burden has now shifted exclusively to the bride's family in contrast to the past when both families shared it equally by matching the bride's dowry with the groom's inheritance. Although the practice of dowry was made illegal in 1961 by legislation for all of India, the practice continues among Kerala Christians, and indeed in every part of India, as a compulsory part of marriage transactions.^{vi}

The dowry in arranged marriages is an indication of the relative status and standing of the families of the bride and groom. The offer of a dowry below expectations may be an assertion of superiority of the bride givers over the bride takers; it could equally convey the unequal treatment of a daughter by her natal family. The offer of a dowry above expectations, on the other hand, becomes a favourite subject of community gossip and insinuation that the large dowry is being used to "marry off" a girl who is dark, unattractive, or "sickly," or has some dubious attribute. Among Syrian Christians in particular, there are strict conventions regarding the appropriate dowries to be given and received by families of particular status groups and marriage circles. While many traditional families still adhere to these conventions and reject offers of exceedingly high dowries for their sons or the high dowry demands made by prospective suitors for their daughters, there are the "new rich" (puthupannakkarar), who offer large dowries to gain attractive alliances with traditional and well-known families. "Good" or "traditional families" who have seen their wealth dwindle and have only their reputation to recommend them might also attempt to get the maximum dowries for their sons, or negotiate lower dowries for their daughters.^{vii}

Here again, the prerogative is always of the groom's family – if they have large

inheritance for their sons they can accordingly demand dowry in proportion to it and if the "good" or "traditional families" have dwindled in their economic status with only their reputation to recommend them, then they might also attempt to get maximum dowries for their sons. There again one is accosted with gender conflict in this situation because if the bride is of "good" and "traditional family" with only family reputation as her recommendation, she cannot have the privilege of having a groom of equal status and is therefore forced to a compromise to marrying in a family of a lower economic status – this in spite of the bride being well educated and drawing a substantial income worthy of her marital home status and the inheritor of whatever property her parents will equally distribute eventually.

So the question is why the aspect of dowry is not incorporated by the advocates of Human Rights? Is it because it is a socially prevalent custom in almost all the communities of the world? Even Queen Elizabeth II was gifted Bombay (now Mumbai) as a part of her dowry when she married Prince Philip. Is there a fear of many member nations opposing this? Will it create a disparity in the social order and cause societal norms to be uprooted? Will family units be disturbed? Will it create a further divide in the existing East/West divide in looking at aspects of freedom, justice and liberty? The answers to these questions will determine whether gendered inheritance in the Syrian Christian community of Kerala and the challenges that come along with it will be addressed by the decision makers on Human Rights.

ⁱ <literarism.blogspot.in/2011/11/cultural-materialism.html>

ⁱⁱ Harris, Marvin. Cultural Materialism. The Struggle for a Science of Culture.

ⁱⁱⁱ <http://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/ca/citd/holtorf/2.0html>

^{iv} (Philips 2004:2)

^v (Vishwanathan 1999:111)

^{vi} (Philips 2003:439)

^{vii} (Vishwanathan 1999:266)

HUMAN RIGHTS PERSPECTIVES OF THE THIRD GENDER IN INDIA

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 14ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Transgender is generally described as a person whose gender identity, gender expression or behavior does not conform to their biological sex. The court says that since TGs do not have reproduction capacity as a either man or woman, they are neither man nor woman and claim to be an institutional “third gender”. TG also includes persons who intend to undergo sex Re-Assignment. The Paper studies the life of TGs concerning to the rights they are enjoyed, also social aspect with the case study of TG community of Burdwan district.

Keywprds: *Transgender, Rights, Human, India, La*

Transgender is generally described as a person whose gender identity, gender expression or behavior does not conform to their biological sex. As per judiciary view since TGs do not have reproduction capacity as a either man or woman, they are neither man nor woman and claim to be an institutional “third gender”. TG also includes persons who intend to undergo *sex Re- Assignment surgery* (SRS) or have undergone SRS to align biological sex with their gender identity in order to become male or female. Transgender or hijra in India are called by different names and different region like *Hijras* in north India, *Kinnar* in Delhi, *Aravanis* in Tamil Nadu, *Jogaties* in Maharashtra & Karnataka, *Shiv-shakthis* etc.

Hijras are magical personality that create fear and sometimes respect to common people. Hijras perform religious ceremonies at weddings and at the birth of male babies, involving music, singing, and sexually suggestive dancing. These are intended to bring good luck and fertility. Although hijras are most often uninvited, the

host usually pays the hijras a fee. Many fear the hijras curse if they are not appeased, bringing bad luck or infertility, but for the fee they receive, they can bless goodwill and fortune on to the newly born. Hijras are said to be able to do this because, since they do not engage in sexual activities, they accumulate their sexual energy which they can use to either bestow a boon or a bane.

Most hijras live at the margins of society with very low status; the very word "hijra" is sometimes used in a derogatory manner. Few employment opportunities are available to hijras. Many get their income from performing at ceremonies (toli), begging (dheengna), or sex work ('raarha')—an occupation of hijras also recorded in pre-modern times. Violence against hijras, especially hijra sex workers, is often brutal, and occurs in public places, police stations, prisons, and their homes. As with transgender people in most of the world, they face extreme discrimination in health, housing, education, employment, immigration, law, and any bureaucracy that is unable to place them into male or female

gender categories. Beginning in 2006, hijras were engaged to accompany Patna city revenue officials to collect unpaid taxes, receiving a 4-percent commission.

Hijras are often encountered on streets, trains, and other public places demanding money from people. If refused, the hijras may attempt to embarrass the man into giving money, using obscene gestures, abusive language, and even sexual advances. In India for example, threatening to open their private parts in front of the man if he does not give away some money. The dominant cultural role of the hijras, as we have seen, is that of ritual performers. It is also true, however, that hijras often engage in homosexual prostitution.

Recognition and protection and promotion for the rights of Hijaras in India traced back to In the time of Ramayana, As [per the popular epic when Rama set for 14 years exile in the forest the citizens of Ayodhya (Kingdom of Rama) followed him with grief and tears, Rama stopped them at the border of kingdom before entering into the forest and asked them to wipe every men and women to wipe the tears. But those man who were neither men nor woman did not know where to go. So they stayed there because Rama did not ask them to go. They remained their 14 years and Snake hills grew around them. When Rama returned from Lanka, he found many Snake hills. Not knowing why they were there, he removed them and found so many people with long beards and long nails. And so they were blessed by Rama. That is why they are respected so much in Ajodhya. During ancient and the medieval period of Indian history they were existing as an institution. In the fourth century B.C. they were employed in the harems. This role of their, in fact, was very significant in maintaining the personal hygiene of the harem in mates and in the administrator of affair of the harems. During the Mugal period, particularly, during reign of Shah Jahan, hijras held very high status. They were also employed during the rules of Akbar.

In 1994, they were given the right to vote. In 1999, Shabnam Mausi Bano became India's first hijra MLA. In 2003, Hijras in Madhya Pradesh have established their own political party called "Jeeti Jitayi Politics" (JJP). In recent Loksabha elections, Daya Rani Kinnar, a transsexual activist, stood as an independent candidate from Ghaziabad constituency against Rajnath Singh. Tamil Nadu became the first state to give recognition to the transgender. In official forms, there is 'T' along with 'M' and 'F' in the gender identification column. In Chennai, toilets are being built for the transgender. Recently a large no. of NGOs has come up to work for the transgender. Things are changing. But the limits to these changes are in our mindset. There is a need to broaden our mindset, to make our mindsets more human or more rational.

1. HIJRAS IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA

Hijras who belong to south India and particulars to madras region, tell about a different type of death ritual. According to them the dead is buried in his own home. If the home does not belong to the death, then the dead is taken out of the home at mid night when no one is there to watch. The dead is taken out in the standing position by three-four of his companions. They take the dead to the jungle and dig a deep ditch. They put two three quintals of salt into the ditch and bury the dead in a standing position. While taking to the jungle he is given beating. After burying the dead they offer a prayer to the goddess to give salvation to the death. The hijras worship their goddess Bahuchara. The temple of the goddess is situated in Gujrat near Ahmadabad. The Bahuchara mata is their main goodness yet the hijras of North India do worship the local and religion goodness, like Vaishnu Devi, Mansa Devi etc. But there are hardly any mythological justification revealed by the hijras. However in the case of Bahuchara Mata there are a large number of stories. Salunke argues, the Bahuchara worship in the form of the vulva is related to the ritual

of castration. The idea is to identify one-self with the deity which is done by feminine dress. Since it gives them a sense of identity, so violation of it is considered threat to hijra culture. According to salunke, violation of any such rule is punishable by the hijra community's court of law, i.e., hijra panchayat. It is therefore within the purview of hijra community to provide religious symbols.

2. HIJRA AND PUBLIC INTEREST LITIGATION

Transgender now a third gender in response to a Public Interest Litigation (PIL), the apex court has delivered a land mark judgment which is expected to bring transgender in the main stream of society. The Supreme Court, in a land mark judgment, has recognized transgender as the third gender in this country. This decision of the apex court makes India the first country to give transgender third gender status. A bench of justices K.S Radhakrishnan and A.K Sikri directed the Govt. to take steps for granting recognition to transgender as a separate third category of gender after male & female. The bench said they are part and parcel of society and the Govt. must take steps to bring them in the main stream of society. The apex court passed the order on a PIL filed by National Legal Service Authority (NALSA) urging the court to give separate identity to transgender recognizing them as the third category of gender.

3. THE VERDICTS OF SUPREME COURT OF INDIA

The Supreme Court judgment on Transgender Right (NALSA vs Union of India) A summary of the 15th April 2014 judgment, by Danish Sheikh, This judgment covers persons who want to identify with the third gender as well as persons who want to transition from one identity to another, i.e. to male to female or vice versa. The Court has

directed Centre and State Governments to grant legal recognition of gender identity whether it is male, female or third gender. Legal Recognition for Third Gender: In recognizing the third gender category, the Court recognizes that fundamental rights are available to the third gender in the same manner as they are to males and females. Further, non-recognition of third gender in both criminal and civil statutes such as those relating to marriage, adoption, divorce, etc is discriminatory to the third gender. Legal Recognition for Persons transitioning within male/female binary: As for how the actual procedure of recognition will happen, the Court merely states that they prefer to follow the psyche of the person and use the "Psychological Test" as opposed to the "Biological Test".

4. ECONOMIC ENGAGEMENT

Almost anyone who has ever travelled in a train across UP/Bihar must have had several misadventures of such type. The question arises that why cannot they think of more ethical and socially acceptable ways of earning their bread?..Do they always have to resort to the usual 'saree lifting' ways?...Sadly, they hardly have a choice. Almost no-one will be willing to employ a eunuch they virtually have no right to education, health care, jobs, etc. they hardly have a voice in the country. Apart from constitutional amendments, they only think that can change the scenario is social awareness. Awareness both for us and them. We need to learn that they too are humans and that matters more than any other reason. We should be more tolerant. And the hijra should learn that they should go out of the way to ensure that the society's perception towards them changes. They should revert firm their usual tradition and behave in such a way that the society's apathy towards them decreases. They shouldn't indulge in such activities that will make the general public hate them even more. People should pay them at weddings/birth so that at least they

can enjoy some comforts of life rather than being discriminated as well as living a merciful life with no mercy of others. There should be some organizations as well who would treat them as a target section and organize a work-force or a community like they do with poor women. 99% hijras are the victim of forced castration. There is no effective law to curb this heinous crime. Removing a small part makes big difference in the rest his life. I do not know god created such an important organ outside the body? The hijra of India are probably the most well known and populous third sex type in the modern world. The Humsafar Trust estimates there are between 5 and 6 million hijras in India. Often called eunuchs in English, they may be born intersex or apparently male, dress in feminine clothes and generally see themselves as neither men nor women.

5. MEANS OF ENTERTAINMENT

Movie/Television: All the hijras are very fond of watching television and movies in the theatres. A colored Television set rests installed in the tent for the entertainment of the members of the group. The hijras lead a very stressful life due to living far from family and to minimize this stress most hijras go to Theater hall to watch a movie at least once in a week. All of them get together and share the experience of the day's work that how much was the earning and, what all problems were faced. The hijras also plan the activities for the next day that which area they had to go for earning next day. The conversation is not limited to them but many topics of current importance are freely discussed. This is the time to relax and vent out their mental frustrations by talking to their housemates.

Each kinnar is allowed to go and enjoy to any place in India once in a year and stay there a number of days, in tradition houses of kinnars in India. The arrangement of a guest kinnar's stay, his food and journey are borne by the natives. The guest kinnar

has never to pay for anything; they just go there and stay until they wants to leave.

6. LAST RITES ANALYSIS

“Nobody has seen a funeral of a kinnar”, “When a kinnar dies his body is beaten brutally and then buried inside the traditional house”-These types of myths are prevalent in the society but death and funeral of a eunuch takes place as normally as of any other common man's funeral and cremation. The information of death of a eunuch is communicated to others by making announcement from the Hijiji. Hindu kinnars are cremated and Muslims kinnars buried in the graveyards. The only difference between burial of a eunuch and common man is that a common man can be buried in any graveyard of Burdwan town but a eunuch can be buried only in a specified graveyard and there to a special section is allotted and reserved for them. A common man cannot be buried there.

7. BURDWAN TOWN: THE LOCALE OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The decision and finalization of the topics and selection of the area of study are almost simultaneously done. The researcher decided to conduct a study on the socio economic condition, and problem faced by hijras in Burdwan town, it was found to be the right place because good number of hijras residing in this town.

As per the Census 2011 data, Bardhaman District has an area of 7,024 km². It is bounded on the north by Birbhum and Murshidabad districts, on the east by Nadia District, on the southeast by Hooghly District, on the southwest by Bankura and Purulia districts, and on the northwest by Dhanbad district of Jharkhand. The district has six sub-divisions, Asansol, Sadar (North), Sadar (South), Durgapur, Kalna, and Katwa. It was amongst the first districts to have a 100% literacy rate. Bardhaman is the

most advanced district in West Bengal both industrially and agriculturally. The eastern part is enriched by the alluvial soil of Bhagirathi River (minor stream of river Ganges), and is one of the most productive agricultural regions in West Bengal. The western part of the district, chiefly Asansol, is rich in coal and other mineral resources. This part is highly industrialized and contains various factories based on iron and steel processing, as well as many cement factories. Durgapur, Burnpur, and Kulti are in the western part of the district. It also contains power plants at Durgapur and Dishergarh.

8. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Main Objective is to understand the socio-economic condition of Hijras with focusing on the ascertainment the social status of hijras, Assessment the economic status of hijras; identification the culture of the hijras; finding out the factors underlying their problem¹s.

For the purpose of the present study the researcher selected Burdwan town as his proposed geographical area of work which falls under Burdwan district of West Bengal in India. In Burdwan town there are 216 eunuchs residing and this population is estimated by local NGO SAATHI, and the age group of the respondents are also estimated to fall between 20 to 45 years².

¹ The method used to collect the data was:

1. Interview schedule:- The researcher prepared an interview schedule which included question according to the set objective and arranged them systematically and sequentially. During data collection the researcher filled the interview schedule by himself. The biggest advantage in the use of interview schedule is that one can observe, interpret and read the body language and attitude of the respondents.
2. Interview guide:- The researcher collected data from the head of one of the traditional house in order to have an in depth knowledge of socio economics and cultural practices of hijras.
3. Observation:- The researcher observed the respondent during data collection tried to code their body language and attitude. So for the allotted task both the verbal and nonverbal attitude plays key role.

² As we know that hijra groups are very conservative, so they fear to share any information to the people who were not belongs to their community. In this adverse circumstances researcher plan the strategy to collect the data after proper rapport building with local NGO SAATHI who are working on this issue. Purposive sampling method has been adopted to

9. MAJOR FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

- In poor family when any genital abnormal child born they hide this matter within few members of the family, and try to find out any solution, on other hand other persons of society was unable to raise the voice against the rich family, due to this, it clearly indicated that maximum respondents who join the hijra group belongs to lower middle class family, and its percentage was 42.5%
- Due to abnormality in genital organ and strange cross dresser attitude, the school mates, friends, relatives, community peoples try to molestate them, whenever possible. Maximum cases of molestation remain when they were alone, maximum respondents were molested by kith & kin, neighbors and school mates its percentage was 65%.
- Maximum respondents have no attachment with other family members, and its percentage was 72.5%.
- Maximum respondents were unable to complete the basic education, due to non supportive attitude of other community members, and its percentage was 47.5%.
- They were not shown any interest toward education, in this stage of life, they choose the way of begging in running trains, homes, red signals and in bus stops.
- From the childhood they were suffering from many obstacles. And many incidents took place in their lifespan.

collect relevant data from the respondents. From the total universe of 216, 20% samples have been selected and thus, the size of the sample selected through the above sampling method becomes 40. All the respondents were above 18 years and lives in the group or Toli of four to six members who have migrated from various places/parts of country.

- All the respondents were male hijra with female soul, among them only seventeen respondents were gone through castration; others reported that their genital organ was not in definite shape.
- A large no. of respondents were earning by the begging in trains/express trains and local trains which were running in the route of Howrah to other cities. During the dhandha/work hour they were bound to pay (30) thirty rupees to the RPF staffs, railway on duty staffs, to catch the train from siding or from the Burdwan railway station. On other hand they were bound to hand over fixed amount (500) five hundred to guru/gaddi, for there per day maintenance.
- Maximum no. of respondents were accepted that there per day income vary from (500-550) rupees, and its percentage is 77.5%
- Living place of hijras was non hygienic, it was the end point of the railway platforms attached with the boundary wall of the railway premises, where the garbage heaps were present.
- Only list no. of respondents accepted that they were suffering from HIV/AIDS, and its number was four.
- Maximum hijras have strong faith in counseling and the treatment provided by the representatives of the NGOs, because they got strong moral support from the organization SATHI.
- Many of them do not possess any valid voter ID card, pan card, driving license due to their typical identity. So they have no any bank account.
- Only list number of respondents accepted that they were working in dance bar previously because it was the good source of earning, but due to high risk of HIV and transmitted disease and huge expense in lifestyle they were unable to save money, and its percentage was 05%.
- Due to unavailable of other profession, hijras choose the profession to collect money by begging in running trains and from the vehicles of red light signals.
- Maximum respondents were prone to cigarette smoking, and drinking due to typical profession and more stressful state of mind.
- The maximum no. of respondents accepted that they went on tour, once in two years, and its percentage was 67.5%..
- All the respondents accepted that, they used sari during the working hours or during earning hours.
- All the hijras know that Koovgama was the religious place of them, in the month of April and May there was a festival of hijras and worship of Bahuchara mata took place every year, in which hijra of all over the world visited this holy place, not only this many common peoples of male and female gender visit to know the cultural aspects of the hijras. As per the ritual of hijra, they become the bride for one night and marry lord Krishna and when the day appears they break there bangles and became widow. Maximum respondents accepted that, they never get the chance to visit Koovgama.
- Hijras have strong we-feeling within the community. So they maintain good cooperation within the members.
- During illness and emergency tour guru/gaddi assist the individual members by giving them economic support to overcome the problematic situation.
- All the respondents come under same guru SHANTI, and lives in groups of same locality. They pay five hundred rupees (Rs.500), to Guru/Gaddi, for overall maintenance.

- All the respondents accepted that there was hollowness in their heart from the beginning, because they never got the desired behavior from the side of family, friends and from society members.
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CHILD RIGHTS PERSPECTIVE OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY IN INDIA

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Delegation to the 1st International Congress on Human Rights & Duties
(Regd: 32ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

Juvenile delinquency is an enormous problem in India by which most of the youth ruin their lives. Because of juvenile crime and relate problems youth, their families and the entire society suffer multiple consequences. Not only does the problem affect the victims of the crime; it also affects the juvenile delinquent's family, their future, and the society as a whole. The most obvious people affected by juvenile delinquency are the victims. The most profound consequence of crimes committed by juveniles carries due to socio-economic and psychological problems which reflect on their family members and the society. Due to the psychological problems, sometimes juveniles involved in robberies, rapes and assaults also are significant. With these criminal activities the juveniles habituate to consume alcohol or other drugs. The main objective of this paper is to study the incidence of juvenile delinquency with reference to psychological perspectives. Hence the sample has been considered from the juvenile homes in Visakhapatnam city where the juvenile delinquents kept. A sample of 60 juvenile delinquent boys and girls between the age group of 10 to 18 years are selected on random sampling method. The juvenile who commit serious crimes challenge their future to protest perceived abuses that have been perpetrated against them. This makes them psychological depression and in turn reflects to commit more crimes. In this circumstance the study on incidence of juvenile delinquency is very important to analyze the causes with reference to psychological perspectives and annihilate in the society.

Keywords: *Child, Juvenile, Delinquency, Crime, law*

Juvenile delinquency is the crime activity charged by a person who is under the age of 18 years. In recent period these criminal activities are increasing rapidly due to many reasons and circumstance. In most of the places juveniles charged with serious crimes, such as robbery or murder which are transferred to criminal courts and tried as an adult. Sometimes prosecutors make this decision, or sometimes allow transfers require a hearing to consider the age and record of the juvenile, the type of crime, and the likelihood that the youth can be helped by the juvenile court. As a result of a get-tough attitude involving juvenile crime,

many counties have revised their juvenile codes to make it easier to transfer youthful offenders to adult court.

Academic experts have long recognized that crime is a young man's game. The typical criminal is a male who begins his career at 14 or 15 and continues through his mid-20s and then tapers off into retirement. The crime statistics denotes the disproportionate impact of those under the age of 18 on criminal activity; while comprising roughly one-sixth of the country's population, they make up a full one-quarter of all people arrested and account for nearly one-third of the arrests for

the seven crimes in the uniform crime index (homicide, forcible rape, robbery, aggravated assault, burglary, vehicle theft and larceny).

The statistics show that somewhere between 30 and 40 percent of children who commit crimes growing up in an urbanized area. Although they account for only a small proportion of the total population, the crime rates are increasing day-by-day. The current levels of crime in India are still lower than in most of the foreign countries, nationally the level of criminality has increased significantly during the transition period (Kury and Ferdinand, 1999). Some argue that 'political turbulence' combined with the 'growth in criminality' led to an increased fear of crime among the people, as well as growing feelings of scepticism and mistrust towards government bodies and the judicial system (Roberts and Hough, 2002). In addition, the sense of insecurity has been strongly influenced among public by the media, now free to report more and more crime 'dramas' on a daily basis. Indeed, there is evidence that the media exaggerate the extent of crime in the country, in particular juvenile delinquency (Haines and Haines, 2001). Therefore to the extent that the media influence public attitudes, these are likely to be based on stereotypes and inaccurate figures from unrepresentative reporting.

There is very little research into public attitudes towards juvenile delinquency. Previous studies are limited to measuring fear of crime activities amongst juveniles, public opinion about the death penalty (Keil et al., 1999) or about delinquency in general (Ionescu, 2000). However, there is no study investigating on the opinions about juvenile delinquency and its treatment in the country. Where public opinion is misinformed it can compromise the fundamental principles of justice (Walker and Hough, 1988). If politicians are to give greater consideration to the 'congruence' of public opinion and punishment practice, in particular to the level of public confidence in the administration of justice (Roberts and Hough, 2002), then the exploration of public knowledge about crime

and criminal activity issues becomes important. However, policy makers need to be aware of the extent and limitations of public opinion, the media's influence in shaping people's views about punishing and the methodological limitations of studies into this area. In this regard, Visakhapatnam city is likely accession to its fast development in all sectors, and the increasing in criminal activities at various circumstances especially by juveniles, research into public attitude on juvenile delinquency in Visakhapatnam city is of greater significance.

Much of the international research into public opinion regarding punishment has shown that public confidence in the administration of justice is low, due in part to the discrepancy between public beliefs and the reality with regard to punishments against crimes. The public consistently misjudges trends in both adult and juvenile crime, tends to underestimate the severity of punishment, and is generally uninformed or misinformed about criminal justice policy. The media have a significant role in shaping people's conceptions about crime because of the emphasis on reporting crimes of violence. Additionally, in contrast to what politicians might think the public support alternative punishment options when these are made salient, as well as rehabilitation and prevention efforts, especially regarding juvenile offenders. Although most of these findings emerged from studies of public attitudes towards crime and punishments in general, or studies focused only on crimes committed by adults, the lack of public knowledge about the criminal justice system is equally reflected in studies looking into public opinion about juvenile crime. Therefore, the present study aimed to analyse the public attitude on juvenile crime.

1. Methodology:

This survey was conducted in Visakhapatnam city. The study reports on 60 juveniles who are committed crimes and staying in Central Jail of Visakhapatnam city. A structured questionnaire was designed and collected necessary information from the

respondents by personal interview. The questionnaire was developed from an

analysis and assessment of crime studies conducted, and drew heavily on the similar works developed through crime surveys. However, the development of the

questionnaire was also influenced by the context in which the survey was to take place; respondents' feedback (via pre-testing and piloting); Visakhapatnam city's historical, political and socio-economic context, as well as contemporary practices within the juvenile justice system. Closed questions with tick-box and Likert-scale response formats were used in order to find out the following objectives.

1. To study the demographic profile of the respondents (e.g. age, sex, education, etc).
2. To study the knowledge and perception of respondents on incidence of juvenile delinquency psychological perspectives.

The pre-designed questionnaires were filled from the 60 respondents who are involved in criminal activities in Visakhapatnam city and put in Central Jail. The data was covered various categories of criminal activity involved juveniles where the distribution followed a purposive snow-balling non-probability design, with correctly completed questionnaires returned.

After collecting the necessary information from the respondents through the questionnaires the data was processed with statistical package SPSS and the required tables were drawn for the analysis. Hence, the following findings were derived from the sample data.

In common with most public opinion studies, findings here are presented mainly in the form of frequencies of responses. However, statistically significant associations in the data are explored, where possible. For example, relationships between demographic profile of the respondents and

opinions on juvenile delinquency, and also psychological perspectives by using Chi-square tests of significance.

2. The main reasons for criminal activity involved by juvenile delinquency

The results of this study show that there is public concern about law and order in Visakhapatnam city. However, in the eyes of respondents the most important social problem was not seen to be crime, but poverty. Over half (58.3%) of respondents surveyed expressed poverty is the most important reason, a finding very much in line with the reality of their lives. The choice of Illiteracy (23.6%) and unemployment (15.7%) as the next most important reasons (after poverty) confirms once again juveniles' dissatisfaction with their socio-economic conditions.

Table-1: Reason for juvenile crime

Reason for juvenile crime	Percentage
1. Poverty	58.3
2. Illiteracy	23.6
3. Unemployment	15.7
4. Other problems	2.4
Total	100.0

Juvenile delinquency and punishments

When asked about recent national juvenile delinquency trends, the majority of respondents (75.9%) believed that juvenile delinquency was on the increase. Only 16% of respondents were aware of changing the behaviour, while the majority (78%) thought that the number of juvenile offenders sent to prison had increased. These results illustrate that the psychological perspectives of the respondents on juvenile delinquency found imprisonment rates for juvenile offenders in Visakhapatnam city is increasing. But the behaviour of the juveniles is not changing. It is also found that most of the juveniles involved in violence followed by thefts.

Table-2: Opinions of the respondents on Juvenile Delinquency and Punishments

S.No.	Juvenile delinquency and punishments	Yes
1	Juvenile delinquency is increasing	75.9%
2	Number of juvenile offenders sent to prison had increased	78.0%
3	Juvenile offenders are changing their behavior	16.0%
4	Most of the juvenile delinquency involves violence	91.5%
5	Most of the juvenile delinquency involves theft	67.2%

There are a number of possible reasons why people's estimations of crime and punishing figures are so wide of the mark. Firstly, official crime statistics are inaccessible to the public and often out of date; lack of knowledge is therefore hardly surprising. Secondly, as the media are the main source of information, public attitudes are subject to influence by unrepresentative reporting. Thirdly, discrepancies between national and local crime rates could induce differences of opinions. Hence respondents living in such an area would have been influenced by the local experience of crime when answering questions about national crime rates. Poorer (low income or no income) respondents were more likely to overestimate the proportion of juvenile offenders engaged in violent crimes. Younger respondents tended to overestimate imprisonment rates for juvenile offenders and the elderly underestimated the imprisonment rates for juvenile offenders who had committed theft and burglary.

Table-3: Comment on punishments and their ability to deliver justice

Comment on punishments	%
1. Confidence in the courts	33.2
2. Somewhat neutral	33.2
3. More critical performance of courts	33.6
Total	100.0

A plurality of opinion emerged when the juveniles were asked to comment on punishments and their ability to deliver justice. One third (33.2%) of the juveniles expressed confidence in the courts, one third was somewhat neutral (33.2%) and one third was more critical of the performance of the courts. One could say from the data that only a third of the juveniles expressing negative views about the courts is a positive result. This indicates that the majority of the juveniles do not have confidence in the courts and this quite rightly should be considered a problem for a democratic country.

Table-4: Opinions of the juveniles in the administration of justice

S.No.	Public confidence	Yes
1	Juveniles should be treated differently from adults	71.0%
2	Judges respect the rights of juvenile offenders and treat them fairly	44.4%
3	Punishments cannot change the behavior of juvenile offenders	63.8%

An important aspect of confidence in the administration of justice concerns the way courts deal with juveniles. In this respect, the vast majority of the juveniles (71%) not only believed that juveniles should be treated differently from adults, but they also believed that the courts give full expression to this principle. Furthermore, almost half (44.4%) of respondents considered that within the punishment process, judges respected the rights of juvenile offenders and treated them fairly. It is also noticed from the juvenile opinions that above sixty percent of the respondents (63.8%) opined punishments cannot change the behavior of juvenile offenders.

Juvenile offender and their treatment

Regarding juvenile offenders and their treatment, a greatest proportion of respondents supported non-custodial punishments, such as community service (54.9%) or probation (31.9%). Only 13.2% favoured imprisonment. These findings demonstrate a considerable rise in the level of public support for non custodial penalties – particularly for minor offences such as theft.

Table-5: Juvenile opinions on their treatment

Non-custodial punishments	Percentage
Community service	54.9%
Probation	31.9%
Imprisonment	13.2%
Total	100.0%

The results indicated that people wanted more juvenile offenders to be sent to prison for violent crimes, burglary and theft. This latter result is not consistent with public support for non custodial penalties for a particular case of minor theft. One can argue that this inconsistency within people's attitudes reflects once again the fact that, when asked about punishment in general, people tend to think about worst case scenarios, even when theft is the offence in question.

Further contradictory results emerged when juveniles were asked other questions about juvenile offenders. In contrast with the traditional mode of punishment practice in Visakhapatnam city, which is based on a strict Criminal Code in which the sentence is based only on the offence and not the characteristics of the individual, the majority of the public (70%) thought that both the circumstances of crime and the juvenile offenders' personal circumstances should be taken into account in the punishing process.

A statistically significant correlation was also found between respondent's standard of living and their attitudes to punishing juvenile offenders: people with low incomes

were more likely to believe that sentences passed by the courts in Visakhapatnam city are too lenient. Interestingly, however, people with lower incomes and lower education were also more likely to favour 'restorative' options.

Age and education have an impact on the way of juvenile offenders. For example, older juveniles were more likely to support rehabilitation as a main punishment objective. The results indicated that juvenile with a higher level of education were more punitive towards young delinquents: the more educated were, the more likely they were to believe that retribution should be the primary aim of punishment.

3. Conclusion

This study has shown that it would be wrong to characterize the Visakhapatnam city as being highly punitive in respect to juvenile delinquency and punishing. Although Visakhapatnam city consider that sentences handed down by the courts are not tough enough, when they are provided with specific examples and questioned in more depth, they think more closely about an issue and their responses change. In contrast to judicial practice in Visakhapatnam city, there is juvenile favour for community based punishment alternatives for juvenile offenders, especially those committing minor offences. Moreover, the juveniles do not have a great deal of confidence in the ability of the courts to prevent crime. They believe that preventing juvenile delinquency is more a question of changing the family and school environment and increasing the chances of gaining employment and providing opportunities for young people to spend their spare time positively, rather than stressing more imprisonment or police on the beat. However, this does not mean the role of punishment in preventing crime. As results from this survey demonstrate punishment was perceived as a major factor in preventing juvenile crime. Interestingly, contrary to common practice in Visakhapatnam city courts, a large proportion of the juveniles are in favour of individualization within the

punishment process and restorative justice. A majority support elements of the restorative justice approach, such as reconciliation between victims and juvenile offenders.

Findings reported in this paper and elsewhere indicate that tend to be punitive towards crime and punishing issues mainly because, when asked about the adequacy of sentences in general, they have in mind more serious crimes. This is coupled with the mistaken impression that juvenile delinquency is increasing and the perception that the amount of violent juvenile delinquency is much greater than it actually is. In the psychological perspectives of the juvenile delinquency it shows the poverty, illiteracy and family disturbances are the main reasons for the criminal activities among young children, which need social change and government initiatives for structural changes in the family live and more reforms for development of education and employment in the society. Some even argue that punishments may not control the criminal activities among younger generation. Moreover, as the media tend to report violent spectacular cases regarding juvenile delinquency, public discussion of criminality focuses mostly on serious crimes, which clearly represent only a small minority of juvenile crimes.

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‘CHILDREN, NOT MUSKETEERS’ – A CALL FOR JUSTICE IN ARMED CONFLICTS

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(Regd: 15ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

This paper is an endeavour to assay the myriad miseries and anguish inflicted on children in the aftermath of armed conflicts. Infringement of child rights during armed conflicts have gone unpunished for long. In spite of significant progress of the international community in building mechanisms with the aspiration of ending freedom from punishment for violations against children, a lot still needs to be done. The dynamic and contemporary nature of armed conflicts necessitates the implementation of aberrant approaches to iron out the steep challenges. Youth-specific reparations for protecting the children today, implicate much more than merely punishing these perpetrators. These include addressing issues like education, loss of childhood, family, psycho social support, rehabilitation, livelihood and many more. Increasing participation of the youth in meeting the ends of justice and innovative modus operandi will efficaciously deal with the current day agony of children in the quagmire of armed conflicts. The paper also attempts to articulate how the grave suffering and violation of children in armed conflict can access justice and how the current system of justice deals with victims and witnesses.

Keywords: *Armed, Children, Reparation, Justice, Miseries*

The young and the budding population of our future nation has been dragged into quagmire for which law is not giving a solution. No doubt children in war conflict are protected by International humanitarian law under the umbrella of civilians or combatants, also several special provisions recognizing their vulnerability and needs in armed conflict are been taken care of, but children as soldiers is a shock to the world's conscience where extreme violence directly or indirectly is targeting children. Millions of children are not merely bystanders, but also targeted in conflict. Children are still recruited by armed forces of the nations. Some children are victim to general onslaught against civilians and others die as calculated genocide. They suffer from sexual violence or multiple deprivation that expose them to hunger or disease. The recruitment of children over the past few decades, especially in Africa, is a serious humanitarian problem. The children are put in great danger not only by taking active part in the fighting but they are also used as supporting roles like providing military intelligence or caring supplies. However the role of children is not limited to fighting. Hundreds and thousands of children around the world are used as soldiers in armed conflict. Children are abducted and beaten into submission while others join to defend their communities, to escape from poverty, or out of the feeling of revenge. The condition of girls in particular is vulnerable. They are forced to serve as sexual slaves. Also, in the modern phenomena children are used as agents of terror such as suicide bombers. Regardless of these, the reintegration of these children into normal civilian life is a long healing and complex process. They are victims who bear serious

implication for their physical and emotional well-being. They are subject to abuse, witness death, killing and sexual violence. The chilling conclusion of child soldiering has sucked the world into a desolate moral vacuum. This space is devoid of most basic human values, a space where children are raped, slaughtered, maimed and exploited as soldiers, by being exposed to starvation and extreme brutality.

CHILD SOLDIERING – “Shame of War”

A child soldier is a child actively participating in violent conflict as a member of that organization which applies violence in a systematic way. The internationally agreed definition for a child associated with an armed force or armed group (child soldier) is any person below 18 years of age who is, or who has been, recruited or used by an armed force or armed group in any capacity, including but not limited to children, boys and girls, used as fighters, cooks, porters, messengers, spies or for sexual purposes. It does not only refer to a child who is taking or has taken a direct part in hostilities.¹ This definition, however is broad in many respects when we worry about child recruitment and focus on specific reasons either from a normative or analytical point of view. The participation of children as soldiers in armed conflict is an alarming situation. Earlier children were recruited supporting role in armies like cooking, porters, spies and messengers. But in today's date 80% the fighting force is composed of child soldiers, that can be characterized as “new war “which constitutes the overriding form of violent conflict which over the last few decade has emerged. Hundreds and thousands of children are kidnapped, conscripted or presumed into joining armed groups. It has been made possible after the proliferation of lightweight weapons such as automatic guns for effective child soldiering which can also be used by under 10year old child. The growth of these light weapons was an obvious pre-requisite for the involvement

of these tiny hands in modern conflict. The easy availability of very light, cheap, and easily maintained weapon with high power and fire, which can even be effectively use by the children without even giving training adds to the problem.

“When they came to my village, they asked my older brother whether he was ready to join the militia. He was just 17 and he said no; they shot him in the head. Then they asked me if I was ready to sign, so what could I do - I didn't want to die.”²

CHILD RECRUITMENT -THE YOUNGEST SOLDIER

WHY CHILD?? ROOT CAUSE-

Children are an important determinant of war strategy. They are viewed as a source to be exploited by military and rebel leaders. Children are innocent and they don't have the conception of death. The myriad image of death is not clear in their mind, so they find it fascinating, adventures and agree to join child soldiering. They also join armed groups for various reasons and by various methods. Recruiting children is seen as cheap, effective and provides obedient fighters. Children are mainly a part of war strategy as they are plentiful as well as they are easy to impress and are expandable. According to the media report in some African countries of civilians and soldiers, they fear child soldiers more than adult ones because they believe children possess magical and extraordinary powers. The main reason for their recruitment is their fearlessness in the battle field and the atrocities which are so easily committed by them. Development and proliferation of small and light weight weapons has made active participation of children possible. Factors such as poverty, lack of opportunity, high orphan rates, illiteracy and displacement are the root cause of child soldiering. The children who are from a impoverished and

¹Paris Principles and Guidelines on Children Associated with Armed Forces or Armed Groups, 2007.

²Myanmar A former child soldier taken when he was 13. (Source: BBC report.)

marginalised background or those who have been separated from their families are most likely to become victims of child soldiering. They are also preferred and desired by commanders as they are "more obedient, do not question orders and are easier to manipulate than adult soldiers".³

The recruitment and use of children has become endemic in the conflict. Despite the protection they are still continued to be recruited by armed groups and armed force. In modern day warfare even girls are increasingly becoming the subject of targeted attack to military recruitment and sexual violence. They are recruited in many different ways. Some are conscripted, kidnapped, others are press-ganged and the rest forced in order to defend their families. The basic problem of child recruitment is that in many countries birth registration is inadequate or non-existent and hence children do not know how old they are. So in compliance with the national laws, on the basis of appearance and physical development recruiters recruit children by guessing them as 18 or plus. Countries which do not conscript systematic registration or with weak administrative system recruit arbitrarily from streets, schools and orphanages. Children from poorer sectors and adolescent boys who work in the informal sector like selling gun, cigarettes or lottery tickets are particularly targeted. In Myanmar, whole groups of children from 15 to 17 years old have been surrounded in their schools and forcibly conscripted.⁴ Children from wealthy and more educated family are left undisturbed. To avoid forced conscription the parents who have means even send their children out of county.

Forced recruitment, where they are beaten and abducted to present or submit themselves to join service. There are other push and pull factors that drive children to join army group. The most basic reason is economic

³Brett, Rachel, Margaret McCallin and Rhonda O'Shea, "Children: The Invisible Soldiers", Geneva, Quaker United Nations Office and the International Catholic Child Bureau, April 1996, p. 88.

⁴Ibid., p. 23

condition and its related factors like poverty, hunger, discrimination or the idea of martyrdom and heroic death. In Lebanon and Sri Lanka, for example, some adults have used young people's immaturity to their own advantage, recruiting and training adolescents for suicide bombings.⁵ Children sometimes voluntarily join armed service to ensure at least one meal, clothing and medical service. Parents also give their children in the movement for this cause. Revenge is a key motivating factor when they witness discrimination on the basis of ethnic, tribal and religious identity and the killing, humiliation of their parents or sisters being raped. However sometime children associate themselves with armed conflict for social cause, self-determination or religious expression or national liberation. In South Africa, children had joined the fight for the pursuit of political freedom, even though there is no voluntary enlistment of child soldiering because the ultimate decision to recruit them or not lies on the decision of adult commanders and so they are the people who should be held accountable for this inhuman act.

Myriad miseries and anguish- Heart of darkness-

They fight like musketeers but die as innocent children. They are the youngest soldiers. Children once recruited as soldiers are given the same treatment as adult's combats. Some start as support function which entail great risk and hardship. Common work assigned to children are to serve as porter, carry heavy loads which can be double their weight or carry ammunition or injured soldiers. Children who are not able to carry their loads are savagely beaten or even short to death. Children are extensively used as lookouts or messengers at the time of war. In Latin America, reports tell of government forces that have deliberately killed even the youngest children in peasant communities on the grounds that they, too, were dangerous.⁶ Also they are used for household chores or other routine services.

⁵Ibid., p. 31

⁶Ibid., p. 52

Like in Uganda, children work as guards, gardener, hunter for fruits and vegetables. Child soldiers include both boys and girls, but girls mainly who are physically strong and can perform same function as boys. In Guatemala, rebel groups use girls to prepare food, attend to the wounded and wash clothes. Girls may also be forced to provide sexual services. In Uganda, girls who are abducted by the Lord's Resistance Army are "married off" to rebel leaders.⁷

CASE STUDY-

A case study showing child's experience of joining armed group from Honduras:

"At the age of 13, I joined the student movement. I had a dream to contribute to make things change, so that children would not be hungry ... later I joined the armed struggle. I had all the inexperience and the fears of a little girl. I found out that girls were obliged to have sexual relations 'to alleviate the sadness of the combatants'. And who alleviated our sadness after going with someone we hardly knew? At my young age I experienced abortion. It was not my decision. There is a great pain in my being when I recall all these things ... In spite of my commitment, they abused me, and they trampled my human dignity. And above all, they did not understand that I was a child and that I had rights."⁸

Starting as an indirect support soon these children become the heart of the battle. Public health hazard has become a major problem which can't be ignored. Any hazardous disease that caused large scale damage to children in past would drag the attention of public health specialist. In today's context also, armed conflict kills and maims thousands of more children as compared to men. Thousands of children every year are

killed due to direct fighting-from bullets, knife, bombs and landmines and many die from malnutrition or disease caused by conflict. Between 1981-88 in Mozambique 454,000 children died in armed conflict. They are vulnerable to collective assault and well-being.

Promoting psychological recovery and social reintegration-

Child best nourishment, wellbeing, development in his best interest is ensured by family and community and develop understanding from local culture, religion and belief. But children in armed conflict are raised in the environment of severe violence and commit cruelties and hardship. During the development of these buds into flowers they are exposed to chronic and traumatic stress which leaves a mental and related physical ill-health impact which severely changes their personality in a negative way and deprive them from normal and healthy development. Historically the primary focus concerned with children in armed conflict was physical vulnerability. But the grief, loss and fear which a child goes through should be taken into consideration and their experience should be taken into account. Childhood has become a nightmare for the children living in war-torn nations. The very foundation of a child's life i.e. home, families, community is being destroyed, separated or splintered by armed conflict. It also leads to breakdown of trust between people, disrupts health and education. Children seeing their parents or loved ones in vulnerable state affects their psychosocial condition which severely undermines their confidence and a sense of fear builds up home deep in their heart. Children have witnessed traumatic experiences like torture, murder or rape of their parents. These traumatic experience increase their anxiety about being separated from their families or they have nightmares and trouble in sleeping. They may cease laughing and playing like other children, as well as they lose their appetite, concentration in education and withdraw themselves from all contacts. They

⁷Almquist, Kate, Robbie Muhumuza and David Westwood, "The Effects of Armed Conflict on Girls", Geneva, World Vision International, May 1996, p. 21.

⁸Brett, Rachel, Margaret McCallin and Rhonda O'Shea, "Children: The Invisible Soldiers", Geneva, Quaker United Nations Office and the International Catholic Child Bureau, April 1996, p. 84.

become depressed, hopeless about their future or develop aggressive behaviour.

Children and Justice for them during conflict –

Some children are direct victims or are affected by war crimes and also some are involved in committing crimes. Justice can be accessed for children who have been victims of armed conflict and can be achieved both during and after conflict through forums like judicial, non-judicial, or traditional justice mechanisms. Ensuring justice or access to it during armed conflict at times can be problematic due to the collapse of the judicial infrastructure and displacement and disappearance of judicial staff, prosecutors and lawyers. Children who have either witnessed or are victims of armed conflict see justice as a support system to find their families, return back to education, live independently and assist them to find employment. But these expectations, inevitably, could not be fulfilled in the true sense, leaving children disappointed and disillusioned and thereby leaving perpetrators free. Also they are used for household chores or other routine services. Like in Uganda, children work as guards, gardener, hunter for fruits and vegetables. Child soldiers include both boys and girls, but girls mainly who are physically strong and can perform same function as boys. In Guatemala, rebel groups use girls to prepare food, attend to the wounded and wash clothes. Girls may also be forced to provide sexual services. In Uganda, girls who are abducted by the Lord's Resistance Army are "married off" to rebel leaders.⁹

Victim and witness in judicial proceeding

The difficulty for victims to confront their harsh memories and their assailants in judicial proceeding is often underestimated. If they speak, there could be vengeance towards them or their families. If they testify, they may have to undergo a vigorous cross-

examination that might be like re-living those horrific events. Balance between the prosecutors and children as participants is also of great importance and concern. Closed sessions, image and voice distortion, pre and post statement, screens between the accused and the witness are all useful methods for protecting child witness from possible consequences when they testify. Also while ensuring the best interest of children while justice is done, a number of new ideas should be developed including protective measures and finding alternative forms of participation ensuring child-specific reparations.

Traditional judicial system and protection under the system –

Local traditional mechanisms are used by some countries to resolve disputes in a community between families and clans to bring about settlement and reconciliation. This traditional justice for many children is sometimes the only form of justice that they view as meaningful for possibility of justice. In this particular case, national justice system is perceived as corrupt and ineffective. Traditional justice gives a number of opportunities to alleged perpetrators to apologise, make reparation or to compensate the victim party. The decisions by them are widely accepted and can be very effective in promoting healing and reconciliation of the community and the victims.

However, as compared with other forms of justice, there is a limitation to the traditional form of justice, particularly in the aftermath of the conflict. Traditional justice is based upon oral traditions and customary practice, which might be lost as a result of dissipation of collective memory, displacement and loss of traditional authority at the time of breakdown of social justice. Also traditional justice often resides with the elder males of the community. So always a patriarchal culture can't be taken into account for child rights, especially for the girl's right who can be subject to discrimination leading to further violence. In addition to this, another limitation of traditional justice is ambit of jurisdiction and it has not been used to

⁹Almquist, Kate, Robbie Muhumuza and David Westwood, "The Effects of Armed Conflict on Girls", Geneva, World Vision International, May 1996, p. 21.

address international crimes and gender-based crimes.

CONCLUSION- A FRAMEWORK FOR EFFECTIVE ACTION

“We want a society where people are more important than things, where children are precious; a world where people can be more human, caring and gentle.”¹⁰

The present paper is the approach for highlighting the protection of children in armed conflict and also focuses on their myriad miseries and anguishes. In the past two decades children have increasingly been affected by armed conflict. It has tried to concentrate on practical and possible aspect. A daring step should be taken in consideration of the future of children. We should find solutions looking beyond what seems immediate to shield children from the consequences of the war. There is a need of some form of accountability, more effective and appropriate methods apart from only detention and prosecution, along with that it should include restorative measures, truth telling, reintegration programme, traditional healing ceremonies. The emphasis should also be laid on prosecuting the perpetrators who bear the greatest responsibility for the sufferings and crimes committed by children. Basic health systems and services and water supplies should be maintained by parties to a conflict. Facilities for adequate rehabilitation, social integration and provisions for proper medical assistant like artificial limbs for injured or permanently disabled children should be made accessible. Rights of the child must be advocated by health professionals. Local professionals, young people and communities in collaboration with organizations and NGO's should focus on child health needs taking in account of factor's like food, health and care. Government and non-State entities during conflict should encourage facilities like

"days of tranquillity" or "corridors of peace" to continue basic child health measures and deliver humanitarian relief. Food crops, water sources and agriculture should be refrained from destroying by the parties involved in conflict in order to avoid disruption of water supply, food supply thus leading to decrease in production capacities. Income generating programmes such as rehabilitation of livestock, agriculture, fisheries should be given special attention for self-reliance and sustainable population. “It is unforgivable that children are assaulted, violated, murdered and yet our conscience is not revolted nor our sense of dignity challenged. This represents a fundamental crisis of our civilization.”¹¹ The first priority of all nations is to devise a framework of effective action to remove and stop child's participation as soldiers from the armed group thus protecting their right from being violated. In addition to it following actions can be taken

- The training and screening of children in national army has to be exhausted and pre-development training should be made system.
- Comprehensive refreshers training for members of the armed forces and Child Protection Units should be done.
- Child protection agencies and the Ministry of School Affairs should provide adequate interim care and reintegration support to demolished children.
- An authenticated and efficient mechanism for age verification should be embedded in military recruitment procedures.
- Release of children from all ranks of forces.
- Effective investigation of incident of child recruitment and a complaint procedure for cases of the same should be established.

¹⁰Archbishop Desmond Tutu speaking at the Eminent Persons Group meeting for the United Nations Study on the Impact of Armed Conflict on Children, Tarrytown, New York, 9 May 1995.

¹¹GracaMachel, The Impact of Armed Conflict on Children attached to: UN Note of the Secretary-general, A/51/306 (1996), para. 317.

- Birth registration should be free or easily accessible in practice.
- Criminalize the recruitment and use of children by armed groups to stop and prevent this inhuman activity.
- Child protection specialist should be appointed in security force.

“Mankind owes to the child the best it has to give.”¹²

It is getting difficult to determine whether children are victims or perpetrators of crimes. So to differentiate the thin line between them and to punish the perpetrators there should be an application of national and international legal framework practiced in international courts and other judicial and non-judicial forums to ensure the best interest of the child. Also for many reasons, the participation of children for justice is very less. So there is an early need for judiciary to pull up their socks and make some remarkable change in this aspect

- Child victims and witness should be allowed to participate in the trial so that the prosecuting authorities and courts can consider child's evidence and protect them from any adverse consequences.
- National courts should enact those legislative provision that are in best interest of the child victim or witness and should have special measures to support and protect them.
- If States decides to detain and prosecute children for criminal activities under national and international law, they should comply with international standards and judicial guarantee. The UN should have access to detention centre to monitor and report the functioning.
- Further, Administrative detention should not be used by the state for children under 15, and should urge to find more appropriate and effective ways for dealing with them so that their psycho-social development is not affected.

¹²Preamble, UN declaration OF The rights OF The Child (1959)

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN AVAILING NGO BASED EYE CARE SERVICES IN NORTH –WEST PARTS OF PUNE DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA.

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(Regd: 33ICHRD2015)

Abstracts:

The health NGO working in the study area, organizes free eye screening camps for last 30 years, observes gender differences in availing operative treatment for cataract as well as probable socio economic factors responsible for it, in the north-west parts of Pune district, Maharashtra.

Key Words: *Ophthalmic, glaucoma, NPCB, Vision—2020, Cataract*

Vision-2020, the program launched for blindness eradication is estimated that about 314 million people are visually impaired worldwide and 45 million of them are blind. Most people with visual impairment are older, and females are more at risk at every age, in every part of the world. About 87% of the worlds visually impaired live in developing countries. The number of people blinded by infectious diseases has been greatly reduced, but age-related impairment is increasing. With increasing life span senile or old age blindness is a major challenge Worldwide. Its more severe for women population as their longevity is more than men. Cataract remains the leading cause of blindness globally, except in the most developed countries. Correction of refractive errors could give normal vision to more than 12 million children (ages five to 15). About 85% of all visual impairment is avoidable globally.

1. Indian Challenges for blindness eradication

Prevalence and controlling blindness is one of the major ophthalmic health challenges in India. The national record of average blindness is 1% of 122 crore people of India. India accounts for 20% of the global blind population, having 7.8 million blinds, out of 39 million across the globe.¹ 62% blindness in India is on account of cataract, 19.7% refractive error, 5.8% glaucoma and 1% corneal blindness. Prevalence of childhood blindness is 0.8 per thousand children with a total of 300000 blind children in the country. The blind population in India is estimated to rise to 15 million by the year 2020. There will be a huge burden of vision impairment, particularly in rural India. Medically, it has been proved that cataract surgery is an acceptable intervention to the age-related blindness, but the levels of acceptance nationally for this intervention are extremely poor.

Majority of population in India still resides in rural areas where as medical facilities are concentrated in urban pockets. Thus a large proportion of patients in rural India continue to remain blind. India is a vast country with geographical, linguistic and cultural diversities and a complicated socio-economic structure. Any one model of blindness control does not suit the entire nation. Installation of eye care medical units is not the only solution towards eradication of blindness in India. The important challenges are confidence building; awareness and psychological acceptance towards eye care among the patients. Advancement in technology & medical facilities are meaningless unless they are accepted by the society. No wonder India accounts for one of every three cases of blindness caused by cataract in the world. Thus with high population and increase in life expectancy, ophthalmic problems are also enhancing. Women are biologically blessed by larger life span, hence old age group outnumber females as well as ophthalmic problems like cataract and blindness.

The major issues in the expansion of eye care services in India are acceptability, accessibility and affordability. Gender equality and providing proper medical help to women can reduce blindness burden in the country.

This paper focuses on the gender based ophthalmic problems, acceptance level for available medical services and socio-economic factors responsible for it.

2. “National Program for control of blindness” (N.P.C.B)

India is the first country to launch a “National Program for control of blindness” (N.P.C.B) in the year 1994. It has been well received by the government as well as various organizations. Now India has committed itself for “vision 2020: the right to sight” initiative launched by the World Health Organization to reduce avoidable

blindness worldwide. While implementing this ambitious program one has to consider the gender inequality in Indian society, gender difference in blindness prevalence and its impact on acceptance for eye care treatment. In spite of the effort from all the sectors there is a huge backlog of avoidable blindness. The role of health NGOs is crucial in making the N.P.C.B. program successful.

The Study Area

North-West part of Pune district, Maharashtra, comprises mainly Junnar ,Ambegaon&Shirurtahasils. Local NGO in the eye care sector has been rendering free services to rural poor’s & people residing in inaccessible mountain areas. There are 185 villages in Junnar, 143 in Ambegaon & 116 in Shirurtalukas. In Junnar & Ambegaon average 20% villages are located in hilly areas of Western Ghat. Shirur is a drought prone area of Deccan Plateau. Rampant poverty, illiteracy & low economic strata are the main features of the study areas. The hilly area is predominated by schedule casts, schedule tribes & adivasis. Comparatively better development is seen along to Pune-Nasik highway passing through the study region.

3. The action plan was framed to reach to every needy patient consist of the following steps-

- To reach inaccessible remote mountains areas towards needy and tribal people.
- Planned free eye-camps at specific intervals.
- Building confidence with head of village, villagers, particularly women and convince localities through teacher/counselor.
- Announcement of free eye-camps, well in advance, through vehicle with loud speakers.
- Visit the village as per the schedule with well-equipped mobile van and team of staff.

- After investigation selection send cataract patients to hospital van.
- Arrangement of free stay, food, medicines, check-up and pathological test of patients.
- Perform operations, post-operative care like giving protective goggles, etc.
- A gift of new clothes as an additional incentive.
- After discharge, take back patients to the door-steps/homes.
- The hospital builds local capacity by accommodating local health works like general practitioners, paramedical, local leaders.
- Exhibition, posters and film screening during public gathering, fairs and festivals.
- Propaganda for IOL as pointless and safe eye surgery.
- Operated/satisfied patient's presence as a motivator in eye camps.
- Follow up of patients by the team of doctors.
- Develop a community research center under which collect long duration statistical data for better planning.
- Partnership in National Program for Blindness Control (NPBC).

Methodology

The health NGO working in the study area, at Narayangaon, talukaJunnar, for last 32 years in the ophthalmic field has authentic primary data. It runs well-equipped eye hospital on charitable basis. The hospital is authorized center for Government induced NPBC Program me. Free eye screening camps has been organized regularly in the study area. On an average thirty eye screening camps are organized in a month. Patients selected for cataract are treated at the base hospital.

The charitable eye hospital data of last five years through light on the fact that out of the total patients operated for cataract, female number is always more. Primary data of this hospital, year 2010 to 2014 is used for the analysis.

4. Socio-Economic factors responsible for fewer acceptances for availing cataract treatment in the study areas

People in the study area are involved in primary occupations like farming and forest collection etc. So poverty is rampant among people. Western part of the study area is covered with mountains known as Western Ghats, which is remote and inaccessible area with less transport and communication facilities. This is the reason for not accessing general medical and even ophthalmic facilities provided by the charitable eye hospital. There is a lack of awareness about eye diseases and treatment due illiteracy and ignorance. People are busy in farms, thus blind people are ignored as they are of no use. They have joint family system in which any blind person can be accommodated easily. Old age blinds can fulfill basic requirements in joint family so getting eye care treatment is not an urgency for physically fitblindor family members. Blind patients need companion otherwise there is no way for them to get to the hospital. Being a backward area, people have insufficient knowledge about cataract and are ignorant to the eye problems until they are completely blind.

Poor access to information regarding the treatment is also the reason for not availing the treatment. Due to ignorance, many people come late. This leads to glaucoma, which is seen mostly among women. Female patients are ignored as they possess low status in the society.

Gender difference in availing ophthalmic treatment in the study area

Cataract blindness in India is considerably very high (62%) and it is easily curable hence unnecessary. In rural India proportion of age related (senile) cataract is more whereas epidemiological transition is the major cause for non-communicable blindness in urban India. It has been observed that eye care treatment is reaching to the needy people through Primary Health Centers & mainly efforts of NGOs. Organization of free eye camps is the most influential positive determinant for acceptance of eye treatment. 50% of the patients only could accept the treatment through eye camps; however, 50% are yet to accept.

Women’s cataract surgery in free camps significantly higher than males due to the following reasons:

Statistics reflect the fact that life span of women in India is more than men resulting more number of women in old age group, and prevalence rate of cataract blindness is more among women for all ages.

The cataract prevalence rate is higher among women due to hardship and low level of nutrients and low status in society. Generally women work in the farms as well as her involvement in domestic work. Rural women cook on fire wood hence long time eye contact with smoke released from chulha causing more frequent & early age cataract.

Low literacy, lack of information about eye care services and less freedom in decision making process for women are some other reasons

Male and female free cataract operations carried in the charitable hospital

	Year	Male%	Female%
0	201	46	54
1	201	46	54
2	201	46	54
3	201	48	52
4	201	45	55

On an average 4000 cataract operations are done in the hospital, in which females are seen more in numbers. 52% to 55% women get operated in the free camp surgery whereas male number is restricted to 45 to 48%. The NGO has sophisticated paid hospital in the same area has more male response from the surrounding region. The average percent availing paid treatment is 63% for male to 37% for females. It shows gender inequality in the study area.

Graph showing Average age for Cataract Operations

There is remarkable age difference in the age of onset of cataract among male and female population. Females suffer from cataract, on an average 4 to 5 years earlier than males.

Important factors responsible for high prevalence & early onset of cataract among females.

More life span hence more old women & prevalence of blindness

low levels of nutrients and low status in society.

Hardship in farms & at home

Smoke from chullha causing more frequent & early age cataract

Low literacy, lack of information about eye care services and less freedom in decision making process

Social-economic implications of blindness

We lose a valuable manpower due to blindness it is not only the loss of family but nation as a whole. It reduces productivity of the nation. Blind people lose their connectivity from family, relatives and society. Patients become dependent and lose their confidence due to visual impairment. It affects the wellbeing of the family as well as society. Patient may go through severe depression and become psychologically

weak. A blind person healthy yet without some usefulness feels a burden on family and society. The patient is forced to lead a lonely life, being completely isolated from the community. There are certain examples of remarriage by men because of blindness in first wife. They have to suffer from the taunts and ignorance of the society. This loses their desire to live. The effects are more in women as they are given a lower status in the family. Blindness is a disease which has severe social and economic repercussions. It adversely affects the productivity of the country. It has been estimated that the maintenance cost of a blind person is rupees 300 per month while the loss of production is calculated to be rupees 600 per month.

5. Conclusion

Various factors contributing to increasing levels of blindness have been identified. These include geometric increase in life expectancy, lack of adequate surgical facilities, increased demand for improved vision and problems in decision making and gender inequality.

Thus the acceptability, accessibility, and affordability of cataract surgical services need to be carefully addressed in the light of gender equality, to improve visual efficiency. Senile cataract or age-related cataract is responsible for the largest number of blind people in the country. Socially backward, economically weak and female populations have a much higher prevalence of this disease. In a developing country like India, the prevalence is believed to be much greater and the onset earlier among women. The case study through light on the fact that free of cost cataract treatment is given to large number of women whereas more number of men prefers paid treatment which they feel better than free services. If more women in old age group are facilitated with cataract surgeries, it would certainly reduce blindness burden in the country.

5. References

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